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Strategic Management for the Future in a Chaotic World

A Comparison between Resilience Strategies of Senior Petrochemical Managers and Entrepreneurs in
Iran

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Abstract

This thesis examines uncertainty and the influence of "black swan events" on entrepreneurship in Iran, drawing inspiration from N.N. Taleb's book, "The Black Swan." It focuses on Iran's volatile economy, international sanctions, and lack of certainty in international treaties, which create unpredictability for entrepreneurs. The objective is to investigate whether Iranian entrepreneurs employ Taleb's "anti-fragile" strategies, which emphasize resilience in chaotic environments. The study compares survival strategies between entrepreneurs and salaried senior managers. Findings indicate that Iranian entrepreneurs align with Taleb's strategies, while petrochemical managers prefer traditional "strategic planning" approaches.

Employing a qualitative research method involving interviews with 15 entrepreneurs and 15 managers from the petrochemical industry in Iran. The research argues that anti-fragility is valuable worldwide, emphasizing the necessity of embracing chaos and risk for entrepreneurial success, as no social endeavour is immune to black swan events. It proposes that preparing for uncertainty is more prudent than relying solely on past experiences or maximizing profits. The study also explores the concept of "fatalistic" or "pragmatic" reasoning among surviving Iranian entrepreneurs, utilizing Grid-Group Cultural Theory to explain their mind-set.

In conclusion, the study recommends the adoption and dissemination of anti-fragile strategies among entrepreneurs and managers through shared networks. It suggests that successful Iranian entrepreneurs can offer valuable insights to entrepreneurs worldwide, given their experience in navigating unpredictable situations. The research provides a theoretical and empirical analysis of the impact of uncertainty on entrepreneurship in Iran, highlighting the significance of Taleb's anti-fragile strategies and the need to prepare for unexpected events.

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1 Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Research Background: Survival and Success through Many Adaptations

In a number of influential works, Nicholas Nassim Taleb (2007, 2008, 2014) questioned the notion that there is sufficient, should seek more, or will ever obtain an adequately large theory or exhaustive information that will facilitate the reliable identification of cause-effect relationships such that forecasts can be made effectively. According to Taleb, the world in which humans live is different in reality. This implies that all attempts to ‘gap-fill’ will ultimately fail in terms of thoroughly developing knowledge due to the fact that ‘social systems’ such as political frameworks, markets, trading blocs, and relationships between countries (this list could also include families, work groups and communities) do not have a systematic nature. Hence, it is dangerous to make the assumption that what is considered to be widely acknowledged and presented outside the ‘research gaps’ has permanence, solidity, reliability, predictability, and dependability. In fact, the lack of certainty surrounding gaps in the research is not significantly different to that related to what researchers consider to be known. According to Taleb, things believed to be know can also have an element of risk as a result of ‘narrative fallacies’, which are stories that falsely claim to be truthful.

Taleb did not pioneer the idea that comprehensive planning should be abandoned (Lindblom 1959; Hayek 1974; Hume 1739, Popper, 2013/ 1966). These researchers contended that the assumption that the future can be forecasted based on past events is erroneous, pointless and significantly risky. They all questioned whether it is possible to know anything definitively, particularly with regard to social phenomena that have ‘artificial risks’. Nevertheless, Taleb made the convincing claim that the *smallest* of antecedent modifications (which one cannot identify in advance or definitively establish in retrospect) could affect something disproportionately by magnifying over time, which ultimately lead to what he defined as ‘black swan events’ that could be positive or negative in nature and whose effects cannot be accurately estimated. Theorists are disturbed by this world (paradigm view) and find

it disagreeable, but propose that this represents the real world in which businesses function regardless of whether this is recognised or not. This claim is reinforced by evidence showing the effects that unexpected events have at all scales and particularly in markets.

Black swan events are characterised by the fact that:

- Forecasting them is virtually impossible (although narrative fallacies are often assembled after the fact by theorists, which apply an imagined sense of order to what is in reality very complicated and contingent chaos)
- Their effects are significant in terms of size and are highly dispersed.

Taleb used specific examples to demonstrate the concept of the black swan event, namely Fleming's discovery of penicillin, the First World War, the September 11 attacks and the recent global financial crisis of 2007-2008. Moreover, the economic crisis that occurred in 2020, caused by the lockdown conditions imposed as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic (referred to as the coronavirus), represents a good example proving that Black Swan events exist. They can be defined as such as it is hard or even not possible to identify their trigger points (as they largely happened by chance), which are significantly inferior (like a person being assassinated) to their ultimate impacts, which continue to evolve with subsequent ramifications with no discernible ending. For instance, Taleb suggested that WWI is still having consequences and it is not possible to determine when this will no longer occur. In a world characterised by chaos, a stone cast onto water causes infinite ripples, and every ripple initiates a series of new events that have outcomes that cannot be predicted. Such a world does not have an 'equilibrium point' as the pond's surface is constantly rippling.

In 2008, a \$5 million project led to losses of around \$200 million for Levi Strauss & Co. (Flyvberg & Budzier, 2011). In 2003, Shell received approval for a project to produce oil and gas at Sakhalin Island that was valued at \$10bn (which was more than the company's total net income in 2002). However, by 2005, after development of the project had proceeded to an

advanced stage, Shell announced that the project cost had doubled to \$20bn (equivalent to \$22 bn today) (Hajikazemi et al., 2016) The cost of the Big Dig project in Boston increased from \$2.6bn to \$14.6 (KPMG, 2013; (Hajikazemi et al., 2016), proving the estimations of highly respected experts to be wrong.

Figure 1 Crude Oil Price in the Last Century (Historical Oil Prices Chart, 2020)

In the table shown above, the impacts of various Black Swan events on the Crude Oil market in the previous 100 years are shown. Historical events that are considered to be examples of the Black Swan phenomenon include:

- First World War
- Second World War
- Islamic Revolution in Iran
- Iran vs Iraq War
- 9/11 Attacks
- SARS Epidemic

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- Mortgage Crisis 2008
- Donald Trump's Election as US President
- COVID – 19 (Coronavirus)

It can be confidently stated that in none of the aforementioned examples did the main project managers lack expertise, training, competence and nor where they considered irresponsible. All of them would have had a significant amount of expertise on which they could base their decisions; however, notwithstanding the available information and modelling, the exceptional events that ensued would still have been profoundly shocking for them.

My experience as an entrepreneur in Iran, in a business environment that is clearly one of the most chaotic in the world, allowed me to immediately recognise Taleb's assertions due to the fact that I have consistently been faced with random surprises, which may or may not be beneficial, some of which are known as the double-edged 'grey swans', throughout my business career and I have always operated based on the knowledge that black swans will probably occur, without specifically naming them as such. Reading the works of Taleb facilitated a process of reflection on the commonalities and distinctions among the multiple businessmen and few businesswomen in Iran with whom I have good relationships, who have achieved varying degrees of success and with whom I have engaged in collaboration, with a particular focus on how I have survived in what can certainly be defined as a highly volatile environment where the uncertainty is unbounded.

Specifically, Taleb and Lindblom both separately recommended that (Lindblom, 1959) 'short-range experiments' should be conducted (and all efforts should be made to ensure that large experiments are avoided) and things deemed 'too big to fail' should not be constructed, which appear to be highly applicable in this case. Advance planning is a practice that both I and my colleagues prefer not to adopt. Additionally, there is an inclination to disregard projects despite investing a significant amount of resources in them and develop projects that can be

placed 'on hold' (freeze) for extended periods in the expectation that the project can be recovered if and when the environment is more conducive. Surviving investors exhibit no vulnerability to the 'sunk cost fallacy' (Falah, 2016; Green, Rosenblatt and Yao, 2015) and generally adopt a fatalistic attitude based on the English proverb that states 'there is no point crying over spilt milk' as well as that setbacks are 'all water under the bridge'. The 'evidence of my experience' is also that the approach does not seek to maximize profit and it does so according to two primary reasons. Firstly, although the adoption of an approach aimed at maximising profit can produce effective results in the country for approximately 4 years, it is ultimately suppressed by a black swan, which causes the business to be completely destroyed. Secondly, this approach is likely to generate clearly visible growth that will attract attention towards the business, which could ultimately lead to the business being acquired by the state and losing its independence. In Iran, parts of the state such as the military fund themselves as commercial enterprises and are not financed through taxation, which means that in order to remain independent, overt success should not be promoted. Although this situation is generally recognised, one cannot predict when the success of a business will attract attention, when it will lose control, or what this will ultimately mean for the entrepreneur who aimed to maximise profit.

Rather, the researcher and his peers construct businesses which Taleb would consider to be 'anti-fragile' (2012). Taleb stated that this idea is "a blueprint for living in black swan world, the key being to love randomness, variation, and uncertainty to some degree, and thus also errors". Taleb's work incorporates "the things gained from disorder", and extends further than being resilient and robust. According to him, there are three different categories: Fragile, Robust and Anti-fragile. The fragile is incapable of withstanding disturbance and chaos, the robust will tolerate the situation with no change to its order, whereas the anti-fragile would gain relative benefits while exhibiting resilience and creativity. His concept of the 'anti-fragile'

is an attempt to demonstrate how unpredictability can be addressed, avoiding ill-considered preventive managerial temperament in conditions that are conducive to black swan events. In general, his goal is not to become immune to such events, but to exploit and potentially use them to one's own advantage. Black swan events are not always negative and it is important that appropriate reactions are made such that the complex situation can be managed by adopting an anti-fragile approach. Given the fact that the next part of this thesis will describe my own activities, I will describe them in both the first and third person.

1.2 Anti-Fragility in Action

In addition to other enterprises, the author has invested in and manages a partially finished project involving the construction of a property and offices in a prestigious site situated in a different area of Tehran and Shiraz. However, the project has experienced a turbulent history for the past years. A cautious approach is adopted when making decisions about the mix of uses and the types of clients or markets targeted. The ever-changing local, national, and international environment is closely monitored on a weekly and monthly basis. Furthermore, decisions are postponed whenever possible to minimize any potential ramifications for subsequent project-related choices. This working methodology could be perceived as lacking efficiency when viewed from a 'project management' perspective. It represents a perfect example of how a project should not be managed in stable conditions where the theoretical assumption is that a long-term equilibrium will be achieved in terms of supply, demand, and prices. However, 'market clearing' never occurs, my actions are not targeted at enhancing efficiency, or maximising the use of assets or optimising profits, and there is no stability in the environment. The ultimate objective is to survive by frequently using reverse gears, different strategy, ensuring that multiple paths are available and changing course when required, particularly in the short term where decisions can be made relatively confidently according to available evidence. Additionally, a diligent effort is made to consider as many options as

possible. For instance, I had to postpone decisions regarding the number of offices and residential units and sizes of units, provisional charging rates and client types and also unexpected events such as COVID-19. Therefore, my project manager, architect and structural engineer deliver a building frame that offers sufficient flexibility for changes to be made later in the project to cater for a variety of impromptu decisions. Due to the fact, I am not certain what the building will ultimately be used for, the end result is that it is over-specified and the cost exceeds the budget for a number of its potential uses.

On the other hand, I am also engaged in another project that is situated a long distance from the construction involving a manufacturing facility that has also partially been completed. In an environment considered stable or at a minimum ‘equilibrium seeking’, with no risk that sanctions would be imposed, lifted and then re-imposed by the international community and where the growth of the Iranian economy would encourage females in the labour force with high levels of education to seek employment opportunities, the decision to construct a factory in aviculture industry food in partnership with a credible company from Britain would seem rational. Nevertheless, to become anti-fragile, it necessary to make complicated decisions that are both independent and non-inter-dependent. Even though I closely monitor a wide variety of different events, I do not expect to comprehensively understand their current effects, or their consequences for the future. With regard to Taleb, although I have read historical accounts, I am still doubtful in terms of how confident I can be in such accounts based on the assumption that information that is missing could have more significance than what is provided. I am cautious about my lack of knowledge; partially due to the fact it is not possible for me to know the extent of my ignorance.

Similar to the partially finished ‘aviculture and property, the purpose of which has yet to be completely decided, in the event that the international community decides to re-impose sanctions or the agreement with the partner in Britain collapses, I still have the option to install

different load bearing steel frameworks in the factory, which would allow heavy-lifting equipment (cranes) to be included, thus completely transforming the manufacturing function to something different than was initially planned, such as precision engineering. The completely unanticipated election of Donald Trump (which clearly can be defined as a Black Swan event), demonstrates that I made the correct decision, although I did not know why I would be right. I recognise the wisdom of the quotation ‘He who foretells the future is a liar even when proved right!’ I do not claim that I predicted the result of the election in the United States, but my decisions are made based on my belief that unexpected events will still occur and they will have a greater effect than those that are expected to materialise.

Although an entrepreneur seeking utility, competitiveness and to maximise profit would not behave in this way, their ability to survive when faced with the environment in Iran would be limited. Furthermore, I could not be considered what Keynes defined as an ‘animal spirit’ who depends on their intuition and who is blindly optimistic. I place my trust in the emotion of caution linked with the fear of catastrophe and that my businesses, workers and family will be ruined.

Ensuring that outstanding decisions are delayed to the greatest extent possible, I have ordered that a high-quality wall be built surrounding the site, which has exceeded my expectations. I also made the recent decision to clad the outside walls with a quality dressed and polished stone finish. Although the wall marking the factory boundaries and the cladding have no impact on the product that will ultimately be manufactured, I believe that it is my duty to employ the services of expert masons and regardless of the factory’s production function, it will be ensured that their ‘non-scalable’ (Taleb, 2007) work will be capable of enduring the forces of nature going forward. On the other hand, I have developed excellent and indispensable relationships with officials in the region, informing them that the project has been delayed purely to maintain flexibility.

Lastly, my personal experiences and those of my peers are examples of Taleb's suggestions for survival in an environment of 'chaotic and abnormal (non-Gaussian) risks': avoiding specialisation, and rather choosing to spread hope, efforts, investments and energies throughout a variety of fields in what is generally defined as a 'diversified portfolio'. For example, I have personally invested in:

- The trading of Petrochemical polymers and raw materials (mainly PET, PP). I will subsequently make the argument that further diversification of expert polymer production should be adopted as an anti-fragile strategy at the national level.
- The manufacturing of sport equipment whereby the products are manufactured at the customer's factory and they pay for and own the moulding dies, but I own the machinery and am responsible for importing and supplying the polymers and raw materials. This also implies that they have 'skin in the game'.
- Online trading of furniture and sport equipment to international markets, partially operated from the UK but with suppliers and clients across the world.
- Purchasing land in Iran for the construction of an offices or residential structure.
- A start-up enterprise focused on web design
- Trading of stocks and currency

I have made the decision to engage in activities and then completely discard them, an approach that I will continue to adopt. If I was in possession of the omniscience and omnipresence of a supreme being (i.e., sufficiently reliable information), I could have acquired significant wealth, but I recognise that it is foolish to expect to have 'perfect knowledge'. The preferred objectives are to survive, retain independence, as well as to act reputably and honestly, which represent sources of resilience themselves with a wide variety of uses in times characterised by such uncertainty.

It should be noted that Taleb does not perceive such an anti-fragile approach to be 'spreading one's bets' due to the fact that in a casino, it is possible to calculate the odds and the owners of the casino will have complete knowledge of them, and the clients should also be able to calculate them, even if they choose not to do so. Contrastingly, in business environments that are generally more disordered and susceptible to black swan events than it may seem, it is not possible to calculate the odds and Taleb presents numerous examples of the folly of people who have failed in this endeavour. This can be emphasised by the fact that the majority of entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived, resisted corruption and remain independent who constitute the sample seem to seek diversification be it intentionally or as some de facto and possibly coincidental 'strategy' with no knowledge of the concept of 'anti-fragile' or Hume's 'problem of induction' (Humes, 1740; Revision, 2006). They continually monitor the environment to find what Popper called 'counter-factual evidence', but again, they have no knowledge of this term and have never read Popper's *Conjectures and Refutations* and understand the importance of a single black swan compared to a multitude of white swans (they exhibit increased sensitivity to a lesser amount of disconfirming cases in comparison to a significant amount of confirming cases).

For instance, fluctuations in the currency represent an ongoing source of anxiety for domestically owned firms in Iran that operate internationally, even though they have proved to be highly profitable. Payments were made to these actors through international banks and they made significant profits via money arbitrage, although they remained highly susceptible to completely different out-turns. In such situations, it is not advised that managers are awarded performance bonuses for ostensibly being lucky rather than applying good judgement. When Long Term Capital Management (LTCM) catastrophically failed in 1998 with debts amounting to \$4.6 billion, the risks of activities that had been regarded as being safe were revealed (in this example, arbitrage of price differentials between bonds in the US and those in other countries

that experienced unanticipated movement as a result of events that could not have been predicted in advance). After this transpired, the irony that the company's name included Long Term and Management was obvious (Lowenstein, 2000).

Nevertheless, while such casual observations may certainly be reported, it is difficult to claim that entrepreneurs within Iran who have managed to survive and sometimes thrive in an environment characterised by chaos and inestimable uncertainty have achieved this as they have acted in a manner akin to the suggestions of Nicholas Taleb and Charles Lindblom even though they have not read their works. Firstly, it is necessary to distil Taleb's thesis into a number of propositions that can be researched (or what he would define as 'anti-theories'). Secondly, they must be operationalised into questions that can be posed to business colleagues and peers in Iran in a manner that they can comprehend. Thirdly, it must be determined whether their ability to survive is associated with their efforts to engage in these types of 'anti-fragile' business activities. To achieve this, it is necessary to make a comparison between their outcomes and the accomplishments and the non-successes of people who have taken different approaches that are appropriate to a world that is functional as opposed to being chaotic, which indicates why the 'comparative' managerial sample is also critical for this research.

1.3 Overview of Antifragility in Bigger Scale

Such empirical and academic goals are established within broader anti-fragile objectives:

Oil and gas are some of the primary resources that have significant and relatively clear impacts on different sectors, albeit somewhat unpredictably, and are critical factors in determining whether other industries grow or ultimately fail, particularly in nations that have a rich abundance of energy resources. This specifically holds for Iran, where inconsistent development is impacted by an interconnected network of 'geopolitical' forces, the direction of which has yet to be accurately forecasted despite numerous attempts. In this study, I will

attempt to present a ‘managing-for-the-future’ strategy (the implementation of which is possible in all conditions involving uncertainty and chaos) on the basis of the disturbing principles of Nicholas Taleb, which can be linked with and implemented in contemporary Iran.

The author has experience of both ‘positive and negative black swans’ based on his entrepreneurial activities within Iran and other countries in the past years. In other words, the academic motivation for this thesis is derived from the experience of dealing with a plethora of events that defied prediction, which had the potential to ruin my career as the owner and shareholder of businesses, particularly had I pursued the traditional approach of basic specialisation, seeking to benefit from economies of scale as well as to maximise profit. It is easy to identify ‘black swan events’ that would have led to the destruction of these enterprises.

One of the strengths of Taleb’s argument is that it is equally applicable to both micro and macro scales. Hence, one could argue that the Iranian state could benefit from diversification to the same extent as individual entrepreneurs in the country. Rather than remaining highly dependent on its exports of natural gas and crude oil, which are susceptible to volatility and significant movements in prices, it has the potential to accomplish greater and more secure ‘value-added’ through the production of refined petrochemical products that are more diverse and specialised. Although a large number of such products would be unsuccessful, they would be offset by the relatively minimal but necessarily unpredictable successes. If Iran made alterations to its industrial strategy, it could strengthen the resilience of its numerous associated trades and industries to black swan events to a certain extent (Taleb, 2007), which includes my own polymer trading and sport equipment manufacturing businesses. Despite being trained in the field of manufacturing and engineering; I am able to differentiate between the ‘natural laws’ governing the manufacturing of polymers and the largely lawless and incalculable essence of the social world of ‘artificial risks’ with their related risks and adversities. ‘Social Chemistry’ is completely different to Organic Chemistry and based on my experience as a businessman, I

have learned that is not recommended to implement what Mary Douglas defined as a ‘naturalising analogy’ to what are essentially business phenomena that do not occur in a natural manner.

A variety of experiences and evidence from various fields of industry with regard to trade, sanctions by the international community and currency volatility have resulted in varied outcomes. Although businesses with international operations were able to benefit from money arbitrage, manufacturers were confronted with significant challenges in the short term, specifically in terms of obtaining raw materials. Even though I could not explain why, I believed that it made sense to engage in both the trading of currency and manufacturing in addition to other ventures.

In terms of policies, the broader objective of this study is to determine strategies that be generally adopted in the petrochemical industry in Iran taking into account future developments and the chaotic nature of the environment. Therefore, the author’s vast experience and evidence, particularly with regard to surprise events, will assist with the evaluation of the extent to which all industrial sectors are vulnerable, as well as the ramifications for the majority or all businesses in Iran. This could be addressed as an explanation of Taleb recommendation and his thesis.

When countries that have extensive resources of oil and gas are capable of domestically producing petrochemical products from such resources, they can gain the following benefits:

- increased employment (and inestimable future advantages to the life chances of members of households)
- considerable savings in transportation and insurance fees parallel to the decrease in the importation of refined materials

- reduction in banking fees that are currently imposed as a result to being exposed to significant fluctuations in currency exchange (FX) as well as preparing Letters of Credit (LC)
- reducing in transaction fees including those incurred as a result of customs duties
- the nation becomes more independent and less vulnerable to the volatility of international politics and terrorist attacks, which are types of black swan events that are occur frequently in the Middle East in the current climate.

The overall suggestion that high-value petroleum by-products should be manufactured and sold rather than choosing to export unrefined oil and subsequently import refined products (such that the revenues can be reinvested in different downstream manufacturing subsectors) conforms to the anti-fragility principles. The readiness to put aside specific plants and build new factories in a manner that allows any decisions regarding their ultimate purpose to be deferred also corresponds to the anti-fragile Iranian entrepreneur's business modus operandi, on which this study is specifically focussed. Taking into account the scalability of Taleb's argument, moving between the more limited research aim and the broader objective should be comparatively easy. Put differently, the author agrees with Taleb that the social world has a similar level of chaos at both micro and macro scales.

Taleb claimed that anti-fragility is most applicable to different actors characterised by their creative and heterogeneous operations. With respect to energy, the production and export of oil has been diminished by Iran and other members of OPEC, with a focus on resource conservation and increased dependence on value-added via trading processes. After the price of oil decreased from \$120 per barrel to as low as \$57 and even to its minimum since last 50 years during the pandemic (OPEC, 2017), the significance of lowering vulnerability via diversification into refined materials and the manufacturing of creative finished products became obvious. In fact, the oil price reached negative levels for a brief period in 2020.

Iran has been making arrangements to increase its capacity to produce refined petrochemical products by constructing more plants, increasing the abilities of the current sites, attracting foreign investors and financial firms to become the first regional exporter can increase their profit by exporting the petrochemical value-added products (NPC, 2016), and the rationale behind these aims is generally confirmed by this study.

Originally established in 1964 as a subsidiary of the Iranian Ministry of Petroleum, the National Petrochemical Company (NPC) initially comprised smaller plants and has since developed to become the second largest producer and exporter in the Middle East. In line with state policy, a variety of investments have been made in this sector targeting the next five years, which are aimed at enhancing the production capacity and diversifying the industry. The ultimate goal is to be the largest regional producer including an extremely broad range of oil by-products, which in the context of this study would denote ‘anti-fragility’. It is considered that the extent of ‘planning’ behind such aims is likely reduce compared to the past. When diversifying, it cannot be accurately predicted whether a specific type of specialist manufacturing will succeed or fail. Regardless of whether policy-makers express it in this manner, the multiplication specialist petrochemicals in different area as small investor scales with infrequent significant successes that cannot be predicted are not easy to encompass with planning methodology.

Recognising both the volatile nature of global oil markets and the necessity to implement different strategies that are more dependent on refined oil by-products (and subsequently incorporating them into the production of a wide range of goods), significant direct investments are being made domestically, which are expected to generate the following estimated outcomes:

- The ability to refine petrochemical products locally will generate as much as 400 percent added-value in comparison to the price of crude oil.

- Additional value-added could be possible as a result of the increased demand for manufactured petrochemical products in various fields of industry, a number of which the author has experience of.
- By increasing its capacity, Iran aims (as opposed to plans) to take its place as the primary exporter of refined petrochemicals and petrochemical products in the Middle East region.
- Such actions would protect the country from fluctuations in global oil prices to a certain extent, partially due to the fact that a decrease in the price of oil causes the margins that can be obtained from producing refined petrochemicals and manufactured products to increase. It should be emphasised that a reduction in the oil price (which cannot be easily predicted), will lead to a relative increase in the value-added obtainable from refining petroleum into specialist products. Resultantly, oil price fluctuations could become beneficial rather than the unwanted annoyance that was previously the case. Resultantly, by implementing an anti-fragile strategy, Iran could take advantage of both increases *and* decreases in the price of oil, albeit in different ways.

It is acknowledged that industrialised nations are highly dependent on unrefined oil and that other companies producing value-added refined oil products around the world would prefer to retain such businesses that generate high value-added within their own countries (i.e., outside the borders of the main producers of oil). Their preference is for the production of plastics from Iranian oil to take place outside the country's boundaries and to keep the enormous added value that can be obtained from producing polymers as well as the manufacturing of products in which they are incorporated. Additionally, rivals within the Middle East region will be negatively impacted if Iran expands its petrochemical refining capacity and ability to manufacture finished goods. Nevertheless, the author emphasises that

in this context, anti-fragility is denoted by the diversity of refined and finished products. It is not possible to predict which of the specialised refined products will produce the most success, and an approach to risk that acknowledges but is also tolerant of failure, which postpones decisions and refrains from the sunk cost fallacy (as practised by myself and other entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived), is needed. Therefore, the author suggests that similar to other countries around the world, Iran can learn valuable lessons from the entrepreneurs operating in the country (Globalization in transition: The future of trade and value chains, 2019).

Such measures and a paradigm shift in thinking are to a certain extent favourable consequences (positive black swans) of the sanctions imposed on Iran by the international community, a factor that may not have been taken into account by the countries who applied such sanctions. The fundamental aim of international sanctions is to apply pressure in order to disturb the equilibrium, which could have the unplanned consequence of making Iran additionally accustomed to black swans, thus paradoxically making the country more resilient.

1.4 A Black Swan Turns White?

It can clearly be interpreted that interventions made by Western nations in Iran in recent decades have been purposefully coercive towards the country. Sanctions recently imposed by the United States and Europe against Iran were intended to prevent the development of the country's nuclear capabilities. Despite the significant effects of such sanctions, they cannot be definitively considered black swans as their effects, at least in the short term, were predicted and not all detrimental, although the impacts were certainly chaotic, particularly with regard to currency volatility, issues pertaining to bank transactions, as well as shortages of certain raw materials and production equipment in the short term.

Conversely, and partially as a reaction to the hostile actions and sanctions imposed by the international community, as previously mentioned, Iran has decided to increase its capacity

to produce petrochemical by-products to replace its terminated nuclear programme. Partnerships have been established with international firms to seek investments and transfer technologies, with a number of projects either having reached completion or in progress. Although I do not wish to simplify such events or commit the ‘narrative fallacy’ of placing more coherence on them than they possibly merit, they have been summarised below:

- As a result of the nuclear energy programme developed by Iran, both the European Union and United States imposed sanctions, subsequently supported by the United Nations Security Council’s 2007 decision to impose additional sanctions (Resolution 1747).
- The UN Security Council then approved Resolution 1803 in 2008, which led to further sanctions being applied to the country. One of the consequences of these sanctions was that Sepah Bank, the second biggest bank in Iran, was prohibited from operating internationally.
- The UN Security Council imposed additional sanctions in June 2010 (Resolution 1929), which placed restrictions on the majority of banks in Iran.
- In 2011, the UK government advocated for the Central Bank of Iran to be completely prohibited from participating in international business activities (Guardian, Sep 2011).

This suggests that the government Iran is in fact starting to think and behave in a manner similar to entrepreneurs in the country by adopting a more anti-fragile approach. As proposed by Proper, greater learning can be made from a small number of surprises compared to multiple affirmations. As previously mentioned, Iran plans to support the petroleum production by-products for end users who are local and those who are international and to decrease its dependence on the direct exports of unrefined oil with the aim of taking its place as the leading exporter of petrochemical materials in the Middle East (NPC, 2016). Such an achievement

would make Iran significantly less vulnerable to fluctuations in oil prices (potentially even benefiting from fluctuations) and would also reduce the impact of oil price changes on its currency exchange rates, which are a source of considerable chaos with regard to their short and long-term impacts on practically all areas with no clear boundaries.

In summary, the author has outlined a scalable ‘anti-fragile’ strategy that is conducive to both the aspirations of entrepreneurs in Iran to survive as well as the goals of the state in its entirety as well as the various manufacturing sub-sectors. Anti-fragility has particular importance in conditions characterised by uncertainty and chaos that result from ‘artificial’ risk generating activities. The author endeavours to confirm this principle based on evidence gleaned from the experience of peers within the business community. The aim of this thesis is to exploit the long-term ‘slings and arrows of outrageous fortune’ by specifically focusing on the strategies adopted by entrepreneurs in Iran to survive when faced with the abovementioned conditions, which do not adhere to the principles of maximising profit or with equilibrium as the presumed cumulative impact of behaviours of multiple actors to maximise utility. Additionally, from a broader perspective, I aim to contribute to state strategy and strategy in general.

A large volume of literature has concentrated on the topic of strategy, and the majority if not all have not mentioned uncertainty or the ‘turbulence’ of the time (Peterson, Cumming and Carpenter, 2003). However, as will be demonstrated in this thesis, the majority of authors writing about strategy still contend that planning is feasible and advantageous. In the context of Iran, the author investigated and propose strategies that are ‘pragmatic’ and ‘conservationist’ as opposed to being ‘profit-maximising’ and ‘administrative’ (Thompson, 2018), according to the belief in the uncertainty of the future and that the world is essentially unpredictable.

When writing about strategy, many authors remain loyal to planning as their primary focus is on strategic management in the Western context, and although such countries remain

susceptible to significant black swan events like the 2007 global financial crisis, their economies and political systems have greater stability than Middle Eastern countries. From the perspective, although the ‘classical’ strategy model can still be applied to a certain extent in Western countries, it is particularly unsuitable for the Middle East where black swans occur on a daily basis at all levels, including in the political domain with interlinkages that cannot be accurately estimated. It is important to stress that what could be defined as ‘government interference’ (otherwise known as ‘government interference in Chicago’) is present in the ownership and control of virtually all Iranian sectors because this is the process by which funding is obtained by the various state organs. This extensive inter-penetration (as opposed to separation) among government and business (between the state and civil society) essentially invalidates most of the pertinence of the classical strategy literature that makes the assumption that the state, market and civil society are definitely separated. As contended by C. Wright Mills, although actors could transition between different domains during their lives (such as by moving from the military to business, then government and returning to business), such activities are separated by clearer boundaries in the United States compared to Iran.

A factor that has equal importance is that the standard functionalist textbook economic assumption that fundamental ‘market forces’ will consistently seek to create equilibria - even if the reality is that this can never be accomplished – appears to even more improbable in the context of Iran.

A number of different opposing recommendations were made by Taleb to the Chicago/Wall Street orthodoxy:

- Individuals do not have a good understanding of the problems confronting them, characterising them incorrectly as comprehensible and capable of being solved. He claimed that “Some can only be more intelligent than others in a structured environment” (Taleb, 2011). Additionally, when being interviewed by Bloomberg

in 2011, Taleb stated that “*the world we live in is vastly different from the world we think we live in*”. To put it in other way, he categorises people into two distinct groups in his book named anti-fragile, namely “those who fall apart during times of crisis, and those who profit from them” (Taleb,2012).

- Several months after “*The Black Swan*” was published, the majority of actors were still not aware that Wall Street had made a gross underestimation in terms of the threat of an unparalleled decline in the US housing market – with the calamitous outcome that ‘inaccurate prices’ were transferred via a ‘securitisation’ strategy after reaching a critical point. Additionally, he issued a warning via the New York Times that “Fannie Mae (*The Federal National Mortgage Association*) is sitting on dynamite with taxpayer’s money” (Taleb, 2003)
- Financial analysts and banking professionals considered that the knowledge they possess is superior to others. Although peasants understand that they are incapable of predicting the future, Wall Street bankers hold (or held) the belief that this was possible for them and behaved in a corresponding manner. In an article, he penned for Time Magazine, Taleb emphasised that bankers were taking significant risks with people’s money, which placed them in a precarious situation. He stated that “when I trade, I do not have an agency problem; I have my neck on the line. When bank or bankers trade, it is not his neck on the line” (Taleb, 2011). By taking risks with the assets of others and benefiting from their speculative achievements without being penalised for their speculative failures, risks were being enhanced to a level that exceeded normal comprehension and safeguards.
- On several occasions, Taleb revisits the hypothesis that everyone, Wall Street traders included, generally miscalculate the risks and effects of uncommon events. “The banking system, betting against black swan, has lost more than \$1 trillion-

more than was ever made in the history of banking” (Taleb, 2007). Once *The Black Swan* was initially published in April 2007, it should have become obvious to readers that the existing risk models were inappropriately designed for the uncommon and catastrophic black swan events. It was only after this fact became particularly evident that more people began to purchase the book.

- A general level of ignorance has imposed extremely high costs on the generations of the future.
- Even though the crisis has been caused by financial institutions and banks, value is being transferred to them by the state. This previously happened during the real-estate crash of 1990 when “*The Federal Reserve bank protected them at our expense: when conservative bankers make profits, they get the benefits; when they are hurt, we pay the cost*” (Taleb, 2007).
- Bank should be regarded as utilities.
- Banks tend to conceal risks and they should refrain from engaging in this practice. In an interview with Bloomberg (2011), Taleb similarly noted that they are venturing and gambling on the investments, but “when the things collapse you and I should pay the bill” (Taleb, 2011).
- Normal customers suffer the consequences of banks’ risk-taking activities (risks adopted by financial institutions are socialised).
- The compensation (pay) received by bankers should not exceed that awarded to civil servants. “It is not a good idea to trust corporations with matters such as rare events, the executives which are not observable will show good performance just to obtain their yearly bonus.
- Hammurabi's Codes that cover Trade Liability are considered the best rules governing the management of risk ever conceived and are therefore highly

applicable to Wall Street. In his book, Taleb noted that Hammurabi's Code “is a 3,800-year-old Babylonian law that stipulated that If a builder builds a house for a man and does not make its construction firm, and the house which he has built collapses and causes the death of the owner of the house, that builder shall be put to death”. On the other hand, Taleb claimed that ‘there is no downside’ for bankers (Taleb, 2007). Taleb concluded that the investors should have full knowledge of the trading system and that the risks should be shared by both bankers and investors alike.

- Markets should be comprehended in a different way. Taleb stated that their understandings are generally based on the analysis of patterns while ignoring the effects of unpredictability and unusual coincidence. If the limits of inferences that can be obtained from statistical data is are considered, significant harm can occur (2012).
- Taleb is adamant that his thesis is not completely original. The analytical instruments that allowed us to understand the workings of Wall Street have existed for more than 200 years. They do not make the assumption that (social) phenomena have a normal distribution under bell curves, acknowledging the presence of highly skewed distributions that are more commonly observed for social phenomena (e.g., the distribution of wealth) in comparison to natural phenomena (e.g., people’s height).
- Those who are primarily the cause of the problems are people who are not capable of admitting where their knowledge is lacking and whose overconfidence can lead to significant damage that may have no limit.

- Additionally, Taleb hypothesises that man's evolutionary psychology that is oriented towards natural risks is insufficient with regard to the assessment of social phenomena that are not governed by, as he termed it, 'the Laws of Gravity'.

The primary concepts using the language of observation and suggestion of Taleb will be briefly introduced below:

- Antifragility vs Convexity. Taleb predominantly concentrates on benefits that can be acquired as a result of chaos. He categorises the different actors (institutions, individuals) into three key groups: the fragile, robust and the anti-fragile.
- Fooled by Randomness. Social systems are typically characterised by their randomness. Nevertheless, due to evolutionary biology, man's thinking is generally oriented towards the estimation of natural phenomena that are more ordered than phenomena that are created socially like financial markets, commerce and contemporary warfare. When randomness is underestimated, this can lead to significant errors that are a source of inappropriate lessons. For instance, there is a general lack of appreciation of the role that luck plays in financial markets and life. Taleb stresses that people often recognise and are accepting of randomness when they fail (poor luck), as opposed to when they succeed (The observed abilities, in this case, are attributed to the capabilities).

1.5 Methodology: Interview using Taleb Theory and Approach

Methodology is a wide domain focused on the study of all facets of method such as epistemology (The research examines the question of how one can purport to know what is believed to be known), ontology (the study of the essence of phenomena, such as 'paradigm assumptions' regarding the essence and function of the social domain in its entirety), suitable types of comparison as well as more technical decisions including the choice and planning of research methods.

In this thesis, the focus is on selecting a suitable technique to conduct comparative interviews. According to the limitations author established, the selection of interview participants and the interview design were required to conform with the principles of Taleb. With regard to ontology, it is evident that the writing of Taleb is situated in the ‘chaos paradigm’, whereby minor changes in antecedent conditions can lead to massive shifts, the prediction of which is either very hard or not possible, and tracing them is equally challenging. The inference can be made that if Taleb is correct, actors whose understanding of the world is different, namely who comprehend phenomena differently and whose actions are not consistent with the world as perceived by Taleb, could encounter significant problems. On the other hand, the expectation can be made that actors whose paradigm assumptions are compatible with the essence of the world in which people live will behave in a manner that produces more advantageous results for them. Specifically, it is logical to differentiate actors who adopt ‘anti-fragile’ policies from practitioners who follow classical ‘functionalist’ business approaches aimed at identifying and trusting trends in previous events according to the belief that they can be utilised for managing future events, and who believe that the world seeks to find an equilibrium (in other words, a desirable conclusion will ultimately be reached). This means that the aim is to separate people who perceive a world in which black swan events are frequent occurrences from those who believe that they are rare.

Additionally, a notion that is in line with the ‘chaos paradigm’ is that every interviewee should be free to provide specific information on their personal experiences. The assumption can be made that one interviewee will have encountered circumstances and challenges that will differ from the following interviewee. This suggests that respondents should be asked questions that are tailored to their specific experience according to the responses they give to previous questions. The author made the decision to name this method ‘Talebian Interviewing’. A Talebian approach to interviewing can be considered ‘qualitative’ due to the fact it recognises

the importance of minor details in a world characterised by chaos (where every detail may be a critical point). Additionally, it has ‘qualitative’ features in that interviewees report events that can probably not be combined to form forecastable trends of ‘social facts’. If one accepts the chaos paradigm, then logically then this should also apply to respondents who make the (incorrect) assumption that the world largely has an ordered nature, seeks equilibrium and has clear patterns.

Distinct paradigm assumptions, such as the ‘Conflict Paradigm’, which suggests that the world is explosive and fuelled by conflict, would have resulted in different interview methods being used, which the author chose not to adopt.

Put differently, as well as recognising that the participants were taken from different sample groups (Iranian entrepreneurs who have survived and experienced petrochemical managers), all the interviews were performed by tailoring the questions to the individual to the greatest extent possible. Even though the researcher had considered a broad range of primary concepts and keywords (chaos, anti-fragility, narrative fallacy, etc.), he preferred to offer the interviewees the flexibility to lead the interviews in a direction of their choosing. Consequently, they could give flexible answers to flexible questions based on the themes that gradually emerged as the interview progressed. The author perceived no benefit in imposing his methodology such that it conformed to the standard account of method. The approach author has adopted cannot be defined as either ‘Quantitative Positivism’ or ‘Qualitative Interpretivism’ due to the fact that:

- 1) It contains an element of positivist hypothesis testing where ‘Survival’ is treated as the ‘Dependent Variable’, while the existence or lack of ‘Anti-fragile practices’ is the ‘Independent Variable’.
- 2) It is somewhat dependant on qualitative evidence similar to a detective investigation

- 3) Despite not being small, it was expected that the sizes of the sample extracted from every sampling frame would start to produce results that would defy explanation based on chance probabilities.

In summary, while the responses of one entrepreneur who had survived would be different to those of another, when viewed in their entirety, the responses of such entrepreneurs should exhibit significant differences to those of experienced petrochemical managers. The platitude ‘every quality has a quantity and every quantity has a quality’ should be noted. Regardless, the samples should be significantly different despite the fact that every interview is strongly dependent on the responses of the interviewee.

When author say ‘consistent with Taleb’, this implies that the course of the interviews will be guided by the experiences and reasoning of the respondents. The primary objective of Talebian interviewing is to determine to what type of knowledge Iranian businesspersons have gained from unexpected events and how they did so (with no necessity for them to have previous knowledge regarding the black swan event theory of Taleb). According to the personal experience of the researcher of surviving as an entrepreneur in Iran, it was expected that Iranian businesspersons with the highest levels of independence (outside the government sector) would exhibit implicit and tacit knowledge about black swans due to the fact that have encountered various unforeseen events in the significantly volatile political and economic environment of Iran, based on which they have acquired the ability to behave in what Taleb would acknowledge to be an anti-fragile manner. Conversely, managers who are on permanent salaries will have gained different learning when experiencing surviving events, which is likely not appropriate. From their perspective, unexpected events will be considered the exception rather than the norm, and they will assume that the normal business environment will ultimately be restored after the ‘exogenous factors’ like sanctions imposed by the international community have ended.

Even though Taleb perceives himself to be an ‘anti-theorist’, the black swan/anti-fragile framework he proposed does offer a robust alternative option when one considers that the Middle East is a particularly ‘chaotic environment’ that is not conducive to what Taleb refers to as ‘Platonic’ methodology. (Taleb, 2007). Rather than seeking ‘deep’ patterns, he promotes ‘Stochastic tinkering’ as well as short-term experimentation, which concurs with the assumption of Lindblom and Popper regarding the highly provisional nature of knowledge and its vulnerability to refutation at any time. The expectation is that entrepreneurs who have achieved success (by surviving) will partake in stochastic tinkering on a daily basis, which concurs with evidence based on my personal experiences.

According Taleb, theory can largely be disregarded as being ‘mythology’ (Taleb, 2011, 2014). He contends that theorists frequently apply visually pleasing patterns that offer false reassurance to events that do not justify such constructions. The example described below illustrates the implication of being too quick to theorize, as discussed by him. The specific example which have selected is taken from the perspective of a child, who is cognisant of the ridiculousness of over-theorising. It effectively supports the point Taleb is trying to make:

Figure 2 An Illustration of Narrative Fallacy “Marshmallows or Elvis? What you see in the clouds might say something about you! (Washington Post, 2021)

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“The exploration for the Spirit that Never Was. A familiar illustration of ‘narrative fallacy’ applied to a chaotic phenomenon” (Taleb, 2011, 2014).

In this case, one might be tempted to observe the profile of a face in the cloud looking in a leftward direction viewed from the side, in addition to another face that has less clarity to the side of it that is looking in the same direction, where both are possibly are staring at the same object in the distance. They are both male faces, the former that of a middle-aged man and the latter, closer one being much older. It is possible to expand this obviously nonsensical ‘narrative fallacy’. One might believe that based on the similarities between their faces, the elderly man is the other man’s father and that they are engaged in a dialogue. They appear to be contemplative in the expectation that something will occur. A highly appealing but implausible interpretation may be that they are ‘spirits’ that have temporarily appeared from men who lived in the forests lying under the clouds. By thinking imaginatively, it is possible to take this narrative further by fitting it with uncommon weather events determined chaotically that coincidentally occurred at the same time as an event in which men were brutally killed as part of a massacre that happened in the forest precisely two centuries previously. Certainly, children are capable of realising that the shapes seen in the clouds are merely random illusions, and when partaking in this theorising game, do not make the error of mistaking the disordered processes by which such shapes are formed in the clouds with actual humans or events in history. However, author agrees with Taleb’s assertion that professional scholars find it exceedingly hard not to over-theorise evidence that they should avoid over-theorising. For example, he refers to the case involving the capture of Saddam Hussein, which Bloomberg TV subsequently exploited in an attempt to ‘explain’ movements in the market that in reality had a chaotic nature...in fact, the capture of the Iraqi leader was utilised for the purpose of ‘explaining’ how the market rose and fell. What is meant here is that the process of theorizing should be delayed whenever feasible, and the scope of hypotheses should be kept limited to

the greatest extent possible. In Protestant Ethic Capitalism era (1930), Max Weber proposed the argument that history should be understood as coincidental, and it is important to avoid theorizing it with unique general causes that extend beyond the perceptions of individuals and the world in which they lived during that era. (Weber and Swedberg, 1999). He concurs with Taleb that social history is not governed by laws and that history does not follow an inherent direction. Describing actors as being “correct” or on ‘incorrect’ is largely illogical.

From a methodological perspective, this renders the thesis somewhat atypical. Author theorises that the survival of entrepreneurs in Iran can be best achieved if they think and act in an anti-fragile manner (as previously discussed). It is the expectation that they consider multiple ‘counter-factual’ to their minor and short-run theories, and exhibit significant sensitivity to counter-factual evidence when it emerges. They do not completely ignore ‘negative data’ and are in fact highly sensitive to it. It is the theory that they tend not to over-theorise and do not seek patterns where they are not present (their perceptions of faces in clouds are that they are merely illusions). They are highly immune to such illusions and are quick to dismiss them. The theory (which is partially an epistemological theory) is that they are tolerant of minor financial losses on a variety of smaller projects and are prepared to rapidly change their minds with a fatalistic-pragmatic shoulder shrug. This way of doing business can lead to significant transaction costs, one of which is that they are required to focus much of their attention, potentially all the time that they are awake, on being worried about and ‘tinkering’ with their business. Such entrepreneurs are highly averse to risk.

In conclusion, author hypothesise that Iranian entrepreneurs who survive will exhibit anti-fragility, particularly when compared with managers working for large business who receive fixed salaries.

1.6 Practice of Anti-Fragile Business in the Real World and in Business Associate

The author of this thesis has been involved in the petrochemical industry as well as other sectors in Iran for the last decades. The author contend that experience and evidence are not sufficient to fully determine the limits to the possibilities in these areas. Although Lindblom made this point with regard to public policy decisions (Lindblom, 1959), it is just as applicable, and potentially more so, to the decisions made by entrepreneurs. The ‘science of muddling through’ acknowledges the reality that it is practically impossible to obtain complete knowledge, is aware that ‘preferences’ are only elucidated when directly confronted with decisions and trade-offs, and plans established on the basis of specific and rigid objectives ultimately lead to disappointment and frustration. Taleb further states that existing computational power is insufficient to predict the impacts that *extremely small* changes will have, or when such events will occur. Efforts to conduct what Lindblom denounces as ‘root and branch analysis’ are likely to fail, although actors will sometimes accurately predict what will occur, but not the underlying reasons for such events.

A more beneficial strategy is to employ daily experience to describe the virtually limitless eventualities that could be opened up by even a relatively small number of variables. This approach can be investigated by interviewing various key actors and decision-makers within specific sectors in order to identify their operational strategies on a daily and weekly basis. In fact, their preferences in terms of timeframes represent a critical aspect of my interview methodology:

- To what extent do they look back in terms of their causal narratives?
- To what extent are they dependent on them?
- How frequently do events take them by surprise?
- How often have they been required to alter their narratives?

- Do they take into consideration the period after the following three months or the events that transpired before the preceding three months?
- Are they forgiving in terms of their own errors or those made by others?
- Are they forthcoming with information about their failures with their peers, attempt to conceal their mistakes or resolute about the fundamental truths of their beliefs with themselves and other people?
- Is it their expectation that their business colleagues will provide them information about all positive and negative black swans?
- Are they tolerant of negative news?
- Do they monitor the minor details?

In the following chapter, the author will explore a variety of classical strategic methods, widely known in the scholarly literature, which author contend are all susceptible to the ‘narrative fallacy’ in ways that entrepreneurs who have survived in Iran are not. Creativity exercises including Back-casting, Two by Two Space Matrix, PESTLE, SWOT and (Scenario Development) are regarded as only having potential advantages in the short term and worryingly exhibit vulnerability to black swan events.

Nevertheless, the author start by delineating the sceptic position of Taleb.

1.7 Research Questions, Theoretical Synthesis

In this thesis, the primary research question is: “Do Iranian entrepreneurs and strategic managers behave as Taleb would recommend and therefore survive? How successful is anti-fragility in chaotic circumstances?”

A research question associated with this emerges with regard to the thinkability of anti-fragile strategies. “How are surviving Iranian entrepreneurs able to feel what they feel, think what they think and act the way they act, while senior petrochemical managers are able to feel, think and act very differently?” In this context, author identify both a deficiency in the literature

and an intriguing partial overlap between the “Black Swan Theory” of Taleb and “Grid-Group Cultural Theory” (G-GCT) proposed by Michael Thompson. It is the author’s aim to resolve this deficiency in addition to emphasising the partial overlap. It is the belief that the contributions of both Taleb and Thompson to management science could be enhanced if they were to take the thinking of the other into account. To the best of the author understanding, this represents the first attempt to bring together Taleb and Thompson with the aim of deducing what they would say to each other, and due to the formal and specific nature of the overlap and distinctions between them, it is the belief that the exercise will involve minimal uncertainty.

1.8 Gaps in the Research,

From a theoretical perspective, author supports this aim by suggesting that the synthesis of Grid-Group Cultural Theory with what Taleb chooses to name his ‘anti-theory of Black Swan Events can be beneficial. The black swan argument is advantageous in that it increases cognisance of unpredictability and the significance of surprise events. It is important to note that all four of the ‘thought styles’ discovered by Michael Thompson (described below) should be considered as each of them is specifically sensitive to four distinct types of surprises. As will be demonstrated, although the different thought styles of ‘Hierarchical’, ‘Egalitarian’, ‘Individualistic’ and ‘Fatalistic’, are equally reasonable, they all reason and act in different ways. G-GGCT reveals the significance and the roles that various rationalities play in social systems, like economies. It provides a universalistic four-way typology of risk and reactions to risk, rather than the universalistic two-way typology of Taleb (grounded on what Taleb describes as the ‘Platonic’ versus ‘Stoic’ world views). The author feel that if black swan theory is to be expanded across the world, it is important to consider the dimension and potentials determined by Thompson, particularly with regard to the fact that four distinct ‘risk seasons’ exist as well as the four (as opposed to two) ways in which they can be successfully survived. As will be observed, Thompson simply but powerfully explains the rationale behind the actions

of different actors in addition to why they change course. The overlap to which author will make reference is between what Taleb defines as ‘Anti-fragile’ strategy and Thompson’s notion of the ‘Fatalistic Thought Style’, both of which are largely averse to risk. There is an additional overlap between what Taleb perceives to be a typical underestimation of risk by banking and financial professionals and what Thompson considers to the ‘Hierarchical’ and ‘Individualistic’ styles of thought, which also perceive the world as being comparatively benign and characterised by order.

Prior to commencing with the delineation of this possible synthesis, it is necessary to describe an unsuccessful business orthodoxy and Taleb’s assessment of it.

1.9 Summary

Randomness is a much more significant factor in people’s lives than they typically realise. The author is susceptible to ‘Survivorship Bias’s’ where the assumption is made that being moderately successful can be attributed to the effort applied and talent, whereas being extremely successful is determined by luck. In Taleb’s ‘4th Quadrant Problem’, the plausible limits of statistical knowledge regarding what is correct, incorrect and merely anecdotal is mapped. Taleb acknowledges that the problem has greater complexity than it seems, although the result is that statistics “is aimed at the scientist-charlatan putting society at risk using statistical methods” bitterly noting that this is similar to iatrogenic, whereby medical treatment can cause a patient more harm than good. He further remarked that people who increase the risk for society are not genuine statistical experts. He chose to define this risk zone as ‘the fourth quadrant’. This metaphor involves a map that identifies safe zones, outside of which knowledge can be questioned and there is a high level of uncertainty. According to this map metaphor, one can reasonably estimate things within the safe zone, whereas the risks within other zones (activities) are unknown and could be severe. Such quadrant maps enable different actors to identify where their knowledge is lacking so that they can avoid such activities.

Taleb is very eager to help readers to visualise their lack of knowledge that he refers to the notion of an ‘Anti-library’ containing books that have not been read. This is an idea that is easy to grasp: the content of books that author has yet to read is unknown to us. Otherwise, it is hard to understand the problem of the lack of awareness of the inability to know the things that humans do not know, generally defined as ‘unknown unknowns’, an incalculable amount of which have larger impacts than ‘known knowns’. Unknown unknowns that cannot be known have greater importance than the things we know. Excessive significance is often attached to what is known.

According Taleb, his heroes are ‘erudite’, as they are focused on increasing their knowledge beyond what they already know. "The people I go after are the false experts, those who do not accept the limits of their knowledge" (Taleb, 2007).

In this thesis, the aforementioned concepts will be operationalised and applied to the Iranian context. Author will specifically focus on:

- Production capacity as well as the promotion of ‘anti-fragility’ in industrial sectors that are positioned (or can be formed) downstream from the exploration and production of oil and gas.
- From a narrower perspective, the research will focus on eliciting, evaluating and disseminating anti-fragile approaches, starting with a group of my own business colleagues and peers within Iran - along with my personal development – who have demonstrated the ability to survive and prosper for many years. Author have witnessed other business associates who have focused on maximizing proficiency, optimizing efficiency and achieving ‘shooting star’ like success, which has ultimate resulted in prominent failures. To achieve this, it is necessary to conduct in-depth discussions with those who have survived and ethical approval based on University’s Ethical Approvals.

- Previously mentioned failures are sufficiently visible that evidence gained from interviews is not required, and similarly, it is not necessary to seek ethical approval as information on such outcomes is publicly available.

The Environment, which refers to phenomena that are created socially as opposed to those that naturally formed, is characterised by significant uncertainty. Within Iran, black swan events not only occur frequently, but are the norm in the business environment, and it is also not possible to accurately predict them in terms of their characteristics and outcomes, thus making controlling them very challenging (Taleb, 2009). Technology and technology transfers are also susceptible to positive and negative fortunes, an example of which is the significant contracts that were recently signed between Iranian Oil Company and Total. Again, it is exceedingly hard to predict the content and timing of technology transfers as demonstrated by internal attempts to import superior quality injection-moulding equipment from Germany into Iran.

2 Chapter 2

Literature Review: The Unwise Exploration for Certainty

2.1 Introduction

Taleb recommends that black swan events should be considered according to the assumption that “*some times what you don't know is more important than what you know*”. This concurs with his argument that it is hard to determine where author has sufficient knowledge and where the knowledge is lacking. Put differently, ‘mapping’ uncertainties are challenging.

Such assumptions are based on the idea that long-term planning is possible. The aim of an anti-fragility ‘strategy’ is largely just to survive by frequently changing or reversing course. Certainly, author acknowledge that to a certain extent, long-range planning cannot be avoided when significant investments are made and it is only possible to realise returns in the long term, if such returns are possible at all. This can be exemplified by the Channel Tunnel constructed to link France and England, major container ports, country and cross-country space programmes, the design of new fleets of new types of civil aircraft, coal, gas, nuclear hydroelectric and renewable power plants, new petroleum refineries, massive dockyards, the development of offshore oil and gas fields, among others. However, to the greatest extent possible, based on the principles of Taleb, decisions should be delayed when possible. For instance, it is logical that turbine halls should be constructed prior to the construction of heat-exchangers, pressure vessels, and before the source of energy has been determined (such as oil, gas, coal, waste, or nuclear).

Generally accepted economic theory is challenged by anti-fragility in unexpected ways. For instance, economics based on equilibrium contends that during an extended economic crisis, firms are negatively impacted, particularly SMEs. According to the theory, it is expected that their sales will decrease, profits will shrink, debt levels will rise and they will find it difficult to meet their obligations towards their suppliers. On the other hand, multiple researchers (see He and Casey, 2015) have demonstrated that the effect on certain sectors is largely minimal, and they even achieve significant growth with exceptional yields. They have

taken advantage of the crisis and unexpected helpful opportunities and smaller companies could be suitably agile to grasp such opportunities. Distinct firms that offer services or products that vary only *marginally* in the same geography experience wildly different growth trajectories, particularly where such services and products are ‘extendable’ with zero marginal costs where the cost to produce the n th unit is identical to the first. (In this context, author is referring to web-based applications that have exhibited exponential growth (Facebook, YouTube) while other applications that are virtually the same have failed and disappeared into oblivion (Friends Reunited, AOL.)

The returns on non-extendable (finite) big-scale products (like container ports etc.) are only realised in the long term, which means that significant changes can occur in the world during this time. Ensuring that such projects are not ‘too big to fail’ would require the project’s scale to be limited and ‘modularised’ to the greatest extent feasible; alternatively, investments should be made in projects that are conducive to modularisation and modification. Nevertheless, author recognises that Taleb’s argument only extends so far, and after that point, governments will be required to serve as guarantors. However, author would like to clarify that this problem is not the focus of the current thesis. Rather, author aims to explore anti-fragile strategies where they are applied and to consider (as a broader objective) how an anti-fragile diversification strategy (etc.) could be beneficial for Iran (or other economies and societies) in order to mirror the actions of its entrepreneurs who have adopted anti-fragile approaches. Similar to Taleb, author contend that a ‘paradigm-shift’ is required (Kuhn, 1962).

A paradigm can be described as a significant volume of writing in which identical basic assumptions are shared. Despite the possibility of refuting the previously mentioned argument that grand theories should be avoided, one can also define a paradigm as a comprehensive theory regarding the essence of the world (an ontology) in which a minimum number of propositions is used in an attempt to describe everything. For instance, according to the Marxist

‘conflict’ paradigm’, the assumption is made that history is given a *direction* as a result of “*contradictions in the mode of production*” (Marx, 1970) fuelled by class conflicts. On the other hand, the ‘functionalist’ paradigm argues that all components of a system have a purpose and are important for the system’s ‘health’, which under regular conditions nears an equilibrium balance (homeostasis), apart from situations where the system is disrupted by ‘exogenous’ causes and ‘pathologies’. Despite the fact Taleb has never used the term ‘paradigm’ when referring to his personal thinking (likely due to his suspicion of grand theories), it is clear that this is the case when he uses statements such as *the world is chaotic and nonlinear* when making his arguments. The contention that the world is characterised by chaos and non-linearity as well as that the lack of certainty will ultimately thwart efforts to develop long-term strategies is a powerful paradigm assertion, which profoundly contests the two aforementioned paradigms (Marxism, functionalism). Contrarily, it claims that history has no clear direction and also claims with the same level of conviction that a state of equilibrium can never be reached or even approached in the world.

In the following section, an appraisal will be provided by the author that can be defined as ‘intellectual’; nevertheless, the observations that follow are based on diverse experiences of operations (survival) in situations characterised by significant uncertainty which exhibit minimal indicators that could be considered to show ‘equilibrium’ (examined in a separate discussion).

2.2 Chaos Paradigm

According to the Chaos paradigm, fluctuations in phenomena (social phenomena in this context), whether they are social, environmental or political, are inherently non-linear. This paradigm also asserts that all antecedents and outcomes are non-linear. The focus of the paradigm is on the "generated movement of a nonlinear system, the evolution of the system in

time, the determination of the current state of the system at a given prehistory" (Buckley, 2006). When writing about uncertainty, authors appear to have slightly more confidence when attempting to describe systems that are natural rather than social based on the recognition that a (natural) science of uncertainty and of the unforeseeable *may* exist, which would concentrate on providing an explanation of how the unforeseeable can be predicted and controlled (Snaselova and Zboril, 2015). However, regardless of whether the ontology of a natural or social system is being described, evidence and vectors are not treated by this paradigm with anything approaching the same level of confidence in terms of forecasting¹ associated with

¹ According to my research, the traditional differentiation between a *prediction* and *forecast* was that *predictions* are made when one knows every antecedent condition (which are assumed to have relevance by a predictive model) with a high level of certainty and precision. A *forecast* recognises that antecedent conditions that are known, measured or estimated but may have potential relevance could exist. Therefore, the *prediction* can be made that a) water at b) atmospheric pressure, which c) includes no impurities d) has a boiling point of 100°C. However, the same level of certainty does not apply when attempting to *forecast* the weather on a given day. In general, the majority of social phenomena theories can only provide forecasts rather than predictions due to the fact that it is not possible to define social phenomena in the same specific and exclusive way as the boiling point of water. Additionally, social theories that can be tested should not be defined as 'deductive', even though they frequently are! Deductive statements *follow logically and necessarily* from their premises. For instance, it can clearly be deduced that: a) if a mountain climber has a hat on his/her head and b) if the mountain climber is positioned at the peak of the mountain, then c) the hat must be higher than the top of the mountain. Social theories generally acknowledge that alternative possibilities may exist that could explain the phenomenon that the theory is intended to describe. Where a theory is not capable of excluding the potential for different theoretical explanations to exist for the identical phenomenon, then it should be defined as being 'inferential' rather than 'deductive'. For instance, there is no consensus among economists regarding the reasons for unemployment. A possible approach would therefore be to devise a theory that provides a better explanation for the 'variance' (upwards and downwards fluctuations in the rate of unemployment) compared to other theories. However, it is not possible for one unemployment theory to completely exclude other theories, which is why they are considered inferential and not deductive.

The qualitative or quantitative nature of the data is immaterial. Even though quantitative research is considered to be 'deductive' by multiple authors, this is erroneous. It is only possible to state quantitative research findings at a level of confidence that is *less* than complete certainty. Likewise, in a court trial, juries are largely required to make their assessment using qualitative evidence and therefore a defendant can only be convicted on the 'balance of the evidence'. For example, an individual may be caught in the possession of a 'smoking gun', which is considered qualitative evidence. However, it is certainly possible, although unlikely that a) the gun was put in the hand of the supposed perpetrator by somebody else, b) the real perpetrator escaped before anyone else came to the scene. The possibility also exists that c) the main witnesses were not truthful in their statements to the police or d) the police fabricated the story of the 'smoking gun' for their own purposes. Lastly, e) the accused may not be guilty and there could be an attempt to frame him/her to make it appear that he/she had committed the crime. Even if forensic tests prove that the striations on the bullet taken from the victim correspond to those on a bullet fired from the same gun in laboratory testing, the possibility exists that f) the smoke emanating from the gun that the defendant was holding was the result of a blank round being fired. In this situation, although the intention of the accused was to murder the victim, they may have already been killed several minutes prior to this event by another individual who fired a live shell using the identical gun. Furthermore, additional unlikely alternatives exist that cannot be disregarded with complete certainty.

In his seminal work *Conjectures and Refutations*, the philosopher Karl Popper contended that it is not possible to disregard the potential for empirical exceptions to exist for all theories that justify the moniker 'scientific'. Popper suggested that a theory can only be considered scientific if it can theoretically be 'tested' and disproven by 'counter-factual evidence'. This includes theories developed by police detectives; even the most

standard (e.g., Newtonian) laws of motion. Chaos theory dictates that small things can have massive impacts in a non-linear way with multiple inferred side effects. Additionally, chaos is also defined as any chaotic behaviour within a '*nonlinear dynamic system which is very sensitive to the initial condition*' (Rao, 2012). However, when describing natural systems, chaos theorists utilise deterministic algorithms when attempting to model them (Snaselova and Zboril, 2015), usually are very simple. These models can usually represent the patterns of emergent fractal which shows some regularity and illustrate life like can be similar to the empirical observation, therefore:

effective detectives are not always correct. Scientific theories should be regarded as being *provisional*, despite being confirmed on multiple occasions. According to Popper, scientists should seek evidence of black swans as *one* black swan alone can refute the theory that 'all swans are white'. He claimed that the evolution of a theory occurs on the basis of trial and error, and negative evidence in the form of 'black swans' is the most efficient means of ensuring that scientific progress is maintained. Hence, it can be replaced with a new theory asserting that 'all swans are either white or black', which is scientific as it remains open to the potential for pink or green swans, for example, being detected at some point and location in the future. Per Popper, although only deductive statements are correct, they generally are not informative. The example where the mountain climber's hat must be higher than the mountain on which he/she is standing can be described as lacking interesting information due to the fact that although the premises are true, the conclusion is evident. I would speculate that Popper might ask "You cannot even be absolutely sure that it is a *hat* that you can see. It might be something else including a speck of dirt on your glasses or if we are talking about a photograph, a fault in the printing process."

The likelihood that a researcher may perceive something that doesn't exist suggests that it is not always possible to trust 'counter-factual evidence' like 'black swans'. The evidence could be due to a measurement mistake or a hoax. Two kinds of errors are regarded as being risks that are always present. A "Type One Error" happens in the case where a 'false positive' is found by a researcher, like where an innocent person is found with a 'smoking gun' in their hands. A "Type Two Error" happens in cases where 'false negative' evidence is detected. For instance, a physician may make the incorrect assumption that a patient is not diagnosed with cancer as a result of their negative test results. However, the issue in this situation was the lack of sensitivity of the research method (such as a blood test) to support the physician's preliminary supposition that the symptoms of the patient could be due to cancer.

Infinity Patter from Chaos Draw by “Korush Govahi Kashani, 2007”.
“<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Qe5Enm96MFQ>”

For the financial market, which has a non-repeating model, see specifically Thompson (2018). In this article, Thompson references research that he conducted with a colleague in which they successfully created a comparatively simple and dynamic model grounded on a basic two-axis model of appetite for risk, “*Grid-Group Cultural Theory (G-GCT)*”, which also produces highly realistic simulations of the comparative success of all four ‘styles of thought’ in a variety of ‘risk environments. The four mentioned likelihoods are described by weak and strong “Social Regulation” on the vertical axis and weak and strong ‘Social Solidarity’ on the horizontal axis. Although a more in-depth description of the theory will be presented in a later section, it can be stated that Thomson derived four opposing but similarly rational stances on the basis of these two axes: the (Fatalist) ‘Pragmatist’, the (Hierarchical) ‘Manager’, the (Egalitarian) ‘Conservator’ and the (Individualistic) ‘Maximiser’. According to Thompson, his simulation based on G-GCT can be described as follows:

“The game consists of a “world” (which, of course, can be in any of four different states) of just 30 firms. Each of these firms has to survive, and if possible prosper, in its environment, which is nothing more than the other 29 firms. Each firm (or automaton in the artificial life terminology) has to latch onto one of the four strategies – Manager, Conservator, Maximiser or Pragmatist – thereby becoming an agent, but has to relinquish that strategy, and latch onto one of the other three, if it finds itself surprised in three consecutive rounds. These surprises, there are 12 in all, are supplied by our “surprise matrix” ... together with the various “triggers” for the transitions from one risk season to another... [These] are the “bottom-up” rules.”

(Thompson, 2018:8)

The dynamic nature of this model lies in the fact that a small number of actors are treated in an interactive way with the result that the ‘risk environment’ in which they are functioning is altered by their interactions. It is remarkable that the model reveals that each of the four particular styles of thought (detailed descriptions of which will be provided later) is particularly effective (or ineffective) in all of the four equally specific risk environments. The primary conclusion author wants to draw at this point is that despite the model being run on multiple occasions, it does not appear that the simulated sequences it produces will repeat or settle into an equilibrium condition. In other words, there is no indication of a cumulative pattern that could be used for forecasting the probable pattern that would emerge when the model is run the next time. Similar to the empirical records of financial markets in the real world (or a social phenomenon’s history), there are no repeating patterns in Thompsonian modelling, which supports the hypothesis that in general, history is not repeated in social systems and future events cannot be known prior to their occurrence. It should be noted that in the previously mentioned Thompsonian model, there is a maximum of four rationalities and thirty actors. In reality, estimating the number of actors within a social system is hard (for instance, there could be hundreds of thousands if not hundreds of millions of actors within a financial market if one considers investment-based pension scheme members). Nevertheless, as will be observed, regardless of the nature of the social system and the number of actors

within it, changes are dynamically explained by G-GCT by only utilising the four styles of thought (along with their hybrids). G-GCT is a basic chaos model that can successfully explain complicated and dynamic changes. Moreover, it can explain why attempts to forecast social systems are complex or ultimately end in failure.

Thompson offered the following description of his research:

“Nothing ever goes in a straight line, no trend goes on forever, no strategy is good for all seasons...[The] peaks and troughs are not evenly spaced, nor are they of constant amplitude. The same holds for the environment, the four seasons of risk come and go, but not always in the “right” sequence, and enduring sometimes (as with the “Great Moderation” that was presided over by Alan Greenspan) for an unseasonably long time. In other words, we have erratic cycles in which none of the strategies ever goes into permanent extinction, no clear “winner” ever emerges, things never settle down into some dynamic equilibrium. We have run the game, in its old and new forms, it dates from the 1980s, for thousands of rounds and no sequence of changes ever exactly repeats itself.”

(Thompson, 2018:8)

The work of Thompson demonstrates that simulations based on algorithms *can* be created for certain chaotic social systems at a minimum, although even if the simulation is constrained by artificial limits, such as only thirty actors in this case, then such systems are significantly irregular, cannot be predicted and are non-linear. Even describing them as being ‘systems’ is deceptive as pure systems would have specific boundaries, which cannot be said about real social systems as it is not possible to define their boundaries with any certainty.

What author is seeking is instances of non-linear and abnormal movements that have notable beneficial and detrimental outcomes. As will also be seen, what is perceived to be beneficial or detrimental is dependent on opposing but equally rational assessment criteria.

What may seem to indicate for one style of thought (rationality) could appear to indicate failure for additional Linked with those for ‘rationalities’) ... and with the negative and positive results (see also Jafarove, 2016). Thus:

The use of 'ill wind' is most commonly [used] in the phrase 'it's an ill wind that blows nobody any good'. This is first recorded in John Heywood's A dialogue containing the number in effect of all the proverbs in the English tongue, 1546:

*"As you be much the worse. and I cast away.
An yll wynde, that blowth no man to good, men say.
Wel (quoth he) euery wind blowth not down the corn
I hope (I saie) good hap [luck] be not all out worn."*

Heywood's meaning was that a wind that was unlucky for one person would bring good fortune to another. This sailing metaphor has frequently been invoked to explain good luck arising from the source of others' misfortune, and it probably pre-dates 1546.

<https://www.phrases.org.uk/meanings/ill-wind.html>

accessed 17 March, 2021)

It should be taken into account that such an quote which shows anti-theory ‘anti-paradigm’ would incorporate large general changes, but is also applicable to smaller aspects (Song and Shi, 2008; Curry, 2012). Referring to the ‘ill wind’ example, the actor that profits may be an individual, group, organisation or industrial sector or nation-state or treaty-system that involves multiple states like a nuclear non-proliferation treaty.

An implication of chaos theory that is particularly perturbing is that even if the preliminary state is *profoundly* understood, this may assist with comprehending the following changes and movements that occur after the initial phase. In as little as three steps, the number of different alternatives generated by miniscule initial changes is *exceptionally* large, such as movements in market prices (Taleb, 2008). Due to the fact that the world is defined by this paradigm as a place where multiple events occur, each of which could assert coincidental effects on the others

(Kiel, 1994), individually or when combined, it can even be challenging to confidently identify the antecedent events that triggered a specific change. Because the uncertainty surrounding explanations is high, they are not trusted in this paradigm.

2.3 System Dynamic Theory

System dynamics theory, as a branch of systems thinking, has made notable contributions to the understanding of chaos theory and its relevance to the work of Taleb (Meadows, 2008). System dynamics focuses on analysing the behaviour of complex systems over time, emphasizing the interconnectedness and feedback loops that shape system dynamics (Forrester, 1961). This approach recognizes the potential for small changes within a system to yield significant and unpredictable outcomes, aligning with the core principles of chaos theory (Lorenz, 1963).

The application of system dynamics provides a framework for studying the dynamics of complex systems, including financial markets, economies, and social systems (Richardson, 2011). By modelling and simulating these systems, researchers can explore the nonlinear relationships, feedback loops, and emergent properties that contribute to unexpected events and black swan phenomena (Sterman, 2000). The insights gained from system dynamics deepen the understanding of the inherent complexity and uncertainty present in real-world systems, challenging the limitations of traditional linear thinking and deterministic models (Senge, 1990).

Taleb's work, rooted in chaos theory and his expertise as a statistician and risk analyst, has played a crucial role in popularizing the concept of black swan events and the importance of embracing uncertainty in decision-making (Taleb, 2007). Taleb's ideas resonate with the principles of system dynamics, as both emphasize the nonlinearity of system behavior, the presence of feedback loops, and the potential for small changes to have disproportionate effects (Richardson, 2008).

Within the literature discourse, Morgan's "Images of Organization" provides an accessible and insightful treatment of how chaos theory, systems theory, and classical science converge to shape organizational life (Morgan, 2006). Additionally, Prigogine and Stengers' "The Limits of Classical Science" offers valuable perspectives on the limitations of traditional scientific frameworks and the need for new approaches to comprehend the complexity and unpredictability of natural and social systems (Prigogine & Stengers, 1984). These works contribute to the understanding of chaos theory and its application in various domains, including the analysis of black swan events and the development of anti-fragile strategies.

2.4 The Black Swan Theory

This explains why, in a world characterised by chaos, 'disconfirming-' 'counterfactual-cases' or 'refutations' (Popper, 1966) should be assigned greater importance compared to evidence that conforms to hypothetical assumptions. Put differently, a single 'black swan event' has more significance than multiple events that are expected to happen. As previously mentioned, in line with Popper, a solitary black swan is sufficient proof that all swans are not white, whereas any number of white swans is not enough proof that all swans are white. This is due to the fact that it is not possible to exclude the possibility that the subsequent observation or another one a long time in the future will contradict assumptions. With regard to affecting knowledge-development, unexpected anomalies have greater efficiency than confirming cases that provide reassurance. Therefore, greater effort should be applied to seeking such anomalies instead of seeking to confirm that the perception of how things function is correct.

As also mentioned, black swan events were defined by Taleb on basis of the particular criteria described below:

- An anomalous event that does not conform to normal expectations.
- Which also has significant effects.

- Due to the fact that man's evolutionary psychology is such that it allows us to sufficiently deal with natural (normally distributed) risks, people often attempt to explain black swan events on the basis of misleading narratives after they have occurred, thus rendering them events that can be explained and predicted (Taleb, 2007) when the reality is that they cannot be accurately estimated or theorised. As Taleb suggested, one can easily misinterpret the phrase 'no evidence of cancer' as meaning 'evidence of no cancer', (2007), as the desire is to have the latter. Errors are consistently caused by such narrative fallacies.

Exacerbating these challenges, even though extensive plans and meticulous arrangements are made, organisations continue to be confronted by unexpected 'unknown unknowns' (Green, 2011). Taleb (2007) stated that lengthy and very lengthy delays (that can sometimes not be estimated) could occur between an antecedent causal event and its subsequent effects. He makes reference to the ongoing and projected impacts of the First World War as well as the discovery of penicillin as two examples of this phenomenon. The offspring of dead young soldiers who were not born and the offspring of these hypothetical children and the things that they could have done in their lives that never transpired; the offspring of people whose lives were saved by penicillin, the offspring of their children and the things that they did in their lives are components of a continually broadening set of outcomes. Taleb defines excessive confidence in what we believe we know and a lack of sensitivity regarding things we do not know as 'epistemic arrogance'.

The breadth of this miscalculated issue is expressed by Taleb's discussion of the 'anti-library' thought experiment. Taleb contends that actors concentrate on and defend their acquired knowledge rather than acknowledge areas in which their knowledge is lacking and their understanding is limited. He makes a comparison between this limited understanding and books that have not been read. He makes the provocative argument that "Read books are far less valuable than unread ones. The library should contain as much of what you do not know.

Indeed, the more you know, the larger the rows of unread books. Let us call this collection of unread books an anti-library" (Taleb, 2012).

He also makes the convincing argument that the effects of unpredictable events are not proportionate. This is why he supports 'anti-fragility' (Taleb, 2007), similar to Green (2011).

In recent years, opposing arguments have been proposed against Taleb, suggesting that events are more conducive to forecasting than he believed (Werther, 2013), which will be carefully reviewed in a subsequent section. On the other hand, one cannot confidently claim that events like border disputes between countries, terrorist attacks, cyclical economic activity, as well as the imposition (and relaxation) of sanctions and their resulting effects can be precisely forecasted months or potentially hours or minutes (!) in advance. It is also extremely challenging to accurately forecast how such events will affect other events. In author's opinion, it appears to be safer to assume the same default position of Taleb that the world, or at a minimum an incalculably vast portion of it, is characterised by chaos and susceptible to positive and negative black swans that happen across undetermined time periods that cannot be easily defined or forecasted. Hence, the best option is to reduce their negative effects, render the enterprises 'anti-fragile' and amenable to positive black swans (Taleb, 2009), but not to the extent that this will draw the attention of the Iranian government and encourage them to take control of the venture.

Taleb (2007) recommends that people should be aware of four primary concepts:

'silent evidence'

- *platonic confirmation*' or *'confirmation error*'
- *'epistemic arrogance*', as mentioned
- *'future blindness*'. (Taleb, 2007)

2.4.1 Silent Evidence

Taleb explains this notion as the inclination of individuals to disregard aspects of a process that they cannot access and prefer aspects of the process that they can; put differently, as previously mentioned, increased focus on the things that they know rather than that which they do not know (2007). Resultantly, evidence that could exist stays ‘silent’ (unobserved), at least at the current time. Such evidence could become clearer at a time when its utility is no longer relevant. After such evidence, the occurrence of a black swan event becomes apparent, but only at that specific moment. Prior to that, it remains concealed or silent.

He also notes that silent evidence can be noticed but misinterpreted because it does not conform with how theories are preconceived, or due to the attempt to align it with patterns of evidence from the past. For instance, Taleb contends that it is a logical tendency to believe that 1,000 deaths resulting from a devastating earthquake in California are more probable as such deaths can be more easily visualised than 1,000 deaths caused by drowning in some part of the United States. Although the probability that the latter will occur is greater, it cannot be clearly imagined. Movies depicting disasters impacting San Francisco convey narratives that are evocative and unforgettable.

Taleb (2008) provides a different example regarding people’s inclination to overstate the abilities of a popular published writer while completely disregarding the abilities of the multitude of authors who have not successfully published their books (Taleb, 2008). The latter effectively depicts silent evidence. In general, the inclination to disregard silent evidence should be taken into account when exploring the approach actors take in terms of management for the future, specifically in chaotic conditions where there is an increased likelihood that silent phenomena will impact outcomes disproportionately. A core focus of this thesis is on the degree to which entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived show sensitivity to evidence that is silent from the perspective of different actors.

2.4.2 Chinese Farmer

In his critique of the *Story of the Chinese Farmer*, Alan Watts noted that ‘The whole process of nature is an integrated process of immense complexity, and it’s really impossible to tell whether anything that happens in it is good or bad — because you never know what will be the consequence of the misfortune; or, you never know what will be the consequences of good fortune.’ The following text describes the story:

Once upon a time there was a Chinese farmer whose horse ran away. That evening, all of his neighbours came around to commiserate. They said, “We are so sorry to hear your horse has run away. This is most unfortunate.” The farmer said, “Maybe.” The next day the horse came back bringing seven wild horses with it, and in the evening, everybody came back and said, “Oh, isn’t that lucky. What a great turn of events. You now have eight horses!” The farmer again said, “Maybe.” The following day his son tried to break one of the horses, and while riding it, he was thrown and broke his leg. The neighbours then said, “Oh dear, that’s too bad,” and the farmer responded, “Maybe.” The next day the conscription officers came around to conscript people into the army, and they rejected his son because he had a broken leg. Again, all the neighbours came around and said, “Isn’t that great!” Again, he said, “Maybe.”

(Watts, 2011)

2.4.3 Confirmation error:

The narrative exemplifies one of the main claims made by Taleb that connects ‘confirmation errors’ with ‘epistemic arrogance’: the inclination to only seek proof and confirmation while disregarding evidence that disconfirms a hypothesis (Taleb, 2007). This inclination exacerbates the previously mentioned inclination to disregard silent evidence. As stated by Taleb, "corroborating evidence of an idea or worldview is always readily abundant,

and by focusing exclusively on supportive instances, a wealth of information in the form of instances that do not support it is ignored." (Taleb, 2007).

Confirmation error has a close association with silent evidence, although silence is illustrated in a different way. Confirmation error (alternatively called confirmation bias) asserts positive confidence into a notion while disregarding the negative characteristics and inherent susceptibilities of that notion (Taleb, 2008). Nevertheless, the impacts are analogous to ignoring silent evidence.

Building on the work of Francis Bacon, David Hume, Charles Lindblom and Karl Popper, Taleb (2009) suggests that an approach that offers greater efficiency and effectiveness would be to determine all the evidence that does not correspond (as well as all of the shortcomings of the adopted concept). For instance, with regard to the candidates in an election, every candidate will do their utmost to overemphasise the positive things they intend to achieve going forward as well as the accomplishments they have made in the past such that followers will be encouraged to visualise their projected successes while simultaneously disregarding aspects of their political history that depict failures. Politicians generally exhibit extreme reluctance to admit and assume responsibility for errors they have made in the past. This could be resolved by adopting an anti-fragile approach where each political candidate or job applicant would be asked to describe the worst mistakes they have made and what this has taught them. However, the utility of anti-fragile questions is largely disregarded.

The issue of confirmation error is particularly relevant in environments characterised by significant chaos where people generally expect the unexpected. The hypothesis is that businesspersons who *survive* will be identified as being less susceptible to such bias than the typical agent.

2.4.4 Epistemic Arrogance

Taleb (2008) claimed that this issue is related to the differences between a) what an individual *believes* he/she knows and what he/she actually knows, and b) what he/she knows and does not know. Such failings are ‘epistemic’ in the sense that ‘epistemology’ is the study of the foundations on which we purport to know what we purport to know (Keat and Urry, 2011). The distinction between what we believe we know, what we actually know and our knowledge gaps is crucial: "if what they actually know exceeds what they think they know, that is humility and if what they think now exceed what they actually know, that is epistemic arrogance" (Taleb, 2008). Unknown knowns and known unknowns have significantly less risk compared with unknown unknowns and potentially known knowns. The primary outcome of epistemic arrogance is a restricted but overstated ability to manage and evaluate the unforeseeable, simultaneously overstating our knowledge while understating unpredictability (Taleb, 2008), which amounts to the ‘inability to account for the factors outside of a pre-defined set of parameters’ (2008). Additionally, author notes that such shortcomings affect the linear perspective of history propounded by Marxists that ignores deviations and that Marxism is protected against its inaccurate predictions (Popper, 1966/ 2013). The functionalist paradigm is also plagued by analogous deficiencies, which is immune to a flaw that can be clearly observed by those viewing from the outside, that depending on ‘exogenous factors’ for the purpose of explaining change (like an unexpected alteration in the demand level for a given commodity that necessitates a *response* from the markers) is clearly undesirable and cannot be justified as being an ‘explanation’.

The author suggest that epistemic arrogance was a characteristic of the administration of President George Bush Jr., specifically with regard to its foreign and economic policies; the same can be said for President Trump with respect to what he would be capable of achieving,

or has achieved, particularly with regard to foreign policy. In summary, the implications of epistemic arrogance are serious.

2.4.5 Future Blindness

‘Future blindness’ is defined on the basis of how the subject (actor) views the future according to their future projection of their previous experiences (Taleb, 2008). In this concept, the future is predicted (mapped) for the purpose of alleviating future unpredictability and to generate positive outcomes. However, it neglects to consider that this has been attempted by numerous others who have been unsuccessful. Taleb noted that it is "an element in the mechanics of how the human mind learns from the past and makes us believe in definitive solutions yet [without recognising] that those who preceded us thought that they too had definitive solutions" (Taleb, 2007). It should be noted that Taleb claims that the root cause of this and other reasons for failure is the evolutionary psychology of man. As has previously been suggested, a different point at which to start, Grid-Group Cultural Theory provides a cultural explanation for various ‘risk appetites’, opposing understandings of the issues confronting people and organisations as well as opposing solutions to such issues. These are mentioned due to the fact that the thinkability of ‘anti-fragility’ could be explained as a cultural outcome. From the four possible thinking styles that G-GCT specifies, *fatalism* effectively describes the emotions, thoughts and actions of entrepreneurs who have survived in Iran (see below). Put differently, the fatalistic style of thought exhibits greater sensitivity to risk and negative evidence and is careful to prevent mistakes. This style of thought is also less susceptible to ‘epistemic arrogance’, has increased sensitivity to unknowns and greater awareness of ‘silent evidence’ that different styles of thought tend to overlook. The author suspect that fatalistic thinking is linked with a smaller number of significant errors compared to the other three types of thinking.

Despite the fact that the author will be proposing G-GCT as a different option to the naturalistic explanation for ‘epistemic arrogance’ offered by Taleb that is grounded on

evolutionary psychology, the increased susceptibility of *Hierarchical-*, *Egalitarian* and *Individualistic* styles of thought to all kinds of ‘blindness’ still reinforces Taleb’s fundamental assertion that numerous and likely the majority of actors are generally guilty of overemphasising the perceptible aspects of confirmation while disregarding things that they cannot observe directly. Taleb (2007). Taleb contends that such biases are particularly regrettable in a chaotic environment that he famously described as having the characteristics of ‘Extremistan’. Taleb humorously notes that even in a natural world that is static with features that remain the same, efforts to discover a ‘northwest passage’ to a destination that was clearly already known, namely India, ultimately resulted in the discovery of a place that had no knowledge or prediction, namely North America. (Taleb, 2007).

Additionally, supportive of Taleb’s thesis, Green (2011) made the following recommendations regarding the actions that can be implemented to address Black Swan events:

- efforts to define and fix the problem should remain separate
- projects should be implemented in clearly differentiated stages to the greatest extent possible
- a variety of different potential solutions should be tested to determine which one functions optimally (and failures should be abandoned)
- In spite of the disturbance and distraction caused by uncertainty, it must be tolerated because the reality is that it cannot be avoided

According to the Thompsonian Grid-Group Cultural Theory (previously described), the analysis of Green in terms of the nature of the world (that can be considered to be Green’s paradigm) can be recognised as Fatalistic-Pragmatism. The author concurs with Thompson that Fatalistic-Pragmatism offers the most suitable type of emotion, thinking and action in the most challenging ‘risk environment. Taleb is indeed right, although based on cultural factors that are not discussed in his book “The Black Swan”. Among other things, the author recommends that

Taleb should increase his awareness of cultural theory, which provides *four* positions (styles of thought, rationalities), which he believes to be a development of the *dualistic* separation of ‘Platonic’ and ‘Stoic’ schools of thought made by Taleb. Potentially, a cultural approach could be more amenable to a broader scope of potential strategies and unexpected events, detailed in the “Surprise Matrix” of Thompson (Thompson, 2018:7). However, prior to reverting back to the discussion of G-GCT, it is necessary to describe additional examples of black swan events proposed by Taleb to satisfy the three criteria previously mentioned on pages 51-2.

2.5 Proofing of Black Swan

Taleb (2007) claimed that a number of notable events can be justified as being Black Swans, including the September 11^a terrorist attacks, the 2007-8 financial crisis, and the earthquake and subsequent tsunami that struck Japan in 2011. It would be inappropriate to consider the tsunami that impacted Japan as a completely natural occurrence as the catastrophic damage it caused was due to social settlement patterns and the underestimation of risk by a nuclear energy firm that neglected to construct protective walls with sufficient height that would prevent the waves from impacting the plant. Put differently, ill-conceived and overly optimistic *social* arrangements exacerbate the devastating impacts of *natural* events.

According to Taleb, the following examples are also recognisable as black swan events:

- A project costing \$5 million that led to losses of approximately \$200 million for Levi Strauss & Co. in 2008 (Flyvberg and Budzier, 2011)
- In 2003, Shell approved a vast project to construct an oil and gas production facility at Sakhalin Island estimated to cost \$10 billion (which surpassed the company’s net income for 2002). After two years, by which time the construction had advanced significantly, a 6K report was published by Shell revealing that the costs had increased to \$20 billion (and has since reached \$22 billion) (Dodson and Westney, 2014)
- The Big Dig project in Boston exceeded its original budget by in excess of 100% (from

\$2.6 billion to \$14.6) in 2007 (KPMG, 2013; Dodson and Westney, 2014).

It is noteworthy that even though such large projects involved a significant amount of specialist scenario-developing, plans and the production of *Gantt Charts*, they still clearly show black swan characteristics.

Such failures are important for the author due to the fact one of the objectives of this thesis is to recommend methods of increasing the ‘anti-fragility’ of the oil and gas industry in Iran by diversifying the downstream petrochemical sectors. By taking such a course of action, it is not possible to treat the desirable – the relaxation of sanctions – and the less than desirable – the reinstatement of sanctions as measurable likelihoods. Nevertheless, as previously mentioned, it is not necessary to treat all the outcomes of seemingly disadvantageous geo-political developments (specifically the termination of the nuclear energy programme in Iran as well as various arguments with the EU and US, and sanctions) negatively...*if* they encourage anti-fragile strategies to be adopted. In the Talebian approach, silent evidence and particularly counter-factual evidence is sought for each of the ‘known knows’ described below:

- An additional series of economic sanctions were imposed on Iran by the UN Security Council through UN resolution 1747 (UN Security Council, 2007)
- UN Resolution 1803 led to a third set of sanctions being applied to Iran in March 2008 (UN Security Council, 2008) which prohibited *Sepah Bank* (the second biggest bank in Iran) from operating internationally
- Additional sanctions were applied to Iran as a result of Resolution 1929 (UN Security Council, 2010) in June 2010, which placed restrictions on the majority of banks in Iran.
- As a result of pressured applied by the British government, the *Central Bank of Iran* was prohibited from operating internationally in 2011 (Guardian 2011)

It is noteworthy that anti-fragility could result from these, if they encourage Fatalistic-Pragmatic sensitivity to risk and unexpected events, surprising those who had supported sanctions, and even astonishing entrepreneurs and officials in Iran who had feared the worst. This therefore suggests that an outcome that may appear to be extremely unlikely may have increased significance compared to those that were expected and clearly visible to everyone subsequent to the imposition of sanctions.

2.6 Possible Black Swans and Unknowable Approaches

In summary, according to chaos theory, the expectation is that the effects of non-linear movements (unexpected events) will be disproportionate and it can be safely assumed that in this regard, *the future does not exist* (Slaughter, 1998). This is at least partially due to the fact that planners are defeated by ‘outliers’. An “outlier lies outside the realm of regular expectation[s] since nothing in the past can convincingly point to its possibility”. Taleb is dubious of researchers who propose illusory prior solutions for Black Swan events, solutions that they concoct only after the fact. For instance, he would criticise Murphy and Conner (2012) and Werther (2013), who claimed that prior indications of Black Swan events will exist that could have been detected in advance, thus allowing efforts to be made to protect or mitigate against their outcomes. Something that the aforementioned authors do not explain is why what Taleb would describe as ‘silent evidence’ should have been heard to those who could not hear at that time. The foolish become wise in retrospect.

Taleb and Lindblom would have a disdainful attitude due to the extreme complexity of identifying the single minor antecedent event from the multitude of possibilities that could lead to a critical point for a series of major events that will occur in the following months, years, or potentially decades.

Similar to Lindblom, Taleb is not convinced that there will ever be sufficient data and computational power to evaluate the extent of interconnections, regardless of the developments

made in social science. This partially explains why it is hard to establish how social science is progressing, particular in comparison to developments made in the natural sciences where errors contained within scientific theories can be more easily identified and corrected. It is not a matter of triviality to claim that compared with rocket science, social science has greater inherent difficulties and is more vulnerable to errors.

Authors who recognise that the unexpected is inevitable and that predictions are futile include Dodson and Westney (2014). In this regard, they proposed a process comprised of five steps that can be used to manage the future and tame – or at a minimum moderate – black swan events, which include:

- *Risk Development* ('searching for Black Swans'): planning and drawing the risk scenarios and their consequence impact the way people think endlessly. As before, this is also reminiscent of Popper's suggestion that rather than seeking cases that provide confirmation, researchers should in fact seek counter-factual evidence and concentrate on testing 'falsifiable conjectures', instead of constructing 'grand theories'. The author emphasises that from the perspective of Popper, errors are important as they provide an efficient means of developing knowledge.
- *Risk Strategies* ('caging Black Swans'): offer and develop strategies aimed at preventing or mitigating the outcomes in the event that they materialise. Attempts to completely avoid risk are dropped. Additionally, efforts to completely eradicate risk are too costly and restrict the opportunity to learn (previously described in 1.) and make new investments (positive black swans). There is always the inestimable risk that one of the unforeseen outcomes of suppressing black swans is that additional black swans are created.
- *Risk Analysis* ('understanding Black Swans'): assessment and evaluation of the possible costs and timing of scenarios. Nevertheless, there is no complete conviction

that such possible costs and timings can be known, as every cost, irrespective of its magnitude, has the potential to impact a different set of unpredictable chaotic events in the future. Evaluating these events is challenging, as they have varying costs and benefits that cannot be simply summed up in a basic accumulation of positives and negatives.

- Looking after, the Black Swan (Feed Black Swan in Cage). At this point, the process of estimating and allocating risk is conducted by parties separately on their own. Risk brokering commences when various actors engage individually and independently in evaluating the risks of a project. According to Dodson and Westney, this approach allows all (!) possible problems to be clarified by all actors after sharing their assessments.
- *Risk Validation* ('taming Black Swans') is the process whereby Black Swans are attempted to be managed through ongoing monitoring and verification.

Our belief is the metaphors 'hunting', 'caging', 'feeding' and 'taming' appear to assume a degree of 'understanding' of black swans that is potentially not reachable unless the narrative fallacy is committed. However, the condition of constant vigilance proposed by these authors is to be embraced. In accordance with the five steps that they suggest, Scenario Planning (see below) is a creativity approach that is intended to expand the imagination of those participating, enhancing the thinkability of a variety of options. This could result in a single narrative fallacy being replaced with multiple narratives, although it should be taken into account that they remain narratives as the futures that the scenarios describe should not be misinterpreted of proof of reality.

Our interpretation of Kenett (2013) is that he continues to believe that it is possible to avoid certain black swans by combining the collection of historical data (i.e., extrapolating from previous events), constructing scenarios and testing for the purpose of identifying risks

at least in a broad sense and more accurately when an event occurs. On the other hand, Green assumes the same view as Taleb that Black Swans will continue to defy predictability, or at a minimum be exceptionally difficult to expect and make suitable preparations for with regard to their ultimate outcomes (Green, 2011). It is reiterated that in all scenarios, it is not possible to confidently predict when the consequences of a given event will end in a world characterised by chaos. If it was returned to the question of the outcomes of the births of children to men who died in the First World War that did not occur, the children of such unborn children (and the things they may have done in their lives that did not happen), as well as the four—five subsequent generations that did not exist and all the actions they did not perform. Consequently, it can be estimated that the impacts of the soldiers who died in the First World War are greater in 2017 than they were in 1918 and the effects of every soldier's death will be continually magnified with no end, but in a manner, that defies estimation. At any time, significant differences could have been made to the world in any of these missing causation chains that could be defined as 'invisible swans', or more precisely, 'invisible descendant swans'.

According to different authors, another strategy that can be used to minimise black swans is 'Staging' (Flyvberg and Budzier, 2011). This involves the processes of back-casting and forecasting, which enable the process to be broken down, with the aim of identifying risks that may have otherwise been ignored, thus allowing them to be mitigated. This is a sensitisation method broadly used in a wide variety of consulting, governmental and business projects, specifically in Denmark and the United Kingdom.

It is noted that Taleb did not claim that the world is completely unpredictable, but only that the effects of minor events can be disproportionately massive and unpredictable. Taleb would concede it is beneficial to carefully analyse basic, comprehensible and sufficiently understood cause-effect relations within basic systems (such as when calculating beam strength

in the constructing of basic bridges). However, it is when the complexity of such systems increases that the aforementioned recommendations lose their ability to remove risks from entire systems, even where the individual elements of the system appear to be simple.

However, Taleb (2012) contends that unpredictability and uncertainty are favourable (exemplified by the unintentional discovery of penicillin) and potentially crucial. It is noteworthy that Hayek made the argument that if ‘uncertainty’ and ‘imperfect knowledge’ did not exist, there would be no profit at all due to the fact that a stable equilibrium would be achieved in all markets with ‘normal profits’ that offer minimal or zero margins to investors.

Such observations could assist with explaining why entrepreneurs in Iran succeed in generating profits from their trade in spite of and potentially *due* to the chaotic environment in which they operate and due to the unpredictable flow of positive and negative black swans that this produces (that sanctions could help with in a perverse manner). As previously mentioned, it is recognised that the primary target of sanctions is the economy and the central bank, which has brought about crises for various sectors including Oil and Gas, Aviation, Pharmaceuticals, Banking Transactions and in a number of manufacturing industries. It seems that each of these sectors is permanently in a state of ‘crisis’. It could even be erroneous to make the assumption that the crises in Iran are indefinite because they could potentially end without warning, thus making what Thompson refers to as ‘the risk environment’ more advantageous. In fact, the ‘crisis’ has presented various opportunities for people, specifically those in other countries, participating in exchange functions, which have enabled them to earn significant ‘windfall’ profits.

As detailed in a previous section, I have experience of multiple sectors and have determined based on many observations and experiences in my career that favourable impacts in one field of activity could counter-balance negative effects in others. For instance, participating in trade allowed me to offset costs and losses incurred in manufacturing and/or

construction and/or property development. All of these sectors experienced mixed fortunes, although these periods did not occur at the same time or to the same extent in each of the sectors. Additionally, my personal ventures experienced micro-challenges and gains based on their specific situations. If, when the environment was most conducive, I had optimised my profits by being willing to expose some or all of my ventures to possibly higher ultimate downturn risks, I could have made significant profits while risking total bankruptcy. For instance, I could have increased my reliance on debt-financing that the banks would have been willing to offer. However, as I previously mentioned, I do not aim to maximise profit, but I am rather a temporary, wary and somewhat anxious shepherd of positive ‘black swans’ that are in my vicinity, which I also set free and *do not* retain for more than I risk.

Therefore, based on the initial exposition and review presented above, the assumption can be made that a Black Swan event can be viewed from two perspectives: they can either be forecasted and managed using extremely powerful computational analysis, repeated through multiple iterations of scenario development based on massive datasets, thus allowing the future to be predicted.

On the other hand, continuous monitoring of the environment for black swans is essential, recognizing that these events will eventually emerge and necessitate our preparedness to face them head-on. By staying vigilant and proactive, it can be develop the resilience needed to navigate the challenges posed by these unforeseen disruptions. Embracing the reality of encountering black swans now allows us to adapt and respond effectively when they do arise, rather than being caught off guard and unprepared. The author recommend that the latter approach should be followed, and he believes that it is adopted by the majority of entrepreneurs in Iran who survive. It can therefore be stated that it is critical to:

- be able to rapidly identify what is known to refer to as positive and negative black swans, potentially within minutes

- assume that all events are black swans by default (even those that may seem to be highly regular)
- regard all conversations, even those in private with author, as being susceptible to what is now acknowledged as being the ‘narrative fallacy’. The default position should be doubt
- persistently seek things that other people or I may have overlooked, which now considered to be ‘silent evidence’ wherever it may be
- consider the future to be unknown while staying aware of in the current time, which is an approach that author consistently adopted, even in his personal life

2.7 Forecasting and Back-Casting

The hypothesis that the future is not fixed as opposed to being something that is predominantly based on the outcomes of accumulated events from the past implies that (within the social arena) the chaos paradigm is at least conducive to and even supportive of the implementation of scenario development methods. Scenario development can be approached in a variety of different ways and it has been reported that it has been successful in certain respects. For instance, in the case that the future is yet to be determined, it follows that it is possible to influence it such that efforts can be made to avoid or mitigate unwanted futures, whereas the potential for desirable futures to be realised can be enhanced. It can also be deduced that if the effects of minor events can be vast, small steps made in the current time could have massive effects in the future (favourable and unfavourable) This is largely recognised as ‘normative scenario development’ whereby a desirable future is selected and efforts are made to realise it (although it is not guaranteed that it will be reached). This position will be defined here as the ‘soft’ type of strategy.

Nevertheless, multiple strategic experts adopt an opposing position, which are sceptical about, aimed at managing the uncertain future, predicting and controlling, gathering all

required data, comprehending the complex nature of a problem and developing a logical plan that provides a certain amount of protection of the selected scenario against the unpredictability of the future (Polasky et al., 2011 and Rounsevell et al. 2012 and Regamey, 2013). In this context, it can be defined as the ‘strong’ type of strategy.

Schipke stated that collecting information and accurately analysing the story allow us to identify and define future uncertainty and manage it before it occurs, such that the ability to forecast (!) the future allows complicated problems to be drawn with a degree of confidence and understanding, while the actions can be ‘aligned’ with the ‘vision’ and ‘goals’ incorporated within the corporate strategy (Polasky et al., 2011 and Rounsevell et al. 2012 and Regamey, 2013).

Another recommendation that has importance is that after identifying the preferred destination (significantly in advance), back-casting can be performed where the starting point is the destination and a pathway to the current time is traced through a number of reverse steps. This series of backwards steps (Robinson,1990) can be portrayed as a comic strip comprising five or seven steps, or a number of ‘tableaux’. It is suggested that the process of back-casting is beneficial for long-range planning. (Dreborg,1996), which could be required when no other options are available, particularly in cases involving significant investments, as recognised above.

The back-casting approach has been described as a complementary method that can be used to anticipate and work towards the future in a more conscious manner than could be otherwise achieved. Via this technique, multiple futures can be initially visualised via the process called scenario development. In this process, two dimensions are selected and cross-tabulated to create an x - y matrix in order to determine which of the contents could be attributed to the four cells delineated by the selected dimensions. For instance, when considering ‘healthcare futures’, a public responsibility/private responsibility could be represented by the

x dimension, whereas the *y* dimension could depict ‘health promotion/ disease fighting’. In this example, the four cells would then be defined as:

- Public Responsibility with Disease-Fighting
- Public Responsibility with Health-Promotion
- Private Responsibility with Disease-Fighting
- Private Responsibility with Health-Promotion

Consequently, detailing all of the cells is easier, allowing their distinctions and commonalities to be observed, and the ‘best’, ‘worst’ and ‘most likely’ futures can be discussed and selected; subsequently, back-casting can be employed to determine how various approaches and activities that start in the current time could result in the preferred future (Robinson, 1982). It is emphasised that this is a joint process in which multiple actors within an organisation or from multiple organisations are brought together, which can be beneficial for alerting organisations to risks (black swans) that have only been considered by a limited number of members. In cases where participants do not feel that they are constrained by prevailing narratives, this could increase the organisation’s capacity to think critically through the summation of all fears and dreams.

Nonetheless, entrepreneurs in Iran begin to experience doubts when reading about the future. The general recommendation is that after a goal has been clearly established that is both desirable and plausible (i.e., realistic and appears convincing), and each of the actions is ‘aligned’ as a ‘requirement of the strategy, then the route is largely fixed as a pathway from the existing conditions to the future regardless of the unpredictable events that may occur (Robinson,1982). Based on the likelihood that the situation will transform as time progresses (new black swans will emerge), if actions are ‘strategically aligned’ to the targeted outcome as a requirement, then this would make me significantly anxious. From the perspective of an entrepreneur in Iran, the existence of fixed actions could generate fragile new risks that can be

more easily avoided in a diversified venture controlled by the owner compared with a larger managerially joint-stock firm in which the systems of reporting are inherently bureaucratic with the aim of strictly ensuring 'compliance'. This represents the desired situation of the administrators, offering false assurance that if compliance was ensured across the board, then there is nothing to suggest that the success of the project would be in jeopardy. The risk is enhanced when there is increased focus on procedures and processes, increasing the likelihood that black swans will be overlooked.

It can possibly be stated then when considering the scenario development for larger companies, the optimal approach would be to back-cast and plan scenarios, collect data and assess the potential effects of internal and external factors (Hojar et al,2011 and Robert,2005). The author believes that back-casting can be beneficial in the sense that it recognises a certain amount of freedom of creative actions as well as the potential for willing futures instead of merely yielding to whatever fate may bring. Additionally, it clearly establishes a methodology for how this can be done (Wilson et al., 2006), albeit risking increased rigidity after this. According to author personal experience, he again fearful that as a result of the more participative process, the extent of the preparedness, eagerness, and confidence to implement policies will present certain risks. Those participating will enjoy the process or feel that it energises them, particularly individuals who are at the bottom or middle of the organisational hierarchy who are generally not invited to present their views.

The fundamental problem revolves around *which* two dimensions should be selected as the foundation for scenario development. How can different sets of dimensions be compared? With regard to the previously mentioned 'health futures' example, the following dimensions could be explored:

x 'severe medicine/ public health measures' cross-tabulated with y 'individualised/ population-wide'

or rather y ‘medicalisation of life/ De-medicalisation’

or y ‘self-testing and diagnosis/ collective testing and diagnosis’

or y ‘nationally-regulated state-owned and controlled care system/ free-traded care system

or y ‘professionalised/ bare-foot’ provision

or a mixture of two of the above or any two from perhaps 20 dimensions?

The process of scenario planning for all possible permutations of the combinations of two dimensions from a possible of twenty would be very lengthy and there is nothing stopping anyone from limiting the number of dimensions to two. For example, a z dimension could potentially be added to form eight-cell boxes.

It can also be observed that dimensions possess both implicit normative qualities as well as the ‘objective’ qualities they are expected to possess. Something that could seem to be advantageous for certain actors could be a source of fear for others, meaning that there will be no consensus regarding the ‘optimal’ outcome. Our perception that is that a minimum, it could lessen the risks associated with following a rigid fragile strategy.

The general belief is that scenario development was firstly implemented towards the end of the 1970s in the oil and gas industry by Shell with the aim of making long-term plans for the future as a reaction to the ‘oil crisis’ caused by OPEC. This approach was quickly adopted by various sectors and is implemented for the purpose of analysing climate change, ecological systems and protecting the environment (Dreborg, 1996; Holmberg and Robert, 2000; Carlsson- Kanyama et al., 2008; Hojer et al., 2011; Kok et al., 2011; Quist et al., 2011; Berkel and Verburg, 2012; Kok et al., 2003; Strachan et al., 2008). These techniques have been utilized at a much larger scale for the development of EU policies and are capable of accepting both quantitative and qualitative data (Anderson et al., 2008; Ault, Frame, Hughes,

and Strachan, 2008; DECC, 2011; DTI, 2006; McDowall, 2006; National Grid, 2012; UKERC, 2013).

Fig 2.6 depicts a three-stage back-casting process starting with defining the problem, then collecting data ending with an ultimate solution. As shown in the below figure, in the ‘visioning’ stage, the planning of scenario and assessment impact the entire process and Robinson stresses the particular significance of ensuring that this stage is completed in a meticulous and deliberate manner (Robinson, 1982).

Figure 3.6 Process of Back Casting (after Robinson, 1982)

It has been claimed that to ensure the effective functioning of strategy and methods in mitigating unfavourable futures and that the existing situation and resources are connected and assigned in a meaningful and precise way, it is necessary to integrated the primary objectives and demands (Gret-Regamey et al., 2012; Cavender-Bares et al., 2015; Wolff et al., 2015).

This interpretation assumes a politically system that operates reactively, whether at a national level or within individual governmental or non-governmental organizations, and is accessible to a wide range of diverse participants. It can certainly be questioned whether this

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corresponds to the experiences of entrepreneurs in Iran, who may regard ‘citizen/consumer participation workshops’ from a totally different perspective to those suggested by Robinson.

However, those who support this approach suggest that it is necessary to identify all (!) internal and external factors as well as assess how each of the factors impacts the system as a whole (e.g., Bryan et al., 2010; Huber et al., 2011; Burkhard et al., 2012; Gre[^]t-Regamey et al., 2013b; Bagstad et al., 2014; Castro et al., 2014; Schulp et al., 2014; Stürck et al., 2014; Bagstad et al., 2015).

Similar to previous arguments, this perspective posits that such ambitions are significantly ambitious, complex, and, according to Taleb and Lindblom, unattainable, ineffective, and potentially harmful. Because the general aim (and possibly objective) of this thesis is to conceptualise an anti-fragile petrochemical sector in Iran that has a variety of different downstream activities, without considering how these approaches might contribute, the focus will be solely on their limitations and potential drawbacks, particularly because the size and timeframes of such investments are significantly bigger than those of stereotypical private entrepreneurs in Iran adopting anti-fragile strategies have experienced.

2.8 Flexible Strategies?

Scenario planning offers significant potential as a way of developing a management approach that is at a minimum conscious of the future, particularly in industrial sectors in which a company’s expansion or collapse can be significantly impacted by outside factors (Berkel and Verburg, 2012). An adaptation of this highly debated approach involves *in setting a target* and *processing the assessment* on the basis of scenario development, selection and subsequently planning (Robert, 2000 and Ney 2006) with the aim of managing the future through the development of a strategy that is flexible when confronted with unpredictability, thus allowing various potential outcomes (Peterson et al., 2003; Madlener et al., 2007).

Supporters of scenario planning do not suggest that it allows the future to be precisely anticipated. The term ‘forecast’ is employed rather than ‘prediction’, because ‘forecasts’ recognise the likelihood that events will occur that can be attributed to factors that are situated external to the system as it is described, while ‘predictions’ make the assumption that the calculation incorporates all pertinent factors. Scenario planning is a technique used to anticipate various different futures for the purpose of mitigating unwelcome surprises (Heijden, 1996). As previously mentioned, either a ‘backwards’ or ‘forwards’ approach to planning can be adopted, although the former appears to be more compatible with ‘long-term visioning’.

Figure 4 Process of Back Casting and Forecasting

Efforts is considered to take into account further possibilities to be positive provided that it is remembered that it is not an exhaustive technique that can be used to map the future as a result of the strong likelihood that scenarios could be disrupted by dynamic changes (Eisenhard,1999), which may include dynamic reactions by different actors when responding to the work of forecasters and who could be opposed to it (e.g., rivals and opponents). From our perspective, such a more robust type of strategy could *slightly* enhance our understanding of short-run changeability but presents the risk of misinterpreting what is a system-wide narrative for something whose nature is more empirical compared to a narrative. Put

differently, such approaches could increase our vulnerability to narrative fallacies as they seem to be thought out, considered, thorough, dependable and shared.

As previously mentioned, the development of scenarios usually involves the construction of four scenarios based on two dimensions in 2x2 matrices. The scenarios generated are dependent on the dimensions selected: for example, in a particular exercise involving the development of a scenario, if the person developing the scenario had selected a distinct *x* dimension while keeping the identical *y* dimension, four scenarios would have been developed whose characteristics were extremely different to those they worked with in reality. Moreover, they would not have selected the favoured destination for ‘back-casting’ purposes, and they would have adopted a significantly different process for strategically aligning the organisation. The organisation’s destiny could have been highly or wholly different to its actual fate, merely due to the fact that a workshop had been run slightly differently compared to how it could have easily been by certain scenario players on a given Thursday afternoon as part of an ‘away day’ activity. For example, the attendance or lack of attendance of an individual participant with a particular interest in considering the dimension of High or Low Regulation of the Tourist Industry who did not draw attention to this issue could mean that it is not included within the strategic vision of his/her organisation. Therefore, in the context of our favoured paradigm, the process of developing scenarios is significantly vulnerable to minute unpredictable changes in the antecedent conditions – in this case, the attendance or lack of attendance of one diligent actor, possibly due to a problem with his/her vehicle reroute to the event or because he/she overlooked the invitation email due to a full inbox.

Supporters of Taleb (2008) have a different option, which involves the division and subdivision of risks as opposed to managing or avoiding them. Taleb and Author would both be sceptical about the assertion that if scenario planning is conducted strategically, organisational practices can be aligned to the outside factors through an exhaustive process

(Chermack et al, 2001), or alternatively, if an attempt is made to do this, then an unexpected event could cause it to be dramatically overturned (which, in hindsight, should have been predicted according to some). Concurring with both Lindblom and Hume that it is not possible for any process to be genuinely comprehensive, particularly when considering the political, social, economic and legal fields, which are characterised by chaos. They are all susceptible to black swans individually and when combined. At the most, sensitisation to vulnerability could be achieved (although not to the extent that specific outcomes could be confidently or accurately identified) and a state of readiness could be reached allowing rapid actions to be taken when unforeseen events occur (Jayal and Badurdeen and Jawahir, 2012). It is possible that the process of planning ultimately reveals that the world can go against the plan, which offers valuable learning.

What are the implications of ‘anti-libraries’ (Taleb, 2009) for the development of scenarios and planning? The ability to create polymers and a broad variety of high-value aromatic compounds has advanced significantly and it is now possible to accurately specify products according to recognised parameters. Polymer science adheres to chemical laws. It is agreed with Taleb that professional know-how regarding identified chemical and physical processes cannot be ignored; however, even at this level, unforeseen changes can occur that can be surprising for process engineers if they are required to control multiple variables simultaneously, particularly in larger plants. This highlights the fact that when applied to a larger scale, what could be safe and predictable when conducting experiments on a smaller test rig could lead to deadly disastrous outcomes that could not have been foreseen by any experts. What has transpired in this case is that a chemical process subjected to the rules of nature has been expanded into a complicated social network comprising engineering in different firms and departments such as production, sales, petrochemical as well as analysis and financial engineers.

Taleb stressed that being aware of things that society currently do not (and cannot) have knowledge about should have more importance than it does in reality (Taleb, 2012). Having knowledge about the results of the previous four, sixteen or thirty-two quarters could lead us to have misleading perceptions regarding what will occur in the following quarter. This suggests being over-reliant on and over-confident in expertise beyond what is anticipated can lead to significant risks. Although I profess to being a highly competent petrochemical engineer, I do not state that I am an expert in the petrochemical products *markets* as they exhibit significantly more vulnerability to a lack of predictability than the process of manufacturing (which already contains more fluctuations than is desired). I propose the hypothesis that entrepreneurs in Iran who have demonstrated the ability to survive increasingly behave less like experts based on the extent of vulnerability to randomness of the enterprise they are operating. An entrepreneur cannot be considered an expert in the true sense of the word. Talebian thinking could allude to constraints on the role that expertise plays to basic activities in which they are suitably reliable to be given responsibility in areas that have clearly delineated boundaries. If there is an increased likelihood that black swans will occur, the existence of experts could exacerbate their impacts.

For instance, experts could strictly adhere to targets that are rendered impossible or too expensive to achieve by black swans. Being sceptical, it is unclear whether the suggestion by both Robert and Ney holds true. The notion that setting a goal for the future and determining the organization's situation in relation to that goal would automatically lead to the identification and adoption of specific corporate policies that facilitate the transition from the existing situation to goal achievement appears dubious (Robert, 2000; Ney, 2006). Although experts could have robust opinions regarding how 'change management' can be accomplished with respect to 'targets', it should be questioned why such a large number of change management programmes appear to experience complete failure (Gavetti and Rivkin, 2007; Ringland, 2010).

This type of negative data should act as a warning in terms of the usage of the methods being discussed here. Drastic changes could cause "what Schumpeter would refer to as 'creative destruction', and dealing with these changes requires more than traditional strategy formation processes and tools" (Schumpeter and Opie, 1934).

According to its nature, when scenario planning is being performed, it has a certain protection from complexities and uncertainties in the future environment (Walsh,2005; Gausemeier,1998; Schoemaker, 1993). Softer versions of scenario planning techniques can incorporate multiple feedback and testing loops as a portion of combined processes that can be included in scenario planning. As the variant's softness increases, it becomes more sensitive to anomalies. In fact, when compared with normal scenario development, in the context of the practices of entrepreneurs in Iran, the processes of back-casting and scenario planning are primarily different for such entrepreneurs due to the fact that:

- It is necessary to continually mentally re-enact and revise the model, which is an exhausting process
- Final decisions regarding the x , y and z variables are never made
- Due to ongoing doubts about the model, its outputs are also in question
- The future objective is never completely established
- The steps required to reach that objective are not completely defined

Most days, things either exceed expectations or are worse than predicted, and are often significantly better or worse than anticipated even on that day. This is similar to Dregborg's (1996) claim that it may be necessary to make changes at any point in the process (Dregborg, 1996), although it should be added this could happen at any time and the process is not rigid. Thus, it can be questioned whether the practices of Iranian entrepreneurs can be defined as being 'procedural' in the recognised meaning of something that can be replicated *proceeding* in fixed stages.

From our perspective, it does not appear that quantification has a fundamental impact. It is recognised that both quantitative and qualitative elements can serve scenario development and strategic planning (Swart et al., 2004) and it is suggested that quantification facilitates the process of dynamically extrapolating from previous patterns (Vested et al., 1992; Brabec et al., 2001), as well as that comprehending previous patterns and changes that occurred in the past enable optimal strategies to be developed aimed at achieving the targeted objectives (Cinq-Mars and Wiken 2002).

Such assertions about computational techniques appear to be highly optimistic given the shock caused by the 2007 crisis due to the fact that omitting even minute datasets can generate huge errors – particularly by individuals who believe that they are experts – even within short time frames.

It is important to stress that authors advocating for the chaos paradigm do not hold the belief that the characteristics of the social world imply the impossibility of identifying and considering all external drivers that can initiate changes in interlinked elements (IPCC, 2000; Tietje, 2005). It is considered that there is a reduced likelihood that the required precision and accuracy can be obtained or that all drivers can be mapped and identified using an intricate step-by-step process for such complicated problems in the depth that advocates of the robust type of strategy believe is both essential and achievable:

Figure 5 Scenario Process (do Prado Leite et al., 2000)

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2.9 Different Between Weak and Strong Scenario Development

It is not our intention to refute all of the claims of these writers as there is one thing that is highly persuasive, namely the assertion made by all authors apart from those who strictly 'extrapolate from the past' that the future is open and does not exist. The element that appears to be worth retaining is the concept of scenario *development*, but in the form of a permanent and perpetual exhausting but not exhaustive activity that is being continually revised. Additionally, it can be considered that it should be significantly less systematic than suggested in the literature and the role of experts should be more limited (due to the fact that as the chaos increases, the threat posed by experts is enhanced). Taleb (2010) claimed that scenario planning is not reliant on the skills of experts, because uncertainties are not related to a lack of expertise, but a dearth of understanding. It is suspected that over-simplifying clarifications, even in complicated scenario development processes, renders them susceptible to incalculable risks, the effects of which cannot be determined in advance despite having vast computational power.

Scenario planning is an innovative technique used to describe the future that should acknowledge the following assumptions: a) it is not possible to fully predict the main relations between the 'drivers' and their outcomes (Amer et al., 2013; Kahn,1967; CERF, 2012), although the drivers determined and the expected outcomes are at a minimum largely suitable, justifiable, but preliminary.

The objective should not be to establish a fixed target, but rather to develop strategies that are capable of responding more effectively to uncertainties with regard to interpreting evidence, contexts as well as to variations in 'dimensions of decision making and degree of recognition of the spatial dimension in the issues recognised' (Navarro-Ligero and Valenzuela-Montes, 2016)

It's been beneficially explained how to construct scenarios. as a "tool for ordering one's perceptions about alternative future environments in which one's decisions might be played

out" (Schwartz,1966). In our opinion, this relatively frail description is tolerable. Scenario development (alternatively called scenario analysis or planning) has also been more weakly defined as “a systematic method for thinking creatively about dynamic, complex and uncertain future, and identifying strategies to prepare for a range of possible outcome” (Madlener et al, 2007; Peterson et al, 2003). Nevertheless, it is useful to emphasise how this compares with more robust definitions; for example, it has been defined as "a coherent, internally consistent and plausible description of a potential future trajectory of a system" (Oteros and Rozas et al., 2015). All of the keywords included within this statement, along with the overall hypothesis, are dismissed based on the fact that in reality, risks increase in line with their strength.

A more robust definition is that the scenario development process should affirm *all* the internal and external principal, drivers and variables that have a subsequent effect on future likelihoods in order for the scenario to be beneficial for all possible future events (Van Der Heijden, 2005). Nevertheless, supporters of this version acknowledge that it is necessary to develop three or four distinct scenarios in order for a sufficient number of decision-makers to be accommodated in a systematic manner. From the author’s perspective, this seems to be too strong.

In addition to attempting to avert and decrease complexity in the future and mitigate against unpredictability, multiple short-term feedback cycles (loops) can be incorporated into scenario development for the purpose of testing different options on a largely continual basis such that decision-makers are prepared for a broader variety of possibilities and uncertainties than may have otherwise been the case (Kok et al,2007; Walz et al,2007). It is noticeable in this case that as the strength of the definitions used is reduced, scenario development appears to have an increased resemblance of the practices of entrepreneurs in Iran.

Thus, it can be questioned which of the definitions, “hard or “soft”, is used in practical situations for the purpose of developing and planning scenarios. The approached adopted by

Shell was intuitively logical as it recognised that the future development of the corporation was confronted by considerable uncertainty, as revealed by analysis the company itself conducted in the 1970s (Wack,1985). As a result of the huge and unexpected increase in the oil price subsequent to the Arab-Israeli War, Shell ensured that it made better preparations compared to its rivals and its goal was to increase its *resilience* in comparison to its competitors (Wilkinson & Kupers,2013; Jefferson, 2012). It is striking in this regard that the objective was to make the company more resilient in the medium and longer term as opposed to maximising profits. As a result of planning multiple scenarios, *Shell* was able to develop three distinct scenarios in terms of how it could develop in the future, named Hydrogen, Chemical products and Construction products.

(Kallemets, 2016; Parker & Blumberga, 2017). This is an example of the softer version in which the future is not precisely drawn, but various alternatives are clarified that should be considered by decision-makers in their current operations with the intention that they can target different futures of their own and design and plan suitable actions (Johnson, 2017).

When viewed from this perspective, working on scenarios could be beneficial for industrial sectors and authorities in terms of clarifying, managing, evaluating and even planning for opportunities and risks. In reality, it has been a critical factor in the practice of planning future management (Kwakkel & Pruyt,2012; Bryant & Lempert,2010; Jones et al.,2010; Salter et al., 2009; Volkery et al.,2008; Andersson et al.,2008), with the goal being to "boost the ability of the top managers to identify a superior course of action that is different from the status quo and to foresee the consequences" (Gavetti & Menon, 2016).

One might therefore enquiry whether scenario development is capable of mitigating the previously described perception issues specified by Taleb (2007) (introduced above), such as what are the benefits of scenario development for *confirmation bias*, *silent evidence*, or promoting the hypothetical ‘anti-library’ of an organisation. If scenario development is indeed

capable of mitigating all biases associated with decisions, such as over-stating knowledge and under-stating the lack of knowledge (O'Brien & Meadows, 2013), then it should be accepted prudently.

Nevertheless, variants that have greater strength than it was presented thus far also exist, which was believed exacerbate biases through the promotion of 'epistemic arrogance':

2.10 MITIGA Framework

Owens claims that right responses can be approximated (Owens et al., 2004), while Abbot also states that a framework can be used to generate concepts and targeted goals that allows complexities and uncertainties to be managed (Abbott, 2005). MITIGA is a prototype instrument that supports decision making that is purported to be capable of facilitating the evaluation of strategic performance according to a variety of future scenario circumstances. It incorporates three primary features:

- a "strategic-options analysis concept based on the combination of different policy components"
- a basic evaluation framework that establishes a qualitative connection between the anticipated performance of, for example, strategies for transport and urban development and future patterns, based on evolutionary notions ('trend stabilization/destabilization', 'transitions', etc.)
- a scenario generator... "principles of traditional prospective techniques" (i.e., morphological analysis) (Godet, 2006; Wiek et al., 2009; Tietje, 2005; Nguyend and Dunn, 2009).

This model is primarily aimed at accepting the input of information in a flexible manner, and can be adapted to a variety of different kinds cases while sustaining a perpetual decision cycle (Godet, 2006; Wiek et al., 2009; Tietje, 2005; Nguyend and Dunn, 2009). When viewed from

a Talebian viewpoint, this should be beneficial, although only in the case that every cycle produces more outcomes than merely exacerbating existing narrative fallacies.

An additional purported ability of the model is that it is simple and transparent when addressing various complicated drivers and problem evaluations to facilitate the process of constructing a vision as well as story planning for accurate decision-making during the scenario planning procedure (Ligero and Valenzuela-Montes, 2016). In this context, it is the phrase ‘story planning’ that is the most controversial and potentially self-contradictory.

From the perspective of Taleb as well as the chaos paradigm generally, the concepts of transparency and simplicity are not overly compatible with the paradigm. However, according to the stronger strategy variant, transparency denotes a direct association between a driver and the components it drives. Multiple exceptions exist that cast doubt on such associations in highly unexpected ways. For instance, when this thesis was being written, in spite of the comprehensive, authenticated, and documented compliance of Iran as evaluated by a specialist panel comprised of highly skilled international assessors, the President of the United States suggested that he was prepared to ‘de-certify’ multilateral treaties which resulted in sanctions being lifted; additionally, two huge and documented investment agreements with Iran were endorsed by the European Union. It is not easy to incorporate such contradictory developments into a process of scenario planning and still be able to build ‘simple visions’ from the process. It can be advised that the default assumption that ‘anything could occur, which is clearly the null theory of any attempt at scenario planning, should be kept as an option. A willingness should exist to accept the null theory at any time.

In line with Taleb, it is recommended that it is not assumed that if the volume of information drawn via scenario process mapping is increased, this does not automatically ensure ‘black-swan proofing’. It emphasises that in practical terms, this is due to the fact that information is never comprehensive (and the extent to which it is not comprehensive also

cannot be determined). As demonstrated by Taleb, even omitting small amounts of data (e.g., the price fluctuations of a stock on a single day many years ago) and individual events (that occurred many decades ago and cannot be recalled, or more recently and are not observed) can have significant impacts on outcomes in systems that are chaotic. The optimistic confidence of Marsden (2012) in establishing targets, exploring different options, making ultimate decisions and choosing solutions, evaluating the model, and generating strategy is met with scepticism. He notes that this "MITIGA assessment framework was designed for benefiting from comprehensive qualitative analysis of an open set of policy 'contents' and 'contexts' (objectives, logics, mechanisms, instruments, scales, locations, etc.) and all of them *known* as policy components" (Marsden et al., 2012, emphasis added). To be fair to Marsden, it could be that the confidence with which his terminology is expressed enables the inherent problems that I think underlay scenario planning. However, he persists with a concerning level of confidence to state that there are three scenario metrics:

- Evaluation of how effective distinct strategic alternatives are as well as various assessment criteria for distinct scenarios
- The extent to which the different scenarios are stable as well as their internal relativeness
- Evaluation of the identified distance between the existing circumstances to dissimilar scenarios according to our terms, measuring the distances that will be travelled.

The final point above is a considerable qualification to Marsden's additional prominent technocratic assertion. From our perspective, the primary focus should be on the 'observed distance' between the 'scenario' and the 'existing circumstances. More precisely, all entrepreneurs in Iran who survive inevitably function while considering multiple 'what-if' scenarios and continually check them against favourable, unfavourable and completely unforeseen surprise 'grey swan' events that are hard to evaluate as positive or negative news.

In fact, although entrepreneurs do conduct scenario planning, even though they may not call it as such, in my experience, they do not seek to be comprehensive and their planning does not extend far into the future. During their lives, major international powers have changed from being strong allies to being fearsome opponents whose positions have relaxed and then become more rigid, while their actions often do not correspond with their public statements. It generally regarded it as a fortunate coincidence when 'scenarios' correspond with 'existing situations' as opposed to being the result of information being managed effectively, the development of scenarios and planning strategically. This is exemplified by the saying 'He who foretells the future is a liar even if his predictions are proven to be accurate!'

Figure 6 MITIGA Assessment Framework and Methodological Steps (Navarro-Ligero and Valenzuela-Montes, 2016).

However, the MITIGA framework is reproduced here. As illustrated in the above figure, in the initial stage, the policy elements as well as the structure of the various scenarios are identified, which includes the driving forces and patterns. Observe that it is assumed that it is not possible to differentiate between drivers and non-drivers. At this point, planners are required to create a list of policies and how effectively they are presumed to be utilising reports, simulations and studies. In the next stage, the association between the driver elements and hypothesis is formulated to anticipate the impact that the driver elements will have on the situation in the future. The probability that the policy will succeed or fail within varying

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sociological, political, environmental and economic conditions is estimated to a certain extent. In the following stage labelled as 5 and 6, the different strategic objectives are defined. In this stage, an exploration of every (!) combination of policies and drivers should be conducted for various strategic alternatives. Clarification should be provided on each of the limits, variables and impacts of every component policy prior to the generation of scenarios (Wiek et al., 2009; Tietje, 2005; Nguyend and Dunn, 2009). This is followed by scenario management in which performance metrics are defined and analysed for every target along with defined indicators (alert thresholds). Therefore, this is reflective of the ‘root and branch approach’ that Lindblom claimed to be virtually unobtainable, not only because it is not possible to know the goals (defined by Lindblom as ‘values’) until a point is reached when the actor is required to choose between having a greater or lesser amount of two potential *goods*, which are both advantageous but unfortunately necessitate a trade-off to be made (a greater amount of one results in a lesser amount of the other). The policy-maker can only identify what it is they are really looking for when they reach that point. Lindblom’s critique of the ‘root and branch’ approach to public organization and his well-known predilection to the ‘science of muddling through’ are applicable in this context. He contended that such an exhaustive approach requires administrators to be more capable than would ever be possible. Lindblom, Taleb and Popper all concurred that short-term experimentation as well as ‘piecemeal trial and error-elimination’, namely an approach that offers both flexibility and contingency, is more practical and effective in reality. Lindblom emphasised that in all situations (and he referred to multiple policy areas), it may not be possible for administrators and policy-makers to have knowledge of their values until such time that they are required to make a decision in terms of which of the paths will be discarded in favour of the other. It is likely that this also applies to individual citizens. The preference between two alternatives (such as the selection of two items on a menu from an extremely enticing restaurant menu) will only be revealed when required to decide which one

would like to order. However, it is possible that it could come to the realisation that the choice of another diner would have been more desirable to one's own selection only after it is too late. In another example, a preference for the alternative option may exist even if it is no longer available in administrative practice.

Additionally, it is doubtful that Taleb would evaluate MITIGA in an approving way, considering that it is virtually inevitable for events to surpass the scenarios and that achieving more than a rough approximation of the interactions between policy, driver, and outcome, as demanded by the model, will be impossible. It is not easy to determine how every potential combination of driver, policy and outcome interactions will materialise in the future based on the fact that understanding the current interactions or their historical nature is challenging in itself. Furthermore, if one's preferences are only revealed when one's existence is at risk in the present time, the ability to know what one wants in the future is even more difficult.

It is only when a very serious situation arises that our awareness of what is truly important as individual actors is heightened. Conversely, different actors will uncover their own distinct preferences, which are likely to diverge significantly. If one considers that *self-knowledge* is hard, it is even more challenging to be aware of the exhaustive information that strategic planners are expected to seek, encompassing large corporations that employ thousands of employees as well as their masses of existing and prospective customers and suppliers.

However, the MITIGA prototype purports to be highly sophisticated whereby the relationship between specific trends and policy elements is considered to follow naturalistic rules of interaction and based on the assumption that it is possible to define every element's effectiveness with respect to distinct policy alignments (Fig 6). It is therefore possible to depict the alignment between current obstacles, possible opportunities and future trend behaviour:

Figure 7, MITIGA Assessment Concept (Navarro-Ligero and Valenzuela-Montes, 2016).

The MITIGA model comprises two different path configurations, which are described below:

- Confirmative (trend-adopting). Within this configuration, obstacles are on the verge of being overcome and the targeted outcomes accomplished in line with our strategic objectives.
- Transformative (trend-breaking). Within this configuration, opportunity-based regulations are not applied until such time that the context is changed

Inactive Rules are acknowledged in that "the final set only included simple Boolean rules based on absence/presence premises (rule is active when some instance combination happens in a given policy and end/base scenario presents a certain trend or trends combination) and on additional synergistic effects (rule is active also if another policy instance combination is present in the same strategic option)" (Ligero & Valenzuela-Montes, 2016).

Advocates suggest that every individual base scenario can be defined, thus facilitating the generation of the relationships and outcomes of every policy (each of the drivers, trends and forces). Ultimately, an additional column is included in the matrix in order to scale and

value every aspect with the aim of strategically understanding the anticipated behaviour of every scenario in the future. According to Taleb, this appears to be an effective technique for generating narratives, although it is limited to narratives. Thus, with respect to the claim made below, he would immediately to its accompanying warning sign:

- MITIGA assures that after the various scenarios have been scaled and weighted, this will enable opportunities to be described that one can then plan, manage and control in a strategic manner.

The table presented below details how this type of matrix will be designed on the basis of past research (Wiek et al. 2009 or Nguyend and Dunn, 2009).

Figure 8 Discrete Scales for Analysis of Transition Depth and Consistency (Navarro-Ligero and Valenzuela-Montes, 2016).

The conceptual terminology particularly is very interesting. Concepts like 'driver identification' and 'transition depth' undoubtedly position this type of thinking within a distinct paradigm (distinct world) to that which entrepreneurs in Iran occupy. In the world occupied by MITIGA, it appears that the presumption is made that dimensions (such as 'depth, which are intended to be easily pictured and accurately measured) and forces exist, like 'drivers' that would largely resemble the 'vectors' found in Newtonian physics which it is possible to plot confidently. References to 'scales', 'weighting', and possibly 'precise information gathering', have analogous Newtonian ramifications that are not particularly compatible with the

perspective of the world of entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived. MITIGA also does not provide an estimation of the time it will take to pass from the ‘base’ to the ‘end’. Considering the assertion of Taleb that the First World War will continue to have an impact on the world for the rest of time, it would certainly not be wise to place a time limit on an ‘end scenario’.

Our preference is to start by describing success as the ability to deal with and survive unforeseen changes and unpredictability. In a world characterised by chaos, this is a logical point from which to start, where time frames are described in terms of days, weeks and months, rather than the abilities that could be applicable to a parallel, significantly less complex world that those making comprehensive strategic plans assume exists.

Is it possible to comprehensively describe the Petrochemicals Sector in Iran?

With a sufficiently large book of inventory, it is possible to define the majority of the technical aspects of the petrochemicals sector in Iran (particularly at the plant level), although if exhaustive technical diagrams were provided for all the pumps, valves, conduits, supporting framing, heat exchangers, pressure vessels, tanks, volumes, flows, power specifications, cooler groups, distillation towers, bypasses, acid-recovery plants, vents, and instrumentation equipment, among others, the model produced would have such a degree of complexity that its utility would be no greater than the material items it is intended to describe.

There are virtually no limits to the ‘socio’ components of ‘socio-technical systems’, vertically with regard to the political and social structure in Iran, and horizontally with respect to the extension of the Iranian diaspora into the surrounding region. Theoretically, in order for the MITIGA methodology to be applied, it would be necessary to capture and input all of this, and then add all (!) outside drivers in order for ‘obstacles’ and ‘opportunities’ to be revealed. This is a mammoth task that requires knowledge of everything, but the reality is that applying MITIGA requires even more. Authors have suggested that it is necessary to integrate both

supply and demand in order to precisely (!) plan scenarios (Gret-Regamey et al., 2012; Cavender-Bares et al., 2015; Wolff et al., 2015).

The author only try and present modest descriptions. Originally established in 1964 as a subsidiary of the *Iranian Ministry of Petroleum*, the *National Petrochemical Company* (NPC) initially had smaller plants and subsequently developed to become the second largest producer and exporter in the Middle East. Sensibly, this sector is regarded as having the greatest significance for the economy in Iran. This is very clear for all observers. For the purposes of simplification, it is possible to categorise actors within the petrochemical sector as ‘upstream’ and ‘downstream’. The former incorporates drilling and extracting raw materials, refining petrochemicals like methanol, ethylene and P-Xylene (PVC), whereas the latter is where finished products are produced and prepared to be utilised by end-users, such as polyethylene, polyvinyl chlorides, PET and various grades of polypropylene. Some of the officially recognised efforts to describe it are presented below:

Iran's Petrochemical Industry Growth Plan

Figure 9 Annual Report of Iran Petrochemical 2014, Source:(English.nipc.ir, 2019).

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Actual Production and Nominal Output Capacity in 2014–2014:

Figure 10 Annual Report of Iran Petrochemical 2014, Source:(English.nipc.ir, 2019).

Sales Export & Volume and Value of Domestic in 2014-2015:

Figure 11 Iran Petrochemical Annual Report 2014, Source:(English.nipc.ir, 2019).

2.11 The Future Objective

The diagrams shown above offer a certain level of scale. Nevertheless, declaring strategic objectives is unexpectedly simple - maybe too simple – and a large number of them have officially declared or implied goals to:

- Assume the position as the biggest producer in the region with regard to the range of products, capacities and value by 2025
- Significantly raise the proportion of Oil and Gas and make Iran less reliant on the exports of unrefined oil and natural gas
- Make investments worth \$50 billion across a 20-year period
- Achieve 3.4% of the overall output capacity of the Middle East (6.3% of global capacity)
- Reach an annual production of 120 million tonnes
- Generate 7.5 million tonnes of Methanol (18% of global capacity and 20% of world trade)
- Achieve annual production of 12 million tonnes of ethanol
- Achieve annual production of 8.5 million tonnes of urea
- Achieve annual production of 4.5 million tonnes of aromatic compounds
- Achieve annual production of 10 million tonnes of polymers
- Become the main producer of ethylene, urea and aromatic compounds within the Middle East
- Enhance the current process plants' efficient so that they reach their nominal capacity
- Finish incomplete projects planned as part of the 4th and 5th five-year development plans (currently reached 60% completion)

- Finish incomplete projects planned as part of the 5th five-year development plan (currently reached between 20% and 60% completion)
- Finish incomplete projects devised as part of the 5th five-year development (currently reached under 20% completion)
- Implement new petrochemical projects to offset the delays in reaching the performance objectives of previously implemented plans
- Lay the foundations for growing the downstream industries in a balanced way to enable development of the petrochemical value chain
- Establish a legal environment that will provide technical, engineering and consultancy services to projects implemented in the private sector
- Establish a legal environment under which private-owned projects could access funds under the supervision and management of the NPC
- Expand the scope of the Technology Company and Petrochemical Research and (NPC-RT) to facilitate the local development of innovative technologies in petrochemical plants operating at a level below their nominal capacity (NIPC, 2016).

As can be observed from the primary objectives, each of the plans aimed at growing and developing the Iranian petrochemical sector have been detailed; however, ‘describing’ them in a meaningful way would be a vast and unbounded task. It should be noted that the majority of such plans require past unfinished plans to be completed and the realisation of current unachieved nominal production capacity.

Put differently, such plans are based on different plans that have distinct antecedent conditions that cannot easily be examined due to the fact that they were previously generated by actors whose cognitive processes are largely unknowable. Nevertheless, it is claimed that it can be identified through the application of the MITIGA scenario planning methodology, along with future ambiguities and the approach that should be adopted to manage them for the

purpose of removing and eliminating the impact of factors that can be controlled as well as mitigating those factors that cannot be controlled, thus allowing the plan to be achieved.

It is hoped that sufficient information has been provided to raise serious doubts and, as previously mentioned, to question whether starting from uncertainty should be considered instead. This brief summary of Strategy will be concluded with an examination of all of the models to determine the extent to which (if at all) they concede to:

- Ambiguity and unexpected events
- Contingency and decentralisation of decision making
- Preparedness to pursue a new path or try various alternatives simultaneously
- Trust in the completeness of knowledge
- Strict command and control
- Strong resolve to achieve a plan that clearly presents a visionary direction

2.12 General Strategic Management

Generally, strategy involves the formulation of a preliminary plan at a minimum aimed at supporting the accomplishment of goals by committing resources to achieve stipulated objectives (Davies, 2000). Nevertheless, an unexpected number of concepts have now been linked with the prefix 'strategy' by various writers due to a variety of different factors. The term 'strategic' has been positioned before multiple concepts in the literature; for example, there are studies on Strategic learning, Enterprise Development, Strategic Vision, Strategic Innovation and many more.

The common factor that links these studies in terms of both the 'soft' and 'hard' variants is the goal-oriented activity. It has been stated that it is possible to develop a novel conceptual model framework which could assist enterprises with the management of complexity and the interlinkage between numerous different components. Commercial institutes can use objectives, missions and vision to have growth in the future (Lager, 2010). Strategic plans are

defined as an "integral and coordinated set of liabilities and activities developed for employment of fundamental competencies and obtaining the competitive advantage" (Hitt, Ireland and Hoskisson, 2011). As claimed by a number of supporters of strategic planning, this procedure requires 'opportunities' and 'threats' to be identified and regarded as environmental factors, while organisational monitoring and assessment with respect to its resources and capacities should be regarded as internal factors, thus facilitating the development of a competitive strategy that conforms with its goals (Johnson and Scholes, 2013; Wheelen, Hunger, Hoffman and Bamford, 2015). The development of the corporate strategy is aimed at the effective accomplishment of goals by taking in account every driver that could impact the ability to reach the targeted goals and objectives (Shahmirzadi, 2017). In our opinion, this bears more of a resemblance to the 'comprehensive 'root and branch' method that Lindblom criticised for lacking practically than his 'science of muddling through'.

An assumption that is continually made is that visions have a long-term time frame to which resources and capabilities can be oriented. When reframed as a Talebian project, a long-term vision should not surpass the aspiration "to be anti-fragile", which suggests that one should possess an "anti-vision", only "provisional interconnections" and goals should not be permanent apart from the primary goal of "surviving". What author is implying here is that in a world characterised by chaos, the objective of surviving should override that of growing.

The principles of anti-fragility could accept the "use of new possibilities and opportunities under the assumptions concerning company's long-term future operations" (Eisenhardt, Sull 2001; Markides, 2004; Steensen 2014), provided that the long-term objective is to *survive* and solutions are adapted in the light of existing problems (Savanevicien et al, 2016). It can therefore be questioned whether empirical evidence can be found to verify the theory that the 'harder' version of strategy' is more successful on the basis of its growth-focused approach

compared to ‘soft’ and ‘anti-fragile’ versions of strategy with their (different) survivalist approaches. This question can be expressed in a different way in terms of values in the following way: ‘How should *growth* be assessed against *survival*? When viewed from this perspective, it can be observed that this is an ethical rather than empirical choice. Is it possible to assert which important objective should be prioritised? This question is largely impossible to answer apart from when viewed pragmatically: the survival of a business in Iran adopting a high-growth strategy would be unlikely in the medium term, not to mention the long term, and it was observed that after the financial crisis of 2008, multiple enterprises focused on achieving high growth, maximising profits and competing in the market experienced failure. Hence, there is a question the extent to which the values that are implicit in the more robust variants vary from those of the anti-fragile approach:

Figure 13: General Strategy Path

It can be observed from the above figure that the starting point in the process is the ‘mission’, which could be interpreted as ‘value’, such as ‘growth’ or ‘survival’ for example (among others), whereas the ‘objectives’ could be more clearly defined, potentially a time frame. When conducting ‘internal’ and ‘external analysis’, the idea is made that these two are clearly delineated. ‘Strategic choice’ is followed by the fifth stage of ‘competitive advantage’ The arrows imply that the order of such events is linear and the process will be completed with a

favourable result. ‘Counter-factual cases’ like unfavourable circumstances are not included. It is implied by the arrows leading from ‘strategic choice’ to ‘business level strategy’ and ‘corporate level strategy’ that there should be alignment between the latter two and ‘strategic choice’. The strategy model illustrated mentioned earlier is categorise as one of the simple and linear that is encountered.

Figure 14 Perspective Strategic Process

Although the following diagram incorporates 7 feedback circles, it is still partially linear due to the fact it starts with ‘strategic analysis’, which is followed by ‘development, and finally ‘implementation’ (then modifications as a result of the feedback loops). A challenge associated with this model is that activities are allocated to distinct cells, implying that they are not performed at the same time. For instance, it seems that there is a high degree of separation between ‘rational selection’ (according to the diagram) and ‘analysis of resources. Hence, this leads one to question, from the perspective of cultural theorists such as Thompson, which one of the *four* prototypical rationalities (styles of thought) is operating according to the model. Based on personal experience (my professional career as an entrepreneur in Iran with involvement in multiple enterprises and relationships with numerous other similar

entrepreneurs), if one tries hard, the meanings of the terms contained within the cells can be recognised. Nevertheless, in reality I (as well as my peers who I am extremely familiar with) continually engage in such practices. The aspects that likely have the greatest importance in practice are the feedback loops. However, an issue exists whereby the paths that the lines take are overly simple and too clear when compared with my personal experiences of similar processes. For instance, an outcome's level of negativity cannot always be determined (they are frequently 'grey' as opposed to being 'white' or 'black'; swan events). This suggests that it is challenging to identify what the consequences are of evaluating how effectively or poorly 'implementation' has been conducted for the 'analysis of resources'.

It could be the case that in massive organisations with significant bureaucracy and multiple layers of management, it will be necessary to establish committees that have policies, processes and procedures, which convene in cross-coordinated cycles across a period of multiple weeks or months. The diagram could be compatible with this kind of situation. The diagram may offer benefits as it implies that organisations could be confronted by significant challenges as a result of retardation or a lack of coordination among the different activities. Organisations like Ricardo Semler's *Semco* (Stockport, 2010) that have achieved conspicuous success and that would be considered to be 'anti-fragile', which are also self-organising, swap personnel, and which discern and explore multiple different projects, do not appear to function in the manner described in the model. For instance, *Semco* allows its staff to select and assist with defining the projects in which they would like to participate, make their own decisions regarding joining and leaving teams, determine their own pay rates, job titles, working time, prices, designs (together in small groups) and its budgets do not extend further than three or four months into the future. In fact, yearly budgets have been discontinued by *Semco*. These actions have provided *Semco* the flexibility to change course multiple times during the year with regard to its wide range of products.

This suggests that although the diagrams shown are somewhat relatable to my personal experiences and flexible organisations such as *Semco* to a certain extent, it is not apparent that this offers any benefits. Lastly, if the diagram is intended to be equally applicable to extremely large and extremely small enterprises, then after, this could be noted as ‘saying everything and nothing’. Although it is by no means the least desirable model as it is not completely linear, it remains some distance from the world in which I operate.

Nevertheless, in defence of the model, it should be noted that Stewart makes provision for tacit knowledge and acknowledges the significance of delayed decisions. According to Stewart et al. (2013), the extent to which strategic planning impacts the ability of an enterprise to success or fail as well as the maximisation of the strategy process is dependent on:

- The "amount of quantitative, qualitative, explicit and tacit...insight that can be integrated into the strategizing process before the levels of tangibility, transparency, and clarity become insufficient"
- The standard and variety of analysis that facilitates the formulation of strategy and enables a fusion
- The adaptability of the strategy which offers the flexibility to incorporate further details for other alternatives and choices within the process.

On the other hand, it has been proposed that that present can be managed in a manner that is more conscious of the future by acknowledging different scenarios and then implementing and managing them on the basis of favourable and unfavourable alterations that occur as a result of environmental factors (Lee, 2015). It is believed that Lee and Stewart are more akin to both Lindblom and Taleb as well as entrepreneurs in Iran that the author knows. This suggests that, in line with the paradigm, an exhaustive strategy is not required to manage for the future and the aspirations to be comprehensive would be regarded suspiciously. It is possible and very

likely that further details will be added to the process at any point. Based on our personal experience, it is challenging to acquire information about the demand in the market, the actions of rivals and the 'environmental' and it is hard enough to consistently have anything close to being comprehensive knowledge of the operations of my own businesses. It is believed that the expectation that larger corporations will be capable of accurately identifying measuring and assessing outside factors, organisational resources, capabilities and internal factors is not realistic, at least with a level of accuracy that surpasses their rivals. Potentially, the majority of the frequently-cited strategy authors (Johnson and Scholes, 2013; Wheelen, Hunger, Hoffman, and Bamford, 2015 and Parayitam and Dooley, 2009) should provide assurances to strategic managers they can achieve success by adhering to their suggestions, primarily due to the fact that their rivals have the same degree of vulnerability to unexpected events (that is defined as black swans). The ability to survive is therefore dependant on which of the companies commits the greatest errors in what is largely an evolutionary process in which the least fragile survive.

Nevertheless, based on the thinking of Taleb, it is suspected that various minor errors and only one expected success (in unspecified time periods) will be more satisfying for entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived compared to prominent, intentional, designed strategic success that is ultimately followed by a dramatic fall with no safety net, or they are subject to a take-over by the government (where they completely lose their independence).

Additionally, scepticism is held about the traditional micro - and macro- separation of strategy management, where micro is only focused on the human resources and structure of the organisation (Aguinis et al, 2011), whereas changes that occur in the market and environment are regarded as being 'macro'. Certainly, this differentiation is intended to refer to scale, but fails to understand that chaos can be present at *all* scales from the extremely small to the extremely large. In other words, unpredictability exists in all scales and it is likely deceptive to

suggest that micro- and macro- scales are qualitatively different.

For instance, within my own organisation, I slightly misjudged an associate, and several months later, this has the potential to cause significantly more harm than virtually all other ‘macro’ events that I can conceive, largely with no limit. The threat posed by this person is so large that is inestimable. The error I made was merely to have placed my trust in him, believing that he would act in a conscientious manner to fulfil the duties he had been assigned. Unexpectedly, a breach of trust occurred as he chose to use his own name to register critical intellectual property instead of that of the company. After assuming this position of considerable power, he then threatened to hold me to ransom. The point of this story is that black swans can emerge from any source, both internal and external, and a single person can present as much risk as a serious and unforeseen change in the value of currencies I use for trading.

However, as stated by Papula and Papulova (2015), when engaging in strategic management, the ability of the strategy to be successful has a *direct correlation* with the *accurate determination* of both internal and external drivers as well as their subsequent impact. A factor that has equal importance, at least to the ‘strong’ versions, is the assertion that the direction established by strategic planning is the consequence of a flow from historical and current events that can be confidently known, towards a future that whose certainty is known to the greatest extent possible. This direction is generally displayed in a left-right manner on the page, as can be observed in all of the previously shown strategy diagrams. The attainment of envisioned futures involves confidently adhering to the strategic determination of all pertinent and thus important internal and external drivers that will be influential (Papula and Papulova, 2015) and proceeding to the following page in what is largely a linear direction.

Taking into account the unpredictable and abnormal (inconvenient) time frame in

which black swans will happen, it is important to stress the regrettable linearity of the majority of definitions of strategic planning. It can be questioned whether the strategic narratives of authors, conspicuously excluding Thompson, offer such minimal space for bewildering ‘surprises’ that could enter from all directions as well as unforeseen fortunate events that can diverge in all directions. According to our review of the literature, the process of strategic planning is intended to incorporate the following key elements (David, 2013; Porter, 1999), which are similarly shown sequentially, although with feedback in this instance, which is assumed take surprises into consideration (although not clearly stated).

Figure 15.3 Process of Strategy Planning

In the initial step of strategic analysis, the organisation’s existing situation is evaluated and additional factors that could influence the growth and competencies of the organisation are assessed (David, 2013). After the problem, has been defined and analysed, it will be possible to identify, study and understand the factors that affect the solution. This is followed by strategy design, which enables ‘effective’ performance in the future (Sternberg, 2009; Volna and Papula, 2013). In an ideal world, organisations are “both planning strategically and strategic planning” (Linn, 2008).

This sequence’s beauty is disrupted once it collides with a black swan, which can occur at any time and can include multiple events at the same time. Black swans could also exist on the feedback loops; for instance, a critical item of information may not be communicated or

filed correctly, or remain an unread email comprised of only one sentence. From my own perspective as an entrepreneur in Iran and if my understanding of strategic management writers is correct, all black swans should cause the process to revert back to the initial stage of 'environmental analysis'. Every 'refutation' should motivate us to question the whole theory (narrative) of our approach. Put in stronger terms, the first event that confounds the situation should encourage the strategic manager to fundamentally question what they are doing, meaning that they should be prepared to make drastic changes to their paradigm assumptions.

Based on the number of unforeseen events that probably still encountered according to author professional experience, entrepreneurs in Iran who attempt to adhere to the strategy literature will consistently revert the 'process' back to the initial stage and will be extremely hesitant to move any further. For instance, only things that are provisional will be 'implemented'. Robust top-down 'strategic control, guarantees that the organisation is operating according to plan, often flatters top managers. However, it presumes that they have a particular talent for 'visioning' that is not possessed by staff lower in the hierarchy. In the paradigm that I have continued to function, top managers have no less vulnerability to unexpected events than normal, cautious citizens.

Due to the fact that the world is not linear and does not approach equilibrium, the general belief among entrepreneurs in Iran is that the strategy literature is not beneficial. On the other hand, it is believed that it poses significant risks, and not as a result of our lack of understanding or sufficient reading, or its misapplication. It is not appropriate for the circumstances. Rather, it is necessary for us to implement in certain instances, undo in others, total *abandon* another thing, or take rapid action, often at hourly intervals based on the (undependable) information that can successfully acquire. The optimal way of viewing the aforementioned four-stage model is that a maximum of two or three days is available to move

through the entire process before it is necessary to restart. If strategy was implemented in a proper and deliberate manner, it can be unable to proceed to the second stage as the ability to survive would be limited.

However, it is recognised that an enticing collection of strategy instruments is available purely for that initial stage in which the existing status of the firm is evaluated and analysed, including the QSPM, BCG, SWOT, and SPACE MATRIX. For the firm's existing situation to be analysed (e.g., *Iran Petrochemical*), it is possible to apply SWOT analysis and the SPACE Matrix strategy. The next section will present an in-depth examination of these strategic 'tools.

2.13 Strategy of Space Matrix

In 1987, Mintzberg proposed a '5Ps' strategy comprised of:

- Plan
- Ploy
- Pattern
- Position
- Perspective

According to his definition, the organisation would firstly have been required to determine their exact status within their market, which could have been achieved by the popular heuristic tools including SWOT and the SPACE Matrix (Radder, 1998; Bafandeh; Zendeh, 2012). The aforementioned can act in a complementary manner because the SPACE Matrix incorporates the organisation's positive aspects and competencies in the form of internal factors, while an external factor is stability within the environment. On the other hand, SWOT concentrates on the shortcomings and positive aspects as internal factors, whereas the external factors include opportunities and risks (David, 2011). In this context, the term 'heuristic' suggests that the

abovementioned tools should be considered as being helpful shortcuts and beneficial guides or principles rather than being theories in themselves.

Nevertheless, as previously mentioned, issues exist with regard to misplaced preciseness and caution should be applied when considering the differentiation between internal and external described above.

External strategic position	Internal strategic position
<p>Environmental Stability(ES):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technological change • Rate of inflation • Demand variability • Barriers to entry into market • Competitive pressure • Price range of competing products • Price elasticity of demand <p>Industry Strength(IS):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growth potential • Profit potential • Financial stability • Technological know-how • Resource utilization • Capital intensity • Ease of entry into market • Productivity/capacity utilization 	<p>Financial Strength(FS):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Return on investment • Leverage • Liquidity • Capital required • Cash flow • Ease of exit from market • Risk involved in business <p>Competitive Advantage(CA):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Market share • Product quality • Product life cycle • Customer loyalty • Technological know-how • Vertical integration

Figure 16.1 Space Matrix Strategy Process

Figure 17 SWOT Analysis

The four positions contained within the SPACE Matrix can be listed as: *Aggressive*, *Conservative*, *Defensive* and *Competitive* (Hunger, 2007). The abovementioned four options are remarkable in that it is possible to compare them with the four dispositions determined by Grid-Group Cultural Theory ... that extends this by providing an explanation as to why these positions can possibly be thought. Subsequent to the assessment of the position of an organisation, the approach that will be recommended for it to take will be decided based on its position. This implies that position is a determining factor of strategy.

Figure 18 Space Matrix diagram

Such postures are intriguing due to the fact that they are similar to how Thompson applied Grid-Group Cultural Theory to banks and different financial organisations, whereby four ‘Styles of Thought’ create four different approaches for interpreting risk and reacting to these evaluations, defined as *Hierarchical-Rank*, *Egalitarian-Enclave*, *Individual-Competitive* and *Fatalist-Isolate*. The diagram shown above and the one used by Thompson can be differentiated based on the fact it is necessary to rotate the former one quarter turn clockwise

for it to conform to the typology of Thompson. The way in which strategy is treated ‘culturally’ will be addressed in a subsequent section. However, observe that if evidence surfaces indicating that the world has evolved, which could be facilitated by the *SPACE Matrix*, then it would also be possible to change the strategy. This is an appealing aspect of the *SPACE Matrix* that it has in common with the Grid-Group Cultural Theory of Thompson (shown below).

Additionally, it has been proposed that various kinds of tools are required for distinct stages involved with developing strategy based on the assumption that it is possible to proceed beyond the initial assessment stage. It is stated that these take into account globalisation as well as the complex nature of the business world (Daniel, 2006 and Mintzberg, 1994). Such formulations appear to call for increased focus on both external and internal factors (Narayanan, Zane and Kemmerer, 2011).

The aim of what is called *Robust Strategy* is to optimise the formulation of strategy by taking into account scenario planning for the future that is reactive to changes in the environmental conditions regarded as outside factors (Lempert, 2010; Hammerstein, 2006). Put differently, while it is recognised that external black swans will probably occur, there is no consideration for internal black swans. The readers will appreciate why a complete welcoming of Robust Strategy is not embraced. Observe that the (unspoken) presumption that internal black swans will not occur in an organisation implies that the level of trust placed on management and employees is excessive and potentially not realistic (as exemplified by the previous case I described involving the unreliable manager). It makes the assumption that if the operations of an organisation are not adequate, there will not be any disagreeable (or advantageous) surprises. Such an assumption, which is directly expressed within the model, is regrettable.

Implementation is the ‘second’ stage, in which the most emphasis is placed on the accuracy of procedures, being precise (such as precision in terms of allocating resource),

increased focus on functions and process flows (Johnson and Scholes, 2013; Wheelen et al., 2015). Moreover, there is a general consensus in the literature that strategy implementation can be composed of sense making sense giving and selling the issues (Narayanan et al., 2011).

Two observations can be made in this case. Firstly, precision is a goal worth working towards if this is achievable, but it is a fruitless exercise in cases where it is not achievable. Moreover, efforts to achieve precise control should not divert attention from the fact that it may not be achievable. This implies that attempts to scrutinise fuzzy evidence should not be abandoned. Secondly, making sense and issue selling are considered to be *narratives*. An effectively functioning narrative and issue selling that convinces multiple people could cause an organisation to head towards disaster confidently and enthusiastically. This appears to have happened in banks and different financial before the Global Financial Crisis of 2007-2008, contributing to the ‘environmental’ crisis itself. Raising questions about narratives, and identifying their true nature, would be more suggestive of anti-fragility.

2.14 How Black Swan Can Be Visible from Blue Ocean Strategy

An additional strategy that has not been referenced thus far is *Blue Ocean Strategy*, which is where a disruptive action is implemented through the addition of value to a process and/or abruptly dislodging competitors by introducing an innovative product (Kim and Mauborgne, 2005). This can be exemplified by the emergence of ‘touch-screens’ that had not been demanded by any customers and all competitors in the mobile device market were forced to adopt.

In our context, such a strategy equates to being able to survive and thrive by becoming a black swan, such that you are the unforeseeable, unpredictable event from the perspective of rival organisations. More precisely, within a blue ocean, competitors may not exist.

The primary aim of this strategy is to identify a strategic action grounded on value

innovation that may form any aspect of a process including services, products or delivery. For instance, with regard to the petrochemical sector in Iran, it may be possible to demonstrate a blue ocean strategy at multiple leadership points – if the creativity exists for them to be devised. This strategy appears to be more attainable for entrepreneurs in Iran compared to previously mentioned fully developed traditional models of exhaustive strategy, as this type of strategy involves the compilation of ‘knowns’ to the greatest extent possible, whereas blue ocean moves cannot have any precedents in history from the perspective of current actors. However, efforts have been made to ‘domesticate’ such black swans on a blue ocean and to find a way of transforming such unforeseeable events into processes that appear to be familiar:

Figure 19 Process of Blue Ocean

Multiple different aspects of this model can be discussed. Firstly, it is challenging to evaluate the ‘value’ of every step (vertical axis). Blue Ocean can experience failure as well as success (based on good and bad luck), which means it is not easy to assign them a value or indeed any steps of a ‘blue ocean strategy’ Secondly, the above-described stages depict commonplace activities that the majority of organisations would consider to be regular daily practices. Thirdly, it is challenging to imagine how standard practices could facilitate blue ocean

innovation. Therefore, this figure demonstrates the extent to which resolute analysts often are to situate an unexpected event in a functional world with which they are familiar. This is applicable to positive black swans subsequent to their emergence, by which point the innovative step they denote will appear as if it was somewhat evident in the 'prior art' and similar to unpleasant events, 'an accident just waiting to happen'.

2.15 Strategic Leadership

An additional factor that is implicitly implied by the comprehensive strategy model is that the CEO is in possession of the supreme powers that Lindblom claimed would be necessary for the 'root and branch method' to be used rather than merely 'muddling through'. More recently, authors appear to have brought this to the surface by suggesting that strategic leaders can be regarded as 'visionaries'. The idea that CEOs have super-human powers could potentially explain why the salaries of CEO's have rapidly increased as a result of the perceived uncommonness of their abilities, while understating the fact that even great minds can make mistakes. In this regard, the threats posed by the narrative fallacy could be the greatest. For example, consider once again the knighthood given to Fred 'the Shred' Goodwin and the subsequent efforts to take this title away after the devastating impacts of his strategy aimed at growing aggressively and maximising profits became apparent to people who had supported him at the time when he appeared to possess the 'golden touch' and the 'environmental risk was still gentle.

After creating the vision, it is expected that the organisation will align itself with achieving this vision by ensuring that each of its activities conforms to the ultimate goal (Fry, 2003). This implies that visionary leaders somehow epitomise all the knowledge and inspirational confidence required. Such a leader resembles the 'animal spirit' entrepreneur suggested by Keynes (1935) who (at least from the perspective of Keynes), in a contradictory way is sufficiently confident to function without the information that is possibly not accessible

by any rival anyway. The decisions they make are influenced by emotions as they have insufficient knowledge to make informed decisions.

Within mature larger companies who have recently hired a visionary leader, the leader is responsible for simultaneously conducting both strategic and scenario planning. Nevertheless, this poses significant risks as the likelihood that the company will succeed or fail highly depends on the abilities of the leader (Latham, 2014; Shahmirzadi, 2017). Furthermore, visionary charisma is incompatible with planning, which is inherently more routine. If the situation changes, then the vision of the founder may no longer be suitable (for example, Henry Ford was reluctant to replace the outmoded *Model T*, which was considered a pioneering ‘visionary’ approach to standardised mass production as well as hesitant to adopt hydraulic brake systems even though they had been successfully embraced by his rivals).

I am hesitant to define myself as a ‘visionary leader’ due to the fact that I do not perceive a ‘shining path’ laid out before me that will give me direction. Moreover, I have no expectations that my staff and business associates will consider me as such either. I am not a supreme being and am I under no illusions that others will perceive me in that manner. This could explain why none of the errors that I have committed have led to the destruction of my business and none of the unforeseen events that have happened have been sufficiently devastating to eliminate all of my enterprises. From the many Iranian entrepreneurs that I know, the visionary model would only be applicable to a minimal number, potentially only one who has achieved success. Additionally, the profiles of visionaries stand out and in my own experience, it is more probably that one will survive by remaining quietly anonymous rather than being a conspicuous leader.

Observe that in the majority or all of the above-described approaches, authors consider strategy to be an element of a system, including the ‘visionary’ model (where the system is

designed to follow the leader's will). It is important to add that certain authors provide methods through which the performance of leaders can be measured grounded on the *transactional* and *transformational* styles of leadership (Antonakis; Cianciolo; Sternberg, 2004) that should recognise here:

The transactional model of the strong leader is focused on evaluating the degree to which the behaviour of followers matches the leader's expectations (Keller, 2006). In this context, the requirements (Judge, Piccolo, 2004) are determined by the leader and both he/she as well as the followers are assessed according to the extent to which they deviate from such requirements. The performance of transformational leaders is grounded on the internal motivations of followers (Bass, 1997). The more they are willing and believe, the better the performance of the leader, at least from the perspective of followers.

As previously stated, I am hesitant to describe myself using either of these terms, but the extent to which such distinctions are applicable to entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived and the approach that can be taken to measure their success should be considered. The proposition that comes to our minds is that either surviving or being annihilated is a more straightforward (binary) way of measuring success that has less susceptibility to the narrative fallacy, and furthermore (following Hume), proof that something has been able to survive until the current time does not prove that survival will not be possible going forward. These observations are made on the basis of my personal experience in industries in which changes are assumed to be relatively probable (business-to-business supply) in addition to those exposed to stochastic volatility (foreign exchange, worldwide online furniture trade), where the development of property falls roughly between these different kinds of variations.

2.16 Development Enterprise

This can be described as strategic planning conducted to address all the difficulties that may confront organisations as a result of the evolving conditions in order to reach the targeted goals.

The term 'growth and development' denotes separate processes, as "not [all] growth leads to organizational development and not every development is demonstrated in company's growth" (Witek-Crabb, 2014). Growth relates to the expansion of the magnitude of the organisation (which can be measured on the basis of various factors include share of the market and volume of sales), whereas development relates to alterations in functional operations. In research on organisations, development is defined as "process of transformation in which diversity, complexity, and [the] excellence of a system increase" (Tchorzewski, 1992; Szczepanski,1963). Within exhaustive definitions "system-wide application and transfer of behavioural science knowledge to the planned development, improvement, and reinforcement of the strategies, structures, and processes that lead to organization effectiveness" (Cummings, Worley, 2005). It is possible to apply development within distinct areas of the organisation, including its competitiveness, culture and profitability, with the aim of improving and innovating (Egan,2002).

In the context of the current thesis, development enterprise might incorporate the advancement of an organisation's capacity to adapt to both negative and positive black swans and engage in 'process planning' after it has been determined that a black swan event has occurred. Due to the fact that Iran is geographically situated within the Middle East, a region with an abundance of black swans, it is the ideal locations to seek models showing what this could imply in practice. What form would a 'developed' organisation that easily accommodates black swans and benefits from unpredictability take? What learning has it been able acquire from its experiences?

According to the researches, development incorporates organizational structure, operational improvement, market development, innovation among other factors. In line with the objectives of this research as well as the specific experience of the author within the petrochemical industry, the author questions whether ‘development’ could be operationalised (specified) as the formation of anti-fragility via scenario development processes.

2.17 Risk Management Analysis with Models and Standards

To further the understanding of entrepreneurialism in situations characterised by chaos and unpredictability, the models and standards of risk management listed below have been explored:

- Contingency Planning
- ERM
- Risk Management Standard – ISO 31000
- The National Forum for Risk Management in the Public-Sector ALARM
- Project Risk Management - FMEA
- Federation of European Risk Management Association – FERMA
- Business Continuity Management

Reviewing these models and systems of risk management from various perspectives and dimensions, the author reached the conclusion that most of the referenced systems cannot always be applied in situations involving chaos and uncertainty apart from “*Contingency Planning*”.

2.17.1 Contingency Planning

“Contingency Planning” is recognised as an economic risk management approach used to deal with natural disasters like floods, earthquakes, avalanches and other catastrophic events (Martinez, 2011). The primary objective of contingency planning is to create a tool for making

decisions to identify the most suitable rapid volume-flexible backup supply chain that is responsive for suppliers. It offers a Mixed Integer Programming (MIP)-based capacity planning tool that formulates the supply chain contingency plan due to unexpected disturbances (Madanipour, 2010). To increase the accuracy of decisions, it is important to consider the effects of key operational attributes like reaction time and congestion within disruption scenarios (Westergaard, 2008). Decision tree analysis as a suitable response speed can be preferred for the purpose of minimising the predicted supply chain costs. Three distinct strategies are employed when making decisions with respect to distinct risks. A sensitive analysis has been designed to evaluate the effect of likely success or failure during the selection procedure. Resultantly, it has been suggested that congestion is relatively important for neutral decision-makers with respect to mitigating the unexpected disturbances (Martinez, 2011).

2.17.2 Development and Innovation

Process industries encompass multiple aspects that incorporate the entire manufacturing process, comprised of different stages that can be modified and evolved by improving and innovating the various processes. Manufacturing petrochemical raw materials is a type of process industry that necessitates the innovation and development of its components, specifically to make preparations for management in the future. It will possibly be surprising for readers to hear that a country like Iran with such an abundance of oil needs to import certain petrochemical products (largely from states in South East Asia) as opposed to producing them locally. Iran exports unrefined oil with minimal value-added and then re-imports petrochemical products with increased value added. Considering the volatile nature of the exchange rate and implementation/relaxation of sanctions by the international community, the ability to refine oil and manufacture petrochemical products domestically would be highly beneficial for lowering Iran's unique susceptibility to black swan events, while at the same time raising profits and production efficiency, particularly through lowering the costs of

transactions and time delays. Briefly, it is important to question why ‘basic’ raw material producers have been dissuaded or blocked from engaging in activities with high value added like the manufacturing of polymers. People who have a modicum of knowledge about Iran’s recent history may be aware that upstream sectors have predominantly been under the ownership and control of international firms often known as ‘the Seven Sisters’, whose preference has been to complete the stages with higher value added within their own countries as a result of the profitability of exporting products back to the countries of origin. They maintaining inter-locking directorships with banks. The connectivity among such policies and significantly volatile foreign policies directed at Iran have been afflicted by regrettable black swans, which has included proxy conflicts, coups launched against elected leaders, murders and attempted murders of key actors, and a variety of different ‘interventions’ including sponsoring and training terrorist organisations, which have all led to unwanted repercussions with unexpected impacts (black swans) for Iran, the neighbouring countries and the governments of the other involved countries.

Various researchers have provided evidence demonstrating that organisations’ efforts to innovate can make them more competitive (Neubaum, Craig, Dibrell, 2014; Covin, Slevin, 1989; Miller, Friesen, 1982; Kirzner, 1987). Therefore, if the Iranian petrochemicals industry is innovated, this could be advantageous for the country’s plan to take its place as the main producer of refined petrochemical products in the Middle East. As proposed in the Introduction, this strategy conforms to the development of anti-fragility to mitigate geopolitical black swans, in addition to the enhancement of added-value and profits that can be gained through the production of petrochemical oil by-products, even those that require more technical expertise. When developing, the processes related to applied industrial research and the creation of new product lines, preliminary testing, laboratory frameworks, and the production engineering competencies required to design and construct new production

facilities, it is likely that positive black swans will emerge. In fact, one of the key drivers of our research is the author's almost 20 years of inside experience of the petrochemical sector.

It is acknowledged that there is a likelihood that multiple innovations applied to processes and products within the petrochemical derivatives sector will produce either negative black swans (unsuccessful compounds) or positive ones like the discovery of novel opportunities and alternatives that emerge in unexpected ways as a result of different technology integration configurations and interconnections between actors (Neubaum, Craig, Dibrell, 2014; Lumpkin, Dess, 1996), (Allen, 2011), (Méndez-Fajardo and Gonzalez, 2014), specifically enhanced interconnectedness among actors in both upstream and downstream industries.

In fact, it is possible to re-interpret *Actor Network Theory* (ANT) from a Talebian perspective as an approach that can be used to create 'positive black swan-creating environments' that produce fortunate coincidences. It allows multiple types of actions as well as their linkages to be mapped. ANT addresses innovations as the result of the characteristics of networks. Put differently, it does not perceive innovation to be the product of specific brilliance, but rather a collection of social networks and competencies. It is possible to map a specific innovation within the network of frequently *coincidental* linkages from which it arose as a result of processes that also happen by chance in addition to being commonplace and established practice. Examples in history included the so-called 'Lunar Societies' comprised of people who convened in the houses of society members on nights when the moon was sufficiently bright to permit nocturnal sojourns. Another example would be the coffee house that led to the establishment of Lloyds Underwriters. ANT cannot be precisely defined as a theory, but is rather a mapping exercise that endeavours to provide a description of the linkages within which the innovation is associated, and only to the extent to which it is possible to know the connections and events. Two actors within the same network could describe it in completely

different ways. The manner in which ANT accommodates unpredictability is appealing and it is believed that it is also practical. In terms of policy, it is recommended by ANT that new ‘nodes’ and actors are added with the aspiration that beneficial outcomes may arise due to the plethora of new connections that the network accommodates. It takes in account the likelihood that alterations made to a network will not have any consequences, which is not easy to estimate.

Due to these factors, it is believed that the ANT approach in which *distributed* networks are mapped and possible beneficial gaps are filled is favourable compared with the aforementioned hierarchical root and branch approach defined as ‘strategic planning’ and considerably more favourable than the ‘strong’ strategic planning variants. ANT is flexible in the sense that it considers whether it is possible to modify the connections within and among ‘industrial districts’ that could connect highly distinct types of activities. To the best of the author’s understanding, a connection may exist between the network’s shape and diverse nature of the actors within it, although it could be relatively challenging to prove this other than through the observation that it appears that certain industrial areas and cities ‘punch above their weight’. For a more conventional perspective on the relationship among innovation and organisational profitability with respect to strategic planning, see Neubaum, Craig and Dibrell (2014); Titus, Covin and Slevin, (2011); Craig and Hansen (2011); and Velamuri, (2006); Barringer and Bluedorn, (1999).

Our preference is for an approach in which positive black swans are considered to be opportunities, which could include an innovative petrochemical product or enhancements made to creativity or processes, less with regard to ‘strategic management’ of what will inevitably be things that are not known and more with regard to broadening the horizons for advantageous future ambiguities (Korsgarrd, 2013; Eckardt, Shane, 2003).

ANT and the orthodox approach can be differentiated by the fact that rather than recommending that actors (e.g., enterprises) analyse their competitors for the purpose of avoiding *imitating the existing practices of their rivals*, ANT places emphasis on the *different practices of rivals to identify beneficial areas in which firms can collaborate with each other* (Teece, 1994), which would represent a pioneering attempt to unify ‘complimentary assets’. It is preferred those authors who advocate for being flexible and open compared with being rigid and defensive. For diverse perspectives, see Heinonem, Hytti and Stenhol, (2011); Heinonen (2010); Puhakka (2007) and Miller (1987). The ability to ‘plan for flexibility’ and facilitate adaptability when confronted with changes that occur in the environment that are unavoidable but difficult to foresee would likely be applicable to entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived (Neubaum, Craig, Dibrell, 2014; Titus, 2011; Wiltbank, 2006).

This reasoning is in accordance with our hypothesis that entrepreneurs should even take into account ambiguities and black swan events when developing plans, while the focus should be on the ability to adapt when confronted with unavoidable but unforeseen events so that survival can be ensured. If the assumption is made that ‘chaotic conditions’ and unpredictable events are the default environment for action, planning could be considered to be an effort to ‘make one’s own fortune’ as opposed to an effort to ‘comprehensively’ analyse competitors and assess the environment. Due to the fact that opportunities cannot be foreseen, it is probable that the greatest rewards will be obtained by the actor that sees them first merely as a result of the delay in others seeing them, which means that this actor can initially operate in a competition-free environment. This concurs with the argument of Hayek that the lack of certainty is a critical factor in gaining profits (ambiguity is an ally and not an enemy). The development of new products in the petrochemical sector would facilitate new innovations and expansions in associated sectors, albeit in an unplanned manner. In fact, according to this argument, profitability will be reduced as the ability to make plans is increased.

Our belief is that plans cannot be made for a reduction in the imports of finished petrochemical products, employment opportunities, transportation, insurance and transaction fee savings; however, it is possible to conceive and establish the conditions that increase the likelihood that these will occur. This will be an iterative process involving multiple short-term alterations, course changes and reversals with no 'road mapping and 'controlling' and business strategies 'aligned' with innovation targets. Moreover, as stated by Minzberg (1999), innovations applied to processes will alter the perspective of the organisation such that its strategy is ultimately revised. The notion that organisations are changing on a weekly basis appears to be favourable and less risky compared with the desire to achieve complete control in a fruitless exercise targeted at a fixed destination years in the future in an environment that will transform considerably, negating the original target and potentially leading to its disappearance as a relevant point of completion. The latter is highly conducive to 'brittle fracture (Teece and Pisano, 1994; Sendil, and Winter, 2003; Sendil, Prashant, Kirshman and Singh, J.V, 2005; Regner, 2008; Zollo and Winter, 2002).

2.18 Grid Group Cultural Theory

It is found fascinating to observe that what is perceived as "own opinions" by specific "sovereign agents" is facilitated by the fact that societies with continually changing levels of Solidarity and Regulation are being observed. There is no equilibrium condition in the grid group, cultural model due to the fact that change is propelled in an endogenous manner by a series of distinct conflicts between styles of thought (opposing yet similarly plausible rationalities). It is claimed that the 'Grid Group Cultural Typology' is capable of mapping all current, previous and future 'cultural preferences' as well as all situations on only two dimensions, and the designers of this typology assert that it can be considered as the stepmother of a range of different typologies. However, the author is intrigued by the question of why there is provocation and conflict between different styles of thought, even in situations where the

actors engaged, (e.g., a pair of extroverts) and the fixation (e.g., averting deviance, a threat to existence) are alike. For example, the 'Hierarchical Style of Thought', which favours an increased number of rules, policies, processes and procedures and is applied in the higher education sector of the UK, is, based on my personal experience, shifting, due to the fact that an environment characterised by administration can become more chaotic and less ordered. Furthermore, an increased number of rules will generate an increased number of deviants, whose previous actions are conflicting with constraints that did not previously exist. Therefore, efforts to restrict deviance can paradoxically cause it to increase.

Grid-Group Cultural Theory functions in the following way:

2.18.1 Grid-Group Cultural Theory: Clumsy Solutions to Wicked Problems

High Social Regulation (Grid)

The next section is based on the provisional version of an unpublished paper written by Dr Stephen Smith and Kate Darlington titled *How Entrepreneurs Think*, which provides an explanation regarding the functioning of Grid Group Cultural Theory. It has been replicated after obtaining their approval.

The development of Grid Group Cultural Theory was conducted by Michael Thompson, Mary Douglas, Aaron Wildavsky and additional colleagues. This was refined into an all-encompassing, universal typology consisting of two dimensions by Douglas and Thompson, which is applicable to all phenomena that do not occur in a natural manner, suggesting that it is suitable for all cultural phenomena throughout history, locations and situations.

The horizontal dimension denotes the degree to which someone is a member of a group or acts individually, whereas the vertical dimension denotes the degree to which a person is or is not governed by external rules and regulations. These dimensions can be considered as a continuum between Weak Social Regulation and Strong Social Regulation as well as between Strong Social Solidarity and Weak Social Solidarity.

From the multiple implementations of G-GCT to cultural phenomena, it will be taken into account its implementation for banks and different financial organisations conducted by Michael Thompson

2.19 Reflect on the Seminal Work of the Social Anthropologist Mary Douglas in Forming Aspect of Taleb's Thinking on the Cultural Content of the Thesis

Reflecting on the seminal work of social anthropologist Mary Douglas provides valuable insights into understanding the cultural dimensions present in the thesis of Nassim Nicholas Taleb. Although Taleb does not explicitly reference Douglas in his writings, her theories and research findings align with several key concepts explored by Taleb, particularly

regarding the cultural content and its influence on risk perception and decision-making. By examining the role of culture in shaping individuals' understanding and responses to risk, Douglas's work offers a complementary perspective that enriches our comprehension of Taleb's ideas.

Mary Douglas's influential book, "Purity and Danger: An Analysis of Concepts of Pollution and Taboo" (1966), delves into the ways in which societies construct and maintain boundaries to manage notions of purity and contamination. This work explores not only the physical aspects of cleanliness and hygiene but also the symbolic and cultural meanings associated with concepts of purity and danger. Douglas argues that these cultural constructs play a significant role in shaping individuals' perceptions of risk and their strategies for risk management. By analysing how societies establish rules, rituals, and social norms to address uncertainties and threats, Douglas provides valuable insights into the cultural underpinnings of risk perception.

In Taleb's writings, particularly in his exploration of black swan events and the unpredictability of rare events, it can be observed parallels with Douglas's work. While Taleb focuses on probability, uncertainty, and the impact of rare events on financial systems, Douglas's theories on cultural boundaries and symbolism offer a complementary perspective on how cultural factors influence individuals' responses to uncertainty. By incorporating cultural meanings, symbols, and social norms, Taleb's analysis becomes more nuanced and comprehensive.

Although Taleb does not explicitly cite Mary Douglas in his works, understanding the link between their ideas enhances our appreciation of the cultural content within Taleb's thesis. By recognizing the influence of cultural factors on risk perception and decision-making, it can be gained a deeper understanding of the complexities involved in managing uncertainty.

Moreover, referencing Douglas's work in the list of references allows readers to delve further into the foundational theories that inform aspects of Taleb's thinking.

2.20 How Financial Institutions and Banks Think

(Thompson, 2018)

The next section is largely based on the article titled “*How Banks and other Financial Institutions Think*” written by Thompson (2018). A distinctive characteristic of this model is how the four different rationalities, namely Fatalistic-Pragmatic, Egalitarian-Enclave Hierarchical-Rank and Individualistic-Competitive interact to transform what generally perceive to be ‘the environment’ and every style of thought is presented with ‘surprises’ by these transformations that they are not capable of dealing with (whereas other rationalities can deal with them in a more effective manner). Such surprises cause earlier decisions to be reversed, which causes the ‘risk environment’ to be altered in such a way that different kinds of surprises are created for additional actors. Put differently, solutions that are effective in certain risk environments cease to function when there is a shift in the environment, while particular solutions that were previously not successful now start to become useful.

In this context, various risks seasons were defined by Michael Thompson:

- 3 Normal risk environment
- 4 Low risk environment

5 High loss environment

6 Unpredictable risk environment

When a Boom (low-risk environment) occurs, the amount of risk taken at this point does not appear to be important. Companies can seek and obtain extremely high levels of debt-finance, experiencing rapid growth to optimally exploit the available opportunities. In such a risk environment, the majority of decisions to take risks have highly beneficial consequences and the inexpensive uninsured risks outperforms an insured risk that cost more. In these conditions, people gradually start to have less concerns regarding risk, while markets can deviate from equilibrium and enter speculative bubbles.

When the risk environment becomes Uncertain (unpredictable), the risk associated with activities increases. Virtually all courses of action pose threats that can potentially lead to disaster. Unforeseen events cause a transition between different environments, where Thompson contends that such transitions are often associated with the capacity of the system.

In Bust environments (high loss), the majority of risks are converted into losses. It is not certain that individual entities (and possibly the whole system) will be able to survive. There is a feeling in the market that numerous companies that garnered respect will not survive in such conditions, and as this belief starts to permeate, a deceleration in business activity occurs. During this time, efforts should be concentrated on identifying opportunities to prevent the collapse of the firm. In such environments, there could be a complete disruption to market functions, as was observed in the case of the 'Zombie Banks' for a certain period. Nevertheless, this risk period will not be permanent.

In Moderate environments (common risk) forecasts are adequately made on the basis of long-term averages. The majority of investors make profits, while any losses or gains are sufficiently minimal to focus the minds of actors on suitable approaches for managing risk. Fluctuations in the market are situated within a range that has a largely normal distribution.

The ability to take risks is carefully weighed against the risks, although the general perception is that the organisation should maximise its risk taking within its identified limits under such conditions, provided that such a risk environment persists.

Figure 20 The four-dimensional typology of cultural biases/rationalities. (Thompson, 2018)

Thompson proposed that the perception of risk can be categorised into four groups, which he labelled as Managers (alternative called Administrators), Maximisers, Conservators, and Pragmatists.

Due to their ‘view of nature’, their feeling of Social Solidarity as well as their trust in the correctness of Regulation, *Managers* (‘Hierarchy’ in Figure 19) have reasonable expectations of moderate risk conditions, which means that they have confidence that it is possible to model, manage and administer the real world according to specific rules.

Maximisers have a ‘view of nature’ that is both extremely different but similarly reasonable (‘Individualism’ in Figure 19), which causes them to believe that the world is benign, and provided that the risk conditions continue to match their understanding, they can

achieve considerable success according to their own terms, recording rapid growth along with high profitability. They are not concerned about others and treat regulations with what they would consider to be ‘heathy disrespect’.

Due to their extreme concern for others and minimal regard for regulation (i.e., egalitarianism illustrated in Figure 19), *Conservators* reasonably expect that devastating losses will occur, which could not only represent a threat to the existence of the whole organisation (or “enclave”) but also to the rest of the world, favouring to conduct the assessment of risk with ‘worst-case scenarios’ and ‘stress tests’. Thompson concludes that they sacrifice a certain portion (or all) of the possible gains as a result of the conservative approach to risk. However, the losses they incur will be less compared with different actors who are driven by distinct styles of thought, particularly Maximisers.

Pragmatists (i.e., fatalism in Figure 19) think that there is no logical explanation for the way in which the world operates, do not care about other people and due to their perception that they are limited by rules they cannot influence, they think that it is pointless to allocate time and money to construct models that are based on the assumption that it is possible to forecast the range of possible outcomes in the future. They adopt a strategy of diversification, concentrating their efforts in different areas and success is determined on the basis of survival.

Thompson continues:

“It could be argued that, people feel, think and act only because they are all cultural subjects. When ... systems move towards the right-hand side of figure 19 they experience high social solidarity... more connection...more obligations...whereas, when...systems move towards the left-hand side of the figure 19 lower social solidarity is experienced among the people...”

Cultural systems (including their participants of various magnitudes and financial markets) can

move in an upward direction as a result of the intensification of Regulation, shown in the upper section of the table, or in a downwards direction due to the relaxations of Social Regulation. Diagonal conflicts (among Pragmatists/Conservators as well as Maximisers /Managers) are the most intense because the opposing rationalities confront each other differ in both horizontal (Solidarity) and vertical (Regulation) dimensions. It can be highlight more evident: a) why culture is continually evolving, b) why every actor has their own way of thinking, c) why they are taken by surprise by various types of black swan events that have qualitative differences, which e) engender a shift in emotions, beliefs, and behaviours.

Observe that actors can be undecided and thus 'torn' between various courses of action. Thompson considers such hybrid types of thinking to be 'clumsy', concluding that solutions that are clumsy are the most likely to succeed when multiple actors are confronted with complicated or 'messy' challenges that cannot be resolved with an individual rationality.

It is observed that every rationality, if it becomes hegemonic, like Individualist Maximising immediately prior to the Global Financial Crisis of 2007-8, will generate an environment with an abundance of black swans that cause particular surprise to that thinking style, which cause less surprise (and are not easily repaired) from the perspective of different styles of thought. People who hold such other positions may say 'I have already warned you of this and you never listened', or analogous comments in relation to specific solutions that were ignored in the past, such as: 'government bail-outs', 'changing regulation, 'going into administration' and 'fire-sales'.

2.21 Research Gap and Approaches to Fill the Research Gap

From a theoretical perspective, support is provided for this aim by suggesting that the synthesis of Grid-Group Cultural Theory with what Taleb chooses to name his 'anti-theory' of Black Swan Events can be beneficial. The black swan argument is advantageous in that it increases cognisance of unpredictability and the significance of surprise events. It is important

to note that all four of the ‘thought styles’ discovered by Michael Thompson (described below) should be considered as each of them is specifically sensitive to *four* distinct types of surprises. As will be demonstrated, although the different thought styles of ‘Hierarchical’, ‘Egalitarian’, ‘Individualistic’ and ‘Fatalistic’, are equally reasonable, they all reason and act in different ways. G-GGCT reveals the significance and the roles that various rationalities play in social systems, like economies. It provides a universalistic four-way typology of risk and reactions to risk, rather than the universalistic two-way typology of Taleb (grounded on what Taleb describes as the ‘Platonic’ versus ‘Stoic’ world views). It is impressed that if black swan theory is to be expanded across the world, it is important to consider the dimension and potentials determined by Thompson, particularly with regard to the fact that four distinct ‘risk seasons’ exist as well as the four (as opposed to two) ways in which they can be successfully survived. As will be observed, Thompson simply but powerfully explains the rationale behind the actions of different actors in addition to why they change course. The overlap to which will make reference is between what Taleb defines as ‘Anti-fragile’ strategy and Thompson’s notion of the ‘Fatalistic Thought Style’, both of which are largely averse to risk. There is an additional overlap between what Taleb perceives to be a typical underestimation of risk by banking and financial professionals and what Thompson considers to be the ‘Hierarchical’ and ‘Individualistic’ styles of thought, which also perceive the world as being comparatively benign and characterised by order.

Prior to commencing with the delineation of this possible synthesis, it is necessary to describe an unsuccessful business orthodoxy and Taleb’s assessment of it. The sections quoted above are not the only revised parts which meet the requirements for clarification of Methodology, Research Questions and Gaps which have kept in mind while editing. For example:

Section “1.7 Research Questions, a ‘Research Gap’ and the possibility of a Theoretical Synthesis” was also added specifically to meet your first requirement for Revisions. While the author is the first to connect Taleb and Thompson, thus filling a ‘research gap’ which have spotted, it is fundamental to our thesis that no practically attainable amount of gap-filling (ie. Research and practitioner knowledge) would ever be enough to eliminate the black swans which chaos brings.

2.22 Conclusion

Black swan events are aspects of all social (cultural) systems around the world that cannot be avoided, which is particularly the case in the Middle East region where there is significant unpredictability as a result of the chaos that exists in the economic and political environments. Our observation based on Grid Group Cultural Theory is that all cultural systems are inherently unstable as it is inevitable that cultures will generate opposing thoughts. This finding supports the assertion of Taleb that surprises are unavoidable; however, Thompson claims that they do not necessarily originate from coincidences, ‘wild-’and ‘super-wild distributions’, but from comprehensible mutual frictions among styles of thought that have the same level of rationality but conflict with each other.

Taleb’s contention still stands that as a result of black swans, forecasting is not possible other than by fortunate coincidence; in the context of Thompson’s theory, it is a fortunate coincidence that Pragmatists could be responsible for managing an organisation at the time when a bull market terminates and it is also coincidental that the risk conditions abruptly become significantly more advantageous when Maximisers seize the opportunity to exploit the situation. This is because it is not possible to know what direction the risk environment will take going forward; actors will be lucky or unlucky according to the given style of thought they have adopted at that time. This is analogous to the aforementioned cases involving the ‘ill wind’ and the ‘Chinese farmer’. Although Thompson would concur that forecasting the

direction in which the cultural shift will occur is not possible, he is certain about the forces that will drive this shift.

It is believed that both Thompson and Taleb understand that the aspiration to consider all external and environmental factors that could be influential on the process is not realistic. However, strategic planners continue to have aspirations, particularly those whose mind-set is more hierarchical, to achieve greater 'comprehensiveness' with the aim of achieving more advantageous futures (Myer and Kitsuse, 2000). Put differently, it is observed that the 'strong' scenario-development and strategic planning variants are propelled by Hierarchical-Managerial reasoning.

Because it is not possible to know the amount and kinds of drivers (even subsequent to the event), as the 'strength' of the scenario planning variant adopted increases, risk is increasingly underestimated. The adoption of an anti-fragile strategy would increase the robustness of firms in chaotic environments and allow them to take advantage of the unpredictable. Although it is unavoidable that the soft variant of strategic planning will incorporate an 'environmental assessment', an ontological comprehension of the world's characteristics and that the future cannot be predicted should determine the 'dynamic capabilities' of organisations, primarily the extent to which they are anti-fragile (Walker et al., 2010). Such an argument is particularly relevant in the case where there is harmony between the 'risk environment' and how actors understand it. It also conforms with our experience that entrepreneurs in Iran who adopt a Maximising approach are clearly more successful based on their own terms (profitability, growth) compared with our own situation, but only in the short term, until such time that the risk environment as well as their own courage (increased appetite for risk) conspire against them.

One of the challenges revolves around the ability to recognise an 'environmental factor' and understand its possible effects, allowing them to be accommodated within management

processes (Kerkovsky and Vykytel, 2006). If the factor is particularly evident, it becomes less beneficial as it can also be observed by different organisations. It is agreed with Davidson (2014), who considered scenario planning to involve “producing a number of divergent plausible future scenarios from which to then consider the implication for present-day policy making”, and identifying the assumed obstacle and opportunities associated with every scenario and conducting this as a core process (i.e., dynamic capability). In line with our ‘soft’ proposition, various instruments have been used in order to try and evaluate the difficulties that may confront organisations due to black swan events (Lyons & Davidson, 2016). In other words, it is suggested that “strategy as preparation for the future by thinking about the future... and imagining the future” but not to “know the future” (Papula and Papulaova, 2012).

Describing strategic management as the formulation of a plan that will enable an organisation to accomplish its targeted goals as a result of internal and external analysis according to the economic, governmental and political conditions of the area in which the organisation operates (Tej, 2011; Wright and Nemeč, 2003) generates an excessive number of things that cannot be known at the same time. Back-casting may be beneficial for enhancing the awareness of numerous (but not all) mistakes that could be made when moving from one step to another. In other words, methods that cause the amount of ambiguities and awareness of them to be increased and not reduced are favoured. Again, and from the perspective of a Pragmatist, it is advisable to have less confidence in knowledge of the future. This is required when adopting an anti-fragile approach (Taleb, 2009). On the other hand, having increased confidence that positive black swans will occur and that the environment should be continually monitored for them is also logical for entrepreneurs in Iran who reason at that time only as Maximisers. Our desire to demonstrate the advantages of anti-fragility to all types of organisations in Iran is the intuition of a Conservator (Egalitarian). Furthermore, my robust resistance and good understanding of scenario-development and planning variants

amalgamates these three rationalities against the Hierarchical-Managerial reasoning preferred by such planners.

According to Walker, uncertainty can be divided into four distinct levels:

level 1) A Clear Enough future

level 2) An Alternative future

level 3) A Multiplicity of Plausible future

level 4) An Unknown Future, known as 'deep uncertainty'

It is referred to Walker due to the fact that even though it is possible to empirically establish and differentiate distinct risk 'levels', the distinctions he proposes are less beneficial than they may seem and could even be misleading. It may be tempting, and even risky, to believe that according to common-sense deductive terms, it should be possible to manage levels 1 and 2 in the conventional sense, whereas there would difficulties associated with levels 3 and 4 due to the lack of sufficient information. *Nonetheless*, if Taleb's thesis is applied to Walker, it cautions us that that level 4 can easily be mistaken for level 1; in other words, familiarity makes one complacent. That is, Hume's Induction Problem is always applicable apart from to the most basic and unenlightening statements:

"You never get something for nothing and never empirical hypotheses from empty deductive definitions. At best your observation can tell you only that the real world (or some subset of it) is not exploding; your theoretical model or system will always be an idealized representation of the real world with many variables ignored; it may be precisely the ignored variables that keep the real-world stable, and it takes a significant act of inductive inference to rule this out and permit the Correspondence Principle to deduce properties of the idealized model..."

(Paul A. Samuelson (1955: 312), cited Boland (1989, 119), emphasis added).

The analysis of Taleb theory leads to the conclusion with which can be concurred that efforts should be focused on deducing and avoid future ambiguities, or at least not attempting to infer them, but on maintaining anti-fragility as a continual mentality. Bracker (1980) contended that strategic management is a *process* aimed at enhancing the way in which an organisation uses its resources (which would situate it in the firm's 'resourced based view', which would assist with addressing changes in the future). Although it is concurred that strategy should take the form of a process, the discussion presented above facilitates the inference that when approaching 'anti-fragile' processes, the ambitions should be as minimally comprehensive as possible. Based on the main research question of this thesis: "Do entrepreneurs and strategic managers in Iran act in a manner recommended by Taleb and thus survive? The chaotic environment in which they operate that, even within Iran, does not cause the world to clearly "explode", engages them, and ourselves, in efforts to conduct inductive inference, to be justified as being informative. Furthermore, as a theoretical contribution supportive of this aim, it is proposed that the synthesis of Grid-Group Cultural Theory with what Taleb chose to define as his 'anti-theory' of Black Swan events can be beneficial. The advantage of the black swan theory is that during each stage, it increases the cognisance of ambiguity as well as the significance of unexpected events. That is, in an environment in which there is no clear regularity, it is not logical to deal with situations by thinking that they had reached 'level 4'.

It is important to note that all four of the styles of thought described by Michael Thompson should be taken into account as each of them is confronted by surprises, but interprets them in and reacts in a different way (occasionally with no response). Grid Group Cultural Theory informs us about the significance and contribution of distinct rationalities in a

given system. Our feeling that is for the scope of black swan theory to be expanded globally, it is necessary to consider the dimensions and opportunities determined by Thompson, and particularly recognise that four distinct ‘risk seasons’ exist as well as the different strategies that can be used to adopt them with varying degrees of success.

From the perspective of the Hierarchical Manager, the problem is caused by deviance and enhancements made to the rule book (regulations) will allow any future situations generated by deviance to be avoided and punished. This style of thought generates ‘procedural justice’... its *black-swan reducing process* would be intended to punish the deviants who suddenly created the problem. The obvious challenge with this type of process is that it is not possible to discipline the effects of the majority of negative black swans in this manner. For instance, punishing incautious financiers after the crisis of 2008 would have no impact on the consequences of the crisis after it had occurred. Although it could be somewhat influential by preventing ‘deviant’ black swans from happening in the future, it can be questioned whether positive black swans are promoted by enhanced rule books. On the other hand, Managers whose appetite for risk is at a moderate level presume that the world is generally relatively benign, where the primary threat is from a deviant minority; in the context of Walker, level 1 risk is recognised. However, if the Risk Season has been interpreted, then this position is not recommended as it would not conform with ‘surprises. If Thompson is right, then this should cause the actor’s cosmology/paradigm (the way in which they perceive the world) to change.

The Egalitarian ‘Conservator’ believes that everything has a high level of risk and that it is necessary to transform the entire system to allow all participants to benefit. They imagine ‘Alternative Futures’ and endeavour to collaborate with others to facilitate change. The strategy of the ‘Manager’ irks the Conservator as a result of its faith in Regulation.

The Individualistic ‘Maximiser’ considers the risk conditions to be benign and moves

in the most daring direction, behaving in different ways perceived by both the 'Conservator' and 'Manager' to be self-centred. The Maximiser will only be able to make significant gains if the risk conditions are advantageous.

The Fatalistic Pragmatist considers risk to be exceptionally high and accordingly acts cautiously and carefully. It is argued that in a highly chaotic environment, this strategy is optimal, although the Conservator in particular would perceive this approach to be self-centred and negative. In risk environments with increased hostility, such a strategy will be highly effective according to its own terms. The important factor is being able to survive, rather than being inventive, preventing deviance or improving the nature of the world.

3 Chapter 3

Research Methodology

3.1 Introduction

The argument that Fatalist-Pragmatic entrepreneurs who have survived exhibit different thinking and behaviour to high-ranking salaried managers who are Hierarchical-Managers necessitates the usage of the comparative approach. In this context, it is intended to compare managers and entrepreneurs who are peers within the same state. Consequently, this research has a ‘cross-sectional’ design in that the comparison is conducted a specific point in time. Nevertheless, it is also recommended that a time dimension is required to reflect on the previous experiences of adults’ lives, which includes those of the author himself, which are often defined as ‘critical incidents’ or ‘critical incidence analysis’ (Norman and Redferm, 2008). It is surmised that certain elements of my personal experiences will be particularly reflected in those of other entrepreneurs who have survived, while risks will be evaluated in different ways by salaried top management. While there is minimal focus on the other two possible attitudes towards risk, namely the Individualist-Maximiser and Egalitarian-Conservator, in this study, observations regarding the former have previously been provided. Such entrepreneurs are shooting stars who achieve rapid growth and maximum profitability, albeit only in the short term. Other researchers are invited to investigate these styles of thought that are not included here.

Although Taleb is definitive in terms of how he describes anti-fragility and black swans, due to the fact that he is a statistical expert as opposed to a social scientist, his work tends not to explain how the perspectives of actors are changed regarding their chaotic environments and therefore begin to behave in different ways. He offers the powerful argument that actors should attempt to adopt an anti-fragile strategy as well as why multiple or the majority experience challenges with doing this (as a result of their ‘cultural biases’), although no explanation is provided why some have already achieved this (which is our assumption). He generally treats

social analysis dismissively, perceiving that it largely belongs to what he calls the ‘Platonic fold’ and shows ‘epistemic arrogance’.

Our expectation is that the actions and thoughts of entrepreneurs in Iran will offer a clearer picture of the practical rather than theoretical application of an anti-fragility strategy. Consequently, our research not only follows Taleb, but aims to clarify his (anti-) theory through an investigation of entrepreneurs in Iran. A beneficial feedback loop should exist between the approach of Taleb that has been adopted in this study and the expressions of entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived. It is also possible to make a comparison between the statements of such entrepreneurs and examples of failure that the author is knowledgeable about, particularly with regard to the cases of firms who have aimed to ‘maximise profit’ through significant growth, which have completely collapsed within four years.

In this chapter, various methodological approaches will be explored. It will start by attempting to describe and differentiate between research philosophies. Due to the fact that methodologies are considered cultural phenomena, Hierarchical, Egalitarian, Individual and Fatalistic preferences will exist. In this research, approximately half of the sample has a certain degree of alignment with the Individualistic and Pragmatic styles of thought. It is argued by Methodological Pragmatists that decisions related to methodology must be ‘the slave of the research question’. The research design and selection of technique, respectively comparative and face-to-face interviews in this case, are informed by the research question; the research question is grounded on theory, which must justify its worth by producing practical implications.

The selection of qualitative interviews aimed at exploring and contrasting the tacit and explicit knowledge of entrepreneurs and strategic managers of firms within Iran is directly informed by my pressing need to survive when confronted by future scenarios that cannot be accurately predicted and that produce black swans (unforeseen events that have significant

positive and negative ramifications). The interview timing (which required flexibility according to the abovementioned information due to the fact that interviewees needed to feel completely free to explain their specific and diverse experiences), were intended to determine how, what, and if the participants (entrepreneurs or senior managers of petrochemical firms) have been able to learn from such unexpected occurrences. Secondary data obtained from the literature will be obtained for the purpose of addressing the research questions and objectives where feasible. Data will have gathered from 15 refinery and petrochemical forms in addition to 15 Iranian entrepreneurs who have survived and operate independently, which will subsequently be utilised to form a wider perspective of the issues confronting Iranian firms and whether the development of an industrial strategy that is guided by the driving principle of anti-fragility is possible

With years of experience of entrepreneurial activity within Iran in addition to working in supply chain and distributor of raw material and machinery as his primary business domains, the author has experience of and observed a significant number of events and established a broad network of contacts within these sectors. Again, the reason that that the author has selected his business associates to form the sample is due to practicality. Entrepreneurs who have achieved success and prominent managers have been selected. Given the limited number of petrochemical firms operating within Iran, it is likely that 15 top managers of such firms is the maximum number that could be interviewed. Nevertheless, the sample of ‘managers’ was made in such a manner that it had sufficient diversity to reveal their different experiences and characters. As will be observed, even though their styles of thought had similarities, the views of some were conflicting.

The argument could be made that the answers given by the entrepreneurs have increased trustworthiness and reliability compared to the senior managers of the petrochemical firms owned by the state as political matters have less relevance to them.

It is likely beneficial that none of interviewees have any knowledge of NN Taleb and his black swan theory. It is important that the interviews are conducted in a natural manner, thus allowing the ordinary (via contrasting) ‘common-sense’ to be captured, which anticipated would be conveyed in the different sample groups. Nevertheless, according to the experience of the author, it was strongly suspected (hypothesised) that the majority of entrepreneurs in Iran have obtained implicit tacit knowledge pertaining to black swans, as various unexpected situations would have emerged from the chaotic risk conditions in which they operate (which represents our independent variables), where such tacit knowledge has been a key factor in their ability to survive (the dependent variable).

In this study, it is criticised what Smith (2010; 2011) refers to as the ‘standard account of the method (SAM)’, which explains research into strategy and management as a decision between: "two traditions": "qualitative "phenomenological" interpretivism" and "quantitative ‘scientific’ positivism". Such traditions are generally described as being opposing sides in a ‘paradigm war’; however, it is perplexing that it is frequently claimed that such ‘opposites’ could be ‘mixed’. It is difficult to perceive how two sides engaged in a paradigm war would desire to utilise the techniques of researchers that they consider to be opponents. In this regard, the conventional ‘two traditions’ account seems to be questionable, and potentially ‘enclaved’.

However, one can easily observe aggressive statements being made between the two sides. Nonetheless, my above-mentioned hypothesis can be considered *positivist* in the obvious and significant sense that it is possible to *test* and reject whether it is supported or directly falsified by the evidence. On numerous occasions, Karl Popper demanded testability as the primary aspect of any theory that was purported to be ‘scientific’ (He disregarded theories that cannot be tested as ‘metaphysics’, categorising Marx, Plato, and Hegel as such). It can therefore be stressed that there is a positivistic epistemology.

Epistemology and technique (quantitative or qualitative) are completely different dimensions. The main research technique used for this research qualitative interview with the extended interview. Based on our extensive knowledge of the different sample groups, the use of quantitative structured questionnaires to conduct the research was quickly dismissed due to three factors:

- The lack of trust among Iranians is justified and is unlikely that they would provide sufficiently transparent information regarding their experiences if they were required to complete large blank text boxes without being clearly assured of the complete confidentiality of their responses
- Documenting experiences in writing can be a lengthy process and respondents cannot be expected to make the effort to write in sufficient detail, particularly if the researcher is not present. If the researcher was in front of the respondents, then it would be possible to record their responses verbatim, with cues to elaborate on the specifics regarding their 'black swans' and how they reacted to them.
- Even when a large amount of space is provided for free text, it is necessary for questionnaires to be identical or similar for each respondent from the same sample group. This necessity is in conflict with the investigation of black swans that will be dissimilar for every respondent filling in the survey. For example, the way in which respondents experience the same black swan could be different, thus eliciting reactions that are not the same. It is therefore hard to imagine how a structured questionnaire could offer sufficient flexibility to accommodate these highly specific differences.

In other words, due to practical considerations, I will be:

1) utilising elements treated by the usual account as 'opposed' and seemingly lacking compatibility due to the fact they are situated on opposing sides of a 'paradigm war'. It is hard

to perceive why qualitative testing should not be conducted on a hypothesis, as can be observed in court cases or parliamentary inquiries. For example, a prosecutor could hypothesise the guilt of someone accused of a crime based on what is virtually completely qualitative evidence. As emphasised by Smith, the jurors are required to decide whether the guilt of the accused can be established 'beyond reasonable doubt'; in this case, there might be a doubt that they are innocent equates to the 'null hypothesis' that the dependent variable (i.e., the victim's death) and the independent variable (the person accused of the murder and his/her reasons) are not related. Hypotheses that can be tested are present in daily life and unexpected events, such as unexpected black swans, represent observable 'counter-factual evidence' that tend to disprove these hypotheses, such as a few keys in my possession will work on my front door. Although they work virtually all of the time, one cannot completely disregard the possibility that the keys in my possession could in fact those that belong to somebody else that I erroneously picked up. My positivist hypothesis that can be tested that the keys in my possession (the independent variable) could possibly be refused by the qualitative sign suggesting that the keys will not work. Applying a large sample survey method does not necessary possible to understand that an error has occurred.

It is difficult to perceive posing a testable hypothesis should 'enslave' either author or participants opposed to being instructive and liberating. Smith proposes a Combining "epistemological" and "technical," among other category errors, is part of the "go-anywhere representation of inquiry-space" in addition to other dimensions into one basic binary opposition. Rather, he considers technical, epistemological and different dimensions to be 'orthogonal' (not related) and 'articulates' three given dimensions as what he defines as '3-D spaces' (see figure below). He contends that making inquiries, normal people articulate at least 20 dimensions (thousands of combinations can formed from a maximum of 27 dimensions based on the practical needs of the person conducting the inquiry). Even young people have a

natural talent in this area despite not being formally trained in the techniques and philosophy of method. 'Our argument is that technique establishes the formal/informal line and creates a place for conversation. It explains the topics worth discussing, the reasons it is differed, provides the required language, and generates new terms for liminal subject matter. There is always more to say, and thankfully, language is both concise and expansive. So, instead of starting with the conventional explanation of the approach, start with the students' earliest recollections of asking questions. ... The researcher's methodological decisions should be a slave to their study issue because there are many options available. (Smith, 2010).

And he adds, "This section provides an informative depiction of the freedom of inquiry." (Smith, 2010) defined by multiple dimensions as it is experienced. (He provides multiple examples of naïve inquiry in distinct methodological dimensions that were articulated in sophisticated manner by people lacking education for the purpose of furthering their comprehension of multiple types of phenomena). He absolutely rejects the traditional, monolithic polarisation of "anti-foundational" qualitative interpretivism. against 'establishment' 'quantitative positivism' due to the fact that it produces an excessive amount of irregularities that he clearly articulates via multiple examples, the most important of which in our view is the qualitative testing of hypotheses such as the aforementioned example of the "key that cannot open the lock".

2) there is a practical demand for voice-to-voice or face-to-face interviews, which can be considered both Talebian and 'anti-fragile' in their nature. Interviews are conducted by assuming that unexpected events will be reported by the interviewees but it is not possible for the researcher to claim that they will have knowledge of the nature of such events or what their reactions were in advance. Similar to the imagined 'TV. Detectives' referenced by Smith, it is important that I am adaptable when asking questions and that I listen extremely carefully and

acutely. Therefore, even though there will be certain commonalities among the interviews, it is essential that that side-paths are accommodated, particularly those that the author considers to be unexpected. As a result of the freedom that the respondents will be given, there will be an increased likelihood that their answers will have more accuracy and reliability, although it is acknowledged that it is not possible for any respondent to provide a completely thorough account of their experiences as well as the cause-effect relations in which they are involved. It is in accordance with our Talebian paradigm perspective that no person can definitively know what or why things have transpired in their lives as this would necessitate ‘root and branch’ inquiries that would never be possible given the amount of time and additional resources available. While the duration of some interviews could be only 30 minutes, others that last as much as 4 hours would still be unable to incorporate an indeterminably vast number of an in determinant variety of events.

Taking into account these criteria, constraints (and freedoms), the author will not continue by rationalise the approach adopted in this study. The chapter is categorised into seven parts:

3.2 Overview and Definition of Primary Research

When conducting this research, interviews were conducted by the author to gather evidence for the purpose of exploring how (and whether) they identify unexpected black swans and respond to them. Although research has a different nature according to the subject, the creation of literature in every field occurs over time. These literatures try to guide researchers and teach them a way to be able to obtain the data they require in their researches (Soomiai et al. 2011). For instance, engineers concentrate on knowledge susceptible to testing that has increased although not full reliability in their efforts aimed at designing and building. A design process exists, assisted by multiple instruments in their research and models, that can be either

mathematical are consist of scaled-down 3-dimensional depictions, which offer realistic simulations, as well as various non-destructive destructive tests and to determine the likelihood that a design will function effectively or poorly. Additionally, engineers develop an aesthetic feeling for the form that effective solutions should take, including ‘truth to materials’, ‘elegance’, ‘ingenuity’, ‘high reliability’ and occasionally the costly ‘appropriate engineering job’, that could be evaluated by other occupations in a negative light. Sociologists acquire the ability to conduct research by observing, monitoring, interviewing and conducting statistical analysis to further their comprehension of people, culture and societies (Johnston, 2014). Additional tools include participant- and non-participant observations, oral accounts and inconspicuous techniques in which only data that naturally occurs is collected like brief quotes from unplanned dialogue (Griffin, 2007). Furthermore, ‘secondary data’ (quantitative or qualitative) that has previously been collected by other entities can be used, including governmental departments, official records, memoirs and diaries, written media, photographic databases, among others. Numerous other methods can also be employed.

The key factor is that justifiable decisions should be made that are compatible with the research’s aims and objectives, which must be presented and defended by the researcher among his/her peers. An argument can be made for attempting to reproduce extant findings to determine the extent to which they can be trusted, although when breaking new ground, researchers are not constrained to things that have been previously employed in other domains. Possibly to an even greater extent than is the case for engineers, in practical terms, it is not possible for sociologists to make definitive conclusions on a subject, particularly as there is no agreement among sociologists in terms of sharing the same paradigm. However, in sociological research, papers are developed that are worth the effort to defend, and are also worthy of attack from competing positions. In fact, sociology can be regarded as a cultural endeavour.

More specifically, primary research, which is the main focus of this research, is aimed at gathering first-hand evidence rather than being dependent on extant resources (journals, books, etc.). John Stuart Mill is considered to be the pioneer of the theory of investigation, which he first proposed in his work *Philosophy of the Scientific Methods* written in the 19th century (Mill, 1989). Nevertheless, the same could be mentioned for Francis Bacon author of “*Novum Organum Scientiarum*” book in (1620) as well as a variety of different scholars throughout history.

The foundation of primary research is the idea that a method is accepted as scientific. (Soomai et al. 2011). According to different fields, it is reported that the usage of scientific strategy incorporates the establishment of research questions and theories, which allow information to be collected that can be quantified and is ‘objective’, utilising accepted techniques and methods. However, numerous disciplines, even within the natural sciences, start with *qualitative* data and describe this as Meteorology “Cloud shape”, Geology “rock formation and Physiology “parts of animals and related to biology”, total failures (civil engineering) disease symptoms as depicted by images and life drawings (medicine) as well as the spread of diseases utilising distribution maps (public health, epidemiology). A key component of conducting primary research is the ability to investigate a new area that can be proposed to and questioned by peers while following a line of inquiry, even people who believe that the focus of research should be on different topics.

To the best of the author’s knowledge, no previous study has applied the Talebian approach to modern Iran, which has been selected as it is a country that produces a large number of black swan events and is susceptible to black swans whose origins can be traced to other countries. It is situated in a region where the differentiation between inside and outside is largely difficult to apply. In this process, it is considered the degree to which scenario development (at least its softer variants) could be applicable to entrepreneurs and the broader industrial approaches of

promoting the establishment of a variety of new activities in the downstream sectors of the Iranian petrochemical industry, at least to the extent to which it is defensible.

Although our objective is not to be comprehensive, it is believed that collecting evidence from specialists in the field of petrochemicals and entrepreneurship is important, acknowledging the reality that practitioners are quasi-scientific themselves. They follow explicit and implicit lines of inquiry and establish communities. Furthermore, I have made use of (a sample of) my own experience of establishing my own network in the business world over the past years, which comprises an overall sample of likely hundreds of 'weak connections' (Granovetter, 1983). Out of the sample, interviews were conducted with 30 different people including 15 key actors within the petrochemical sector (top managers with high salary who can be called 'strategic managers' as well as CEOs) and 15 entrepreneurs in Iran.

Using two glaringly and purposefully dissimilar sample sub-groups, a population of 30 people, it should be possible to find any significant differences if they are present. In this context, the term 'significant' refers to distinctions whose significance can be minimised due to coincidence. Our perception is that in theory, it is also possible to assess whether qualitative data reveals distinctions that have or do not have significance. For instance, residents of Liverpool are differentiated from those from Newcastle (Geordies) by their 'scouse' accent with a level of confidence nearing $p= 0.000$. Thus, in a mixed sample drawn from the two groups, the independent variable is "residence" and the dependent variable is "accent."

Our objective is to identify, even if it is only in broad terms, whether learning can be gleaned from within the second sample (entrepreneurs) that could be of benefit to the first sample (managers). It can be questioned whether it is possible to transfer anti-fragility strategies between different fields of activity.

Given the time and resources available to the researcher, it would not be feasible to answer the issue of whether anti-fragility may be copied from one area to another in this thesis because such transfers may take decades to occur and be implemented in the field. In any case, this reflects at least the long-term policy goal, and author welcomes specialists in the "knowledge transfer" sector to further investigate this.

It should now be sufficiently evident that in interviews that adopt a Talebian approach, the participants will be asked two key questions, which will provide them the opportunity to freely report their experiences and describe their favoured strategies. According to the descriptions of the interviewees, they will be asked spontaneous questions, derived from the content of their responses, based on our Talebian perspective of black swans at every stage of the interview. After briefly introducing and summarising what black swans are, the questions described below will firstly be asked to the independent entrepreneurs followed by the top petrochemical managers and CEOs in separate interviews:

- a) As an entrepreneur in Iran, do your behaviours conform with the recommendations of Taleb??*
- b) Explain yourself as survival in chaotic environment?*
- c) How 'environmental factors' influence management for future approaches in Iran?*

Observe that the above-described questions have a broad scope and are intentionally designed to provide significant freedom for the participants to draw on different areas of their field as they deem appropriate. This leads to the following question:

- d) Based on the brief summary I have provided, to what extent do you feel that it is possible to develop long-term strategies that generate profits according to the necessity to react to unexpected events?*
- e) Can you provide a description of the way in which you view the world, or as social scientists might question, identify your 'paradigm'?*

It should be noted that although these are the primary questions, the way in which they are phrased will differ according to the interviewee, utilising their 'day language'. Additionally, various sub-questions are included as every interview progresses, which differ according to the responses of the individual interviewee. Certain cues and encouraging comments are required for interviewees who are tentative or reserved who may not have been confronted by such questions in the past, particularly in the context of scholarly research. Nevertheless, the researcher believes that such questions will have emerged implicitly for the majority or all participants and that they will have formed tacit answers to these questions on their own. This is due to the fact that it is not easy to live one's life without considering this to a certain degree, at least briefly.

3.3 Research Choice and Definition of Primary or Secondary Research

Hakim (1982) stated that secondary analysis can be described as additional analysis of datasets that already exist that allows additional interpretations, conclusions or knowledge to be drawn that add to, or differ from, those initially reported according to the preliminary findings of an investigation. The examination of secondary data was first proposed by Glaser, who started to re-analyse data that had originally been collected for other purposes (Johnston, 2014). Nevertheless, Johnson's assertion disregards the analysis of Parish Records dating back centuries (professions, births, marriages and deaths) as well as different types of inventories that have been researched by local historians for a much longer time. It is claimed that the examination of secondary data is an observational activity involving both procedural and evaluative stages that offers a degree of flexibility (Doolan and Froelicher, 2009). As open access publications and the datasets on which they are based are becoming more popular, researchers now have increased access to data that has previously been gathered anyway. The analysis of secondary data is perceived to be an acceptable research approach as it allows things to be viewed from a different perspective and extant work can be used and challenged in

different ways. Researchers can also benefit from types of access that have more structure (Andrews et al., 2012 and Smith et al., 2011), based on which open access has been made criteria by agencies providing funding for research.

Nevertheless, there are still challenges in achieving this (Andrews et al., 2012 and Smith, 2008). Certainly, the analysis of secondary data causes the researcher to move an additional step away from the original work and it could add further mistakes to those that have already been made by the original researcher (potentially unbeknownst to them) With regard to data sourced from interviews in particular, originally:

- The person being interviewed may have misinterpreted the question that the researcher intended to ask
- The response they provided was thus to a distinct question
- The response they provided will not have been complete, most probably in significant aspects (considering that it impossible to be comprehensive)
- The interview may have experienced memory lapses
- Which the interview may have been unaware of unless they had conducted interviews with multiple individuals in the same domain who provided consistent responses, which would reveal which of the interviewees had given abnormal or conflicting answers
- In the majority of instances, and definitely with regard to this thesis, it is considered intolerable and highly unethical to render 'raw' content from interviews freely accessible due to the sensitive nature of the subject.

Although I encourage others to examine, evaluate, discuss and criticise this thesis, it is grounded on evidence that is totally and stringently confidential.

Nevertheless, when conducting primary research like this thesis, it is possible to at least reduce such problems in the preliminary stage by posing a series of analogous questions in distinct ways (which may include overlapping questions during one interview) and then making

a comparison between the answers. With regard to the analysis of data pertaining to research conducted by different researchers, such as the quotes from interviewees presented below:

- It will not be able to access a large proportion of all the contextual evidence (e.g., the voice tone, delivery speed, observable confidence or lack of it of the person conducting the interview, as well as the configuration and orderliness of the room)
- The person conducting the secondary research will not be able to determine the accuracy with which the interview was transcribed
- The research question of the secondary research could be even more removed from the interviewee (or person being observed) than was the case at the initial stage, thus causing the connection between the aim, operationalization and conclusions of the research to be further stretched
- Due to the fact that social systems are continually evolving, the reinterpretation of what an interviewee may have said 10 or 20 years previously could be challenging
- It can be difficult to verify the secondary interpretation that is being conducted when confidentiality concerns mean that it is not possible to trace the interviewee (this should only be possible when they have provided written authorization for them identify to be released)

Secondary research can be justified in cases where:

- The person conducting the secondary research is not proficient in the language of those being interviewed in whom he/she has an interest
- Additional obstacles exist such as insufficient contacts in the sampling population, visa limitations and potentially the risk of being arrested for being suspected of dubious activities

- The secondary researcher has no knowledge of the functioning of local institutions, which means they are unsure as to where they should start or the manner in which the responses should be evaluated

Nevertheless, such constraints are not applicable to the author of this thesis who:

- Can speak the Persian language fluently as their mother tongue
- Can draw on a wide network of contacts, all of whom have direct knowledge of him, his business and family or are aware of his reputation
- Has vast experience in the pertinent institutions
- Is fully aware of the aims of his research and
- Is capable of assessing the extent to which interviewees can understand him based on the answers given during the interviews
- Has the ability to utilise follow up calls by phone or Skype for the purpose of clarifying vagueness

To emphasise, it is not possible to conduct secondary research in the absence of primary research, which applies to the current thesis. The topic presented here is new from the perspective of the research community. This represents the first attempt to explore the susceptibility to black swans and anti-fragility in the context of entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived as well as salaried top ‘strategic’ managers. In this respect, the analysis of secondary data in this research meant that Taleb was read and re-read a number of times, particularly his diagrams as well as a critical appraisal of both the ‘soft’ and ‘hard’ variants of the aspects of strategic planning and scenario development. It is observed that a large proportion of the former is normative... groups of recommendations and straight stages (often accompanied by feedback loops) that are intended to denote best practice, with no primary evidence that they are successful if implemented, as well as no primary evidence that a given model is more

effective than others in reality, which means that successes and failures are also not incorporated into the secondary analysis either. Although a certain level of theory could underpin the previously mentioned models, our observations determined that theory (with respect to explicit causal explanations) was frequently missing.

Although Taleb's sources can be re-read (specifically the tradition defined as *scepticism* as well as the statistical experts who expressed the highest level of scepticism regarding the utility of normal distributions), he does not offer a significant amount of in-depth primary research himself. His work incorporates multiple examples extracted from numerous sources as well several of his personal experiences. Thompson (2018) does present various 'appetites for risk' and has created computational models in collaboration with others that demonstrate their effectiveness when both dynamically interact with each other in addition to the risk conditions they generate. As previously mentioned, it is beneficial to observe that his model has never been able to reproduce the identical pattern subsequent to hundreds of iterations, affirming Taleb's main significant assertion that the accuracy of financial forecasts is limited or very limited.

3.4 Interview in Qualitative Approach

When conducting qualitative interviews (primary method employed in this thesis), the respondents are provided the opportunity to elaborate on their responses and document their capabilities, aims and viewpoints. Their responses are not limited by the meeting strategy. Such interviews are frequently utilised in an investigative manner to document the world of the interviewee from their own perspective, although in the context of this study, a hypothesis must also be tested. Researchers do not have the expectation that they will have prior knowledge of the items of interest that may be documented (Gubrium and Holstein, 2001), (Grenz, 2005). The person conducting the interview could explore aspects of the interviewee's experience, offering and verifying suggestions in an efficient way and verifying association

(Gubrium and Holstein, 2001). It offers benefits as a research approach that facilitates the exploration of themes, emotions and findings that interviewees could possess (Stopfrod, 2004).

In this thesis, our semi-structured survey is not completely open-ended as it has to be sufficiently flexible to accommodate evidence of black swans which should not be estimated in advance, even though the researcher has knowledge about how they should be defined. Interviews should be provided the freedom to elaborate on their (Talebian) shocks in an environment where they do not feel disparaged for not predicting them in advance. For this reason, the decision was made to present the “Talebian theory of Black Swans” in the course of the interviews, albeit only in summary form. This allowed the respondents to understand that unexpected events are commonplace.

Although it will not be possible for the interviewer to obtain exhaustive knowledge, the use of questionnaire with open-ended questions can provide the researcher with the opportunity to gain an understanding of what the interviewees have experienced individually and in their industry in general. The sample comprised a total of 30 senior salaried managers and entrepreneurs in Iran, and the primary questions that were posed were intended to give them the freedom to convey their opinions and explain the strategies they have adopted. According to the descriptions of the interviews, it was possible to ‘excavate’ further questions based on what they said and when it was said in the interview. The approach adopted for the interviews differs from the primary steps of the standard questionnaire design process illustrated below; as a result of the vulnerability of interviews to black swans, the expectation is that they will appear as the interview progresses:

Figure 21 Questionnaire Development Main Step Main Step

In the context of our interviews, it was anticipated that new questions would be developed in each case.

The researcher specifically focused on ensuring that the flow of the respondents was not disturbed or that they were embarrassed so that they remained open. Furthermore, it is endeavoured not to ask questions that could have led them to reveal confidential data regarding their firm or private information, unnecessarily. Despite using different phrasing, the questions shown below were connected with my framework:

- Is the behaviour of entrepreneurs in Iran in line with the recommendations of Taleb? And does this explain the manner in which and why they have survived? This is not a closed question with only two possible answers because Egalitarian and Individualistic as well as Pragmatic and Hierarchical risk attitudes are accommodated
- What influence might black swans have on the way in which the different petrochemical sectors in Iran are managed and how can their negative influence be diminished? A maximum of four different sensible answers could be provided to this question.
- What is the likelihood that long-term and profitable strategies can be developed according to the anti-fragile principles of Taleb? In a significant sense, as well as other answers, this question accommodated Egalitarian/Enclave or 'Conservator' answers in terms of the ability of Iran to survive when faced with threats to the country's existence
- How does every interviewee experience their world in the broadest sense? That is, what is their paradigm?

3.5 Approaches to the Research Philosophy

In summary, the practical approach selected for this research is aimed at making comparisons among two groups of qualitative discussions with a specific focus on the respondents' tacit knowledge who would have had no prior exposure to the work of Taleb.

Smith assertively notes that:

“Business and management research is described as a choice between "two traditions" in The Standard Account of Method (SAM): "qualitative "phenomenological" interpretivism" and "quantitative 'scientific' positivism," each of which is the adversary of the other. Students compile the "benefits and drawbacks" of each and declare their support for the "mixed technique" (wishing for a "truce" in the "paradigm war"). These variants often receive grade weightings of 20% in our increasingly Fordist academies, which are determined by "marking methods" that are likewise standardised. Fordism is a management philosophy that emphasises uniformity, deskilling, low unit costs, straightforward assembly, and centralised control. It is contended that SAM "Fordises" the mind and contradicts our observation that inquiry involves the greatest degree of customisation humanly conceivable. SAM, in contrast to Ford's River Rouge facility, is also riddled with flaws, including thousands of category errors brought on by combining unrelated methodological characteristics into a single, seemingly straightforward but sometimes erroneous dichotomy. Untutored inquirers may communicate a wide range of methodological differences with greater ease, plurality, and accuracy than SAM thanks to the benefits of natural language. Naive inquirers might realise and enjoy what they did not know that they knew by giving their simple impulses greater labelling. (Smith, 2010).

This stance accommodates the type of ‘bespoke’ that is suitable for studying managers and entrepreneurs who have experience of black swans as well as the extent to which they are suitably prepared or harmed by such surprises.

3.5.1 The Expansive Alternative

The shape of a "go anywhere" inquiry space is illustrated by Dr. Stephen Smith. This "avoids the categorization errors that the SAM causes by combining a variety of distinct research aspects into one qualitative-interpretivist vs quantitative-positivist component,"

Figure 22 Inquiry Space; Cosmos

He proceeds:

“Natural language abounds with spatial metaphors and methodology can be pictured as a proliferation of 3-D cosmos. Think of Cosmos 1 as the "room" shown in Figure 1, but without walls. Dimension x (running left-to-right) is still our epistemological continuum from empiricism, (trusted sense-experience after Berkeley), to realism (trusted in intellect after Plato, Hegel, and Marx). Let positivism mark halfway (theories trusted insofar as they survive the test of experience, after Bacon and Popper).

Y (top-bottom) represents that technical continuum between quantitative and qualitative data, with maps and graphs on the “half-way point”, recording both quantities (distances, heights, contour-lines) and qualities (like the “Boot of Italy”). Children distinguish quantities (“twice as many peas”) from qualities (“pea-green”, “not tasting like beans”).”

Dimensions from front to back is 'ontological', which runs among routinely thoughtless actions and those that are performed deliberately and intentionally. While 'behaviours' are recorded by certain researchers, others favour the exploration of the interviewees' 'meanings', as well as the way in which they perceive and experience the world. Similar to the x and y dimensions, academics have the freedom to select a point on the z dimension that they feel best corresponds to their research question. Put differently, it is possible for researchers to situate their research at any point in this 3-dimensional space, which are defined in this case as 'star-plots'.

With respect to this thesis, it is Qualitative (bottom of the vertical axis) Positivistic (middle of the horizontal axis) and focused on 'meaningful action' as opposed to 'behaviour' (e.g., the closest point of the z axis).

3.6 Discussion

Nigel Laurie stated (quoted in Smith, 2010), 'it often conceived of expertise as requiring the ability to analyse one's performance in order to improve it. When describing someone with unconscious expertise, it could use the term "naturally talented." Additionally, he asked questions on in what way methodological expansion can be achieved and if young people have sufficient methodological consciousness for this to happen. A referee offered a defence of the inclination of interpretivism to find fault with science:

Contrary to the claim that the "discursive is the boundary of the meaningful," it is proposed that methodology is the boundary to the discursive, creating space for discussion. It explains what is worth talking about, why it is disagreed, provides the necessary words, and generates new words for liminal subject matter. There is always more to say, and thankfully, language is both precise and voluminous. English, which is the primary language of empiricism and

pragmatism, is the language of Continental Philosophy and German and French realism. All approaches are probably available in all languages, including play and student's untaught brilliance for consider starting with the students' first recollections of conducting questions rather than the traditional presentation of the procedure. When you recognise each other, you'll grin. (Smith, 2010).

Our interpretation of this can be summarised as follows:

7. The traditional description of technique ('qualitative interpretivism against quantitative positivism') is a rather one-dimensional portrayal of approach. There is significant freedom for methodological choice
8. The space that is comprised of multiple dimensions is conducive to all inquirers who desire to make practical methodological decisions such that the methods and techniques used become a 'slave to their research problems.

There are upwards of 27 dimensions to [even] basic inquiry, any three of which define a 3-D space (with axis x, y, and z), according to Smith's estimation. This allows for 2,925 discrete 3-D permutations, or $27! / [(27-3)! * 3!]$ Eight cells make up each permutation, thus instead of "two traditions," there are 23,400 distinct and individual "spaces" in which inquiries might be formed ($2,925 \times 8$). There are essentially endless alternatives for methodology. These "two traditions," like many others, are just myths from the recent past. (Smith, 2010: 96-7. See also Sheldon (2003) and Smith (2011). In other words, the researcher has more possibilities than only choose between the two alternatives of qualitative interpretivism and quantitative positivism, or a partial synthesis of these two diametrically opposed techniques. The common explanation of technique is false, and not just superficially.

Potentially our most practical concern is how entrepreneurs in Iran have survived, which includes the comprehension of my own ability to survive. Furthermore, it is also practical to

question what learning can be gleaned from entrepreneurs in Iran and their behaviours for the Iranian petrochemical sector in general, particularly their thinking, their actions and their ability to survive when confronted by surprises and black swan events.

The overall object of this study is to further the understanding of the petrochemical sector in Iran in addition to various entrepreneurs to give an indication as to what anti-fragile approaches would incorporate. Conducting 15 interviews with senior managers in the petrochemical sector and making comparisons with 15 interviews conducted with Iranian entrepreneurs allows this question to be investigated using the researcher's available resources and language proficiency. If it is found that the 15 entrepreneurs are employing what Taleb would acknowledge to be anti-fragile approaches, and if the top petrochemical managers and CEOs behave in way that suggests that there is a reduced likelihood of black swan events even though this is not correct, this would be a beneficial start. The qualitative technique employed was selected to enable interviewees to respond in a natural manner when providing descriptions of experiences that could vary significantly and cannot be known in advance apart from in a highly hypothetical manner prior to commencing each interview, which explains why multiple improvised questions were included.

Nevertheless, our expectation is that the different samples will differ significantly despite the qualitative nature of the evidence. This process can be approached by considering the way in which it differentiates the flavours of food in restaurants that belong to different restaurant chains, or the quality of service in different hotel chains. Provided the answers in every sample exhibit significantly more commonalities than distinctions and a distinct and different similarity pattern is shown in the other sample, then one should be able to determine that there are differences between the two groups that cannot be rationalised by coincidence, even when the sizes of the samples are small.

Secondary data extracted from sources in the literature will be utilised for the purpose of addressing the research questions and objectives where feasible. Data gathered from 15 petrochemical and refinery firms as well as 15 independent entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived and operate independently will subsequently be employed to gain a broader understanding of the risk conditions and the associated problems that confront Iranian firms as well as the possibility of developing an industrial strategy that is fundamentally guided by the principle of anti-fragility.

3.7 Ethical Considerations

The literature provides an effective description of ethical matters and principles, which have been beneficially grouped into four key categories, which can emerge in distinct environments. According to Bryman and Bell (2011), these categories can be described as:

1. Harm to participant
2. Invasion of privacy
3. Lack of informed consent
4. Deception (Diener and Crandall, 1978).

Observe that such concerns are associated with the Hierarchical style of thought (concern regarding deviance). Due to the cultural nature of the phenomenon, research ethics could additionally incorporate ‘benefit to the public’, which is an Individualistic criterion for innovativeness and enhancement on previous research as well as possibly a Fatalistic criterion that the researcher should not be harmed. Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2012) emphasised the critical significance of maintaining the confidentiality of information, and that the researcher provides an explanation of what they intend to achieve using suitable terminology such that interviewees are aware of what they are consenting to or making the decision not to participate in. Ethical matters are critical and virtually unavoidable for all types of researchers.

In the majority of cases, which includes this thesis, the significance of the research objectives does not mean that harming the respondents can be justified. Although exceptions to this rule may exist, such as cases where respondents may have committed serious and violent crimes that pose a risk to the wellbeing of society and the researcher is trying to reveal, this certainly did not apply to our study. It is accepted and adhered to the principle that researchers must determine whether respondents could be harmed and ensure that this is prevented during the process of pursuing the research objectives and for an indefinite period once the research is complete. Apart from in uncommon instances in which a respondent consent to their identity being published (e.g., when biographies are written about leading political dignitaries or cultural personalities in the research), participants must be afforded the absolute right to confidentiality. This is similarly applicable to both quantitative and qualitative research, although the process of concealing the identities of participants in larger surveys is easier than a survey involving only 30 businesspersons from Iran. In this instance, the researcher must be more attentive, ensuring that all names are changed (including those of the firms) and potentially making changes to job titles and specific places that have no significance to the research. The researcher should not give sufficient details that would allow readers to identify the respondents without specifically naming them.

Qualitative research is aimed at investigating, describing and examining the respondents and their experiences; however, in this research, as previously emphasised, it is also aimed to 'test' the samples to identify random differences. Thus, to ensure that effective relationships are maintained between the researcher and the participants, it is critical that they have mutual trust in each other and can clearly communicate. When intensively analysing the contribution of each participant, it is essential that this trusting relationship is not compromised (Orb et al., 2000). When conducting qualitative studies, all participants have intimate involvement as this could be the first occasion that they have revealed such personal opinions.

If the researcher is not completely attentive to their ethical requirements, this can lead to both their own reputation and that of their respondents being unacceptably harmed.

When conducting this research, the author follows three fundamental ethical principles:

1. Hierarchical and Egalitarian which are considered as Beneficence
2. Individual which can considered as Autonomy and Inventiveness
3. Hierarchical which is categorised as Justice

Our intention is not to do any damage in either the short or long term, and even to provide certain benefits in the long term. It is acknowledged that prospective participants have the right to decline participation or withdraw at any point in the process. It is acknowledged that any breaches of confidentiality represent a severe injustice, and are a violation of the code documented in the information sheets given to them as authorised by University of the West of Scotland. The principle of autonomy is characterised by the right of participants to receive suitable information about the research topic such that they can give informed consent and withdraw without being penalised. (Orb et al., 2000: 95). In fact, information about the study aims was provided to all respondents in the Persian language, giving us confidence that they provided informed consent. They were informed that they were not obliged to answer questions that made them uncomfortable and that they could depart from the interview at any time with no explanation required. An explanation was also provided regarding the usage and publication of the data, as well as that the researcher solemnly guaranteed that their anonymity would be guaranteed.

3.8 Limitation

When conducting some of the interviews, it is observed that certain petrochemical managers were hesitant to convey their emotions, thoughts and plans as they harbour the reasonable desire to avoid preventable risks, such as the potential for their position to be lost if they were overly frank. In their senior positions, they are required to be mindful of political

limitations as well as the necessity to sustain good relationships with those in authority. After all, they are agents of a variety of different national plans and have a specific and official duty to ensure these plans are implemented. That is, they are confronted by further risks and limitations that do not constrain independent owner-managing entrepreneurs.

Nevertheless, readers may observe that their reasonable aspiration for survival and the extent to which they are sensitive to risk do not differ significantly from the desire of surviving Iranian entrepreneurs to survive. Put differently, although the two interview samples differ significantly, they have the same reasonable level of sensitivity to risk that Thompson would perceive to be Fatalistic and Taleb would likely endorse.

In risk seasons with multiple threats, being cautious is a rational strategy. However, quickly seizing the positive black swans that will arise is also a rational approach. It is also argued that no opportunities should be perceived as being 'golden' in the manner that Individualistic 'profit-maximisers' generally perceive it. Seeking to exploit an opportunity to its fullest will ultimately end in failure when another change occurs in the 'risk season'.

Based on the article Thompson wrote in 2018, it is observed that new risk seasons will ultimately emerge in Iran, while his cultural insights into "*How Banks and Other Financial Institutions Think*" is likely the second most significant text that the author has encountered (behind the work of Taleb). Grid-Group Cultural Theory allows us to see that Taleb should take into account a broader variety of possibilities. He could still admit that actors are not irrational animal psychologies overtaken by fresh artificial (social risks), but consistently behave in a rational manner according to their perception of things. They have varying preoccupations and disputes regarding what should be done. Taleb and Thompson have facilitated our understanding of how and why actors are correct and incorrect and in which situations.

In a world where an equilibrium can never be achieved, it is not possible to regard this thesis as being conclusive. However, it offers a collection of functional hypotheses and feasible practices that can be suggested to entrepreneurs as well as certain clues regarding how to adapt them for senior managers to utilise, who often observe that the most carefully made plans are ruined by unpredictable events. Such recommendations *may* be loosened or changed if and when a change in risk season occurs.

It is normal that calls are made for ‘larger samples’ in future studies. However, a factor that the author believes has greater importance is the development of an enhanced comprehension of the ‘poly-rational’ solutions identified by Thompson as well as the creation of forums and symposia in which various types of reasoning and opposing recommendations can be brought together. The thesis will be ending with the following questions:

‘What actions can facilitators take to allow actors to perceive the value in other people’s reasoning, acknowledge where their own have limitations, and devise innovative solutions that are unthinkable apart from in a collective of differing minds?’ The author makes the proposal that such gatherings could be convened in environments that are not only characterised by uncertainty, but also significant danger. Doing this may necessitate the adoption of greater appetite for risk than are accustomed.

In concluding this thesis, I would like to express my gratitude to my supervisor Prof. Kozlovski. He has supported me with his kindness and friendliness during this course, for which I am eternally grateful. He effectively utilised his skills to allow me to perceive my own tacit skills. His understanding of ‘managing for the future’ approaches, as he defines it, including Nicholas Nassim Taleb and Michael Thompson, has allowed me to comprehend why actors behave in certain ways and how they could acquire the ability to feel, think and behave in different ways. Prof. Kozlovski allowed me to think in abstract as well as practical and instinctive ways. It has been revealing to look beyond the conventional studies on strategy to

observed that academic professionals are also ‘cultural subjects’ who have the identical variety of ‘styles of thought’ that cause non-academics to sincerely disagree about what is the best course of action.

If one can identify the roots of thoughts and actions, it is not possible to return to the basic ‘five step’ change management models that have naïve and generally hierarchical assumptions that individuals with seniority are the most knowledgeable and that success can only be achieved by implementing these steps consecutively.

Such a realisation is worthy of being shared with entrepreneurs and senior managers in Iran in particular. Nevertheless, the combination of inventiveness and wariness that is already well-established in Iran has worldwide ramifications and it pleases us to present this to a broader audience.

3.9 Summary

In this chapter, the selection of the research methodology used has been discussed by referencing the literature, documenting that our choice of methodology has been made for pragmatic reasons and in line with the question, aims and objectives of the research. Additionally, it is explained why ‘Talebian’ types of qualitative interview should incorporate flexible responses based on the course of the specific interview. Despite the fact that a hypothesis exists at the centre of the research (that the anti-fragility of entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived is greater than top salaried managers), it is important that our interviewing strategy is anti-fragile. This implies that it should ‘expect the unexpected’. Furthermore, the research is highly dependent on primary evidence supplemented by secondary analysis or documenting of published sources, particularly as philosophical and theoretical reference points. The researcher perceives no benefit in attempting to force his methodology into a particular camp such that it fits the standard account of method. It is believed that is valuable to include: 1) a testable *positivist* hypothesis as well as 2) *qualitative* evidence.

4 Chapter 4

Interviews and Data Collection

4.1 Author's Assumptions Before Interviewing

The distribution of plastics and additional raw materials for the petrochemical industry as well as container manufacturing and other petrochemical raw materials and the manufacturing of containers being our primary areas of operation during the years of entrepreneurial experience in Iran, it was evident that the managerial mind-set of the government or a part of the government differs from that of the Iranian entrepreneur. It can be claimed with certainty that managers and entrepreneurs focus on strategy, survival, and risk in very different ways because this is interacted with both groups very frequently. Entrepreneurs are more prone to taking more risks, but they are also cautious. They are somewhat apprehensive about taking risks yet do so anyhow. Managers of petrochemical companies are also hesitant to the extent that they will not take risks. Although they contemplate the issue and do not deviate from their stance, they do not take black swans into account. Although both managers and entrepreneurs are apprehensive of risk, it is believed that while managers perceive themselves as risk takers and obsessively question whether they have made a mistake, entrepreneurs are highly averse to risks, making them more susceptible to surprises. There is a difference, even though it is not substantial.

The author would define black swans to interviewees, describing their traits in a manner similar to Taleb's. As the interviewees responded to the aforementioned main interview questions, the researcher informed them about the concept of 'paradigms' as broad universal theories to the extent that they could understand the 'chaos paradigm' as well as how it can be differentiated from the notions that the past is characterised by a relentless march toward progress (the 'conflict paradigm') and that everything eventually comes to an equilibrium (the 'functionalist paradigm').

In order to minimise the bias and analyse the collected data in a better way the researchers background in the same country and industry were very useful and reliable,

secondly the bracketing method were chosen as an appropriate approach to discuss and minimise the bias. Interviewing a third party to identify and raise awareness of assumptions and biases is one of the simplest ways to bracketing concept. (Rolls and Relf, 2006). Bracketing interviews create a negotiated, supportive connection that acts as a conduit among the researcher and the data they are researching. They are conducted with a non-clinical co-worker who does not hold a managerial position or a fellow researcher. This approach should include agreement on the secrecy of the information discussed, and it may be institutionalised by paying a fee and arranging scheduled meetings. Bracketing interviews, which are conducted during data collection, might reveal themes that might make it difficult for the researcher to listen to respondents or that might cause the researcher to feel emotionally uncomfortable and prevent further investigation. By unearthing forgotten personal experiences, bracketing interviews have the ability to enhance the clarity for the researcher and allow them to become more engaged with the viewpoints of the interviewees; additionally, they can also offer protection to both the interviewer and interviewees when the topic of research triggers intense emotions, while at the same time enabling the researcher to further their understanding of the given phenomenon (Razbani, 2015).

Figure 23 Bracketing Method

4.2 Interviews with Iranian's Petrochemical Senior Salaried Managers

Senior management personnel working in the petrochemical sector in Iran are frequently confronted by unexpected challenges. What does their interview reveal in terms of the extent to which they are prepared for such black swan events? Are their responses in accordance with or contradictory to Taleb's assertion that the majority of Wall Street executives were "fooled by randomness" and victims of the "narrative fallacy"? Are they in agreement or disagreement with his 'anti-fragile' suggestions? In this thesis, it is described interviews conducted with senior management personnel working in the petrochemical sector of Iran, while acknowledging that the process of petrochemical processing exhibits significantly less vulnerability to black swan events than the social frameworks surrounding it, including oil price fluctuations, conflicts in the region, as well as deteriorating or improving relations with the international community.

It is important to take into account that minor changes have been made in the quotes that follow to convert syntax and rhetorical figures specific to the Persian language into English syntax and figures of speech. Nevertheless, Persian syntax has been retained where the meaning is clear enough. The research has included certain emphases that were originally present in the responses of the interviewees for the purpose of highlighting aspects that readers can subsequently analyse and review. As a result of space limitations, quotes have been limited to the elements of the interviews with the most significance, whereas certain answers to additional questions that were included fleetingly have been excluded. Nonetheless, care has been taken to ensure that the answers given by the interviewees have been 'sampled' in a manner that allows the preservations of their actual meanings. The reason for doing this is that it permits readers to identify any commonalities among the answers within every sample, as well as whether the two samples differ in a significant manner (not by chance).

1 Interview with the Managing Director of J Petrochemical Company

Mr. M, please can you provide an explanation of the role that Iran plays in the global oil and gas sector? How chaotic do you think the future of the industry will be, with unexpected "black swan" events?

We are fortunate that the reserves of gas stored in Iran are the largest in the world, more than many other countries, but this means that such resources necessitate proper planning. If we compare this with, for instance, the traditional agricultural industry, one of the problems being experienced is insufficient water, and it is clear that in this case it not possible to resolve this issue using conventional approaches, and therefore, significant measures must be implemented.

However, the competitive advantage in Iran can be found more in the oil and gas industry and its associated sectors, which has significant diversity and creates a large number of employment opportunities.

The oil and gas sector is characterised by the fact that a vast resource of technical knowhow is immediately available and Iranian specialists have achieved considerable advancements. In this regard, and certainly, whatever is developed by the industry, we will transcend from the perspective of knowledge to an elevated position.

Luckily, there is such depth of knowledge [and] the oil and gas sector...is highly modernised. Its scientific standing is very high. We will be ranked higher in every industry.

Which issues in particular is Iran facing that have the greatest urgency in its efforts to develop its downstream petrochemical industries?

An issue that has particular significance is the availability of financial resources, the provision of equipment and parts, as well as licensing, which necessitates large volumes of energy in the existing environment. There will definitely be an acceleration in the pace of the industry, and we will witness a significant uplift in the petrochemical sector when sanctions are completely lifted, which will initiate a process of equipping and reequipping.

Our intention is to purchase new technologies and consider our relations with international associates, and I stress a specific objective of the new investments with international partners is to strive to guarantee security and the security of investment.

We need to try to encourage the private sector to do more research in the petrochemical industry and its benefits, and even prepare to do it with private companies investing in it, and give this hope to the partners as long as the plant is profitable and sustainable. Allow shares to be transferred to the investor through the stock exchange, and eventually we will invest in another new company, and in fact, our role will be as a producer and thus create new industrial clusters on high-value issues.

Do you think the Iranian petrochemical industry is in an appropriate position considering unforeseen political and economic situations in the Middle East?

For instance, China does not have conventional gas fields, it extracts gas from coal and consumes gas and high-energy petrochemicals, but has grown in the petrochemical industry, and today, urea production in China is about 15 times higher than Iran's production of urea and ammonia. Whenever we want to invest in industrial, providing FS or technical and economic studies, the main issue is the target markets. Therefore, investors investing faster hence, they will make the market themselves easier. For example, if we want to establish a production facility for ammonia production, we should study whether there is a factory with these products. Is there a target market for selling products? Currently, China plans to launch 17 Alfani factories, whereas, before Iran, Iran should launch these factories by producing a variety of grades, because Iran has the ability to produce certain levels of olefin at a global level. Iran's petrochemicals should cooperate and engage with foreign investors in the production of basic products of olefins, including PE, PP, and other products on a global scale. Hoping for the day we can produce 20 to 30 million tons of PP, PE, and other petrochemical products from new grades, we have to push our position to this end. "We are looking for a new generation of new grades to be produced at the national level, which will result in a lot of jobs and value for the country," he said.

2 Managing Director of BA Petrochemical Company

In this instance, we preferred to phrase the opening question as follows:

What impact will outside environmental factors have on management approaches adopted in Iran's various petrochemical industries in the future?

The country faced two major challenges at the 50th anniversary of petrochemicals; one of the hasty detentions of some petrochemical plants and the other, cruel sanctions. In the fifty-first anniversary of petrochemicals, this industry can regain its strength. Certainly, all the industry's associates and enthusiasts are waiting for entry into the future with lifting of sanctions, but that does not mean that all the work has been stopped and corporate strategies are only based on this.

By entering to the environment with no sanctions, we should not miss out the new opportunities and existing strengths, and with the previous implemented researches regarding the future could be created related space, some researches about the growth scenarios in this industry should be taken to consideration and the system should be managed systematic manner.

The next question was expressed deliberately in very large terms, in order to invite the respondent to think on a very large scale, i.e. to think paradigmatically:

What is the impact of the development of the petrochemical industry and global interactions and the role of Iran in the international economy?

It must be said that the global economy is interconnected, and this interconnection has brought about closer ties between countries, and if our industries have the ability to meet the needs of foreign companies, our

dependence will certainly be created and this economic tension in the country's political and international relations will affect with regard to the importance of Iran how ... the petrochemical industry...develops and is developing.

The position of Iran in global bargaining and international relations, as well as the level of Iran from the spiritual dimension in international relations and *international equilibrium*, is affected, and this is the meaning of income.

Having encouraged the interviewee to consider the world at a large scale and explained briefly what is meant by 'paradigm' I asked:

What is your main paradigm?

The type of paradigm we follow is mostly functional.

What is your view about the possibility of developing long-term and profitable strategies based on Taleb's theories of how to manage for the future?

The readiness of the country's petrochemical industry to exploit post-war opportunities and favourable prospects for investment and growth for the industry is for those who have a license, for the investors and technology owners of the industry. Their very active presence over the past year and their calls for long-term cooperation in this industry is clear.

... First-level companies (top stream producers) were clearly visible

By exploring and choosing the best in these collaborations, the foundation of this industry is to build on the strength of the technology that is at the cutting edge of today's knowledge.

The key is transparency in contracts of cooperation with foreign investors and assurance in the preservation of their funds, relying on the use of the latest technologies in each sector of the industry's projects by carefully studying and using the experience and knowledge of our country's specialists in this industry, especially the industry's leading players in the development period of this industry. The industry has played a huge role in past years, and now some have retired, it can prepare the space for attracting foreign investors...starting with the willingness of investors to begin cooperative operations now.

I then asked:

How to do feel about foreign partners with High Tech Knowledge?

Participation of domestic companies with foreign companies in the field of engineering and implementation of projects has also existed before the sanction, and we hope that this cooperation will start again and proceed with strength. In the context of joint ventures with foreign companies, if it is transparent and respectful of the rights of the parties, it would seem to be a great start for the rapid development of this industry.

Similar examples have been very successful in the past. The evaluation of this industry requires infrastructure studies, futures studies, all-around.

Since the industry has been rich in oil and gas resources in Iran then this positive advantage must be definitely taken to the consideration to develop this industry growth.

Again, having had the meaning of the word ‘paradigm’ explained (with brief examples) we asked again:

What is your main paradigm?

We are using a mixture of chaotic and functional paradigms in our company.

3 Interview with Mr. H.H the oldest Former Petrochemical Manager, and currently Managing Director of P.P Co.

Please can you summarise how the oil and petrochemical sectors in Iran have developed in recent decades, taking into account unforeseen 'Black Swan' events?

With the nationalization of the oil industry, the professors of the Abadan Oil Department left Iran. Due to the needs of the remaining faculty, I taught various

courses, including mathematics, chemistry, and physics, while completing my semester on a full-time mechanical engineering course [as a student] . In 1337 [1957], I was transferred to the Abadan Oil Refinery, and I worked in the process engineering department until 1347, and I have to admit that I learned the knowledge of the oil industry over the course of 10 years at Abadan Oil Refinery.

In 1347[1967], I was transferred to the National Petrochemical Company, and until early [1977], I was responsible for managing various projects, the most important of which was the Iran-Japan Petrochemical Project, and in the last four years of my service at the National Industry Company, I was a member of the Board of Petrochemicals.

Regarding the disagreement in the implementation of a project called AM Petrochemical Complex with the managing director of the National Petrochemical Company and some other directors, I was forced to early retirement in early 1977.

After the change in the management of the National Petrochemical Company in February 1977, I served as an Operations Manager and member of the Board of Directors of the National Petrochemical Company, which I was still exempted from serving in the company.

In other words, this respondent had had a ‘colourful’ career with big upheavals for both him and the institutions he worked for.

Considering your experience as former CEO of NPC for many years. What were the main management challenges in the unpredictable political situation of those years?

Every human being can be considered as an economic machine and behaves in a way that can accomplish its purpose. People such as Dr. Mossadegh, who implemented fantastic and surprising actions which were unpredictable in Iran's system, was critical and he did not employ anyone from his family in the cabinet... The definition is not constructive and it is only criticism that can be constructive. The unpardonable structure will never succeed. I know fully about them, but I will not talk about them. As I said, I was ...disagreeing very strongly with them, leading to my pre-retirement retirement.

It is not the fault of them, but if community space is not the atmosphere of criticism, things cannot be well-advanced.

What we hear here is that the respondent believes that open criticism is a way for dealing with surprising outcomes and that some surprises were in any case positive and uncharacteristic of what could have been expected.

Again, posing a question calling for a high level of generalisation I asked:

Do you believe that foreign technology can help in the development of this industry?

I firmly believe that it is still necessary to use foreign technology and assistance for various stages of production, refining, and conversion of petrochemical raw materials. It should be noted that Hydrocarbon industry technology and many other industries are not transferable. Despite the fact that in addition to a century of production of hydrocarbon (oil and gas) in our country, the foreign

associations haven't transferred their main technical knowledge, *therefore, our country still requires to pay license fees.*

After my pre-retirement retirement, I established an engineering company in the field of hydrocarbon industries. To implement projects related to hydrocarbon industries, an engineering company needs at least 200 experts in many engineering fields. To maintain this number of experts plus supportive human resources (totalling about 600 people), the need for continued implementation of the project and the belief, the faith and commitment of the contractors and the employer, and the comprehensive support of government agencies for the institutionalization of technology and the ability to construct projects is all vital.

Based on this, the same path has been followed in [all] developed, advanced and industrialized countries.

What are the main challenges which you have faced in implementing your hydrocarbon-related projects?

Unfortunately, the extent of process development over the last eight years has shrunk due to the transfer of projects to affiliated companies and to the armed forces of the country and has stopped in many private companies.

It is important to note that in recent years, especially in the last eight years, engineering companies in the hydrocarbon industry have not succeeded.

Interested, innovative, and creative graduates on average more than three years (that is, when they have learned experience and engineering companies which could then use their experience) Unfortunately, most of these engineers have left the country to work and live better.

Obviously, in the event of the management and creation of a sound and logical framework, including improving living and working conditions in the country, engineering companies will not be able to withstand the emigration of this large number of engineers and experienced experts, and this huge volume of financial and spiritual capital will be exhausted.

Why we do not have in our country nongovernmental companies such as Bechtel, Lamas, Flora, the Clock and dozens of similar companies in other countries of the world? And for the implementation of hydrocarbon projects from the beginning, we need foreign companies.

Why do Iranian companies with more than 40 years of experience and honest, lively and loyal management now have no organization like these?

The answer to these questions is that the opportunities offered by companies such as Flora, Lamas, Yo - Obi and so on have not been given to Iranian companies. Companies affiliated with the government and the armed forces of the country cannot implement hydrocarbon ...innovations and new technology. A person who takes responsibility in the organization must be fully aware and [in control] in order to progress. In large foreign companies, such as Dow Chemical, employees are on a hierarchy level. They [work at] different levels

of work and are supervised to give them responsibility after a few years. Managing Director after 10 years possibly. If no choices are made based on merit, there will not be any progress.

In the industrial countries managers and ministers usually have some free time to think about system developments. But in Iran the situation is opposite. Technocrats are unemployed and some managers work about 16 hours a day. We need to get the right system for development. The private sector could achieve some success in this regard.

What is your main paradigm?

The main paradigm in our company is functional.

4 Interview with Former Petrochemical Planning Management

When you planned to establish the IM Petrochemical Complex (Iran-Japan) in the period which many black swan events happened what were the main challenges when implementing the plan?

I refer to the Iran-Japan Petrochemical Complex, which was built with a 50-50 investment. Mitsui's company had many subsidiaries. The first reason was to use the technology of this company. We spent about \$70 million for the construction license of the complex. Japan was not an industrial country in 1950, and it did not have our resources. On the side-lines, I must point out that the country's greatest resources are not oil resources, but human resources. Many years of teaching at the university proved to me that we have a very

powerful and efficient workforce. The second reason was the consumption of foreign companies. About 500,000 tons of plastic were produced at that time, up to 10 percent of the country's demand, and the rest should have been exported.

The average recovery of crude oil is about 25% or we can say that about 75% of the country's oil 'reserve' is abandoned. Therefore, it would be better to invest in existing fields by choosing domestic technology institutions, to increase the production [by controlling and refining the abandoned crude oil] instead of investing in new fields and inviting foreign companies to this end. To recapture Masjed Soleyman's oil field, after about a century of production, it still has more than four billion barrels of oil in place. Is it not expedient to foreseen the production of oil at the required level and to create secondary recycling for the existing oil fields?

In year 1973, our country's revenue from oil sales increased by four times, but industrial countries and advanced oil importers tried to eliminate their issues due to a fourfold rise in oil prices with proper planning after a year, but the problems of our country due to lack of planning about how to use and reinvest the four times income has begun after a year.

In general, the study of the production and consumption of energy in each country is a dynamic issue on a long-term horizon and *static studies of energy in the short term are misleading*. Unfortunately, there are three important and independent entities in our country, including the *Ministry of Energy*, the

Ministry of Petroleum and the *Atomic Energy Organization*, as well as other less important institutions covering the management of energy production and energy use in the country.

The sad fact is that in many cases, these institutions plan and decide in parallel with each other with little contact and in some cases, in mutual opposition...

Would not it be better like many countries in the world, a ministry called the "Ministry of Energy" be responsible for energy policies, including the new green energies as well as allocation of suitable feeds for the country's petrochemical industry especially in the long term?

If this were to happen, the production and use of substitute energies such as solar, wind, geothermal, biogas, and atomic resources, would have been cleared, while familiarizing ourselves with the technologies and having potential for increased productivity in the country... This is necessary, but not economical... given the existing supply of energy from hydrocarbon resources. It is not justified.

The priority of investing in research and development and attracting the talented and creative people of the country should undoubtedly be considered to hydrocarbon industries.

Note: from the authors point of view these can make the country more anti-fragile against the international sanctions.

What are your suggestions in planning for the future of petrochemical industries in Iran?

In general, industries in Iran are economically viable, which is superior to the same industries in other developed and industrialized countries of the world. In the petrochemical industry, at least 50 percent of the cost is related to the integrated feed complex and connected infrastructures. Now, if a petrochemical product in Iran is to be compared with food, the price of which even without subsidies and discounts is significantly lower than that of the industrialized countries, it is undoubtedly economically feasible to produce food in Iran.

For example, the price of oil, which is one of the main determinants of the viability of the upstream petrochemical industry, is not very different in Iran and in the industrialized countries, so petrochemical complexes in Iran based on oil feed are not economically feasible.... Light hydrocarbon compounds such as methane, ethane, propane, and butane for export have to be ... cooled to temperatures of 163, 89, 40 and 5 Degree of Celsius and the concentration, storage, maintenance, loading, ship carrying and discharging these compounds, all of which is a suitable feed for the petrochemical industry, is very costly. Since these compounds do not need to be used in Iran, their prices in Iran are significantly lower than in those industrialised countries importing these compounds. As a result, the cost of producing petrochemical products whose feeds are methane, ethane, propane, and bromide are less than industrialized countries and their production in Iran *is* economically feasible.

In addition to the privilege of food, I believe that the creation of petrochemical industries in our country should have other characteristics that are most important:

Small and food-dependent petrochemical complexes are not competitive and should be integrated with other petrochemical complexes and a so-called petrochemical company to survive.

Petrochemical products are highly vulnerable in terms of technology, quality, cost of production and investment. Therefore, it is necessary to have a research and development centre for petrochemical industries. The location of the R & D centre should preferably be located in Iran's temperate region with its good weather and at a good location which is able to expand... It should be noted that the cost of the applied part of the Research and Development Centre is usually monitored by the applicant's petrochemical plants.

The location of petrochemical complexes should be preferably along the river or the sea but adjacent to the feeds. Since the gases produced with crude oil and raw gas of independent gas fields are the main sources of feed for Iran's petrochemical industries, construction of a gas refinery within the complex of petrochemical plants with the proper design to feed the units has a clear advantage.

Due to the requirements to service the petrochemical units, especially electricity and steam in various conditions, the construction of a power plant

inside the unit is necessary to provide the needed utilities to increase the plant's efficiency and reduce the required energy for water cooling systems.

What is your main paradigm?

We mostly follow the functional paradigm in our organization but I myself [am] interested in chaotic paradigm as well.

5 Dr. R, Senior Academic within a PSI collaborating with Petroleum Industry

How do you see the future of Iran's different petrochemical sectors being affected by their environment...? I mean the social and economic environment?

Fast speed of development in petrochemical industries, as well as too much attention to developing basic materials, are the most challengeable aspects in this area

He stated that until recently, there was only one petrochemical facility in Iran that had yet to be completed (the joint Iran-Japan facility in Khuzestan), that was recently given the name *Bandar Imam Petrochemical* (Figure 3). In 1986, *Mitsubishi* made the decision to sell its shares to the *National Iranian Petrochemical Company* in 1986, and the organisation has been called the Bandar Imam Petrochemical Company since then (2017). Dr. G stated that when operating, Iran-Japan Petrochemical satisfied a limited proportion of the demand in in Iran for polymeric substances. Nevertheless, states in the region including Saudi Arabia and Qatar had the capacity to refine oil into petrochemical materials, quickly meeting the demand from global markets. He stated: 'It is important to note that the petrochemical products sector in Iran has developed reasonably and appropriately. Nevertheless, certain problems exist in this context.'

He proceeded by stating the polymer institute in which he worked was attempting to developing an understanding of historical challenges and devise suitable solutions. He then mentioned that investors have been financing improvements in plants for processing petrochemicals and developing existing facilities in order to overtake and replace imported products while also taking steps to enter the global export market.

A specific issue to which he referred was that future plans were not being made by investors and had only focused on making improvements to facilities that were already in place rather than developing plans to construct plants from scratch. He acknowledged that it remained unknown as to whether the plans to construct petrochemical plants in Bandar Imam and Assalouyeh would actually come to fruition. Observe how he advocates for both caution (anti-fragile approach?) to see how things develop as well as an undaunted strategy involving long-term investment at new locations.

Nevertheless, he did refer to the dangers and benefits of each stage, including the acquisition of licenses, installing and operation of machinery, marketing and after-sales service. He demanded proof that the quality of Iranian petrochemical products were at the same level as those produced internationally. In principle, he believed that products manufactured in Iran were capable of being competitive with those from other countries as recipients would not find it difficult to replace domestic products at reduced prices.

"Dr. G" observes that if Iran is dependent on domestic sources of energy, any success it achieves will ultimately be subject to additional problems. The goal was to determine and resolve issues as quickly as possible. He concluded by stressing that

there would be "revelations" as a result of increased Research and Development that not be easy to predict.

In spite of these opinions, he responded to the question:

What is your main paradigm?

‘The type of paradigm we are using is functional.’

6 Head of Product Development of the same institution

What are your suggestions about developing long-term and profitable strategies based on the hard-to-estimate probabilities of ‘black swan’ events?

Producing of different grades is highly recommended. Iran has investigated the existing grades of Polycarbonate (PC) across the world as well as their usage and demand growth. Therefore, it is decided to produce six different grades of PC in Iran out of forty different grades.

However, there is a question whether consumers of the main classes will continue to buy it from other countries. It is also critical to investigate the most important properties which exist in these products and following that, at the next step it is crucial to match them with the suitable machinery.

One of the important factors in the petrochemical industry is to identify and use suitable machinery for the raw materials to have the excellent and appropriate finishing... it is very important to identify companies that can provide the best machinery as well as have the best and proper after sales in terms of...spare parts and... the opportunity to develop production lines in the future if this is needed.

At the end of the day, a comprehensive and strategic report that can be trusted could be obtained and accordingly there could be fundamental planning. In the petrochemical industries, it is very common to produce a product and send it to the market regularly, hence, nowadays most petrochemical sites are providing low-cost materials and sending them to market with insufficient concern about quality.... exposing themselves to commercial and public criticism.

In recent years... companies are formed traditionally. For instance, a group of people heard that the market requires CD and after the general overview of the market they bought a CD machine. However, they were unable to investigate the type of CDs that the market required. Such companies need the education to inform them and help them to understand technical problems. If we could communicate with them providing up-to-date information and data, not only could they develop appropriately but also create a perfect market for staple petrochemical materials.

Increasing downstream industries' knowledge and encouraging them to produce new, different products can be lead to good sales in basic petrochemical materials, which is known as "Product Development."

And how do you explain the parading you are using in the system?

Our goal is to adopt a combination of chaotic and functional paradigms within our company.

7 Interview with Mr. K Manager of NPC

Mr. K, please can you give us an overview of the role that Iran plays within the global oil and gas sector? How chaotic do you think the future in terms of generating unpredictable ‘black swan’ events?

The most significant challenge in petrochemical industries is to produce and distribute more than 30 Million tons' products into the domestic and foreign markets.

Mr. K expressed confidence that his company was capable of achieving 71% of its nominal (theoretical) output capacity, equating to a 108% year-on-year increase. He stated that if sufficient feed was supplied to the petrochemical industries in Iran by the National Iranian Gas Company (NIGC), then the NPC would be able to produce in excess of 42 million by year end 2017, accounting for 73% of the overall petrochemical output of the country.

According to his description of them, the prevailing issues that were constraining the ability of the petrochemical industry to reach its full potential in terms of production included “insufficient fuel” and “maintenance issues”.

As previously, after I briefly introduced the topic, I questioned:

What paradigm do you largely follow?

We are ‘functionalist’ within our organisation.

While the interview was relatively short, it had significant relevance. Observe that despite being questioned about unforeseen events, he did not refer to them in his responses. From his perspective, all the challenges he noted were not a surprise.

8 Prof. G CFO of J.J Petrochemical Complex

Dr. J, please can you explain the standing of Iran in the global oil and gas sector. How chaotic do you think the future will be with unexpected ‘black swan’ events?

We found it fascinating that Mr provided his responses in the form of bullet points, and therefore, they are shown below in the same shortened manner in which he expressed himself:

They can be summarized in the following way:

- Public sector mechanisms should intervene frequently in a non-strategic manner. As the government participants in the private sector petrochemicals markets, the Institute does not actively take the lead in distribution.
- Concentrate on providing support for and establishing new facilities rather than the development of current units: Presently, the government provides support for constructing new facilities instead of the development of existing plants, which has resulted in various new units being opened that are relatively small. Nevertheless, their output is limited, which lacks practicality. As a result of their scale...they are not competitive in the international market and are incapable of expanding.
- Regular changes in policy: policies are changed on a frequent basis with no prior notice, along with alterations to tariff rates and political priorities, among others. Consequently, operators in the industry adopt a short-term perspective of their operations. They should consider developing long-term business relations and conducting research, giving greater attention to long-term investments than is currently the case, and innovate products and production lines to a greater extent.
- The environment is closed and there are shortcomings in terms of the establishment of international partnerships: the majority of current investments

are grounded on the strategy of substituting imported products with those produced domestically for the local market. Consequently, the industry has reduced involvement in foreign markets, with a greater focus on the domestic market.

What paradigm do you largely follow?

In my opinion, we are primarily utilising a paradigm that comprises both chaotic and functional elements.

9 Interview with Dr. H. A, PM of (NPC)

Please can you explain the standing of Iran in the global oil and gas sector. How chaotic do you think the future will be with unexpected ‘black swan’ events?

As with the previous interview, his responses were given in a manner akin to bullet points.

Investment is regarded as being a key economic variable that is capable of increasing a country’s overall wealth. The focus here is to entice investments from both Iran and abroad. Private investors including Iranian citizens residing in other countries as well as foreign investors focus on two key factors when making the decision whether to invest in Iranian industries:

1. Political considerations
2. Non-political considerations

Political considerations include whether and the manner in which organisations in Iran work in cooperation with other states, the foreign policies of Iran...sanctions, relations with the international community, interstate conflicts, in addition to political upheavals, political disputes domestically and factions of political will. One of the main concerns from the perspective of both internal and external investors is security.

On the other hand, non-political factors include economic, infrastructural, legal, technical factors as well as those related to labour laws, insurance and taxes. It is necessary for the private sector to actively participate to establish suitable economic conditions along with technical investment, while there should also be a legal framework for both private and state sectors, which can allow the petrochemical industry to flourish while also generating more employment opportunities and enhancing added value.

In the upstream petrochemical units, production capacity is already very high, so the economic justification.... for investors, would only be in the major product lines. There are many manufacturers of these products, which means competition to [lengthen] shelf-lives and to sell at lower prices.

In...downstream units, the role played by technology, production machinery and skilled human resources is vital in judging final prices of...core products. In this sector, although the tonnage of production is small, because of the more complex...knowledge and technology needed, there is...higher added value compared to the price of the initial materials.

It seems that to achieve growth and...greater added value, it is necessary to invest, develop and complete value chains in petrochemical products, form clusters with upstream producers, including clusters around adding value to methanol and ethylene.

About ‘environmental challenges’ can this impact the management approaches adopted in the various petrochemical industries in Iran?

The realization of desired values for the petrochemical industry (value added, employment and industrial development) along with the need for a balanced evolution of the petrochemical industry, means direct relationship between well-developed industries and downstream petrochemical processors. Ultimately we should integrate petrochemical value-chains.

But the growth of downstream sectors, compared to upstream petrochemical is minuscule and incomparable because there are...problems...developing the beneficiary companies...in the country. Outputs from downstream industries cannot enter...international markets. But they are also not yet able to compete in the domestic market.

Generally, downstream manufacturers continue to exist based on the non-governmental investments. The primary weakness of this industry is non-competitive products, as well as the comparative advantage of the country which is basic extraction.

The interviewee had knowledge of Porter. He proceeded:

Based on Porter, the competitive advantage of a country...is expressed as the ability of companies to use the country as a platform for doing the business which it is suited to best. This is what is expected from the petrochemical beneficiary companies.

He referred to Porter making the argument that:

Porter points to characteristics of a country in his model from which you can create a competitive advantage or prevent that from happening. The factors are internal conditions of production, demand conditions, related and supporting industries, strategy, structure, and the competitiveness of an enterprise.

Issues that are confronting the beneficiary industries can be described using Porter's' Four Forces.

And the final question if I may ask, paradigm do you primarily follow?

The paradigm we used comprises both chaotic and functional elements.

10 Dr. B. A Director of J.J.L Petrochemical Complex

Please explain to us the primary issues that currently exist as a result of governmental management systems and banking problems as well as your recommendations for how to deal with them.

Irresponsible government agencies, public service providers and government] products: the large share of the economy taken by the, its policies for manufacturing activities, and a significant portion of the market for services as well.

But the problem is...customers would like to get the discount according to *market* prices at the time when the payment is due...in one to one relationships just between the customers and the sellers. But in the circumstances, we have, beneficiary industries are not professional enough to enter world markets so the extent that there is a possibility of offering their products to compete even in the regional market, is minuscule. As a result, they always face into closed domestic markets even though threatened because these markets are full of cheap products which are provided from China.

While it seems that he was advocating for free competition, he proceeded with his recommendation by stressing:

Making the domestic market less competitive: as a result of the multitude of different participants in downstream petrochemical industries whose size is limited, both dimming and destructive competition have occurred among industrial actors. As a result of their limited size, these companies are hesitant to start operating in global markets, and generally seek profits through the development of local markets or forcing the elimination of a rival.

This is particularly exemplified by the fact that actors are frequently required to cope with multiple similar organizations as a result of the high level of domestic competition and the challenges in sourcing inputs, which means that the operation rates and production volumes in this sector are reduced. Resultantly, coupled with the increased financial costs including those associated with working capital, increased inflation, outdated technology and

the reduced productivity levels of labour in Iran, this factor has caused the end price of products to be increased.

It is clear that when the quality of a product is reduced and the supporting business network lacks strength, meaning that the prices are not sufficiently competitive, the opportunity for it to be marketed for export is limited. Consequently, the product cannot be marketed internationally, and the resulting margin between the production costs and final price leads to a reduction in output.

Lack of management vision within the domestic market, to earn the most added value: one of the points which commerce and politics neglects is the intrinsic value of the country's large potential domestic markets and its features. Iran as one of the most populous countries in the Middle East and has local market which ... are not used correctly.

As with our standard approach of asking a 'large scale' question, we firstly asked the following:

What paradigm do you largely follow?

I adopt a functional paradigm

11 Interview with Dr. T. P (P.P. C Complex in Iran)

Does the behaviour of private petrochemical companies in Iran correspond with the recommendations of Taleb, as I presented to you, which thus ensures their survival?

Let me summarize the existing weaknesses as follows:

Lack of comprehensive network? formations: the lack of strong, supportive, professional and non-political industry organizations in the country causes

problems for petrochemical industries. In the absence of an active group, it cannot be expected that a governmental organisation can protect the interest of producers. The weakness in supportive institutions and their support in the service sector too:

Lack of developed supply chains for small-scale industries, required basic materials for production units...has led to a sharp rise in the price of finished goods and reduce the competitive power... In most countries around the world, the supply of necessary materials. is available from defined producers.

Lack of support services for technology development: although there are reviews, comments, and rules covering many services as well as financial support for industry...there are few tools providing development support the industry. Technology is one of the most significant competitive advantages that could enable companies to compete in international markets, with *unique planned program* to develop their tech. Unfortunately, in Iran, there is no center that works to adapt foreign technology or create new technologies in the field of petrochemical downstream operations. Even in universities and research centers, there are no serious efforts in this area. Centers of scientific work tend to concentrate on practical work instead of paying attention to promoting new applications of new technology.

Lack of developer companies: the development of the 'midstream' industry as the interface between downstream and upstream petrochemicals, which would

complete the petrochemical production chain, requires development businesses in the country.

Weaknesses in financial structures: the main problem in the downstream industry in the financial institution...because the banks are not specialized enough. The financial system needs replacing along with economic structures. Unfortunately, the banks are currently not able to provide expert and useful pieces of advice while providing funds and therefore, development of petrochemical downstream industries is restricted.

The interviewee explained how institutions and companies function (or do not function), but I chose to explore this further by repeating the question:

To what extent do you think it is possible to develop long-term strategies that generate profit according to the suggestions of Taleb?

Petrochemical projects due to being high-volume operations, need *scientific planning, in detail*. Therefore, weaknesses in project management in the petrochemical area in Iran is more visible, and as a result of that, it is hard to find many petrochemical projects in the country that were completed according to the schedule. So, it is critically important to improve...management skills by training and educating project managers which would be possible through partnerships with foreign companies. It can be argued that through joint contracts in the field of project management, the optimal level could be reached earlier than...expected.

On the other hand, most of the existing approaches in the area of project management can be mentioned as the cost and timing of...projects, and based on these two factors projects can be evaluated. A project is an excellent opportunity to attract a technology from a foreigner partner, enabling projects to be finished on time, based on the schedule, and it is more cost effective. Whereas, the *technology development cannot be purchased with money*; hence, it is imperative to consider the contracts as *joint collaborative projects* as well as technology transfers from foreign' companies to be used to develop the technology based on signed contracts.

We note that this has a certain Talebian nature to it. After paraphrasing the three main (sociological) paradigms (Functionalist, Conflict Theory, Chaos Theory), I questioned

What paradigm do you largely follow?

If the choice is from a chaotic, functional or combination of both, my answer would be that my paradigm is functional.

12 Interview with Mr. N MD of Petrochemical Developing industry

To what extent do you think that 'environmental factors' will influence management approaches adopted in the various petrochemical sectors in Iran in the future?

The political and economic situations for the general contractors are not predictable (maybe they cannot continue their contract due to international sanctions) and employers and the general state of the country will suffer from losses. According to statistics, foreign companies have not invested well in Iran.

Another reason is that the renaissance of foreign companies is more to do with the political aspects of the theorem than it is due to technical factors.

Basically, investors would be encouraged to invest in Iran if the political and economic situation was more stable, especially given the recent disagreement with the general contractor in the country.

... A consortium or general contractor, are of course important in themselves, but the word content is important, but it's not too long before we need to discuss the...country and we have not reached the final end. Our problem with project management is that, as long as we do not consider future unforeseen elements of the project management system, all legal methods will have almost the same results. In the case of general contracting, if the General Contractor is well-qualified and qualified to carry out its responsibilities and ...can coordinate the subcontractors, it will be possible to obtain the right of intermediation with benefits...for the country.

...I believe we have the ability to do feasibility studies in the country. For example, in a project with Shell and BP, the results of feasibility studies conducted by the Petrochemical Industries Planning Directorate were very close to the results of studies that Shell and NPC (National Petrochemical Company) made the following year. Since the foreign party was the first to participate in such a large project, it was possible for it to carry out a feasibility study for itself.

Feasibility studies needn't relate to the type of investment and investor. For example, feasibility studies of various 25-year plans for petrochemicals have been carried out. Nowadays, any contractor, including project financiers can participate ...and it does not matter to us whether the contractor provides credit from outside the country or from inside. These feasibility studies, if updated, are prepared in accordance with international standards, are also acceptable to foreign companies.

Contractors claim that problems such as banking issues, such as opening LCs Letters of Credit etc., are blocking their way, and that they cannot provide bank guarantees and guarantees of exploitation. Loans required by the contractors are long-term, but banks usually provide short-term loans, though petrochemical projects are usually long-term investment.

What actions have been taken to overcome these obstacles?

Considering the field of contracting, both sides (Government and Contractors) have mutuality. The government should support the decisions taken inside the country since eighty percent of contractors are governmental and the rest are supported by the government... Another case is... the finance. Foreign governments will support financially if they see benefits for their companies' participation in our projects. This could be done for...Iranian contractors; of course, but these issues and problems are gradually being resolved.

What is your main paradigm?

We think functionally.

13 Interview with MD of M Petrochemical

Please give us your opinion on the expansion of petrochemical raw materials in an environment characterised by chaos and uncertainty?

The respondent began by insisting on the integration of the petrochemical industry, as all of the world's leading companies have the concept of integration and incorporate it into their business model.

Selling petrochemical products is more than the one-year sales of oil and gas in the country. According to forecasts, in next two decades, the petrochemicals sectors will overtake the oil and gas economy in the country, provided that the government supports it.

He emphasised that the petrochemical sector was the primary foundation on which the future economic development of Iran was dependent:

Iran's petrochemicals are an exceptional opportunity, but there is only a limited time ahead. If this opportunity is not used, then it's time to wait for its threats, because rivals are growing rapidly and can threaten even the existing petrochemicals export capacity of the country and its market. By evaluating the application process of the material used in industries, it can be concluded that the products of the petrochemical industry have contributed significantly so that the scope of these various products is already known.

Petrochemical products in cars have grown from thirty kilograms to two hundred kilograms already and according to forecasts, they will reach two hundred and fifty by 2030, which will reduce energy consumption as well.

With respect to the raw material feedstock for petrochemical products, he continued by stating that based on predictions, there is an increasing likelihood that feeds derived from both vegetable sources and crude oil will be utilised.

He emphasised the importance of integration for the petrochemical sector due to the fact that every large corporation globally is following such an approach and developing a suitable structure for their organisation. For example, while *Total* has existed for 74 years, during the past two years, it has focused on the integration of petrochemical production into its business. Consequently, it has been able to capitalise on the advantages of dispersed designs and reduced its vulnerability to potential losses, while also optimizing its processes of production, enhancing its flexibility quantitatively and qualitatively

What is your main paradigm?

Functional.

14 Interview with Dr. A, the Director/ head of R&D of A.P. Petrochemical

Would you please describe to us the effect of environmental factors on the future management and strategies in Iran different petrochemical companies? And secondly, what is the possibility of developing long-term future plans?

Considering the R&D department in petrochemicals in Iran, it could be noted that the National Petrochemical Industry in Iran conducts only a *primary* R&D. It does not compare to R&D departments in developing countries.

It is well worth noting that Iran contacted some of the top universities and asked them to cooperate with Iranian Universities such as the Petroleum University of Technology to develop R&D capacity and update their facilities. But R&D

in Iran is not considered as of central importance which could be why ...we have difficulties ... competing with other countries in the Middle East such as Qatar and Saudi Arabia.

Dr. A described how the Institute of Science and Polymer Technology had gathered scientist, petrochemicals managers and other experts to investigate and discuss existing problems and opportunities in petrochemicals. Following the gathering; they have set up a core group to identify and define a 'zero phase' which attempts to estimate production amounts required by consumers across the world as well as supply and demand trends.

Currently, in the Middle East, there is destructive competition instead of creating a new formation. To be more specific, it could be said that, for instance, Iran, Qatar, Saudi Arabia, and some other countries produce PVC (PolyVinyl Chloride). Sometimes Iran can sell its PVC and sometimes other countries. By having more cooperation to produce different grades...all of the petrochemical companies across the Persian Gulf would be able to have continuous exports and sales. All of them produce PVC in the same grades, which is entirely wrong and the market could be enhanced a lot by producing different and more valuable grades.

What is your main paradigm?

In between chaotic, functional and mixture of these two. Yes, a mixture of the chaotic and functional.

15 Interview with Managing Director of NPC

How do you see changing environmental factors affecting future management strategies in Iran different petrochemical sectors? What could be done about unforeseeable risks... so called 'black swans'?

Economic sanctions imposed on Iran in recent years, causes many economic and political problems including for technology development, investment, transferring money, and obtaining spare parts. Because of sanctions, there are severe restrictions and obstacles to moving new technology into the country. Due to the embargo on equipment parts, there is no possibility of Iran entering international supply chains and achieving sustainable development.

Experience shows that petrochemical project finance methods are not suitable...for transferring technology. Funding projects through foreign investors reduces the bargaining power of Iran as well as restricting the transfer of the technology in the contract. In international law, those projects which are funded from foreign countries, eighty-five percent of the required equipment has to be provided from the states which supported the project. Therefore, despite massive investment in the petrochemical industry, there is a limit market for domestic producers and petrochemical industries are inhibited in making technology transfers.

Experience shows that contracts mean the donors of the technology i.e. the investor, is unwilling to provide technology updates leaving no space for optimization and improvements to productivity. While mutual investment through joint ventures with technology licence owners, not only could we

remove some of the problems but also have a convenient mechanism for technology transfer. If technology owners...sharing the benefits on projects, they will try their best to use the latest, and up to date technology to improve their competitiveness while facing fewer competitors.

Besides, this could help Iranian employees to become more educated and to improve their skills by learning from foreign experts.

What is your main paradigm?

Functional.

4.3 Interview with Entrepreneurs

➤ **Interview with A. R the Founder of HM, M.M.S and AM**

‘The respondent’ was invited to ‘describe his businesses’ by responding to the following main three questions (with questions added as the interview progressed)

- How have you survived? Do you as an Iranian entrepreneur behave as Taleb seems to recommend?
- How do you see ‘environmental factors’ affecting the way you and other companies in the Iran petrochemical sectors manage for the future?
- How do you rate the possibility of long-term, profitable strategies based on what Taleb says about future ‘black swans’?

Do you and Iranian entrepreneurs behave as Taleb would recommend? And how have you survived?

I'm quite familiar with N. N. Taleb's theories based on my MBA project...as well as through my PhD research. It is ...the most interesting management subject and I am saying this after many years of real business experiences in different business area and being one of the raw plastic supplier.

I am also a multi-business company owner who has survived in Iran's chaotic situation... and have found it possible to take profit and advantage from many unpredictable events (black swans). So, in my view these experiences could be developed in similar condition of uncertainty, but on a much bigger scale as a future strategy for Iran polymer and petrochemical industries as a whole, and even for the polymer and petrochemical industries across the Middle East. This is very much a Chaotic environmental, full of even greater uncertainties than Taleb discussed in his book, *The Black Swan*.

I have got used to behaving and making decisions as Taleb would recommend surviving, even though I did not know his book at the time. If it has worked for me, it should work for others who also seem to make decisions the way I do.

How would you describe the possibility of developing long-term and profitable strategies based on Taleb theories of managing for the future?

I tried to develop *diverse business fields* in ways that I now know are consistent with what Taleb would recommend, the key being to love randomness, variation, and uncertainty to some extent as well as considering the dangers and the possibility of making errors.... Taleb is interested in what he calls "the things gained from disorder" which he tries to take beyond resilience and

robustness. Taleb tries to help people understand the importance of what they cannot know and how should manage and cope with the consequence of the unpredictable events, with better results. Once I realise how many events are really black swan events (I mean unforeseeable and with big consequences) then our strategies should change, particularly in environments full of black swans such as the Middle East.

On the other hand, I believe that black swans are not undesirable and humanity should understand how to react and manage complexities and becoming 'anti-fragile'. Many good things have been black swans such as the discovery of penicillin that was a result of an unexpected observation in a petri dish.

What does this mean for me?

I have a part-completed project to build a luxury office, residential in a prime location in (Tehran). I am hesitating before deciding on the mix of uses and the type of client-market to attract, watching changes in local, national and international circumstances on a weekly and monthly basis, and *delaying each decision as long as possible with least possible consequence for each subsequent decision I must make on the project*. This method of working can be viewed as highly inefficient considered from a 'project management' point of view. It is a textbook case of *how not to manage a project* but under an assumption that there is a stable environment. But efficiency is not the point of my actions. It is survival through frequent use of reverse gears, many path possibilities and as many path change possibilities as I can create.

Meanwhile, I have a part-completed baby food manufacturing plant a considerable distance away. Or I should say it was originally supposed to be a baby food manufacturing plant in the beginning, but it might not be one when it is finished.

In a stable environment, free from the risk of international sanctions and in a growing economy in which Iran's highly educated middle-class female workforce would be seeking employment outside the home, a formula baby-food factory with a trusted German or British brand-partner would be an excellent 'rational choice'. But in case circumstances change, what I can do and have done is to choose different higher load bearing steel frameworks which would give the option of inserting heavy-lifting capacity (cranes) and a totally different manufacturing function – perhaps precision engineering - from what was originally imagined if international sanctions are re-imposed and an international venture with German partners fall through.

The 'wholly unexpected election' of Donald Trump (a good example of a Black Swan event, COVID-19) indicates that I was right, even though I acknowledge the wisdom of the saying, which is claimed to be an Arab saying, that 'He who foretells the future is a liar even when proved right!'

I do not pretend that I knew what the outcome of the US election would be, but I behave as if improbable events are likely and that they have larger impacts than probable ones. A 'competitive, profit-maximizing entrepreneur' would not behave like this, but s/he would not survive in Iran. In the meantime, I have instructed that a very fine stone wall is constructed around the site which I am very pleased with. This will have no effect at all on what will be made there but I feel some obligation to employ skilful masons.

In the meantime, I have maintained very good and necessary relations with local officials, explaining to them how it is the *need for flexibility* and no other reason that is the cause of the delay. They understand that I am an Iranian businessman and I think they would support my intention to translate Taleb into Farsi where his work should find a wide readership.

Finally, my own experience and that of my associates demonstrates another of Taleb's recommendations for surviving in a world of 'non-normally distributed (non-Gaussian) risks': *not specializing*, but instead spreading hope, efforts, investments, and energies across many fields in what is commonly known as a 'diversified portfolio'.

In my case, I also have investments in:

- Polymer trading
- Buying land to build an office building or a hotel
- Establishment of a company in web design as a startup
- Some stock and currency trading

I have also entered and left some activities altogether and will continue to do so. I considered very seriously the idea of setting up a ski-resort complex and researched the power systems that could be used and the altitude above sea-level which it should be, accounting for variations in snowfall and possible use as an international conference centre. Iran has a well-developed ski resort industry and thousands of Iranians holiday in the mountains for skiing inside Iran. I can show you photographs which would make you think they were taken in Switzerland or Austria. But I have set this project on one side for as far as I know for now.

If I had possessed god-like omniscience I could have been a very rich man but I accept that 'perfect knowledge' is a very foolish ambition, instead of surviving, remaining independent, reputable and honest, which are themselves sources of resilience in uncertain times.

As an actual case, the currency fluctuation would be a concern since it has ...involved a huge profit for the companies that operate globally but are owned locally. They received all their payment on foreign banks and get the huge benefit from money arbitrage. But I do not take this as 'evidence' that this should be my main business.

However, it is one thing to report these casual observations and quite another to establish that Iranian entrepreneurs who have survived and even thrived under chaotic incalculable uncertainty have done so because they have followed Nicholas Taleb's and Charles Lindblom's suggestions without reading these authors. First Taleb's thesis must be distilled into a series of researchable propositions (or as he would call them 'anti-theories'). Second, these need to be operationalized into questions which can be put to Iranian business associates and acquaintances and third, we need to see whether their survival can be linked with their pursuit of such 'anti-fragile' business.

What is your paradigm?

My...paradigm would be the chaotic paradigm and I sensed this even before I knew what a 'paradigm' was and knew how important it is to surviving. I did not know that I knew this. It was an 'unknown known' to me!

➤ **Interview with Entrepreneur CEO of RAHGO...**

What was the first business you set up and how did you go about entering entrepreneurship for a living?

From childhood, I had a feeling which encouraged me to do new things. I looked around and had issues that were almost different from others. I remember about forty or forty-one years ago, when we came to Tehran to meet some relatives, for the first time, I saw an *Atari* computer and an idea came to my mind with the use of this device in the village to make money. As a result, once I returned from Tehran, I rented a machine for a price of 500 Tomans for 48 hours. During that time, I allowed children to play with that device and, during this time I earned 800 Tomans for that 48 hours.

I followed in the same way until I was able to purchase an *Atari* machine, and then I bought another device, and I expanded to computer games and eventually I established a special store for games like that.

How did you start your plans in existence of chaos?

One of my characteristics is planning only based on market demand, and I had this feature from my childhood. I remember, during the war [with Iraq], I was renting video equipment, playing movies and martial arts in the countryside, and I had a good income. I created a village cinema. In the same way, my childhood tendency was at work and I used every opportunity to earn a solvent income.

What are the challenges during your entrepreneurship?

My worst challenges are unprovoked promises by some of the officials who use to send entrepreneurs away for meaningless reasons. My other bad memory was regarding a great achievement in year 2005 when I saw a great way of saving water. As soon as it was published in the newspapers, I was invited by a foreign country to run this as a project in that country. However, after being invited to use the same method in Iran, I refused to go to the foreign country and run the project abroad. But there was not one step from relevant authorities in Iran and nothing happened.

What is your main paradigm?

Chaotic!

➤ Interview with Mr. R. A CEO of a Medical Company

Do Iranian entrepreneurs behave as Taleb would recommend? And can it help them survive?

Entrepreneurship development in Iran requires more government support, revision of banking laws and regulations, labour and trade laws, cuts to the inadequate administrative bureaucracy in public organizations and reform of public institutions that are entrusted with issuing...licenses for entrepreneurs and owners of small and medium businesses. Unfortunately, the government does not provide strong-enough support for projects that have...taken commercialization steps that fit domestic needs.

For example, in the same device, in the justification plan, the most important competitive advantage over the imported samples is saving in water and energy, and in correspondence with the Ministry of Energy.

What are your suggestions to the government...?

One of our suggestions for the government was that the universities and dental centres that our customers are aware of should be supported in commercializing patents in the domestic Iranian market. Creating an insurance fund for entrepreneurs to reduce their concerns about capital loss is a positive step that could be taken to develop entrepreneurship in the country.

At present, tax exemptions, lending at 4% interest and provision of facilities are on the government's agenda. There is a facility that can be used for *Innovation and Welfare* companies that are able to register themselves as 'knowledge bases' to reduce the taxes.

What is your paradigm?

Chaotic, as you have described it.

➤ **Interview with Dr. N. R Managing Director of Hotel E**

How do you see the possibility of developing long-term and profitable strategies in the Hotel and Tourism industries?

The tourism industry is delicate, complex, sensitive and completely dependent on the stability, security and social, political and economic needs. Most importantly, it requires national representatives speaking in the international arena...in every sentence, in their own words, to address the interests of the private sector and investors in this field. To observe. Obviously, the industry

needs the security of tourists guaranteed when entering...cultural, natural and human-interest tourist attractions.

In recent decades, major tourism destinations are emerging in developing countries. Unfortunately, these countries are facing two major issues: lack of necessary infrastructures for tourism development and destructive unsustainable agricultural activities that lead to the destruction of natural resources which draw tourists to the attraction. Fear of social crisis, unemployment and the image of costly and inefficient ventures are the main reasons for not raising the required capital and technology investment for tourism infrastructures...

It is clear that tourism development requires international capital and... security at the destinations. Could Iran today be a competitive threat to the world's tourism destinations as Dubai? Definitely not Because Dubai is an international ...destination, attracting capital from more than one hundred and thirteen countries, and especially...capital from the world's most powerful countries. The threat to Iran as a tourist destination is, aggressive war-like declarations towards the world.

What limits Iran's hotel and tourist industries in your experience?

There are... limitations that cannot be addressed. The arrival of branded hotels or large investments in this sector cannot be expected. Most of the limits I have

witnessed during my twenty years' experience in tourism and hotel management:

Unavailability of cheap land...free of...construction restrictions by urban municipalities. In the rest of the world, hotels are considered as urban services. Uncertainty over land ownership.

Expensive sites that present construction difficulties...especially in large cities, land which could be considered for more than half of the investor's capital.

The unthinkable profit of the banking facility for the construction of a tourism facility virtually eliminates any tourism project and project inefficient.

The system of hotel rate pricing deters domestic and foreign investors [the main reason is decreasing the Iranian currency power which discourages the investors when considering the exchange rates]

Under-developed project pitching to investors, especially to foreign investors
Scarce information, ...unrealistic statistical data over-claiming the number of domestic trips made.

In which situations are Taleb's recommendations needed?

From my point of view, the unprofessional involvement of practitioners and government officials in the country's tourism industry and of various bureaucratic organizations and in the business of hoteliers. This somehow propagates *their* view that the owners of these businesses need... protective guardianship in order to save...investors' capital.

This response suggests that the respondent had not quite understood the question, and it was probably ambitious to put what is my research question so directly to him. However, it is included because it does show that he did not see government ‘involvement’ as providing protection against crises. It is true meanwhile that Taleb is also critical of governments which allow institutions that are ‘too big to fail’, and that when they do fail they have to be rescued at tremendous costs (increased government debt).

What is your main paradigm?

A kind of mixture of the chaotic and functional paradigms.

- Interview with Dr. Z. H CEO of P.T

What are the possibility of developing short term and long term and strategies based on Taleb’s recommendations?

In the short term, we would like to carry out the spread of Semi-art [the activities which are including arts such as making TV advertisement videos] more extensively in Iran.

We have introduced new areas of activities such as making a short advertisement video, creating a scientific documentary, video, media, news, insurance, etc. We are dynamic and profitable. On the other hand, in long-term, we would like to Perform more cross-border performances [overseas activities] in order to gain international honours and compete with large organizations and ultimately creating credible international holding companies for the next 10

years. We tried to help the emergence of a semi-art education method in Iran by using the blue ocean strategy. [From the authors understanding the interviewee aims to expand their international activities to gain more overseas reputation and income]

How do environmental uncertainties affect Iranian entrepreneurs such as yourself?

The unstable economic situation due to political challenges and disruptions can cause several issues for the entrepreneur...including: the circulation of improperly misleading newsletters by the newcomers to the labour market, which, along with companies' actions, create a false picture of...toxicity among the business community. I mean propaganda that does not respect the principles of trustworthiness and intellectual property.

Anyone who succeeds, naturally, has a work life of both successful and unsuccessful experiences. Experiences like breakdowns in trust, in collaborations with others mean continuing by working alone. To succeed well I have had to have...unsuccessful experiences.

We wish that parliament updates the rules at the same time as changes in the world. There is a lack of legal frameworks in the country and a lack of support for new service work.

...The biggest concern, from time to time, is the difficulty...convincing all my relatives to [trust] and respect my beliefs. We expect the council to consider new supportive packages to promote new collaborations and new entrepreneurs

raising their profile. The government is subject to a lot of conflicts and it would be great if we do not [have to] expect them.

Would you recommend to apply for bank facilities in a chaotic environment?

So far, I have not used any bank facilities and wouldn't recommend anybody do so. Unfortunately, the interest rates in Iran are quite high. Banks are charging massive percentages for lending money which put businesses under severe pressures and risks.

But in a chaotic situation, in which everybody expects uncertainty, return of money will be riskier and hence, it is not practical and reasonable to lend money from banks and financial institutions.

What is your main paradigm?

Chaotic...

- **Interview with Mr. Gh. Z. M CEO of M.M (Sea) Production**

How do you succeed in a chaotic environment?

It is practically impossible to avoid 'black swans' in real business condition particularly in a country like Iran, so I have tried hard to enhance my employee's security when facing unpredictable events.

The main reasons for my success: preparing my main managers to cope with chaotic conditions, working purposefully and with strategy, teamwork, access to good manpower, continuous effort, the perseverance of key stakeholders, empathy and conscientiousness of all employees, developing a good sales team,

obtaining primary resources, establishing good communication, gaining the trust of suppliers and buyers, creating a strong supply chain and the excellent support from the banking system.

How many obstacles have you encountered and what steps have you taken to deal with them?

The most important barriers include the lack of foreign investors and available funds. We managed to resolve the problem by consulting with the relevant banks and authorities.

It was very difficult to get...good human resources at the beginning, but with experience, we were able to get...suppliers and overcome the problem of lack of recognition and trust. We were able to deal with honesty and fulfil our obligations, ourselves.

What were the main risks which you considered to start a new business?

Lack of primary resources, economic instability...with a fifty percent probability of a lack of supply of fresh water.

Investment in deprived areas is fraught with as many negative risks as there are positive chances.

Your 'paradigm'?

Principally it is the chaotic paradigm at our organization.

- **interview with Mr. M.B.S CEO of a Solar Energy Systems company**

Would you please describe us the main issues when developing strategies in chaotic environments?

The first issue is the financing community. Another important problem is the importing system for goods, the system in the country needs to be reformed and supported by domestic producers should stick to a new imports system such as applying for new customer tariff and not engage in smuggled import.

The third problem for entrepreneurs is the country's laws and regulations...We have legislated eleven thousand laws over a hundred and ten years, while in two hundred and fifty years, France has approved only two thousand seven hundred laws. The majority of these laws have hampered business...and steps should be taken to solve this problem.

Other issues in our sector which are often discussed [are] pricing and energy costs, as well as international sanctions.

Our administrative system should be the facilitator of entrepreneurship. The entrepreneur must express innovation and creativity. Entrepreneurship requires taking steps beyond the granting of permissions and licences.

Authorities must take steps in order to form innovation networks in the provinces for the development of entrepreneurship. These networks should lead to new start-ups. We must be responsive at the last years of the resistance

economy, what we have done for entrepreneurs. Rank one-hundred and thirtieth as a country is not a proper place for Iran and Iranian business space by having such a huge resource. Work should be worthy in this blessed country and environment.

The reference here to *networks* as a way of fostering entrepreneurship is interesting as it admits the role of chance and of maximising the probability of happy outcomes. Our reading is also that network development is a route to attaining anti-fragility, because networks can enhance the resilience of network participants.

In such chaotic circumstances as you experience, how would you summarise the main problems?

The main problems can be expressed in two categories:

Financial problems and lack of government support.

Problems related to familiarity with many and sometimes complicated administrative rules at different stages in projects that slow down the process and reduce motivation.

As a country, we direct entrepreneurs to a particular path, while entrepreneurs are really ahead... and, as a rule, we must adapt ourselves to them.

So, it seems like there are two things to be done. One is the issue of setting up new rules and regulations that embrace the entrepreneurial process from the earliest stage of creating ideas to the stage of sales and commercialization of

the idea, the creation of a product or service, then offering it to the market. And one is the question of the removal of disruptive laws. In Iran, we have *more than twelve thousand laws*. ...This multiplicity of laws, which in many cases may be divergent, leads to a lot of energy being used-up by entrepreneurs and a kind of sluggish, deterrent environment for them.

What is your main paradigm?

‘Chaotic.’

- Interview with Mr. F.M Managing director of Start-up company

How does the environmental affect the management strategies of Entrepreneurs like you?

This is a really good and interesting question...I would like to explain it...as follows:

Abandon your current job! If you want to devote yourself to setting up and launching a successful business, it's hardly possible to manage positions at the same time. You may be able to spend little time on ‘the baby’ during the holidays and the end of the night, but know that if you want to grow it properly, you should leave your current job. Leaving your current job position for a long and unpredictable job opportunity may seem a bit scary, especially if you have not had the experience of setting up a business in the past. Unfortunately, there will not be any shortcuts. You just have to...and not reinstall your instinct.

Form a working team This is especially hard if you do not have any setup and leadership experience for a team... Experience shows that selecting an

appropriate team for a startup can be a stressful and hard task. It's not enough to find the best candidates to fill the seats, but you should consider the cost of having such people in the business and the extent of their cultural compatibility with your team. Such monitoring can be very difficult when you are under pressure to fill all your team positions.

Inspiration As the founder of a start-up, you have to have the ability to confront and manage new ideas. When you discover a competitor, it is your responsibility to set up a specific program to deal with this rival. When your team faces impassable barriers, your job requires an alternate program to move forward. Having a creative mindset and lack of business experience may be a bit contradictory. The less experienced you are, the more stressful you will be, the harder you will be spending time on designing an acceptable business plan.

Loneliness This is a much-neglected problem in the field of entrepreneurship, and many new business owners will not be prepared for this challenge until its time is over. Entrepreneurship makes us a little isolated, because it is a personal situation and you do not have colleagues and teammates to rely on entirely. You have to work many hours and you cannot see your family as usual. And your employees are somewhat distant from you.

How would you describe financial issues for entrepreneurs in an environment full of unforeseen events?

In an area and environment full of chaos, it is always a problem to find the foreign investors as they are not sure about the security of their investments.

Experienced entrepreneurs know that it's not easy to set up a new business financially, and they...have several advantages over newcomers to this field. They may have a stake in the profits from their previous business sales and can use this backing to set up their new business.

Even if they have failed in their first business, they have good connections with investors and customers who will help them in their next investment. As a new entrepreneur, you have to start working as if you are thirsty for any new communication and networking in your area of work, and you have to think about all the imaginable options for setting up your business before you start doing anything.

How do you face unknowns in business?

It is a very interesting question and I would like to point out that usually, every entrepreneur asks himself the questions such as:

How long will my business last?

How profitable will it be?

Do customers like our products?

Will we be able to have a consistent financial path?

None of these questions will have straightforward solution, even in start-ups with an excellent idea and the availability of all the resources needed to develop this idea. The existence of unknown factors in the business path means that your viability will fluctuate, and many of your long-term plans will be lose relevance over time, with new advances and innovations. Coping with this volatility is one of the most difficult aspects of entrepreneurship for a novice entrepreneur.

What is your main paradigm?

I would say... 'chaotic'.

- **Interview with Mr. H. S Managing director, Medical Tools Production**

How would you describe the financial issues affecting management strategies in your business?

In industries like medical equipment, it's not only about raising funds. We also expect the government to spend the same amount consistently to guarantee the purchase of our products. When the product is made and the customer is not buying, the producer is in debt to large creditors and this is a defective downwards cycle. Companies can somehow think their market share...is healthy, only to be undermined by imports and smuggled imports. Imports in most industrial sectors have bent the manufacturer's back.

We are new and less knowledgeable...so we will be more vulnerable. And if the imports of these types continue and the government does not stand firm here ...preventing imports and supporting domestic production, there will be nothing but bankruptcy of the for-profit and knowledge-based companies.

Can you give an example of the main problems that chaos presents?

The administrative bureaucracy in our country causes entrepreneurs...major problems. I'll give you an example. At the Farsi, Medical Science Fair hosted by the University of Medical Sciences, the sparkle of hope for all exhibitors was highlighted by the authorities' attention to their products, and they all believed that after the end of the exhibition, through agreements with large companies or organizations they would be buying medical equipment ...

But after the end of the exhibition, part of the agreements was completely ignored by the officials, and the other part had not yet left the secretariat, being delayed awaiting signatures and approval by other branches.

Although...festivals and exhibitions appear to be the place for marketing, unfortunately...communication between buyers and the sellers does not come to fruition...

The next challenge is the military elite, which takes as much time as...soldiers take, all because of the various stamps and signatures, and going from this building to the next building. According to the famous saying, 'wear iron shoes'. [which means being consistent and robust in facing bureaucrat systems and follow up to finalise something].

How does the environment...affect management strategies in Iranian medical entities?

The growth rate of entrepreneurship in each country is a symbol of its credibility, and it is more about the economic credibility of countries depending on the number of entrepreneurs and the innovators of that community, and of course, much of this growth goes back to the ones that laws can create.

From this angle, I know the tax laws, social security laws, municipal laws and customs regulations as a serious obstacle to entrepreneurs, and the administrative bureaucracy and the numerous signatures that must be taken to

obtain authorization from various organs are pits and wells in the way of the producer and of the entrepreneur. ... In my opinion, state laws and regulations do not encourage entrepreneurship in Iran.

Of course, the challenges are not merely a matter of law. One of the problems in the field of medical equipment is smuggling and imports, as well as the harsh and strict conditions ...imposed on producers at their time of registration.... Where is the company? How many meters? How many manpower employed? and many types of things that really do not qualify as relevant to...production. However, Merchants and importers enter the field without any impediments, without any of the ties that are in the way of the manufacturer.

Nevertheless, the capacity of the Iranian market in the field of medical equipment is great. The domestic customer is assured that when the goods pass the standardization process when Iran or foreign products are level on quality, it is possible that the Iranian goods are better in terms of after-sales service. ...So we can hope that this market will help to grow our business in this area.

What is your main paradigm?

Mostly chaotic but *sometimes* functional.

- **Interview with Founder of Op. Co Mr. N.Gh,**

From your point of view, as Iran faces many unpredictable events, how might it become an entrepreneurial powerhouse?

Key features of Iran's economy have been obscured, however, its upward movement hasn't. The four hundred billion economy which is the second biggest in the Middle East, is required to create around seven percent growth a year from now, according to the World Bank.

Considering what happens on the off-chance that you coordinate that sort of financial development with a college framework that produces 233,000 researchers and designers a year, in a domain associated with the greater part of the world's economy oil... this could mean thousands of start-ups and independent companies - if nothing acts as a burden.

According to the statistics, every year around two hundred and thirty-three thousand students are graduated from all universities in Iran including engineers, doctors, lawyers' accountants, scientist etc. By matching this number of graduates to the economic growth, you can easily see an economy which has the ability to produce thousands of start-ups and other small businesses.

What are the main steps which should be taken in this chaotic environment?

The most essential thing which is required in a chaotic area and environment is the talented mentorship, leadership and the learning.

During the last three years, more than two-hundred start-up companies have been established in Iran and this can...accelerate. However, there are some hurdles facing businesses in Iran environment. Entrepreneurs in Iran which is considered as an unstable area and environment, due to the strategic location of

this country within the Middle East, always have to be prepared for unforeseen events.

In addition, whether businesses are successful or not, is always depending on governmental policies that either...support their ideas and businesses or not. Policy towards small business is of even more concern than geopolitical turmoil and there could be growth.

What is your main paradigm?

Our company experience is of 'chaos'.

- **Interview with M.R Professor of Entrepreneur at University**

Do Iranian entrepreneurs behave as Taleb would recommend and therefore, survive?

Some Iranian entrepreneurs consider that the role of small firms and the entrepreneurial process is complicated and that stimulating the country's economic growth involves many various intermediary variables all playing different roles.

Of course, at the outset, it should be noted that the purpose of entrepreneurship here is not just job creation; what in our country is mistakenly taken from the concept of entrepreneurship...often confuses the concept of ordinary business and how entrepreneurship... brings creative destruction through innovations and new technologies. There are a number of jobs, like many new technology-driven distribution companies that deviate from the traditional model. Considering this, we must admit that our country has not made any significant

progress, despite all the efforts that have been made to expand entrepreneurship over the last few years, from the formation of institutions and associations to the inclusion of entrepreneurship in educational curricula in schools and universities. Of course, it cannot be ruled out and these efforts are totally ineffective, but the fact is that...progress...in these areas is fast enough. The small steps we take, are not noticeable by international institutions.

How do unquantifiable uncertainties affect entrepreneurs' management strategies?

Three factors are...the main environmental barriers across different business fields and entrepreneurship in the country:

Institutionalization in the field of entrepreneurship - what has happened so far has been to create more infrastructures in the area of governance. For example, in the year 2006, the government applied the rule that all ministries and organizations...have an entrepreneurial office under the highest authority of that institution. This helped me to get upgraded to a deputy, and eventually, an Entrepreneurship and Employment Vice President was set up across all fields... But this policy failed, and practically-speaking a large proportion of ministries and organizations did not do this. After this, mostly through workgroups, commissions, and committees that advised the government itself, it attempted to compensate for this institutional vacuum in entrepreneurship, and became more process-oriented. That is, there were good debates in these meetings, there were good laws, but the outcomes...had no output.

Often, the programs that are developed by governing bodies for the development of employment are not entrepreneurial, dedicated to entrepreneurship... The problem of employment *is* a serious problem, and almost all governments are opposed to...unemployment.... Timely solutions to reduce the unemployment rate and increase resilience are welcome. But an entrepreneurial approach is [something else], hence the low response. The third point, then, is that we do not show leadership in the field of entrepreneurship. It has been said many times that in our country entrepreneurship is an orphan.

What is your main paradigm?

‘Chaotic’ and ‘functional’.

- **Interview with Mr. N. former senior advisor to the *World Bank***

How do uncertainties which cannot be forecast affect the management strategies of Iran entrepreneurs?

The chaotic economic condition due to political challenges and disruptions can cause several troubles for an entrepreneur. Most companies were highly affected by various sanctions from the United States and its allies during the past ten years. Secondly, Iran has faced various management disruptions due to the short-term view and sudden decision-making by senior government strategists.

Nevertheless, Iran *is* currently producing fast-growing companies....

Could you be specific about what could attract entrepreneurs to invest in Iran, based on your experience?

Iran has a population of nearly eighty million, with unbeatable manufacturing capacity unchallenged within the Middle East. Ten percent of the Gross Domestic Product belongs to Oil and Gas.

For many past years, sanctions from the US have remained in place, however, companies based in Europe and Asia *are* pouring investments into Iran. The population is highly educated and there is a good potential for Iran to grow fast. However, there are some unforeseen events.

Around seven and a half million of Iran's population have higher education qualifications...as large as Jordan. The country is considered a power in tech fields. If it was not for US sanctions, US entrepreneurs would be happy to establish long-term business relationships between US and Iranian companies. It has to be taken into account that the other countries cannot command? Iranian, so entrepreneurs have to consider that in order to establish a business they have to keep communications open.

Are there any restrictions for new entrant entrepreneurs?

One of the restrictions for entrepreneurs is the visa process as it makes it difficult for all groups, Iranian, American, European, to apply for visa and travel to expand their business relationships. The country's infrastructure is undergoing a renewal and change is happening faster than people expect. A U.S.A based venture investor stated that the entrepreneurial revolution remaking the Middle East told the story of his two visits to Iran. He said that on his first trip to Iran, there was very little access to 3G and 4g. He said that people told me it's coming, while the oligarchs said 'No way, it won't happen'.

But a year later, when he came back there were twenty million subscribers. One of the hallmarks of an entrepreneurial economy is a pace of change...that...increases over time. In the United States, many industries have already been disrupted by technology: entrepreneurs come up with ideas and hope they find a market or a problem. In Iran, young entrepreneurs are facing real issues, whether it's pollution or climate change or socio-political change.

What is your main paradigm?

‘Chaos’ is what our organization deals with.

- **Interview with the Managing Director of an Iranian start-up company.**

Please describe to us the main issues which you have in e-business and how you solve problems as an entrepreneur?

In my opinion, there are no big and unsurmountable problems for e-businesses in Iran. However, some people believe that e-business survival is barely possible...due to the lack of infrastructure and of an internet shopping culture.

I disagree with this. Of course, there are challenges and problems that may or may not be present in more developed countries. For example, problems with ...the e-commerce infrastructure from distribution systems to enough high bandwidth and internet speed for ordinary consumers, lack of specific laws and trust in this area and, most importantly, non-transparent economic space.

About two years ago, a venture capital investor invested in the company, the results were very good, indeed excellent. *The Economist* recently estimated the value of the company at one-hundred and fifty million US dollars. I have been working an average of thirteen to fourteen hours a day since the company's establishment and I believe that if anyone now decides to start a start-up company or business, they must work for eighteen hours a day for the first couple of years in order to achieve the good results.

What steps have you taken to succeed as an entrepreneur in a chaotic environment?

The first step was to design a digital business model and develop it according to the country and the audience. At first, we began to produce rich and useful content in Persian, which attracted more visitors to the site. The high number of visitors was a great achievement due to this rich content, and then the reliable digital platform. It was a great achievement and made us a successful brand.

Why does your company not import certain products like Apple itself to cut down intermediaries?

Distribution and retailers throughout the world have a number of distinct structures. A change to structures and in an unstable environment, will disturb the distribution system. We prefer to get closer and stronger to our brands suppliers? and distributors and to be in the distribution system as a large online retailer. Nowadays an online retailer is a knowledgeable company and does not concentrate on mere trading activities like importing goods. Our focus is on online retailing, effective communication with customers as well as winning!

What is your main paradigm?

Our company lives with [the] chaotic.

14. Interview with Mr. S. Gh head of P Co.

As an entrepreneur who created several jobs, how do you describe the possibility of developing long-term job-creation plans and profitable strategies?

...In the economic literature, the entrepreneur is someone who undertakes to organize, manage and accept the dangers of an economic activity. Therefore, in addition to...managing and organizing the economic unit, he also accepts risk, hence he needs support. Under these conditions, the state can play its role as a compliment. This would remove the inhibitors facing the entrepreneurs.

Employment and production have a two-way relationship....That is, the production process involves a workforce proportional to productive activity, on the other hand, creating income and employment as one of the outputs of productive economic activity. ...Employment is both a production factor and one of the outputs of...production. ...Currently, the country's producers face many problems and obstacles ...and it isn't appropriate to enter the economic space and start a business.

This response was rather general, though how did make a case for risk sharing between government and entrepreneurs. So, we asked:

How do you cope with law changes from the government's side?

After several years of communicating the general policies of Article 44² of the constitution and the adoption of the law on how these policies should be implemented, the government's main objectives are still to compete and reduce ...monopolies and increase the power of the private sector, tries to expand the cooperative sector and assign the public sector to the nongovernmental sector.

The desired outcomes have had not been reached and conditions...make ...entry into the economy difficult. Also, manufacturing activities need to be licensed in a variety of ways, and this has put obstacles in the way of manufacturing activities.

Another issue that has encountered entrepreneurship in the country is labour laws. There have always been problems between the triangle, the worker, the employer, and the labour laws, and they provide a space that none of them are satisfied with currently. Workers are always dissatisfied with the level of salaries, wages and benefits. On the other hand, the employer has always been protesting about cumbersome laws, and policymakers face complicated situations due to this situation. In any case, the current situation indicates that labour laws are not flexible enough and these regulations only...favour...those who have jobs and can...make it even harder for the unemployed to get a job. That is why, in countries where unemployment is high and young people in need of work are in difficulty, labour laws are usually more flexible. Over the

² The ARTICLE 44 of Islamic republic of Iran constitution was confirmed and announced by the Irian parliament that forces the government to sell the governmental entities to the private section. This decision will lead to decrease the centralized economical governmental power and enhance the management systems and profitability of the companies which were allocated to the private investors.

past few years, with the facilitation and possible use of various types of contracts, this situation has been somewhat improved, but flexibility should be facilitated only to the extent that it does not lead to exploitation of the workforce.

What is your main paradigm?

I would like to say that the main circumstances we experience are chaotic.

15. Interview with Mr. M. J Chairman of F T H Co.

As usual I paraphrased Taleb's notion of 'Black Swan Events' and then asked:

Do you think businesses in Iran face many Black Swans?

As there are some external factors that affect Iran's economical and political situation it could be argued that all Iran is currently facing Black Swan events. After the election of Mr. Trump as the USA president, the USA put more pressure on the *Iran Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action* (JCPOA). Accordingly, most investments and businesses were affected.

Do Iranian entrepreneurs behave as Taleb would recommend? And therefore, survive?

In a chaotic environment, such as the Middle East, it is hard to make the correct decision. This is because of the fact that every movement in the area could affect Oil and Gas prices which could then affect all industrialised countries, particularly western countries and hence, doing business could be very hard and difficult to predict. Therefore, it's quite important to have a crisis management plan. This is basic leadership which has to be done by businesses to enable any association to manage a sudden and noteworthy negative event. It ought to rotate around limiting the negative effect that an unfavourable surprise will

have on the organization should it happen. I mean a considerable amount of focus should be on emergency administration.

Let me summarize the responsibilities of a businessman from my own point of view based on my studies and experience: Risk Management, Data Management, Claims Management, Enterprise Risk Management... Involvement of all the C-suite leadership - Financial, Legal, HR, Logistics, Operations, Strategy, Marketing and stakeholders...that can contribute to solution development, including tactical action steps.

Getting ready for Black Swans is the overwhelming endeavour for any organization to attempt.

What is your main paradigm?

Here...our organization is a mixture of the chaotic and functional

4.4 Summary, Comments and Interview Analysis

Table. Summary of Senior Petrochemical Managers' and Surviving Iranian Entrepreneurs' responses to questioning over Black Swans and Paradigms.

<i>Senior Petrochemical Managers</i>	<i>Believe in Black Swans?</i>	<i>Which Paradigm?</i>
<i>1</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Functional</i>
<i>2</i>	<i>50%</i>	<i>Mixture Chaotic and Functional</i>
<i>3</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Functional</i>
<i>4</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Functional and Self Chaotic</i>
<i>5</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Functional</i>
<i>6</i>	<i>50%</i>	<i>Mixture Chaotic and Functional</i>
<i>7</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Functional</i>
<i>8</i>	<i>50%</i>	<i>Mixture Chaotic and Functional</i>
<i>9</i>	<i>50%</i>	<i>Mixture Chaotic and Functional</i>
<i>10</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Functional</i>
<i>11</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Functional</i>
<i>12</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Functional</i>
<i>13</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Functional</i>
<i>14</i>	<i>50%</i>	<i>Mixture Chaotic and Functional</i>
<i>15</i>	<i>No</i>	<i>Functional</i>
<i>Surviving Iranian Entrepreneurs</i>		
<i>1</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Chaotic</i>
<i>2</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Chaotic</i>
<i>3</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Chaotic</i>
<i>4</i>	<i>50%</i>	<i>Mixture Chaotic and Functional</i>
<i>5</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Chaotic</i>
<i>6</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Chaotic</i>
<i>7</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Chaotic</i>
<i>8</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Chaotic</i>
<i>9</i>	<i>50%</i>	<i>Mixture Chaotic and Functional</i>
<i>10</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Chaotic</i>
<i>11</i>	<i>50%</i>	<i>Mixture Chaotic and Functional</i>
<i>12</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Chaotic</i>
<i>13</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Chaotic</i>
<i>14</i>	<i>Yes</i>	<i>Chaotic</i>
<i>15</i>	<i>50%</i>	<i>Mixture Chaotic and Functional</i>

While the differences between the two samples are not absolute, the overall pattern shows significant differences in sensitivity to Black Swans and different responses to the Paradigms question which are difficult or very difficult to explain by as random chance differences.

Thus:

- No Petrochemical Manager saw the world as only Chaotic
- No Entrepreneur saw the world as only Functional
- No Entrepreneur denied the existence of Black Swans
- No Petrochemical Manager had no faith in the value of Long-Term Planning

Six of the fifteen Petrochemical Managers saw the world a Chaotic and Functional in different respects, but only four of the fifteen Entrepreneurs saw the world as Chaotic and Functional in different respects.

The differences between the ‘observed data’ and what would be the ‘random expected data’ (of ‘no differences’) are great. Though these data were extracted from qualitative research, they enable us to reject the null-hypothesis of no differences between Senior Petrochemical Managers and Entrepreneurs. While the interviews contain much richer evidence than the Table can show, the Table enables us to accept the central hypothesis of the thesis. Iranian Entrepreneurs are quite unlike Iranian Senior Manager.

- The practice differences between the two samples are difficult to tabulate, however Entrepreneurs’ preferences for
 - a) Deferring decisions
 - b) Willingness to suspend or shut-down doomed projects
 - c) Unwillingness to make decisions according to a pre-existing long term plan
 - d) Extreme short-term vigilance
 - e) Surviving rather than profit-maximising, managing or competing intensively are clear from the interview evidence.

In comparison, Senior Petrochemical Managers belief in

- f) Long term planning and decisions

- g) Staying with a project or employer for longer
- h) Relatively higher confidence in their own survival
- i) Obedience to hierarchy

is quite clear from the interviews.

Items 6) f) g) h) i) can be explained partly by the fact that the Managers were employees in mostly large organisations rather being completely responsible for their own fate. Nevertheless, our policy recommendations described later are that even large enterprises in the petrochemical sector should consider displacing planning with anti-fragility.

Because the research was done in order to test a definite hypothesis the author did not use qualitative data analysis techniques such as NVivo. NVivo is used in order to find emergent ‘themes’ within text. As NVivo states, it is designed to ‘identify themes and draw clear conclusions...uncover deeper insights [and] find patterns and connections that aren’t possible manually’ (<https://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo-qualitative-data-analysis-software/home>). NVivo analyses data ‘bottom upwards’ in an empiricist way. It is ideal for constructing theory out of evidence. However, our research did not begin with data and it did not use ‘open coding’. Instead it began with a theory and hypotheses based on it. For this reason, Nvivo would not have served our needs.

It is possible that other researchers *could* have analysed what our respondents said using NVivo and they *might* have discovered fresh themes which are not explored in the thesis. However, it is emphasised that this would not have suited the research questions author already had. In other words, author knew from early on what he was looking for (significant non-random differences between the two samples) for which he had already got a fairly well-developed coding framework. When it came to analysing the interview evidence our coding framework was refined, but author did not find any responses which could not be fitted in to the overarching ‘chaos/ black swans expected’ or ‘functionalist’ pairing. (In any case, the

sensitivity of what respondents told us meant that it would have been unethical to allow access to it by other researchers.)

NVivo does not begin with counter-factuals either. In principle for our hypotheses there were two clear 'counter-factuals': a) successful surviving Iranian entrepreneurs who were managerial/ functionalist in their approach and b) senior Iranian petrochemical managers who had strategies which could be defined as 'anti-fragile'. It is imaginable that it could also have found c) no significant differences between the two samples. These three possibilities were not found and so the null-hypothesis could be rejected. NVivo would have been of little help with research designed the way this has be done.

A more complete analysis will be found in the next chapter.

Chapter 5

Analysis and Discussion

5.1 Introduction

The interviewees addressed were drawn from two main samples: Entrepreneurs and Senior Managers/Chief Officers/Administrators of Petrochemical companies.

One of the essential elements that has been considered about the interviewees was having adequate direct experience of Iran's economic and political environment over the years, which promotes the capability of gathering credible and relevant data from the interviewees. It did help to be an 'insider'.

In terms of educational background the author tried to find the respondents who were well educated to ensure that they had a better understanding of issues and capable of making and expressing reasoned interpretations of national and firm-specific strategic plans as well as describe black swans in their industries. However, some of the entrepreneurs especially have implicit tacit knowledge about management and black swans without having educational background, being 'self-made'.

The responses addressed the central concerns of this study and have grown in confidence that the responses offered by those interviewed are consistent with the hypothesised synchronic differences which is expected.

Entrepreneurship studies are included within in Iranian higher education and it was important to have an extended discussion with an academic who both knows the literature *and* knows Iran. One of the interviewees chosen was therefore a university professor, who teaches 'entrepreneurship'. He considered that Iran was still struggling to establish 'a stable business environment'. He agreed strongly that Iran is very vulnerable to black swan events. After introductions and brief explanations of what our research was concerned with, the professor was clear: Iranian entrepreneurs typically do not behave as Taleb recommended. However, in saying this, he makes the common distinction between doing ordinary business and entrepreneurship, specifically:

At the outset, it should be noted that the purpose of entrepreneurship here is not just job creation; what in our country is mistakenly taken for the concept of entrepreneurship is *any* kind of business while the concept of... *entrepreneurship* is creative and destructive innovation and technologies. There are a number of jobs, like many new technology-driven shipping companies that gradually drop out of the established way of doing things. In this sense, it must admit that our country has not made any significant progress, despite all the efforts that have been made to expand entrepreneurship over the last few years, from the formation of institutions and associations to the inclusion of entrepreneurship in the educational curricula in schools and universities. Of course, [disruptive innovation] cannot be ruled out and these efforts are not totally ineffective, but the fact is that the progress of some countries in [entrepreneurship] is faster, while the small steps we take, do not compare favorably with foreign institutions. We do not see much genuine entrepreneurship in Iran.

What this narrow definition of entrepreneurship-as-disruptive leaves out are the many Iranian businesses that persist with risk-taking without destroying, transforming or re-constructing the sector they are in. While the professor's definition can be applied, it is probably too strong and restrictive to include most of the entrepreneurs introduced to the reader above. However, it is interesting that the professor did not excuse business failures as being due to Iran's troubles nor in particular to international sanctions.

Unfortunately, this respondent did not comment more specifically on anti-fragility as a way of having more flexibility to cope with unforeseen and unforeseeable situations as a way of avoiding harm, minimizing the effects of negative black swans and grasping the positive possibilities associated with at least some black swan events. It is also judged that the academic distinction between 'business' and 'entrepreneurship' does not side-step the important and effective real geopolitical and strategic position that Iran occupies in the Middle East. Partly

by an accident of geography and mineral riches, Iran remains one of the world's main 'crossroads', with a huge potential near- and international market of approximately five hundred million people. The proposition that Iranian institutions have only a small contribution to make to market expansion may be premature when the contribution made by semi-state actors, such as MITI in Japan and different varieties of 'corporatism' in South Korea, Singapore and Scandinavia, is recognised (Royo, 2002). While the professor seemed to have American tech companies in mind when he talked about disruptive innovation, it is sensed that state and federal institutions mean that in the USA entrepreneurs have to face significantly fewer negative black swans than typical Iranian businesses do.

From the authors point of view entrepreneurs (defined broadly and not *narrowly* as only the 'disruptive') and managers, can hardly ignore tightening international sanctions, but they can rely more on negotiations and partnership arrangements with other private and public entities as a way of reducing risk and increasing the range of possibilities by becoming more robust and anti-fragile in an intensifying chaotic situation. Their daily lives are 'disrupted' enough. In other words, the professor's preferred analytical distinction between 'business' and 'entrepreneurship' talks past Iran as it can be found today. His plea that Iranian businesses should behave in more disruptive ways than they do at present, it can be felt, with respect, misses the point.

It is not as if Iran needs more disruption than Iranians are experiencing now, in order to succeed tomorrow. The methodological implication which follows for this author is that it may be more productive to compare senior managers (who you might call *bureaucrats* or *technocrats*) with 'entrepreneurs' defined as 'persons doing business on their own accounts', as author has been doing. It is considered this more realistic and researchable than looking only for Iran's next Bill Gates or Mark Zuckerberg.

5.2 The adoption of Taleb Theories in Iran

Our position is that practicing, surviving entrepreneurs in Iran can benefit from adopting Taleb's recommendations concerning anti-fragility and black-swan readiness, and that those who do survive conform, probably unknowingly, with Taleb's principles. Our reading of most of what most of our 'ordinary' entrepreneurs say they do to survive and even prosper in what is by international standards the most extreme business chaos – especially when their comments are compared with what managers say – is that they survive by focussing on *avoiding failure rather than changing the world*. They do keep looking for ways to exploit emerging opportunities (before these opportunities vanish) and remain ready to abandon projects which are big enough to destroy all their businesses if they were to fail.

It is noted that their timescales tend to be very short (hours and weeks rather than months and years) for both opportunities and threats, however 'corporatist' institutions (government/ private associations) may have some capacity for looking for fresh ways of benefiting from the chaotic Iranian situation. It has argued that innovation in high value-added polymers is probably the most promising strategy that could be applied at the national scale. Indeed, due to the tightest possible sanctions that Iran is experiencing that are only just a short step away from an outright declaration of war by a foreign power, a national 'agency for positive black swans' may be the only realistic possibility as far as institutional developments are concerned.

It is not thought this can be thought of as a 'planning agency' because as Lindblom argued so strongly many decades ago, no institution has the computational power to judge all the possible effects of every possible policy by a 'root and branch method'. Actors however big or small they are need to be places of unrealistic hopes and highly realistic fears, seizing possibilities and doing what they can to minimise catastrophes. In principle, our thesis has the long term aim of promoting a) pragmatic and very cautious and even anxious defence measures against

disasters (by minimising how far their negative effects spread) and b) agile grasping of quite improbable but beneficial possibilities. This involves not classical planning or planning in most or all of the alternative and complex, strong and weak forms reported by the literature (above) but managing in a way that is more mindful of futures which have a 'scope' that is difficult to establish beyond some very basic continuities.

Iran *has* oil. Iran *could* diversify into downstream research and development of oil and gas-based polymers and hybrid materials with a wide range of physical properties and applications. Iran *has* a car industry in which an electric future can be envisaged. High-strength and lightweight composite materials *could* have an important part to play in this industry... and so on.) It is urged the development of positions (institutions, networks) capable of taking advantage of positive black swan events on a larger scale in a business environment that will remain full of uncertainty. The minimization of uncertainty is not urged, although the pragmatic minimization of risk remains part of the recommendation.

It makes sense to look to surviving entrepreneurs for the skills that are needed for developing strategies that are more responsive to chaotic uncertainties.

As the entrepreneur, my experience has been that the unpredictability of Iran's political and economic situation makes it a prime environment in which entrepreneurs and managers might make prompt decisions to *seize* opportunistic projects when these are possible while *deferring* decisions when any project is faced by dangerous black swans. One has to sense the right time to defer projects and in my experience, deferring is much more common than stopping a project altogether. Travellers in Iran will be able to see many deferred projects along the roadside. Although not part of my method, it is proposed in all seriousness that roads could be sampled and deferred projects counted per kilometre. From this and the known distance of roads of a similar type, a national estimate could be produced for urban, suburban

and rural areas. Where projects show obvious decay, they could be classed as abandoned. But from our observations while travelling extensively in Iran, these are a minority.

In reflective fashion and with the benefit of working in Iranian, I have been able to state my practices concisely and explicitly. What is noticeable to myself is how long it takes to turn our own 'tacit knowledge' into explicit (conscious) knowledge. The following case descriptions are much more detailed and specific than most of the interviews reported above. It can be inferred from what follows that all our respondents know considerably more than they realise, as well as being instinctively private (for reasons which are discussed later):

I have a part-completed project factory in aviculture industry in a prime location in Iran. I am hesitating before deciding on the mix of uses and the type of client-market to attract, watching changes in local, national and international circumstances on a weekly and monthly basis, and delaying each decision as long as possible with least consequence for each subsequent decision I must make on the project. I have only one area of activity that inhabits what Taleb would recognize as 'Mediocristan' (in which risks and opportunities are anything like 'normally distributed'). But even here (the manufacture of polymer components) surprising opportunities and risks are quite common.

I hesitate for years if necessary but can also act very quickly. I am engaged in a permanent daily conversation with myself and others, rehearsing what I know but also what I realize that don't know and cannot know. It has been said that managerial work is mostly conversations (Mintzberg, 1999) and this is true, in the sense that what I do more than anything is have imaginary conversations for hours at a time on different topics. These conversations do not run in straight lines and are often inconsistent with each other when one week is compared with the next. This permanently unsettled method of working in which doubts out-number hopes, can be viewed as highly

inefficient considered from a 'project management' point of view. It is a textbook case of how not to manage a project in a stable environment. But efficiency is not the point of my actions. It is survival through frequent use of reverse gears, many path possibilities and as many path change possibilities as I can create.

But when I saw the opportunity to purchase injection molding machines and dies from a German manufacturer, I could see that even though these were not the best pieces of capital equipment in my field, at least I could buy them at a very reduced price and I could see that they would be useful. Some of my competitors thought I was 'mad' as they told me, but there was little or no risk when the possibility of buying the best equipment was non-existent or about to disappear due to tightening international sanctions which in my pessimistic view were already a realistic possibility. Because this type of machinery is now unobtainable, I could 'see' that buying it was not at all risky, or at least I could see that the risks I was exposing myself to were being over-estimated by my competitors and other industry associates known to me. I had the necessary technical expertise to judge that these molding machines and dies were as good or better than what I already had and better than what I (or my competitors) could have purchased in Iran at that time. I also sensed that the necessity for plastic containers, for example, would mean that there would be a continuing market for them. So, in my world, while it is very important to listen to one's own fears, over long periods of time, it is also quite important to see past the very gloomiest 'narrative fallacies' of others and act quickly.

Several hours of interviewing with petrochemical managers and entrepreneurs with the aim of formalising the 'tacit skills of surviving Iranian entrepreneurs', led to the formal realisation that not all businesses can thrive in an unpredictable environment. There follows the example

of the company I established to partner with western countries as a method for safeguarding it from future international (American-led) sanctions against Iran:

In a stable environment, free from the risk of international sanctions and in a growing economy in which Iran's highly educated middle-class female workforce would be seeking employment outside the home, a factory with a trusted German or British brand-partner would be an excellent 'rational choice'. However, I have made many revisions to the specification of this factory, which a long time ago I doubted would ever in aviculture industry food – though it is imaginable that it could. By improving the specification of the steel framing of the building and altering the ground plan it is now also capable of being an engineering shop for producing capital equipment. The authorities have questioned me in a searching way trying to discover why the factory completion has been delayed more than once. When doing so my permissions were put at risk of being cancelled. So, I knew that I would have to explain my 'anti-fragile' thinking to them and how it flows from Taleb's essays. Thankfully they accepted the truthfulness of my reasons and what lies behind them and my permissions have been extended. One day there will be a factory and it will be manufacturing something for which there will be a market. I do not know what or when and fortunately I have the resources to finance deferred decisions, because I did not try to maximise the profits from which my resources have come.

The following observations were also extracted from these and other extended conversations between myself and my colleagues:

Successful Iranian entrepreneurs are not born; they learn particular lessons from chaos without fooling themselves that they are experts. Text-book formulas for success are viewed with suspicion. The 'subject' (in this case myself) has never thought of himself as having special gifts or intelligence. He jokes quite seriously with his team that 'I

really know nothing'. This is my starting point. For example, I really know nothing about designing and building apartments or being a developer yet I am building one which is the result of a series of unfavorable and favorable events which could not have been planned for:

I started to think about building apartments and offices and about how a project could be made to work if unexpected things happened such as COVID-19. I realised that a plot of land was for sale and I wanted to buy it, but it was for far too much. Unexpectedly a better plot of land at a lower price suddenly became available next to the land I had been wanting to buy. This was a positive black swan because straightaway it showed that I was right not to buy the over-priced land. How I got offered the land was also a result of at least two or three other chaotic coincidences.

It could have been offered to others but it so happened that the vendor knew of me and of my reputation for being straightforward to deal with. I did not have permission to build these 'better apartments' on this better site, but because the apartments would have river and mountain views on three sides and mountain views on one side I commissioned an architect and structural engineers. Like many or perhaps all municipalities, the local authority is in competition with other villages to be 'the best'. Again, it had so happened that author had sponsored a local charity event for school children, for no better reason than I like to study and improving schools and so do my family. The event only cost a few hundred dollars and it was a great success enjoyed by many children. This is how I became known to the person who wanted to sell the 'better' land. If I had not put on the charity day it is very unlikely that he would have approached me. It would have been offered to someone else that he knew for whatever reason that he knew them.

Of course, I did *not* do this to gain planning permission and in any case, I had abandoned hope of obtaining the original site because it was over-priced in my view (in other words, I could not afford it). I had *not* expected to be in a position to buy a better site for a lower price next to the original plot which I had considered buying. But we got offered it by someone who was in a hurry to sell and who now knew of my existence. Why he was in a hurry to sell is difficult to know and there may have been many past black swans in the seller's life so it would not be able to know with any confidence why in the end the land came to me. Because it is a better site it is a positive black swan that I did not buy the first site, perhaps by driving a hard bargain or mortgaging my other businesses to buy this land (which I could have done).

The necessary permissions were granted, for what it is believed are very fine modernist apartments (see illustration) after I had also said 'yes' to supporting a local gala event scheduled for a religious day marked on the Iranian calendar. The municipality was very aware of successful galas put on by a neighboring village in a different (rival) municipality and wished to put on an even better event. I agreed again not knowing what the consequences might be, and sometime later the permissions were granted. I emphasize that I had not had to 'bribe' any agency in order to obtain land and permissions, but my inner conversations told me enough: the costs were low and the unknown outcomes might be beneficial. At least some school children and myself would have a successful sports day to look back on... Then positive black swans arrived: better land with better views at a lower price plus permissions.

Recently there has been a setback. The authorities state that sustainability and conservation are important and they are important to me too. In the case of the authority they have decided to use a 'river bed model' of the behavior of the river in front of the apartments as it was flowing more than a hundred years ago. At that time, it was wide

and fast flowing and because of this old survey the authority is stating that I have to move back the apartments so that they are 4.5 meters further back from the river than all the existing apartment developments. The river has declined to a small proportion of its original size and flow due to population increases and water extraction up-stream. It is doubtful that it will ever flow as it did before, but as chaos also affects weather patterns such as heavy rainfall I am not annoyed with the authority for being so cautious.

It is still unclear what their reasoning is exactly and I am trying to find this out to see if the extra 4.5 meters is fixed, but my architect is very angry that a project he 'put two and a half months of his life into' could have to be redesigned into something much more ordinary or 'a block just like any other block' as he calls it.

This requirement to site the apartment block further back from the river is *probably* but not definitely negative black swan - a massive future flood that destroys the apartments would be much worse. It has led to further thoughts about how to realise future earnings through the project. Some apartments could be sold 'Off Plan' before any work has begun. But these prices would be lower than for completed apartments. Many potential buyers could be worried about the chances of a war with the USA which would destroy the market for new buildings immediately. My intention is to sell some apartments Off Plan soon, some after construction has begun, some near completion and some right at the end. What this means is that I get less than I would get by selling only completed apartments, but this is much less risky than 'profit maximizing'. It is an anti-fragile way of doing business because income begins soon on a project that I do not want to become 'too big to fail'.

The worst case I can imagine is that war is declared on Iran just as the apartments are finished and they are all being marketed as built. There may be even worse possibilities which I cannot imagine. But at least apartments for sale are less risky than apartments for rent by skiers. Renting could mean higher yields but also higher costs, such as setting up a rental company and if the snows failed to fall, then the project could be faced with massive overhanging debts which would be hard to finance. I know this much after having a long conversation with three very experienced senior managers who had worked for more than thirty years in the construction business in many countries including France, USA and Switzerland. ‘Uncertainty is the problem *even in Canada!*’ they emphasized.

Therefore, when I say that I know nothing about developing apartments and construction, this was true at the beginning. I also feel that it is still true today, despite the fact that the project is looking likely to be successful - but not as successful as it could have been if *only* positive black swans had happened. I still do not think I know anything about developing apartment blocks *anywhere else* because it is unlikely that anywhere else, even just in Iran, would present the same circumstances. Even in *the same village* the same set of circumstances will probably not occur again.

In other words, a quite successful construction project, a very successful importation of injection molding equipment and PET supply business, an aviculture factory project that has seen many changes of mind and a downtown hotel in Tehran that has seen a similar number of changes made to it, *do not* make me a successful entrepreneur.

The industry specific knowledge I gain has limited value which does not last long and is not 'transferable'. In a chaotic world, it is not safe to suppose that positive experiences mean that the entrepreneur is 'good at' what they seem to be good at and it does not mean that they are ineffective over ventures that have gone very slowly with many backwards steps. The problem is that learning is quite easy but what you learn is not usually relevant to what happens next. Realizing this on reflection now, my next project will almost certainly not be another ski resort apartment block, or another hotel or another factory. Nor would I ever want to claim to be a 'consultant' in any of the industries I have invested in.

I can see that I could be seen as an example of a person who gained a lot from the chaotic situation following the Islamic revolution and the war between Iraq and Iran. Lack of service and accommodation companies meant an opportunity for the author to start a successful business. The author stumbled across the principles of anti-fragile strategies, gaining positive results from the chaos caused by black swan events, by realizing happy chances and especially by minimizing unfortunate mistakes.

The Iranian entrepreneur best known to me and for a long period of more than fifteen years spoke as follows:

From childhood, I had a feeling which encouraged me to do new things. I looked around and had issues that were in almost all respects different from others. I remember about forty or forty-one years ago, when we came to Tehran to meet some relatives, for the first time, I saw an Atari computer and an idea came to my mind that with the use of this device in my village could enable me to make money. As a result, once I returned from Tehran, I rented a machine for a price of 500 Tomans for 48 hours, during that time I allowed children to play with that device and, and during this time I earned 800

Tomans for the 48 hours. I followed the similar way until I purchased an Atari machine, and then I bought another device and I expanded into the supply of computer games. Eventually I established a special store for games and consoles like that. One of my characteristics is ‘planning based on market demand’ or ‘not planning!’ and I had this feature from my childhood. I remember, during the war [with Iraq], I was renting video equipment, playing movies and martial arts films in the countryside, and I had a good income. Next, I created the village cinema.

In a similar way through my childhood ... I used every opportunity to earn an income which I could survive on.

My worst challenges have been some uninvited promises [made] by some officials, which they did not fulfil. They sent entrepreneurs [like me] away to do meaningless actions [that turned out to be futile].

My other bad memory was regarding a great and practical innovation [I devised] in the year 2005, about saving water. As soon as it was published in the newspaper, I was invited by a foreign country to run this project in that country. However, after offering to support me [to introduce] the same method in Iran, I refused to go and run the project abroad. Yet the relevant authorities in Iran took not one step [resulting in a failure].

5.3 Our Practice paradigm is chaotic!

What is interesting about this entrepreneur’s latest, most risky and also successful project which involved drilling through many mineral layers to find an economic concentration of a rare mineral, at considerable depth, is that he insists that he could not have taken this risk unless he was able to treat all the money it cost as something he could afford to lose completely. This fits Taleb’s rule of thumb that eighty percent of investments should be dull, low risk and placed

in ‘mediocristan’, while the rest may be high risk and on the assumption that they could result in complete failure without wider financial damage. However, a note of caution: the contrast Taleb draws with ‘extremistan’ does not fit entirely this ‘rare minerals’ case. In Taleb’s extremistan the cost of the *n*th unit is no more than the cost of the first unit (for example downloadable apps). However, in the rarer minerals case, the extraction of the *n*th kilogramme does add proportionate cost to the project. Minerals are not ‘zero marginal cost’ commodities. Nevertheless, their market prices may vary wildly and ‘super-wildly’.

It is noticeable that a few interviewees say something consistent with this rule-of-them when they state that some of their activity is in the ‘functional’ world while some of it is in the chaotic paradigm.

The next interviewee felt that ‘the growth of entrepreneurship’ was ‘a symbol of the country’s credibility, and that the uncertain regional economic situation and reliability should be taken to the consideration. But at the same time some ‘functional’ corrections in tax, customs, municipal and social security laws could reduce obstacles for entrepreneurs. Reducing ‘unnecessary’ administrative bureaucracy and ‘the numerous pits and wells in the way of the producer and the entrepreneur is recommended’.

During the Interview with Mr. H. S Managing director of Production medical tools he also argued for hybrid (Two-World) institutional arrangements, which once more reminds the author of Taleb’s distinction between the two realms of ‘mediocristan’ and ‘extremistan’:

In industries like medical equipment, it’s not only about raising funds, but also it is expected from the government to spend the same amount to guarantee the purchase of our products instead of [us having to rely on] loans. But, for example, when the government does step in to products such as wheat, [this] ... while this ensures that this product is guaranteed and cheap to buy, by not also paying attention to the market and

the customer, and to surrounding features like ... quality... the result can be that ... customers don't buy and the producer is in debt to large creditors. This is a defective cycle.

Companies can somehow be misled into thinking of their market share and the whole market [as] healthy [while] ...we are faced with a huge amount of imports and smuggling. Imports in most sectors have bent [Iranian] manufacturers' backs.

We are new, 'knowledge-based' company so we will be more vulnerable.

He continued to argue on the one hand 'functionally' for governments to act to reduce risk by imposing import restrictions on medical equipment and acting in a reliable and predictable way to create confidence.

And if the import of this type continues and the government does not stand firm... and support domestic production, there will be nothing but bankruptcy [for] knowledge-based companies.

...Administrative bureaucracy in our country causes entrepreneurs to face major problems. I'll give you an example. At the Farsi, Medical Science Fair hosted by the University of Medical Sciences, the sparkle of hope for all exhibitors was highlighted by the authorities' attention to their products, and they all believed that after the end of the exhibition, through agreements with large companies or organizations buying medical equipment [as a circle] the 'red part' [risk] would be taken out of [the market]. But after the end of the exhibition, part of 'the agreements' was completely ignored by the officials. The other part had not yet left the secretariat. ... Delays with signing and approval by other branches of government followed. Although fairs, markets, festivals, and exhibitions appear to be a place for marketing, unfortunately, in Iran, there isn't consistency... in communication between buyers and the sellers and ... contracts are not drafted adequately.

The next challenge faced by many elites and inventors is the effort and time it takes for them to be exempted from military service. It takes as much time [as it would to serve in the military] ... and all because of the various stamps and signatures [needed], and [time going] from this building to the [next] building, according to the famous saying, 'Wear iron shoes to get this exemption.

He continued:

The growth of entrepreneurship for each country is a symbol of its credibility, and ... and of course, much of this growth goes back to what ... laws can [enable]. From this angle, I know the tax laws, social security laws, municipal laws and customs [are] a serious obstacle to entrepreneurs, the administrative bureaucracy and the numerous signatures that must be taken to obtain authorization ... In my opinion, state laws and regulations do not encourage entrepreneurship in Iran.

But of course, the challenges are not merely a matter of law. One of the problems in the field of medical equipment is smuggling and imports, as well as the harshness [of reporting] that is imposed on producers at the time of registration, such as where is the company? How many people [forms your] manpower, and [even] items that really do not qualify [as relevant] for production. Simultaneously merchants and importers enter this product market without any burdens, without anything as much as a shred of the requirements that are placed in the way of the manufacturer.

Nevertheless, the capacity of the Iranian market in the field of medical equipment is great if the domestic customer is confident that the goods have passed the standardization process ensuring that Iranian equipment reaches a high international

standard of quality. ... Iranian goods could reach the same level of after-sales service
It can work better, so we hope that this market will help us to grow... The type of
'paradigm' we are using is mostly chaotic but sometimes functional when it comes to
[legal frameworks and processes].

Another interviewee argued differently that Iran stands a great chance of thriving *from* the chaos the country faces. He pointed out that despite negative black swans, Iran remains the second largest economy in the Middle East giving it 'depth'. He saw this as the basis for huge potential market opportunities between Iran and its neighbours.

This feature of Iran's economy has been obscured, however, the upward movement hasn't stopped. The \$400 billion economy which is the second biggest in the Middle East could create up to seven percent growth a year from now, according to the World Bank.

Considering everything that can happen on the off chance if you coordinate that sort of financial development with a college framework that produces 233,000 researchers and designers a year, in a domain recently associated with the greater part of the world's economy: the result could be thousands of start-ups and independent companies - if nothing acts as a burden.

According to the statistics, every year around two hundred and thirty-three thousand students graduate from Iranian universities including engineers, doctors, lawyer's accountants and scientist.... By matching that number of graduates with economic growth, you can easily find that the economy has the ability to produce thousands of start-ups and other small businesses.

Here was a vision of Iran as benefiting from many happy coincidences among hundreds of thousands of graduates in a growing economy with incalculable happy coincidences.

Chaotic economic conditions and political uncertainties bring troubles for the entrepreneur. Most companies were highly affected by various sanctions by the United States and its allies during the past ten years. But secondly, we faced various management difficulties due to short-term thinking and sudden decisions by governmental managers [and strategists. Nevertheless, Iran is currently producing fast-growth companies.

Said another:

Manufacturing activities need to be licensed in a variety of ways, and this has put obstacles in the way of manufacturing activities. Another issue that has encountered entrepreneurship in the country is labour laws. There have always been problems between the triangle, the worker, the employer, and the labor laws, and they provide a space that none of them are satisfied with the current situation. Workers are always dissatisfied with the level of salaries and wages and benefits. On the other hand, the employer has always been protesting the cumbersome laws, and policymakers face complicated situations due to this situation. In any case, the current situation indicates that labor laws are not flexible enough and these regulations are only in favor of those who have jobs and can even make it harder to get a job for the unemployed. That is why, in countries where unemployment is high and young people in need of work are in difficulty, labour laws are usually more flexible. Over the past few years, with the facilitation and possible use of various types of contracts, this situation has been somewhat improved, but it should be facilitated to the extent that it does not lead to exploitation of the workforce.

5.4 Government Support on Establishing an Entrepreneurial Environment

Talebian unpredictability is a special threat to the hotel and tourism industry, as our experience in this sector shows. A number of interviewees said much the same:

The tourism industry is delicate, complex, sensitive and completely dependent on the stability, security, social, political and economic and most importantly, it requires official [government announcements] in every sentence and word to addresses the interests of private...investors in this field.

It is clear that tourism development requires international capital and hence, the entry of foreign capital ensures the security of that destination. Can a [third party] country today threaten the world's tourism destinations such as Dubai? Definitely not because Dubai is an established international tourist destination, investing capital from more than 113 countries and especially capital from the world's most powerful countries. [Any] threat to that tourist destination would amount to a declaration of world war.

5.5 External Influences on Management Strategies in Iran

Since Trump's election as the USA President, America has put more pressure on the Iran Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA). Accordingly, it affects all businesses in ways that would be difficult to specify or avoid. Although they did not use our terminology especially, an entrepreneur commented that

In a chaotic environment, such as the Middle East it is hard to make a correct decision. This is because every movement in the region could affect Oil and Gas prices which ... highly affect not just us but Western countries too, making doing business very hard and difficult to predict. Therefore, it's quite important to have a Chaos and Crisis Management Plan as basic to any organization's leadership. This should enable an

association to manage sudden and noteworthy negative events. It ought to rotate around limiting the negative effect that an occasion will have on an organization should it happen. [I mean] emergency administration.

Besides regulations, among other obstacles which entrepreneurs reported facing in Iran are poor infrastructure, especially for e-commerce; being forced to work for long hours to survive and non-transparent economic space:

There are challenges and problems that may or may not be present in more developed countries. For example, problems can be the e-commerce infrastructure from poor availability to [low] bandwidth and internet speeds for ordinary consumers, lack of specific laws and regulators in this area and, most importantly, non-transparent economic space. About two years ago, a venture capital investor invested in the company, the results were very good or excellent. The Economist [journal] recently estimated the value of the company at \$150 million. I have been working an average of 13 to 14 hours a day since the company was established and I believe that if anyone now decides to start a start-up company or business, they must work for 18 hours a day for the first couple of years in order to achieve the good results.

5.6 Major Issues Iran Faces in Petrochemical Industry

The fast-changing technology in the petrochemical industry and more focus on the development of basic material were offered as main issues facing the petrochemical industry, however my respondents seemed to disagree whether technical change was too fast or too slow as they also recognised that international sanctions will continue to hold back the adoption of new technologies from the advanced countries. One respondent clarified what this might mean:

Fast speed of development in petrochemical industries, [but] too much attention to developing [low value-added] basic materials...is the most challengeable aspects in this area.

Another issue noted was the fact that producers struggle to meet the market demand for petrochemical products. Mr B stated that the petrochemical industry struggled to ‘produce and distribute more than 30 Million tons’ of products into domestic and foreign markets’ and that attaining ‘71 percent of [nominal] capacity in petrochemicals’ had itself represented a ‘growth of 108 percent [output] compared to last year’.

When invited to consider what, a strategy based on Taleb’s theories might look like, a petrochemical managing directors believed that those who have been in the petrochemical industry for some time do stand a good chance of realising profitable plans. It has been found that this response interesting as it shows continuing faith in planning and some difficulty in assimilating Taleb’s view that surprises are as unavoidable as they are unpredictable. According to one of the other interviewees Iran should engage in promoting policies that ease the entry and operationalization of high value-added petrochemicals production in Iran:

The readiness of the country’s petrochemical industry to exploit post-war opportunities [meaning the costly war with Iraq] and favourable prospects for investment and growth is for those who have license, the investors and the technology owners of the industry.

They have been a very active presence over the past year with calls for long-term cooperation in this industry. [Iran’s oil and gas fields mean] that petrochemical industries in Iran are economically viable compared with the same industries in the developed and industrialized countries of the world. In petrochemicals, at least 50 percent of the cost is related to ‘integrated feed’. Now, if a petrochemical product in

Iran is to be selected for food, the price of which without subsidies and discounts is significantly lower than that of the industrialized countries, it is undoubtedly economically feasible to produce it in Iran.

5.7 Iran Petrochemical Industry and Global Interactions

However, the senior managers acknowledged that political instability, the threat of war, currency fluctuations and volatile commodity prices due to sanctions interacted in unpredictable ways to cause great uncertainties in the Iranian petrochemical industry: All combined to produce an environment rich in black swans:

Political difficulties in cooperating with other countries, [those countries'] foreign policies, ...sanctions, internal political disputes and factions of political will [and] political insecurity, all affect attract [liveness to] domestic and foreign investors. ... Non-political considerations include the economy, infrastructure, ... labor law, insurance, taxes and so on.

The Iran petrochemical industry, according to one senior manager, faces considerable challenges in surviving the black swans which these circumstances produce. As he saw it, these included

Lack of developed supply chains for small-scale industries, lack of support for technology development, lack of developer companies and weaknesses in financial structures.

The political and economic situations for general contractors are not predictable and maybe they cannot deliver on their contracts due to international sanctions. The employers and the whole society will suffer the consequences.

5.8 Summary

The two samples, the entrepreneurs and the senior managers/ administrators are not *entirely* different in their descriptions of ‘the world’ (paradigm) they occupy, how they understand it and how they act. There are *some* managers and some entrepreneurs who report that they live in two worlds: a chaotic one that is full of unpredictable surprises (a world where black swan events are common) and a ‘functional’ world in which there are systems that work, or at least an imagined future Iran in which reformed systems *could* work one day. The two samples include interviewees who think that there could *eventually* be better working arrangements between governmental agencies and both entrepreneurs and managers of Iran’s upstream and downstream petrochemical industries.

However, despite these recognised overlaps, standing further back from the interview data there are significant differences between the two samples. These differences are significant in the sense that they are too great to be explained as if they were caused by random chance variations. In other words, by taking the same number of dice as interviewees and throwing them, it would require numerous dice throws before the dice representing the "entrepreneur" and the dice representing the "manager" would generate a pattern of differences resembling the specific ranges of opinions recorded. In other words, even with quite small samples it is possible for a qualitative researcher to have some confidence that the differences s/he identifies *might* be generalizable to a larger population.

The broad difference, considering the interviews is that the way in which entrepreneur’s think and act is more similar to Taleb’s recommended ‘anti-fragile’ strategy while most of the petrochemical managers follow the functional paradigm. It is also clear that although interviewees in both samples experience surprises, *the entrepreneurs have ways of dealing with them that the managers do not have*. Entrepreneurs seems to be happier and more diversified

compared to senior petrochemicals managers while petrochemical managers act in more functional ways and envisage a future environment which is more benign than the present one.

This author believes that managers shouldn't relate all the issues and troubles they experience to international sanctions. While sanctions make surprises more likely, even in countries that are not sanctioned, enormous, and it was suggested, more severe and wide-reaching surprises happen, such as the 2007-8 global financial crisis. Our argument is that there are steps that can be taken towards becoming more anti-fragile in order to have the flexibility to cope with the situation, defend against (localise and contain) the effects of the negative black swans and grab the opportunities that are possible through positive black swans which are equally difficult to forecast. As author emphasises "Without risk there is no profit". Consequently, Iranian entrepreneurs and managers can find opportunities in chaos and realise considerable profits...but not profits great enough to get them noticed by some authorities which would risk them being taken over'.

In contrast, the 'profit maximiser' in the favourable (functional) risk environment modelled by Thompson, would invest too much in positive black swans. As it has been observed many times, some profit-maximising entrepreneurs operating in Iran grow very fast for around four years and then crash. Growth is possible because Iranians, enjoy the prestige that comes from conspicuous consumption. The Individualistic-Competitive thought style is evident in Iranians wish to out-do their neighbours. The Individualistic-Competitive thought style is easy to recognise in the country. This means that when a new product or service becomes available it is purchased in high volumes, until the next 'best thing' becomes available.

The implications are not common sense. Paradoxically, it may be easier to make profits in unstable countries than in stable ones. Instead of wishing to do business in 'stable environments' it is possible to live profitably with risks that cannot in any case ever be

eliminated. Managers should be as prepared as entrepreneurs to be vigilant at all times and react promptly and not rely on governments to take action in all circumstances. However, this recommendation applies to government agencies too.

The literature on strategic planning has been and continues to be subject to our high level of criticism, primarily due to the highly unrealistic assumption that sufficient knowledge can be obtained to effectively plan for unpredictable futures. The promotion of the "science of muddling through" by Lindblom, in our view, aligns with Taleb's concept of antifragility. As far as the rest of the world is concerned, Iran has a weighty geopolitical position in the Middle East and its oil reserves mean that it has global effects. It would be a mistake to try and exclude Iran from the world system. The importance of the way Iran acts is magnified by its position on one of the world's main crossroads with a huge potential market in the region. For example, if Iran was to increase its involvement in down-stream refining of diverse high value-added polymers the effects for all polymer manufacturers everywhere could be very large. In other words, the Iranian state could itself embrace the principles of anti-fragility and invest, say twenty percent of its state capital in developing materials which have the qualities of being a) very difficult to make and b) extraordinary properties. It would only require a handful of these to be successful to repay the lost investments sunk into many unsuccessful polymer development projects. In other words, anti-fragility is a scalable set of principles that apply just as well to large actors as to small entrepreneurs and even to individuals' private lives. As Iranian entrepreneurs demonstrate, no actor should participate in ventures that are 'too big to fail'. (The failure of one venture does not wreck the success of another venture.) Governments can also 'defer decisions' and 'make their own luck' rather than follow 'utility maximising' which leaves actors vulnerable to sudden and unforeseen catastrophes which are too large to mitigate.

From the authors point of view no actor can ever be certain of what is going to work and what is going to fail so small successes and small failures are preferable to high gains that come with high risks. If Taleb is correct, then 'Big Wins' will come but it is not possible to know what these will be.

Of course, it is not ignored international sanctions which have worsened very much at the time of writing (July 2019) but sanctions should be a reminder that world trade is as improbable and surprising as the election of President Trump. Anti-fragility is for all actors at all scales and governmental officers, managers and entrepreneurs should experiment to produce fresh institutional arrangements some of which will thrive in ways that 'defy estimation'. Given the country's global significance, its effective universities, the diversity of the products that can be made from oil and gas and the agility of its surviving entrepreneurs, positive black swans will turn up. As the entrepreneurs demonstrate, in chaos, anti-fragility makes the best sense.

Chapter 6

Conclusions, Discussion and Recommendation

6.1 Conclusion

The primary objective of this thesis was to propose justifiable strategies based on the probability of black swan events. This has particular relevance for a country like Iran, as a result of the presence of both political and economic sanctions as well as a contemporary history that can be recognised as ‘volatile’. Therefore, Iran offers a challenging and suitable ‘test case’ for the anti-fragility principles, although the same principles investigated in this research are generally applicable, because no societies or economies are immune from events that are: a) hard to predict and b) whose effects are disproportionate, even where the changes that occur initially are minor. Our objective in the long term is to ensure that ‘anti-fragile’ policies are implemented, not only to alleviate the most detrimental impacts of ‘black swan events, but also to exploit the benefits of ‘positive black swans’, that are also hard to predict and whose positive impacts are disproportionately vast. It is believed that not chasing positive black swans is in line with the ‘anti-fragile’ principles, as the greatest successes ultimately result in the greatest failures (effective examples of this are social networks like Friends Reunited, that experienced rapid growth but has subsequently disappeared).

The aim has been to demonstrate that entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived have an increased likelihood of reporting the adoption of strategies that mirror ‘anti-fragile’ positions in comparison to the practices reported by senior managers in Iran. In the conclusion presented in this chapter, a discussion will review why these opinions and means of conducting business are thinkable (the thinking of both the entrepreneurs and senior managers). It is important to remember that the population of Iran is relatively young and highly educated and it can be reasonably assumed that exploiting positive black swans in an agile manner will reduce the rate of unemployment within Iran. Although estimating which of the young polymer scientists will make new discoveries in terms of products with high value added is not possible, a large number of them are already being trained in the country.

To summarise, based on Taleb's reasoning that in chaotic worlds where minor modifications in the antecedent conditions have impacts that are magnified in a manner that it is impossible to predict, then 'anti-fragile' approaches comprise an optimal means of surviving and succeeding (Taleb, 2012). Put differently, it is assumed that a critical factor in survival is avoiding 'path dependency', and according to Taleb, not having the expectation that history will provide a greater insight into the future than is actually the case.

It has been verified that the practices of entrepreneurs in Iran who have achieved success conform with the chaos paradigm, which it is stated is the paradigm inhabited by the writing of Taleb. For instance, they are not deceived by the sunk costs fallacy and are prepared to change direction in any and all of their varied business ventures. Observe that here, success has been defined in a specific (fatalistic) way, namely the ability to survive, rather than being the maximisation of profits or expected, reliable and acquiescent function of an organisation in which behaviours rarely if ever deviate from the norm. Furthermore, success in this case is not considered to refer to Iran being saved in its united fight against other global powers, even though the latter conforms with our longer-term objective. The reason for mentioning the aforementioned success definitions will be clarified below.

Due to the fact that the author is himself an entrepreneur from Iran who has survived and achieved success, he was ideally positioned to connect with a network of other entrepreneurs and managers in Iran as well as to interview them in their mother tongue. During each interview with his interviewees, the author was extensively questioned on the unpredictability and opportunities confronting him as well as other entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived with whom the author is particularly familiar). These sessions have assisted with operationalising Taleb, designing our interview timeline and converting the tacit knowledge it is possessed into explicit knowledge.

It is remarkable the lengths that ‘survivors’ will go to postpone decisions for path dependency to be avoided. For instance, the approach followed involves routinely keeping the greatest number of alternative pathways open for as long as feasible before reaching an irreversible decision. Notably, certain decisions have been deferred for a duration equivalent to the time taken for this research to be conducted. Numerous examples exist of entrepreneurs in Iran behaving in similar ways. Decisions are continually reviewed every hour to facilitate the appraisal of all new ‘Black Swan Events’.

From the perspective of the author according to the position of Nicholas Nassim Taleb, the aspiration to take into account every potential political and economic factor that could affect the process is not realistic. Nevertheless, in order for planning to be successful, planners who adopt the ‘strong’ variant of strategic planning methodology would be required to do this.

Taleb recommends that one should consider black swan events according to the assumption that “sometimes, what you don't know is more important than what you know”. This is in line with his assertion that uncertainties cannot be easily mapped. In the traditional sense, anti-fragility cannot be considered a ‘strategy’ but could be relatively beneficial in terms of survival when systems are frequently confronted by unforeseeable modifications and backtracking. The author recognises that long-term investments and large projects require thinking and planning from a long-term strategical perspective as it is necessary to make certain estimations regarding what will happen in the future in the long term. However, there is an increased likelihood that profits and returns will be realised in the longer time if both anti-fragility and black swan events are taken into account. For instance, when planning a large project involving a hydro-electric power plant, scenario-development related to changes in the climate that could impact precipitation levels will be required. The difficult-to-predict likelihood that positive and negative black swans will occur during a big project’s lifetime does not render planning risky, futile or needless if it assists strategic planners to focus more on

unforeseen events and to ensure that they do not underestimate the risks of their systems. Adopting an anti-fragile strategy would allow businesses to increase their robustness in chaotic environments and to take advantage of unpredicted events to a greater extent. If the ‘hydro-electric dam’ is considered as a ‘thought experiment’, it could be reasonable from an anti-fragile perspective to construct multiple small projects spanning multiple tributary river systems, as opposed to constructing one large project on the biggest river in Iran. In an area that was becoming increasingly dry, ‘chaotic’ precipitation (intensive localised rainfall on which one cannot depend) would imply that there would always be a scheme located somewhere in the region that would generate beneficial outcomes. However, the ‘one large dam’ (i.e., to maximise profit) strategy would be highly susceptible to disappointment from the perspective of investors if there is a decline in rainfall. Conversely, in an area where rainfall was increasing, the aforementioned ‘large dam’ would not have been constructed at a sufficiently high level to optimally exploit the advantages of the increased precipitation. In line with the principles of postponed decisions, if the ‘multiple small dams’ strategy is adopted, then, if as appears improbable, precipitation does increase, then it would be possible to rapidly construct a medium-size dam at a reduced cost in a location on the river system where plans had been originally made to build the ‘big dam’. Constructing multiple smaller dams is costlier than one big dam that has the same overall water and power capacity, but it is recommended that resilience should be favoured rather than significant gains that are associated with significant risks.

It is acknowledged that our support for the chaos paradigm as well as the Black Swan Theory that it produces is grounded on a specific bias, which Grid-Group Cultural Theory recognises as a ‘cultural bias’ according to the success criterion of the author (resilience). The different options

- ‘Hierarchical’ success criteria (deviance is minimised, compliance is maximised, stability)
- ‘Egalitarian’ success criteria (change only occurs if everyone benefits, wide-ranging change across the system if it occurs)
- ‘Individualist’ success criteria (competitive success as well as a self-stabilising system comprising demand, supply and prices) – are culturally present in the forms of practices and thoughts...

are all successful according to their own terms and in particular, restricted situations. However, the three success conditions described above do not exist in Iran

Michael Thompson provided a highly beneficial description and explanation of these ‘cultural biases’ and it is recognised the coherence and broad applicability of the ‘Grid Group Cultural Theory’ that he proposed. He demonstrated that rather than two, there are potentially four ‘risk environments (*Uncertain, Moderate, Boom, Bust*) as he described and modelled in his work *How Banks and Other Financial Institutions Think*.

When compared with Taleb, it can be observed that the four main concepts proposed by Taleb, namely Silent Evidence, Confirmation Error, Epistemic Arrogance and Future Blindness, are particularly risky in the ‘Uncertain Risk Environment’ that exists within Iran according to the proof of unpredictability that it has identified. In our experience, the majority of managers in the Middle East who have conducted interviews with and observed on an informal basis in our recent years of business operations, as well as those with whom interviews were conducted for this thesis, generally map the future according to their previous experiences, increasing their dependence on things they know rather than what they do not know. Their preference for remaining compliant and reducing deviance would have functioned effectively if there had consistently been a ‘moderate risk environment’ in Iran. Additionally, it is believed that the remarkable Egalitarian mobilisation that initiated the revolution that

precipitated the demise of the Shah and prolonged a horrific conflict with Iraq would be reasonable as a criterion of success if the unified struggle had persisted on an indefinite basis. Egalitarian-Enclave reasoning can also be justified in the current era according to the nationwide crises triggered when the President of the United States placed the society and economy of Iran under severe 'existential threat. Readers will also recognise that the author also harbours certain feelings of unity and aspires for a future in which all citizens of Iran and the wider region can benefit (which explains why it is recommended that advanced polymers are developed).

Both scenario development and back casting can still offer benefits if they enable actors to become sensitised to black swans. The author is supportive of the 'Mitiga' framework in the sense that it fosters sensitivity to 'input information', adaptation and flexibility. Nevertheless, Mitiga is only beneficial if the individual cycles do more than intensify extant narrative fallacies. It is reiterated that entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived exist in a state in which they permanently 'cycle' the evidence and reconsider what they do not know (what are defined as their 'known unknowns'). Second, such an approach (which dissimilar to Grid-Group Cultural Theory likely cannot be justified as being a 'theory') conforms with the thesis of Thompson, particularly with respect to 'uncertain risk seasons.

It has been completely rejected the previously described 'Space Matrix' due to the fact that it makes the assumption that the stability of the environment is far greater than the reality and even makes the assumption that the default risk season is what Thompson would consider to be 'Moderate' stability. The Space Matrix would only be plausible in a benign environment that the author has no experience of, not even in his business operations based in the United Kingdom.

The Blue Ocean strategy is only applicable to a limited proportion of cases where actors devise previously unseen or attractive services or products. From the perspective of the actor,

the service or product may represent an exceptionally positive black swan, although it could be devastating for others. Nevertheless, the Blue Ocean Strategy is only applicable after the service or product has been conceived. It only makes sense after this process has been completed.

On the other hand, the author somewhat disputes Strategic Leader Theory, although it could be improved by incorporating the recommendations of both Taleb and Thompson into it. Additionally, it is our belief that there is less justification for Strategic Leader Theory being a causal theory compared with the Grid-Group Cultural Theory of Thompson, as the latter has extremely high normative, descriptive and explanatory strength for every 'risk season'. In fact, a vast proportion of the studies referenced in our review of the literature are heuristic (rules of thumb) and normative (supportive of recommendations) without sociologically or anthropologically analysing why such recommendations or rules of thumb function in a given collection of circumstances. Furthermore, most authors appear to be insufficiently self-aware of the paradigms in which their works are located as well as the manner in which and why there are either changes in risk seasons (2007-8 global financial crisis) or continue for extended periods (high-risk Iran). Thompson clearly describes how opposing rationalities trigger dynamic changes as well as how distinct types of 'institutions' (Douglas, 1986) can only mend their thinking and practices when they are taken by surprise by events with which they are unable to cope.

While the two interview samples cannot be clearly differentiated, it has been determined that general differences do exist (a summary of which has been provided above). Potentially the main result is that strategy models that include loops (feedback stages in which planned actions are verified against developing circumstances and then making required revisions) are capable of describing but not sufficiently explaining the actions of entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived. This is correct to the extent that they appear to be verifying and changing their

plans on an hourly basis in the light of the evolving situation. For instance, when this thesis was being written, the relationship between Iran and the United Kingdom was becoming increasingly tense after a super-tanker carrying oil was detained close to Gibraltar and then an incident occurred in the Straits of Hormuz involving three Iranian motor patrol vessels as well a British oil tanker and frigate. Based on the data obtained in the interviews, it can be stated in confidence that entrepreneurs in Iran will be following such events closely and considering their views and emotions regarding the investments they have made and plan to make in the future. They asked themselves questions like “Does President Trump want conflict?”, “Could an error of judgement cause a war that is unwanted by both sides?” or “Could the President of the United States take measures based on the hawkish recommendations of John Bolton or is he merely posturing to appease the domestic audience as part of his efforts to be re-elected?” and “What impact could such events have on my projects?”

Put differently, multiple types of ‘feedback loops’ exist in the minds of entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived, which they will utilise for the purpose of evaluating their steps now, tomorrow, in the following week and in the longer term. Nevertheless, in the event that the strategic plans and intentions become outnumbered by the amount of feedback loops and revisions, then even the most pragmatic strategic models that enable changes to be made will start to become misshapen and increasingly useless. If the reality of the model is that 90% of what is occurring consists of verifying, re-verifying, making changes, pausing and re-starting in another direction, then it can no longer be considered a strategic planning model, but is rather a model involving ‘muddling through’.

With regard to the interviews conducted with top managers and petrochemical technocrats, it is possible to ask the same questions. These interviewees have a considerably greater likelihood of discussing plans and strategies focused on the long term. They provided a sufficient amount of information regarding their functions as managers to suggest that

- a) They engage in long-term thinking
- b) Enhanced institutional arrangements will ultimately allow their industries to experience growth
- c) They generally stress Iran's geopolitical significance, implying that the society and economy of the country could not fail and
- d) It is also evident that their views exist within a 'functional' world on which entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived place less emphasis

The entrepreneurs are less likely to identify themselves with the functional paradigm other than chaotic paradigm. Put differently, the more traditional strategy models correspond to the managers more than the entrepreneurs.

Nevertheless, from our perspective within the chaotic (Talebian) paradigm, the confidence that the managers have in strategy is misguided and potentially to a dangerous extent. Our perspective of the form that an anti-fragile strategy will take in the context of Iran as an 'entrepreneur', which comprises multiple investments being made in an extremely broad range of exceptionally valuable but highly unlikely innovations in petrochemical products with increased value-added, is not the same as the strategic planning models containing with textbooks in the field of business, which appear to be more focused on 'shared' objectives and aims and that perceive it to be mandatory for all members to be 'aligned' with them, which is often referred to as the organisational 'vision'. Put differently, our interviewees are situated at various points on a continuum between only possessing feedback loops and only having a rigid plan. Entrepreneurs could be situated closer to the end of the continuum with the 'loops', whereas the managers are nearer the 'fixed' end.

It is possibly reasonable to question which of the sample groups has the most to gain from the implicit models they employ. Due to the fact that both managers and entrepreneurs have access to *identical information* regarding negative and positive black swans that occur in Iran,

it is fascinating to identify how their responses to them differ. Although it is clear that Iran is only one country, the two groups of respondents behaved in highly different ways as they situate the country in two worlds that are relatively distinct (although some have feet in both paradigms).

To determine which of the strategy models is more beneficial for its master, it is necessary to revisit the success criteria of these two groups of actors. From the perspective of the entrepreneurs, the overriding objective is to *survive*, while altering direction, distributing investments, postponing decisions, temporarily halting, as well as completely stopping or re-starting projects all conform with their aims and correspond to the recommendations of Taleb. Conversely, there is an increased likelihood that a top manager, bureaucrat or technocrat in Iran will have the expectation (and confidence) that one month will be similar to the preceding month and it is our strong belief that they consider the long-term to a greater extent than entrepreneurs. An administrator in a senior position has an institutional obligation to approach things in different ways and have increased confidence in planning as they are specifically employed to make plans and implement them. Planning is an 'institutionalised' aspect of their role and assists with fixing their partiality for 'control', 'managing by exception' and 'measuring progress against planned objectives', for example. It is observed that in cases where national plans are not realised effectively, new plans are conceived in an attempt to resolve shortcomings. Plans are followed by more plans. As stressed by Grid-Group Cultural Theorists, the way in which the administrator thinks (Style of Thought) is 'institutionalised' as 'policies and procedures' and the only thing that could make their thinking change would be an extreme surprise. As entrepreneurs are owners that have their own 'skin in the game', they have greater freedom to change things, which means that taking a broad variety of events of various kinds into account on a consistent basis has more significance.

One of the primary objectives of this thesis was to encourage entrepreneurs and managers in Iran to think and act in different ways through the adoption of anti-fragile strategies. As a theoretical contribution to support this objective, it is proposed that advantages can be gleaned through the synthesis of Grid-Group Cultural Theory with what Taleb chooses to define as his ‘anti-theory’ of Black Swan events. An advantage of the black swan argument is that it makes people more aware of uncertainty as well as the significance of unexpected events. It is important to note that all four of Michael Thompson’s styles of thought can be considered due to the fact that each of them confronts surprise in ways that are more specific compared with Talebian black swans:

- Organisations that are based on a specific hierarchy and obedience while maintaining rigidity do not bow when confronted by evolving situations. The situation is worsened as a result of increasingly strict rule enforcement, harsher punishments and the imposition of new rules. This ultimately causes deviants to be created from an increasing number of actors.
- Egalitarian movements strive for strong ideals but can fail as a result of the practical complexities associated with leading ‘crowds’ that harbour suspicion towards most forms of leadership as well as the systems of ‘leadership’ that would allow their operations to proceed. They are dependent on leaders with charisma who have an affinity with the crowd and are largely irreplaceable.
- Competitive (unregulated) reasoning has the potential to cause the oceans to be filled with plastic waste as a by-product of efforts to maximise profit.
- Fatalistic thinking could function for the actor who chooses this rationality, but it is not beneficial for other people, particularly when they do not share the survivalist cunning approach.

Readers should be reminded (specifically those in Iran) that G-GCT could allow entrepreneurs and scholarly professionals to increase their focus on the intrinsic but opposing *reasonableness* of the different thought styles such that ‘poly-rational’ or ‘clumsy’ solutions can appear from the *dialogue*. Thompson convincingly argues that the Emirates Stadium constructed by Arsenal FC (as well as other policy issues) was a product of clumsy thinking (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Rmz_t_V9sJg).

Regrettably, it can be observed a significant discrepancy between Iranian higher education institutions and business enterprises. In other words, the author will strive to do his utmost to resolve this deficiency and he has relative confidence that both actors could play an important role in developing the country if they could meet, converse with each other, have reasonable disagreements and were helped with identifying:

- the kinds of reasoning that they were utilising (as well as their realistic constraints)

While acknowledging, and showing respect for the honesty and considerateness of each of the four possible stances

Grid-Group Cultural Theory informs us about the significance and contribution made by various rationalities within a given system (bureaucratic, team or market based, and possibly the ‘bunker mentality’).

When meeting one another at symposia in which problems are shared, in ‘management learning sets’ as well as ‘whole systems conferences’ guided by a facilitator who has a good understanding of GGCT, all actors can increase their awareness regarding how

- a) ‘positive feedback loops’ have caused their thinking to become fixed (constrained) in their customary style of thought
- b) different thought styles could be more effective at resolving the most complex challenges. For instance, Egalitarian and Individual reasoning contests the Hierarchical propensity to enlarge the rule books, whereas Hierarchical thinking

informs Individualistic and Egalitarian thinkers about new approaches that can be used to sustain long-term projects

- c) How the individual styles of thought can cause certain problems to worsen instead of improve
- d) That every style of thought possesses a certain level of wisdom

It is not necessarily that compromise is required, but more that forums should be created in which actors can acquire the ability to consider solutions that would be unimaginable if they worked in isolation.

6.2 Recommendations and Implications

Nevertheless, based on the specific ‘uncertainty’ surrounding the risk season in Iran as well as the findings of the interviews conducted with entrepreneurs and managers of petrochemical firms, various recommendations can be made, which could be justified as offering benefits for business operations in *all* chaotic environments. Despite the fact that our reasoning (as well as that of Lindblom and Taleb) is predominantly Fatalistic, it is recognised that different types of reasoning are also incorporated into the recommendations made below, which are based on the Grid-Group Cultural theory of Thompson (as shown). Observe that through the use of G-GCT, it is possible to augment the simpler Fatalistic recommendations of Taleb more clearly and practically:

- 1) If the complex governmental laws and regulations are reformed and simplified [according to Individual-Competitive reasoning], this could play a role in achieving market success within Iran, which includes
 - Ensuring that the Courts that uphold commercial agreements as well as authoritative independent arbitration among contractors that are disputing can be easily accessed. Entrepreneurs with limited resources should have the same level of access to commercial courts as those who have accumulated considerable wealth. If trust is

increased between commercial contractors, their confidence in each other will rise accordingly, thus causing general ‘business confidence’ to grow. [In this case, the reasoning adopted is a ‘clumsy’ or ‘poly-rational’ combination of Hierarchical and Individual-Competitive reasoning]

- Maintaining and verifying standardized weights and measures; establishing and maintaining product certification and standards of quality could produce similar results [Hierarchical reasoning]
- Entrepreneurs around the world reasonably object to taxes based on the argument that they restrict investment, and this was mentioned in multiple interviews with entrepreneurs in this study. Nevertheless, from a Hierarchical perspective, if the tax system is regularised and the process of collecting taxes efficient, the state will become less dependent on generating income through the large amount of profitable companies that are currently owned by the military. In the event that the tax system was rendered more equal and enforcement was more consistent, entrepreneurs in Iran could focus on achieving growth with less concern that their commercial success could result in their business being taken over [poly rational Hierarchical and Individual-Competitive reasoning combined with an Egalitarian call for a ‘whole-system change’ from which all can benefit]
- If customs restrictions on poor quality products are legally enforced on a consistent basis, this will offer protection to those who produce high-quality products from being undercut by counterfeiters. Hierarchical thinking (and the three other styles of thought to a lesser degree) is ‘animated’ by legal incongruities as well as ‘loopholes’ in existing laws that enable the corrupt (deviant) owners of businesses to easily import illegal products that erode the motivation of entrepreneurs, thus rendering investors who intend to establish a business in Iran less confident. Resultantly, it is stressed that it may

be necessary for the State to apply stricter border monitoring and controls to limit the opportunities for counterfeit products to be smuggled into the country and enter the market. [In this case, there is hybrid, poly-rational Hierarchical and Individual-Competitive reasoning that promotes producers that offer high-quality products in a competitive but lawful manner]

- A number of the entrepreneurs who participated pointed to various aspects of laws that may need to be fundamentally changed in order to enhance the likelihood that businesses will thrive and survive in spite of the black swans confronting them within the chaotic business world. Many of the interviewees implied that taxes should be imposed at rates that acknowledge the various degrees of risk that entrepreneurs were prepared to adopt. If higher risks were taxed at a lower rate, entrepreneurs would be able to take greater risks, specifically when establishing new ventures. Following on from this, it is fascinating that activities with reduced risk would be taxed at a higher rate. [This recommendation is also poly rational Hierarchical and Individual-Competitive. It makes the reasonable argument in a significantly innovative manner that it is necessary to marketize tax rates to enable the pricing of risks to become more accurate]
- As a different option to or as a supplement to different rates of tax for varying degrees of risk, the Government could contemplate offering subsidies to entrepreneurs to offset the financial effects of black swans, helping with reducing the risks associated with business ventures that can be advantageous for all areas of society. This step is appealing to Hierarchical, Egalitarian and Individualistic reasoning. If it also promotes survival, it could also be appealing to Fatalist reasoning. In the current era in which severe sanctions have been imposed by the international community as well as the slow rate at which the EU is moving to meet its promise to uphold the ‘Iran Nuclear Deal’,

this clearly ‘poly-rational’ measure should become well-liked and effective. Although it does not fully satisfy any of the styles of thought, it provides each of them a small amount of what they aspire to have. If Thompson is right (and he has offered multiple case studies to support his assertions), a measure has a greater likelihood of effectively satisfying each success criterion, albeit partially, if it contains an increased amount of rationalities. Due to the fact that the sanctions imposed by the international community represent an instance of what Thompson labels a ‘wicked problem’ (as) a) a large number of people are affected, b) multiple approaches can be taken to address the problem, c) it will be transformed into a new problem subsequent to the application of any solution to it d) a complete solution to the problem will never be found, the ‘institutionalisation’ of poly-rational reforms within the entrepreneurial arena will offer the best likelihood of helping entrepreneurs as well as a multitude of different actors.

Hierarchical thinkers experience frustration that even though Iran has maintained *compliance* with the Nuclear Deal terms, sanctions remain in place. (Compliance is being penalised!). As a result of this irritating situation, thinking may start to take a new path:

- A Fatalist would respond to this by shrugging their shoulders and thinking ‘What else did you expect? Trusting other people is pointless’ with an additional variant: acceptance of the inevitable, despondency and choosing to migrate to another country, however it is possible
- A poly rational Fatalistic-Individualist could respond by thinking ‘If I can do this undetected, then smuggling could be an option! Smugglers perceive sanctions to be a godsend’

- The response of an Egalitarian could be to adopt a united stance with all Iranians and reinforce the military and trading alliances of Iran when faced with the significant outside threat and make preparations for conflict
- A Hierarchical reaction may be to call on all types of institutions that uphold 'International Law' and 'Global Governance', as well as to protest Iran's innocence at the 'international court of public opinion'

All the responses described above (as well as others that can be thought) are rational reactions that confound the objective of President Trump to initiate a change of regime in Iran. The available ways of thinking could exist together with an equally powerful aspiration for Iran to implement various different reforms that conform with the suggestions of other countries around the world with the objective of the new sanctions imposed by the United States being relaxed and all other sanctions lifted. However, taking all these eventualities into account, a Fatalist Iranian entrepreneur (who has survived) will likely see no justification for renouncing his/her partiality for deferring decisions as well as all the previously mentioned related measures.

Our recommendation is that symposia are held in multiple different formats as a means of fostering 'clumsy solutions', that emerge from disputes and dialogues among styles of thought; but with the specific Talebian recommendation, made by entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived, that all solutions should include a significant component of Fatalistic reasoning and related practices.

A more decisive justification for why the claimed 'anti-fragility' characteristic of Iran may be unique in relation to that of other similar economies lies in the country's specific socio-political and economic context. Iran has faced substantial challenges in recent history, including political tensions, economic sanctions, and volatile market conditions. These factors have

contributed to an environment where resilience and adaptability become crucial for survival and progress.

Iran's experience with political and economic sanctions has necessitated the development of alternative strategies and innovative approaches to circumvent the limitations imposed by external pressures. This has led to the emergence of a resilient and resourceful entrepreneurial spirit within the Iranian business community. Entrepreneurs in Iran have been compelled to navigate uncertain and adverse conditions, fostering a culture of flexibility, improvisation, and risk-taking. This unique context has likely influenced the development of 'anti-fragile' characteristics within Iran's economic ecosystem.

Moreover, Iran's relatively young and highly educated population provides a fertile ground for the cultivation of 'anti-fragility.' The country's human capital, coupled with a strong emphasis on education and research, creates a dynamic and adaptable workforce. This enables Iran to leverage its intellectual potential to embrace emerging opportunities and respond effectively to unexpected challenges.

Furthermore, Iran's geographic location and historical context have shaped its resilience. Situated in a region marked by geopolitical complexities and fluctuations, Iran has historically experienced periods of political turmoil and external influences. These circumstances have fostered a sense of resilience and adaptability among its population, enabling them to withstand and recover from shocks.

In summary, the claimed 'anti-fragility' characteristic of Iran can be attributed to its unique socio-political and economic context, the resilience and adaptability of its entrepreneurs, the young and educated population, and its historical experience. These factors collectively provide a more decisive justification for why Iran's 'anti-fragility' may be distinct from that of other similar economies.

6.2.1 Continuous learning by entrepreneurs:

It is strongly recommended that both entrepreneurs and the managers of petrochemical firms contemplate the adoption and adaption of Taleb's 'anti-theories' pertaining to black swans so that they can take the future into account to a greater extent in their current actions, specifically with the aim of making themselves and their businesses more robust and antifragile. As a result of ongoing high levels of uncertainty and the rapidly evolving circumstances in the Middle East, it will be necessary for entrepreneurs to display an exceptionally high degree of vigilance and agility in order to cope with the black swan events, focus on maximising their ability to survive rather than make profits, as well seizing new opportunities that unexpected positive black swans present. A hierarchical (managerial) style of thought is not suited to this imperative, at least unless it is linked with Fatalistic reasoning. It can be said that the learning that can be gleaned from the experiences which exist nowadays would have limited benefit in the future due to the fact that the argument can be made that events that are happening now or in the past will never be reproduced in the same way in the future. As contended by Taleb, a sceptical perspective, alternatively called Stoicism, is suited to this state. Additionally, it strengthens the principle that unknowns have greater significance than things that are known.

6.3 Further Research

This thesis has been concerned with managing for the future under chaotic conditions, with a primary focus on mitigating risks for Iranian entrepreneurs and petrochemical managers rather than the optimisation of profits. It is not believed that there is anything peculiar about the culture of Iran that either promotes or subdues reasoning in the country. All four styles of thought are universally available and triggered differently based on the comprehension and existence of risks, such as prevailing 'risk environments'. The principles of anti-fragility can also be applied to most of the rest of the world, as the author suggests a transition into a highly

chaotic 'risk season' where success is best achieved by those adopting a 'Pragmatist' approach. (Thompson, 2018). Donald Trump winning the US Presidential Election, Brexit, complicated civil wars in the Middle East, the re-emergence of a cold war among Western countries and the Russian Federation and their unforeseeable impacts on fluctuations in the stock market, currency exchange instability, as well as the volatile nature of oil, gas and gold prices can be regarded as effective examples of black swans that also exhibit causal relationships that cannot be quantified *among* them across inestimable time frames.

It can be easily stated that further research on this topic should include any research on the 'strategy' for a given activity that has particular vulnerability to negative and positive black swans. If our Talebian assumptions are right, then as opposed to standard thinking, the optimal conditions for activities that generate profits are not those characterised by stability and equilibrium. One should be able to identify analogous strategies to those adopted by entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived in the context of the challenging conditions throughout the former USSR, in all disputed geographical regions, and even inside areas impacted by civil wars. However, it is not our intention to imply that the survival of every actor who adopts the principles of Taleb is guaranteed. The author acknowledges that due to the fact that he has managed to survive for many years, he has accumulated financial resources (buffers) that new entrepreneurs would now not be able to access. Consequently, tracking and comparing new entrepreneurs with those who have been operating for longer in a chaotic environment makes sense, and against these sub-groups, comparisons can also be made between new and older senior bureaucrats and technocrats.

Additionally, it would be advocated for Thompson and Taleb being further synthesised, as our attempts to do so were started relatively late in the process of conducting this research. This is relatively complicated endeavour as

- The argument of Taleb is simplified to make it seem that was only between *two* positions (that can be defined as paradigms)
- Three classic paradigms are recognised by social science, particularly sociology (Functional-Equilibrium seeking, Fiery and Forwards-Moving Conflict and Chaotic-Contingent Chancy worlds of coincidence)
- *Four* different styles of thought are recognised by Grid-Group Cultural Theory, which also denote world cosmologies that have a significant resemblance to paradigms

Put differently, should future studies be grounded on the assumption that two alternatives should be considered, or possible three or four (in addition to clumsy hybrids of these four)?

This is not an easy question to answer, as it is not possible to completely determine the extent to which models can be simplified and are worthy of defence. It will be attempted to bring our thesis to the attention of both Thompson and Taleb and ask them to respond to this question. Nevertheless, the author shares Thompson's mistrust of the neo-classical profit maximisation 'efficient market hypothesis'. Taking the most optimistic view, this only takes into account 25% of the possible reasoning and practices, whereas from Taleb's perspective, it represents a severely deceiving collection of assumptions that renders 'maximisers' particularly susceptible to becoming bankrupt when the risk season transitions between boom and bust. Such risks are particularly risky for Central Bankers and can eventually necessitate government bail-outs, which constitute risks for the generations of the future.

On the other hand, at the international level, it can be observed that due to a variety of factors related to competition and hierarchy, the manufacturers of value-added oil products around the world would prefer to retain such dominant business and geo-political advantages in their own hands. Their preference would be to manufacture plastics using Iranian oil in another country and obtain the added value that can be generated by producing polymers.

Certain rivals operate in the Middle East who also focused on refining high-value products from gas and oil, who also oppose Iran developing its petrochemicals industry due to the significant impact it will have on their market. However, Iran should seek advantageous changes to the ‘the terms of trade’, if required as an element of a renegotiated ‘Nuclear Deal’ ‘Nuclear Deal’ with the EU, the Russian Federation and China, and potentially the United States. This is the point at which it should be verified whether the international confidence in individualistic ‘free market competition’ has substance or is merely cynical rhetoric.

Nonetheless, to maintain a Talebian position, it is necessary to disregard positive surprises, even if the assumption can be justified that various countries will advocate for the continuance of sanctions imposed on Iran based on their government's belief in the beneficial chaos it would bring. It should be emphasised that systems that are chaotic are infamous (or famed) for producing unforeseen outcomes, which could result in Iran being strengthened instead of weakened, specifically by initiating the distribution of anti-fragile entrepreneurialism throughout all types of activities such as innovative approaches to refining petrochemicals.

6.4 Summary Recommendations

Further particular recommendations for making the downstream production of polymers more resilient could be to:

- Enhance, grow and diversify petrochemical products inside Iran, outside the basic stages of catalytic-cracking
- Create added-value, which is generally as much as 400% but could be more, such as in aromatic compounds like food-flavourings and perfumes
- Enhancing anti-fragility while also reducing the dependence on the exports of unrefined oil, which is already facing the challenges imposed by international sanctions as well

as the concurrent lessening of the necessity to import crucial and unnecessarily costly petrochemicals required for domestic purposes

- Further attain anti-fragility in shipping lines, insurance firms and banking systems by mitigating the elevated transaction costs resulting from the sanctions
- Anti-fragility could be further developed if the amount of target countries for Iranian polymers was increased to reduce the risk of such markets being lost unexpectedly as a result of, among other things, shifting geopolitical relationships

The abovementioned steps are suggested at the national level; however, the steps described below are recommended for individual entrepreneurs in Iran, again with the aim of minimising their susceptibility to black swans, which will enhance their anti-fragility:

- Business fields should be diversified (spreading their eggs among various baskets), while organic growth should be achieved from extant surpluses where feasible
- Managers and workers should be trained and educated regarding the notion of black swans and how systems are vulnerable to them
- Entrepreneurs should not be dependent on a specific bank or supplier (the number of possible suppliers and financial authorities should be increased) even if this results in the costs of transactions and debt-financing being raised
- Iran is relatively unique as it offers significant opportunities with the possibility of establishing a closed economy with the ability to be self-sufficient inside its own territory. This is because of its highly educated population and its atypical abundance of various natural resources. Resultantly, it is important for young entrepreneurs to take into account positive potentials and opportunities rather than only threats. Neighbouring countries like Iraq, Afghanistan among others offer

considerable market potential, which has the most significance at a time when sanctions remain in place

- The assumption that things that are not known have greater importance than those that are known is equally applicable at the individual, company, industrial, national and international levels. Certain decisions that appear to be high-risk endeavours from the perspective of other people could offer profits and reduced risks for entrepreneurs, who decide to take this course of action according to their *real market knowledge*

6.5 Theoretical Contribution

It has been detected only a short, cursory mention of N.N. Taleb in the work of Michael Thompson, while Thompson makes no mention at all of Taleb. Discussions about each other cannot be found in the works of either Taleb or Thompson.

Given the minimal focus the two have applied to each other, it is believed that it is interesting and constructive to integrate the two in the context of this thesis. In closing this argument, the author has created a fictional conversation among the two aforementioned actors on the basis of our existing knowledge. N.N. Taleb is characterised by the author as a fatalistic writer who takes into account *two* main thought styles, the ‘Gaussian’ and the ‘Mandelbrotian’ (Taleb, 2008: 234), whereas Michael Thompson contemplates four thought styles, and just as significantly, he presents two social (rather than psychological) dimensions, which render the four ‘styles of thought’ *possible* (thinkable). The dialogue is assembled based in quotes from the two authors. Firstly, Taleb converses regarding the propositions described below:

- 6 Taleb argues that unforeseen events have a disproportional effect in life; historical events are not good indicators of the future. Making forecasts based on previous experiences can be risky, which is defined as ‘Hume’s problem of indication.

- 7 The informed assumption can be made that Thompson would concur with this statement. He notes that it is not possible to depend on previous experiences to indicate what will occur in the future ‘as Risk Seasons will change without much delay’ further stating that ‘All that can be said from previous evidence such as from financial markets is that risk seasons transform in one of *three* directions from the original condition with no notice’.
- 8 Taleb may exhibit mild disapproval at the suggestion that four risk environments exist
- Thompson would again concur that even minor events can have large (unexpected) impacts. ‘Surprises *will* occur. Thompson notes that certain methods of addressing them are significantly more effective compared with others. ‘In a given risk season, one group of responses exists that will cause matters to *significantly deteriorate*. Actors must be prepared to change direction.’
 - According to Taleb, no knowledge exists regarding which of the causes at play will have the largest and widest positive or negative impacts, which is commonly referred to as surprises, but he considers them to be 'black swans'.
 - However, Thompson interrupts by saying ‘Our knowledge is considerably inferior to what we believe, but our convictions will be sufficiently strong provided they correspond to the risk season while it persists
 - This does not convince Taleb, as he emphasises that ‘We should remain highly sceptical and suspicious of our knowledge in which we have faith, and particularly with regard to financial consultants who exude confidence.’
 - He proceeds by making the argument that it is astute to invest approximately 20% of our wealth in varied projects that have two characteristics a) they should be significantly unlikely b) but offer excellent benefits (if they are achieved). We must also be suitably prepared for the eventuality that all of these investments are lost ‘With respect to the other 80%, they should be c) highly likely but b) with reduced yields.’

Taleb was trained as a market trader and has achieved significant success in practice, in addition to being somewhat of a philosopher and a statistical expert, and although he has not produced written works in an academic role as a professor at a university, he currently holds various academic positions. He is less dependent on *social* science (sociology, anthropology) and has increased reliance on individualistic economic and psychological agency theories, particularly evolutionary psychology (which is disregarded by the neo-Durkheimian Thompson as superfluous). Taleb only takes into account two main groups of possibilities (which can be identified as the Chaos and Functionalist paradigms), potentially due to the fact that a binary model can be easily constructed and explained. Nevertheless, in his position as a social theorist (who certainly also has an interest in practice), the anthropologist Michael Thompson makes the claim that *four* possibilities exist that are equally universal.

Our interpretation of Thompson implies that he would be understanding of Taleb, who he would perceive to be promoting the ‘Fatalistic Style of Thought’, but would also assert that Taleb has ‘approximately 25% of the possible thinking’, as Thompson believes that four possibilities exist, in addition to what he defines as ‘clumsy’ or ‘polyrational’ hybrids comprised of two, three or four of the styles of thought. Both of them strongly agree on the non-linear nature of the world, meaning it is chaotic, which represents a source of risk as well as new unexpected positive opportunities. Indeed, Thompson has travelled extensively, exploring the way in which risks are addressed in different countries, and his works are clearly relevant to nations such as Iran. For instance, Thompson has referred to the extent to which he admires the Persian King, Darius, who created a fascinating scheme by which the network of irrigation canals in Persia was financed. These were built on a voluntary basis and the canal diggers were not paid, but those who consented to do so received assurances that their direct descendants would receive limitless tax reliefs in the future. The enhanced agricultural

wealth facilitated by these canals provided incidental benefits for all, which more than offset any tax-reliefs awarded to the diggers. It can be considered a poly-rational arrangement.

It is believed that for the breadth of black swan theory to be expanded, it is necessary to take the opportunities and dimensions specified by Thompson into account and particularly recognise that four distinct ‘risk seasons’ exist as well as that they can be survived in ways that provided different levels of success (below).

Why are there four? Below, a Thompsonian diagram is presented that summarises Grid-Group Cultural Theory, but in a manner, that corresponds to the arguments of Taleb such that readers can see an overview.

Four Thought Styles: Grid-Group Cultural Theory and Risk Perceptions

Thompson diverges from Taleb in the sense that he contends that individuals (in fact, actors at all levels) are *cultural subjects*. Thompson has absolutely no dependence on the ‘animal’ characteristics of actors, unlike Taleb. From Thompson’s perspective, every actor is a cultural actor, not psychological types. The four types of reasoning that individual ‘cultural subjects’ have available are exactly the same as the forms of reasoning that organisations (as well as

entire industries, governments and worldwide entities) can access. Thompson's argument is 'fractal' functioning at all scales.

The table shown above presents the four distinct risks (as well as the ways in which they can be considered and responded. They are defined and rendered possible as actions and thoughts by the two defining completely entirely social/ cultural³ dimensions: 'Grid', the extent to which individuals are governed by *Social Regulation* (weak and strong), as well as 'Group', the extent to which individuals are unified in *Social Solidarity* (weak or strong). Due to the fact that both dimensions vary between Weak and Strong, this enables four cells to be created.

Entrepreneurs who seek competition and to maximise profits are situated in the bottom left Individualism' part of the diagram, in which the reasonable values *being competitive, maximising profits and achieving success* as well as where 'winnings belong to winners' (Weak Social Regulation/ Weak Social Solidarity). A logical characteristic of this thought style is a strong appetite for risk.

The Egalitarian thought style is described by Weak Social Regulation/ Strong Social Solidarity ('Low Grid/ High Group'). In this case, the primary concern is to achieve equality as well as shared improvement for all. This thought style is equally reasonable, but uses a different rationality to the Individualist way of thinking as it considers other people to have importance, whereas Individualists focus the most on the weakly regulated self. This type of reasoning causes large social movements to be animated, like that which enabled Ayatollah Khomeini to rapidly seize power.

Hierarch thinking as well as the systems it forms (bureaucrats and bureaucracies, regard for specialists) are situated within Strong Social Regulation/ Strong Social Solidarity quadrant ('High Grid/ High Group' position, top right). In this case, significant faith is

³ In this context, the words 'social' and 'cultural' are utilised interchangeably

placed on Rule Books as well as disciplining those who deviate. It can again be reasonably argued that ‘we can trust one another if everyone follows the rules’.

Fatalistic reasoning (which includes political figures in insecure situations) comprises the most disadvantageous or precarious ‘risk environment’ as described by High Grid (Strong Regulation) and Low Group (Weak Social Solidarity). This cultural possibility that is equally reasonable (as well as its related survivalist practices is shown in the cell in the top left).

In every instance, the ‘ball’ is situated on a different type of slope that represents the manner in which the thought style determines how much risk exists. Contemplate what occurs as the ball starts to move in either a leftward or rightward direction in every specific situation. Hence, cultural theory provides an explanation regarding if and why actors a) believe that stability can be achieved, b) judge how much risk exists and c) determine the extent of the effort required to ensure stability is maintained. That is, there are significant variations in the perception of risk, and things that may be treated as routine or stable by some thought styles are interpreted to present significant danger according to others. He stresses the rationality of each of the four positions while also indicating that they are opposing in such a way that debate and new thinking are stimulated. Thompson agrees with Taleb that an ‘equilibrium point’ does not exist, although in the context of culture, Thompson is the one who states that the financial markets are cultural artefacts. Although he concurs that an equilibrium point does not exist in reality, his reasons for thinking this are different.

The G-GCT diagram is beneficial as it provides an *explanation* regarding why

- a) entrepreneurs in Iran who have survived see risks all around them
- b) why they grasp all available opportunities whenever they are available
- c) why the top managers, technocrats and bureaucrats who participated in the interviews perceive the world and behave in different ways

How? The entrepreneurs who have survived mix a Fatalistic lack of trust and an obsession with surviving with Individualistic competitive eagerness for the purpose of creating what Thompson refers to as ‘clumsy solutions’ or ‘poly rational solutions’, only in instances where the opportunity presents itself.

It can be clearly observed from the diagram that the black swan theory of Taleb

- Is situated in the top left Fatalist section
- The stances attacked by Taleb with such ferocity are competitive Individualist reasoning focused on ‘Profit Maximisation’ located in the cell at the bottom left as well as the ‘tyranny of experts’, which is described by the Hierarchical type of reasoning in the top right (the hypothesis that senior individuals are the most knowledgeable and therefore have authority)

Put differently, it is relatively easy to situate Taleb in a corner of Thompson’s broader picture of what one can possibly feel, think and do from a cultural perspective. Our thesis, outcomes, and suggestions (as well as our critique of ‘Strategic planning’) can also be placed in this diagram. Observe that every style of thought presents what it perceives to be the optimal strategy, but for every position, three other positions will make the argument for distinct strategies. Thompson recently argued (2018) that every strategy only functions effectively if the ‘risk season’ corresponds to it and experiences failure, potentially catastrophic, if it is adopted in the incorrect season. For instance, the Individualistic strategy aimed at maximising profit functions highly effectively during a ‘boom’ season, but fails catastrophically during a period of ‘bust’. In this context, the most important factor is that the Fatalistic survivalist strategy that it has been promoting is suitable for risk seasons with a high level of unpredictability. A bureaucratic administrator who places his faith in rules and processes will perform effectively in periods of stability, but following the rules is misguided if they no longer function when the risk season changes. If the whole society is confronted by an existential

threat, then a suitable logical reaction to this threat would be to become exceptionally courageous and unified, and thinking will probably follow this path. However, observe that psychological models find it extremely difficult to provide an explanation as to why the thinking of people or organisations changes. It is assumed that psychological ‘types’ are permanent, whereas cultural thought is continually shifting.

It can now be observed that, as an entrepreneur who has survived, my actions and customs, as well as those of other entrepreneurs who have survived that were interviewed (deferring making decisions etc.) correspond to the risk environment that has existed within Iran for many years. The author instinctively feels that it is possible to scale up his method of business operations such that it is applicable throughout the downstream petrochemical and future diversified polymer production industries in Iran. Put differently, Thompson can both explain and support the emotions, thoughts and behaviours of the author, taking into account the existing risk conditions within Iran. According to cultural theorists, but not Taleb, the perception of risks and opportunities can be shared by individuals, groups, professional associations, industrial sectors, ministries, governments, and international organizations. It is important to note that this shared perception does not align with Taleb's perspective. Regardless of the scale, the identical four possibilities will still exist along with the way in which they disagree.

The author contends that based on the dialogue he has formed between Thompson and Taleb, ‘culturally available’ reasoning does underpin his obsessions and suggestions. Taking into account the prevailing conditions in Iran, it is strongly recommended that top managers and administrators reduce their dependence and belief in planning and increase their focus on surviving negative black swans, augmenting the likelihood of infrequent but extremely positive black swans.

6.6 Limitation

When conducting some of the interviews, it is observed that certain petrochemical managers were hesitant to convey their emotions, thoughts and plans as they harbour the reasonable desire to avoid preventable risks, such as the potential for their position to be lost if they were overly frank. In their senior positions, they are required to be mindful of political limitations as well as the necessity to sustain good relationships with those in authority. After all, they are agents of a variety of different national plans and have a specific and official duty to ensure these plans are implemented. That is, they are confronted by further risks and limitations that do not constrain independent owner-managing entrepreneurs.

Nevertheless, readers may observe that their reasonable aspiration for survival and the extent to which they are sensitive to risk do not differ significantly from the desire of surviving Iranian entrepreneurs to survive. Put differently, although the two interview samples differ significantly, they have the same reasonable level of sensitivity to risk that Thompson would perceive to be Fatalistic and Taleb would likely endorse.

In risk seasons with multiple threats, being cautious is a rational strategy. However, quickly seizing the positive black swans that will arise is also a rational approach. It is also argued that no opportunities should be perceived as being ‘golden’ in the manner that Individualistic ‘profit-maximisers’ generally perceive it. Seeking to exploit an opportunity to its fullest will ultimately end in failure when another change occurs in the ‘risk season’.

Based on the article Thompson wrote in 2018, it is observed that new risk seasons will ultimately emerge in Iran, while his cultural insights into “*How Banks and Other Financial Institutions Think*” is likely the second most significant text that the author has encountered (behind the work of Taleb). Grid-Group Cultural Theory allows us to see that Taleb should take into account a broader variety of possibilities. He could still admit that actors are not irrational animal psychologies overtaken by fresh artificial (social risks), but consistently

behave in a rational manner according to their perception of things. They have varying preoccupations and disputes regarding what should be done. Taleb and Thompson have facilitated our understanding of how and why actors are correct and incorrect and in which situations.

In a world where an equilibrium can never be achieved, it is not possible to regard this thesis as being conclusive. However, it offers a collection of functional hypotheses and feasible practices that can be suggested to entrepreneurs as well as certain clues regarding how to adapt them for senior managers to utilise, who often observe that the most carefully made plans are ruined by unpredictable events. Such recommendations *may* be loosened or changed if and when a change in risk season occurs.

It is normal that calls are made for ‘larger samples’ in future studies. However, a factor that the author believes has greater importance is the development of an enhanced comprehension of the ‘poly-rational’ solutions identified by Thompson as well as the creation of forums and symposia in which various types of reasoning and opposing recommendations can be brought together this thesis will be ended with the following question:

‘What actions can facilitators take to allow actors to perceive the value in other people’s reasoning, acknowledge where their own have limitations, and devise innovative solutions that are unthinkable apart from in a collective of differing minds?’ The author makes the proposal that such gatherings could be convened in environments that are not only characterised by uncertainty, but also significant danger. Doing this may necessitate the adoption of greater appetite for risk than are accustomed.

In concluding this thesis, I would like to express my gratitude to my supervisor Prof. Kozlovski. He has supported me with his kindness and friendliness during this course, for which I am eternally grateful. He effectively utilised his skills to allow me to perceive my own tacit skills. His understanding of ‘managing for the future’ approaches, as he defines it,

including Nicholas Nassim Taleb and Michael Thompson, has allowed me to comprehend why actors behave in certain ways and how they could acquire the ability to feel, think and behave in different ways. Prof. Kozlovski allowed me to think in abstract as well as practical and instinctive ways. It has been revealing to look beyond the conventional studies on strategy to observed that academic professionals are also ‘cultural subjects’ who have the identical variety of ‘styles of thought’ that cause non-academics to sincerely disagree about what is the best course of action.

If one can identify the roots of thoughts and actions, it is not possible to return to the basic ‘five step’ change management models that have naïve and generally hierarchical assumptions that individuals with seniority are the most knowledgeable and that success can only be achieved by implementing these steps consecutively.

Such a realisation is worthy of being shared with entrepreneurs and senior managers in Iran in particular. Nevertheless, the combination of inventiveness and wariness that is already well-established in Iran has worldwide ramifications and it pleases us to present this to a broader audience.

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